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Data Network

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A reanalysis of relative Sea Level trends

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1. Background and scope¹

Sea level is probably the single most important ECV considering that its evolution over the next few decades is predicted to cause trouble to millions of people, especially in vulnerable areas. More specifically a variety of scientific methods shows that global sea level – the average height of the sea surface across the planet - it's been rising over the last century.

Sea level has been measured at some stations for more than a century, providing data about sea level going back to 1880. Starting from these data, trends can be assessed at Individual stations or in comparison with other stations, while global changes are investigated by looking at tide gauge data over periods of 30 years or more.

Since 1933, the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL)² has been responsible for the collection, publication, analysis and interpretation of sea level data from the global network of tide gauges (Holgate, 2013).

PSMSL RLR³ and the global sea level trends products are based on each station data (which is quality and datum controlled) and compared to that station's long term mean over the baseline period of 1960-1990.

A period of at least thirty years of sea level data must be available to include the station in the product (see the PSMSL method page⁴ for further details), therefore the product is only covering long term trends.

In this report⁵, using EMODnet Physics available PSMSL RLR monthly data, we discuss sea level trends calculated over recent baseline periods. PSMSL RLR time series of sea level have been reduced to a common datum. This reduction was performed by the PSMSL making use of the tide gauge datum history provided by the supplying authority. To date, approximately two thirds of the stations in the PSMSL database have had their data adjusted in this way, forming the 'REVISED LOCAL REFERENCE' (or 'RLR') dataset.

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² https://www.psmsl.org/about_us/

³ <https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/rlr.php>

⁴ <https://www.psmsl.org/products/anomalies/methods.php>

2. EMODnet Physics

EMODnet Physics is a domain specific infrastructure aggregating data and metadata from several data portals and services (Martín Míguez., 2019; Gorringer 2019; Calewaert, 2016, Novellino, 2014). EMODnet-Physics map portal (www.emodnet-physics.eu/map) provides a single point of access to validated in situ datasets, products and their physical parameter metadata of European Seas and global oceans. More specifically, time series and datasets are made available, as recorded by fixed platforms (moorings, tide gauges, HF radars, etc.), moving platforms (ARGO, Lagrangian buoys, ferryboxes, etc.) and repeated observations (CTDs, etc.).

EMODnet Physics data portal is currently providing easy access to metadata, data and products of: wave height and period; temperature and salinity of the water column; wind speed and direction; horizontal velocity of the water column; light attenuation; sea ice coverage and sea level trends (relative and absolute, river runoff data, total suspended matter and underwater noise (acoustic pollution).

The acquisition of physical parameters is largely an automated process that integrates operational data source and key marine data integrators e.g. the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre and/or Global Data Assembly Centres.

Data quality is flagged according to an automatic – unsupervised procedure at the data source. EMODnet Physics is operationally processing this data flow to generate map layers and extract in situ (monthly) trends, averages and peak values of the parameters.

Historical validated datasets are organised in collaboration with SeaDataNet and its network of National Oceanographic Data Centres, which are supplying EMODnet Physics with products (climatology) on temperature and salinity of the water column. EMODnet Physics is also acting as the in situ historical data collections broker between users and the NODCs. This “federative” approach facilitates interaction with other established databases for data preservation at both European (e.g. Global Runoff Data Centre, ICES databases, etc.) and international (e.g. GOOS, SOOS, NOAA, IMOS, etc.) levels.

EMODnet Physics is also leading the process of developing and supplying the full data management, hosting and dissemination chain of “younger” parameters/platforms/technologies such as river outflow, water noise, sea surface currents as recorded by river stations, marine data from gliders, etc. (Río Fernandez, 2018; Campuzano, 2018; Rubio, 2017)

Figure 1. Relative Sea Level Trends – the PSMSL RLR product integrated in EMODnet Physics

3. Sea Level Data in EMODnet Physics

By integrating more than 400 European tide gauge stations, the 290 Global Sea Level Observing Systems (GLOSS) core network, 930 IOC sea level monitoring stations and more than 1,300 Permanent Services for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL), EMODnet Physics is offering one of the widest in situ data collections for sea-level data.

Based on the PSMSL collection, EMODnet Physics is already making available a relative sea level trend product and a sea level anomalies product. Based on the SONEL product, EMODnet Physics is making an absolute sea level trend product available.

The full list of the TG and GNSS linked stations is listed in file "EMD_TG_DB_20200430.pdf"⁶.

Figure 2. Tide gauge in EMODnet Physics (3620 platforms)

The calculation of global mean sea level from tide gauges is not straightforward due to a number of considerations, including local and regional changes in winds and ocean circulation that impact sea level, the impact of atmospheric pressure changes on sea level, the relative lack of long, continuous records, and the lack of a common datum across tide gauge site. In order to have consistent global datum (benchmark) to combine tide gauge measurements from multiple locations into regional or global means we decided to use the PSMSL product and more specifically the PSMSL platforms that have a RLR timeseries. The following figure shows the platforms with RLR data.

⁶ The integration and mapping of the various data sources is a long time consuming process. The annex show that mapping is a continuous process and some metadata need to be update.

Figure 3. Platforms with PSMSL RLR timeseries (1050 platforms)

4. Data source and method

Input data is PSMSL revised local reference (RLR) monthly mean time series from EMODnet Physics (see section 7 for details), defined as follow:

- $MMSL_i(m)$, where i is the station index, m is the month

Baselines:

- B_1 – from 2000 to 2019
- B_2 – from 2005 to 2019
- B_3 – from 2010 to 2019

For each station, the mean value for the baseline was computed. If there was not any data in the period, the station was not included in the process (the 7000 field value was given). The mean value is arithmetic mean of all monthly means available over the chosen baselines period. Two other mean values were computed: the mean value for the entire time series and the mean value for the period not covered by the baseline

- $MB_n(i)$, where n is the baseline period and i is the station index
- $M(i)$, i is the station index
- $M_{not_B_n}(i)$, where n is the baseline period and i is the station index

Once removed the PSMSL offset (7000mm) the rise offset levels were computed:

- $R1 = MB_n(i) - M(i)$
- $R2 = MB_n(i) - M_{not_B_n}(i)$

$R_x/(B_n * y)$ gives the rise trend (in mm/y) over the last y years in the B_n baseline.

Figure 4. Example of the processing for the RLR timeseries in BREST. The dashed blue line is the monthly RLR timeserie, the black line is the annual average trend timeseries, the solid blue line is the mean sea level of the monthly RLR along the baseline (2000-2019), the solid red line is the mean sea level of the monthly RLR along the full timeseries (1807-2019), the solid green line is the mean sea level of the monthly RLR along the timeseries but the baseline (i.e. 1807–1999).

Table 1 - Table 3 provides the completeness of the timeseries for the given baseline. The figures for all the processed stations along the three baselines are provided in attach in a zip file.

The Relative Value for a given month is calculated by dividing the monthly value by mean value in the baseline period

$$- \quad RV_{n,i}(m) = MMSL_i(m) / MB_n(i), \text{ where } n \text{ is the baseline period and } i \text{ is the station index, the month}$$

Based on this processing, we have a first product (MRVB) showing the monthly relative value vs the baseline. The data is presented for each station and

If $RV_{n,i}(m) < 1$ the monthly trend is negative, if $RV_{n,i}(m) > 1$ the monthly trend is positive,

The products are available on SLV⁷ - sea level variation over recent baseline data - EMODnet Physics product page. The following picture presents an example.

⁷<https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/maptest/Products/V2/PRODUCTS.aspx?PRODTYPE=SL&type=PSMSLSL¶m=undefined>

Figure 5. EMODnet Physics SLV product

<https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/Products/V2/PRODUCTS.aspx?PRODTYPE=SL&type=PSMSLSL¶m=undefined>

The RV is then processed to extract a rising value. Many of the RV are not complete and for processing purpose holes have been filled with the mobile_average value⁸.

Each RV timeseries is also processed by a decomposition function (Wang, Smith, & Hyndman, 2006) where the decomposition is written as $y(t)=T(t)+S(t)+R(t)$, where $T(t)$ is the smoothed trend component, $S(t)$ is the seasonal component and $R(t)$ is a remainder component.

For strongly trended data, the seasonally adjusted data should have much more variation than the remainder component. For strongly trended data, the seasonally adjusted data should have much more variation than the remainder component. Therefore $\text{Var}[R(t)]/\text{Var}[T(t)+R(t)]$ should be relatively small.

Given the timeseries is composed of monthly data, a period of 12 was used as input parameter for the decomposition function. In general, the residuals shows strongly trended data (see e.g. Figure 6)

Then, time series is processed by a polyfit function - a general least squares polynomial fit function - which accepts the data set and a polynomial function of any degree (we applied degree = 1, i.e. linear fit), and returns an array of coefficients that minimizes the squared error.

The function returns the coefficients for a linear interpolation

- $y=RRx + R0$, where RR and $R0$ give information about the rise trend over B_n
- R^2 , that gives the accuracy of the fitting.

⁸ Let's consider an array of 3 values $[a, b, c]$, the mobile average is processed for each value as follow: $\text{MAV}_a = \text{mean}(a)$; $\text{MAV}_b = \text{mean}(\text{MAV}_a, b)$; $\text{MAV}_c = \text{mean}(\text{MAV}_b, c)$

Figure 6. Example of the decomposition process and results for the BREST - RLR timeseries. From top: Observed monthly RLR (source data), Trend, Seasonal, and Residual components.

Averages and trends are not corrected for local land movement. Furthermore, no attempt has been made to assess the validity of any individual fit, so results should not be treated as a publication quality values suitable for use in planning or policy making. Events like land movements (e.g. earthquakes, glacial isostatic adjustment), unexplained instrumental datum shifts, changes in atmospheric pressure, short records may generate anomalous trends.

5. Results

Please note that these are calculated relative mean sea level trends without any correction for vertical land movement. Furthermore, no attempt has been made to assess the validity of any individual fit.

The figure presents the results for the analysis as described in the previous section. Once selected the baseline period the user can select the Rx to be shown. Figure shows the example for R1 along B1 (2000-2019).

Figure 7. Reanalysis of level rise for along the baseline time periods

<https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/Products/V2/PRODUCTS.aspx?PRODTYPE=SL&type=PSMSLSLR¶m=undefined>

6. Trends

For this exercise we considered about 1050 platforms with a PSMSL RLR timeseries. Only a limited number of these platforms have enough recent data to process variation levels as described in the previous sections. The following figures show the completeness of the timeseries along the considered baseline

Figure 8. Completeness of the RLR TS along the baseline period 2000 - 2019 (60% - 501 platforms)

Figure 9. Completeness of the RLR TS along the baseline period 2005 - 2019 (60% - 483 platforms)

Figure 10. Completeness of the RLR TS along the baseline period 2010 - 2019 (60% - 470 platforms)

Considering the platforms for which we have at least 60% of the monthly RLR along the baseline, it is possible to see some features. The following paragraphs shows results for the three considered baselines.

6.1 Baseline 1 - 2000-2019

Figure 11. R1 is the difference between the mean sea level value along the baseline and the mean sea level value along the full timeseries

The 44% of the selected platforms show a rise in the sea level in the range of 42mm – 168 mm along the baseline. If we consider the mean value along the baseline compared to the mean value of the timeseries (but the baseline period), the rise is more evident and 67% of the platforms recorded a rise in the range of 31mm – 196mm.

Figure 12. R2 is the difference between the mean sea level value along the baseline and the mean sea level value along the period before the baseline

6.2 Baseline 2 - 2005-2019.

Figure 13. R1 is the difference between the mean sea level value along the baseline and the mean sea level value along the full timeseries

More than 50% of the selected platforms show a rise in the sea level in the range of 15mm – 156mm along the baseline. If we consider the mean value along the baseline compared to the mean value of the timeseries (but the baseline period), the rise is more evident and 60% of the platforms recorded a rise in the range of 51mm – 232mm.

Figure 14. R2 is the difference between the mean sea level value along the baseline and the mean sea level value along the period before the baseline

6.3 Baseline 3 - 2010-2019.

Figure 15. R1 is the difference between the mean sea level value along the baseline and the mean sea level value along the full timeseries

More than 50% of the selected platforms show a rise in the sea level in the range of 2mm – 160mm along the baseline. If we consider the mean value along the baseline compared to the mean value of the timeseries (but the baseline period), the rise is more evident and 70% of the platforms recorded a rise in the range of 32mm – 232mm.

Figure 16. R2 is the difference between the mean sea level value along the baseline and the mean sea level value along the period before the baseline

Considering the coefficients of the linear interpolation curve, we have a rising trend of 1,41 mm/y (along the considered baselines).

Figure 17. Coefficients RR in the linear fitting curve $y = RRx + R0$

6.4 PSMSL Trends

Figure 18 shows the rise trend levels [mm/m] as computed on the PSMSL trends coefficients. Coefficients are in the same range of the applied interpolation method that is described in the previous sections.

Figure 18. PSMSL – Trends coefficient in mm/month

7. Result details

The following tables provide the reader with details and results of the processing as described in the previous sections.

Table 1. Results for B1 – 2000 – 2019

Station	latitude	longitude	sample	completeness	psmsl mean	mean tot (realigned val)	mean (baseline)	R1 (mbaseline - mtot)	mean notbase	R2 (mbase - mnotbase)	coeff RR	offset RO
ALVARADO	18,7667	-	228	100%	6.980,5965	13,9550	-	33,3585	27,3934	-	0,15	75,63
AMDERMA	69,7500	61,7000	228	100%	6.914,3509	2,3435	85,6491	83,3056	24,1168	109,7659	0,21	100,26
ANABAR	73,2167	113,5000	228	100%	7.062,5044	35,1371	62,5044	27,3673	20,2754	42,2290	0,15	11,47
ARKO	58,4842	16,9606	228	100%	7.078,2018	65,6337	78,2018	12,5680	31,6594	46,5424	0,25	24,17
ARRECIFE2	28,9719	-	228	100%	7.043,7412	25,6017	43,7412	18,1395	13,4867	30,2545	0,14	13,01
ARRECIFE-D	28,9658	13,5379	228	100%	6.763,8904	274,6397	236,1096	38,5301	295,9800	59,8704	0,16	327,63
BERGEN	60,3980	5,3205	228	100%	6.855,1842	120,4016	144,8158	24,4142	110,4562	34,3596	0,08	86,70
BOURGAS	42,4833	27,4833	228	100%	7.160,6316	0,1441	160,6316	160,7757	38,8318	199,4634	0,30	184,67
CAPELAMBERT	-	117,1860	228	100%	7.099,1711	72,9139	99,1711	26,2572	10,0277	89,1434	0,45	5,07
CHUUK,MOENISLAND	7,4467	151,8467	228	100%	7.047,4518	5,9195	47,4518	53,3712	21,1216	68,5734	0,13	74,36
CLEARWATERBEACH	27,9783	-	228	100%	7.000,3772	29,8606	0,3772	29,4834	45,6081	45,2309	0,16	81,09
DIAMONDHARBOUR	22,2000	88,1667	228	100%	6.938,5263	4,9705	61,4737	66,4442	25,5239	86,9975	0,15	79,65
DOUGLAS	54,1500	-	228	100%	7.021,3377	3,9085	21,3377	17,4292	1,1317	22,4694	0,02	9,52
DUBLIN	53,3500	-	228	100%	7.252,1184	71,0354	252,1184	181,0831	22,1658	229,9527	0,39	145,56
EVENSKJAER	68,5833	16,5500	228	100%	7.049,6184	82,3706	49,6184	32,7522	92,0706	42,4522	0,06	114,15
FISHGUARD	52,0132	-	228	100%	7.049,8991	38,5571	49,8991	11,3421	4,7943	45,1048	0,24	1,22
FURUOGRUND	64,9158	21,2306	228	100%	7.102,3596	29,5825	102,3596	72,7772	14,8947	87,4649	0,13	57,04
GRONDINES	46,5833	-	228	100%	6.936,7675	56,8916	63,2325	6,3408	54,4939	8,7386	0,01	49,40
HANASAKI	43,2833	145,5833	228	100%	6.803,1491	-	196,8509	101,2185	318,0270	121,1762	0,14	402,35
HAUOVERPIER	25,9033	-	228	100%	7.006,6579	19,0624	6,6579	25,7203	88,2781	94,9360	0,48	100,51
HEYSHAM	54,0318	-	228	100%	7.007,5833	14,3411	7,5833	6,7577	17,6718	10,0885	0,04	29,66
IMBITUBA	-	-	228	100%	7.066,2939	27,1017	66,2939	39,1921	16,1261	50,1678	0,10	24,68
JOHNSTONISLAND	16,7383	-	228	100%	7.027,5526	55,5978	27,5526	28,0452	65,2352	37,6825	0,06	86,71
KAINAN	34,1442	135,1914	228	100%	6.975,7588	49,0671	24,2412	24,8258	58,0217	33,7805	0,06	76,30
KODIAKISLAND,WOMENS BAY	57,7317	-	228	100%	6.380,3202	168,2282	619,6798	451,4516	29,7400	589,9398	1,12	397,88
KOTAPHAONOI	7,8333	98,4333	228	100%	6.992,2368	61,0079	7,7632	68,7711	80,2231	87,9862	0,16	150,10

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is financed by the European Union under Regulation (EU) No 508/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 on the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund.

KOTKA	60,4500	26,9500	228	100%	7.161,5658	59,5872	161,5658	101,9786	40,0800	121,4858	0,17	- 64,77
LAJOLLA(SCRIPPSPIER)	32,8667	- 117,2567	228	100%	7.041,1711	13,9747	41,1711	55,1458	- 26,6223	67,7934	0,09	- 69,73
MACABALANPORT,CAGAYANDEORO	8,5000	124,6667	228	100%	6.844,4825	- 89,2069	- 155,5175	- 66,3107	- 34,3651	- 121,1524	- 0,43	23,87
MARSEILLE	43,2788	5,3539	228	100%	6.974,7193	52,2666	25,2807	26,9859	- 59,0514	33,7707	0,03	- 72,25
MOREHEADCITY	34,7167	- 76,7333	228	100%	7.062,2544	1,0722	62,2544	61,1822	- 20,6041	82,8585	0,19	- 80,58
MURMANSK	68,9667	33,0500	228	100%	7.193,5044	62,7010	193,5044	130,8034	16,8988	176,6056	0,34	- 93,51
MYRTLEBEACH	33,6833	- 78,8850	228	100%	6.981,0044	64,9938	18,9956	45,9982	- 87,0333	68,0377	0,17	- 127,78
NEWLYN	50,1030	- 5,5428	228	100%	7.084,6404	- 16,7243	84,6404	101,3646	- 32,7804	117,4207	0,12	- 117,08
NORTHPOINT	22,3000	114,2000	228	100%	7.161,6447	30,2529	161,6447	131,3919	- 2,9595	164,6042	0,28	- 134,83
NUKU'ALOFAB	- 21,1368	- 175,1807	228	100%	6.948,3728	34,3370	51,6272	- 17,2902	- 22,7082	- 28,9190	0,09	- 8,57
PALMADEMALLORCA	39,5524	2,6389	228	100%	7.060,3421	40,5875	60,3421	19,7546	28,4370	31,9051	0,12	5,95
POINTENOIRE	- 4,7833	11,8333	228	100%	7.012,3465	18,5160	12,3465	- 6,1695	21,3703	- 9,0238	0,05	40,15
PORTBLAIR	11,6833	92,7667	228	100%	7.137,0439	30,2845	137,0439	106,7593	8,3944	128,6495	0,18	- 94,89
PUERTOCORTES	15,8333	- 87,9500	228	100%	7.184,6447	101,6372	184,6447	83,0075	76,4431	108,2016	0,21	3,07
QUEBEC(LAUZON)	46,8333	- 71,1667	228	100%	7.064,1404	108,0648	64,1404	172,2052	- 141,9392	206,0796	0,25	288,47
REGGIOLABRIA	38,1000	15,6500	228	100%	6.948,8026	83,0367	51,1974	31,8393	- 94,0319	42,8345	0,06	- 111,29
SANDWICHMARINA,CAPECODCANALENTRANCE	41,7667	- 70,5000	228	100%	7.144,3772	99,7324	144,3772	44,6448	74,9332	69,4440	0,30	0,33
SKAGWAY	59,4500	- 135,3267	228	100%	7.189,7412	84,0532	189,7412	105,6880	54,3472	135,3940	0,23	- 41,72
SOUHDASII	35,4875	24,0825	228	100%	6.855,0219	56,8031	144,9781	- 88,1750	6,0165	150,9946	0,44	67,89
ST.PAUL'SHARBOR,KODIAK	57,7450	- 152,4817	228	100%	7.133,0877	116,1427	133,0877	16,9451	76,1852	56,9026	0,29	66,72
TANJONGCHANGI	1,3903	103,9989	228	100%	7.023,0439	1,0011	23,0439	22,0428	- 12,5678	35,6116	0,15	- 42,85
USTOLENEK	73,0000	119,8667	228	100%	7.080,2105	56,1687	80,2105	24,0418	48,8802	31,3304	0,07	20,48
VARBERG	57,1000	12,2167	228	100%	6.971,9912	41,0966	28,0088	13,0878	44,3748	16,3660	0,00	- 42,68
VARNA	43,1833	27,9167	228	100%	7.035,6053	62,6126	35,6053	- 27,0074	69,4271	- 33,8218	- 0,03	82,12
VENEZIA(S.STEFANO)	45,4167	12,3333	228	100%	6.954,7149	101,8398	45,2851	- 147,1249	124,3376	169,6227	0,16	240,18
WEST-TERSCHELLING	53,3631	5,2200	228	100%	7.153,4868	70,2448	153,4868	83,2420	51,9340	101,5528	0,16	- 31,31
WILLETSPPOINT	40,7933	- 73,7817	228	100%	7.093,0044	47,5438	93,0044	45,4606	36,2571	56,7473	0,09	2,54
ZHOHOVA(ZHOHOVAOSTROV)	76,1500	152,8333	228	100%	6.988,8860	0,9832	11,1140	- 12,0972	6,5952	- 17,7093	0,06	26,74

ALAMITOSBAYENTRANCE	33,7500	-118,1167	227	100%	7.189,3921	106,8525	189,3921	82,5396	76,7427	112,6493	0,24	1,37
ARICA	18,4667	70,3333	227	100%	6.501,6564	183,6855	498,3436	-314,6581	82,3321	416,0115	0,70	151,68
BELFAST	54,6000	5,9167	227	100%	7.079,3656	14,5539	79,3656	93,9196	51,9054	131,2710	0,31	142,48
BILBAO	43,3515	3,0451	227	100%	7.169,5198	153,3355	169,5198	16,1843	114,1234	55,3964	0,30	102,14
BITUNGII	1,4333	125,2000	227	100%	7.223,9824	138,2247	223,9824	85,7577	90,2069	133,7755	0,39	11,79
CADIZII	36,5278	6,3114	227	100%	7.412,4317	108,8538	412,4317	303,5779	44,2767	368,1551	0,54	253,57
DUCKPIEROUTSIDE	36,1833	75,7467	227	100%	7.146,2819	75,0450	146,2819	71,2370	36,5819	109,7000	0,31	28,72
FORCADOS	5,3500	5,3500	227	100%	7.024,7974	86,5786	24,7974	61,7812	119,6456	94,8482	0,24	165,88
MATSUYAMAI	33,8589	132,7122	227	100%	6.815,0969	88,0396	184,9031	-96,8635	45,2831	139,6200	0,39	64,50
MINAMIIZU	34,6167	138,8833	227	100%	6.968,9119	52,7172	31,0881	21,6291	61,6913	30,6032	0,07	77,59
POINTATKINSON	49,3333	123,2500	227	100%	7.164,7709	1,0909	164,7709	163,6800	31,5461	196,3171	0,27	187,15
SANNIKOVA(SANNIKOVAPROLIV)	74,6667	138,9000	227	100%	7.140,3921	42,8494	140,3921	97,5427	12,2763	128,1158	0,22	66,56
STOCKHOLM	59,3242	18,0817	227	100%	6.976,6696	143,7073	23,3304	-167,0377	172,1730	195,5034	0,24	335,56
TUAS(WESTJURONG)	1,2833	103,6667	227	100%	7.045,7709	33,5211	45,7709	12,2499	26,7972	18,9737	0,09	6,00
ULUKHAKTOK(FORMERLYHOLMAN)	70,7363	117,7612	227	100%	7.127,8811	65,5383	127,8811	62,3428	24,5806	103,3004	0,34	34,90
YEOSU	34,7472	127,7656	227	100%	7.310,0441	278,1561	310,0441	31,8879	260,7453	49,2987	0,08	251,55
BUZZARDSBAY	41,7417	70,6167	226	99%	6.770,1106	155,1469	229,8894	-74,7424	65,0887	164,8007	0,76	5,88
CHURCHILL	58,7667	94,1833	226	99%	6.989,6460	25,1424	10,3540	-35,4964	35,1202	45,4742	0,11	87,03
FEDOROVA(CHELUSKINMYS)	77,7167	104,3000	226	99%	7.083,0310	4,1619	83,0310	78,8691	19,9474	102,9784	0,17	80,26
KRISTIANSUND	63,1139	7,7344	226	99%	6.952,6681	540,6567	47,3319	-587,9886	746,5996	793,9315	1,51	1.226,14
LAPALMA	28,6778	17,7680	226	99%	6.632,1195	173,0114	367,8805	-194,8692	33,1690	334,7116	1,03	118,23
LOSANGELES	33,7200	118,2717	226	99%	7.239,8407	123,8778	239,8407	115,9629	97,8402	142,0006	0,20	7,61
N.SPIT,HUMBOLDTBAY	40,7667	124,2167	226	99%	7.087,9027	72,7867	87,9027	15,1160	23,4585	64,4441	0,34	18,10
NEWYORK(THEBATTERY)	40,7000	74,0133	226	99%	7.099,2655	21,1491	99,2655	120,4146	37,1965	136,4620	0,12	143,91
RECIFE	8,0500	34,8667	226	99%	7.217,4425	103,8714	217,4425	113,5710	70,3128	147,1297	0,27	36,41
UBLI	42,7500	16,8333	226	99%	7.102,6460	87,2978	102,6460	15,3483	32,3420	70,3040	0,30	39,17
WEYMOUTH	50,6085	2,4479	226	99%	6.968,6372	76,5523	31,3628	45,1895	102,1738	70,8110	0,22	147,00
ALGECIRASB	36,1214	5,4371	225	99%	7.106,4267	81,1948	106,4267	25,2319	63,4547	42,9720	0,18	31,63

CANAVIEIRAS	-	-	225	99%	7.072,8400	47,0917	72,8400	25,7483	38,6098	34,2302	0,08	10,76
DAUPHINISLAND	30,2500	88,0750	225	99%	7.004,5289	36,4411	4,5289	40,9700	53,6226	58,1514	0,14	87,96
MALYSHEVA(MALYSHEVAOSTROV)	72,0667	129,8333	225	99%	7.147,8933	17,4709	147,8933	130,4224	30,0669	177,9603	0,32	119,15
PORTGILES	-	137,7683	225	99%	7.050,4667	91,4864	50,4667	41,0198	113,6596	63,1929	0,16	145,73
SOUTHEND	51,5145	0,7238	225	99%	7.199,2978	77,5996	199,2978	121,6982	48,0859	151,2118	0,23	61,09
YOKOSUKA	35,2881	139,6514	225	99%	7.045,0578	17,0438	45,0578	62,1015	40,0162	85,0739	0,12	70,21
ZEEBRUGGE	51,3500	3,2000	225	99%	7.090,6489	9,8546	90,6489	80,7943	12,0577	102,7066	0,18	87,09
CROMER	52,9344	1,3016	224	98%	7.103,7902	46,9075	103,7902	56,8827	16,6044	87,1858	0,25	34,67
FUKUE	32,6961	128,8494	224	98%	7.123,7545	92,3627	123,7545	31,3917	52,8422	70,9123	0,36	15,98
HELSINKI	60,1536	24,9562	224	98%	7.129,5759	98,3518	129,5759	227,9277	129,1249	258,7008	0,24	338,47
KUSHIRO	42,9756	144,3714	224	98%	7.124,9196	11,1961	124,9196	113,7236	20,8024	145,7220	0,24	115,70
SANDOWNPIER	50,6511	1,1532	224	98%	7.229,6429	212,0339	229,6429	17,6090	170,6597	58,9831	0,37	149,52
SHALAUROVA(SHALAUROVAMYS)	73,1833	143,2333	224	98%	7.119,0536	32,2972	119,0536	86,7564	5,4903	113,5632	0,20	63,70
SOUTHSOUND	19,2667	81,3833	224	98%	7.126,5982	79,2649	126,5982	47,3333	56,3395	70,2587	0,18	16,94
STROMSTAD	58,9500	11,1833	224	98%	7.283,9777	158,6428	283,9777	125,3348	134,9824	148,9952	0,18	24,16
ABURATSU	31,5769	131,4094	223	98%	7.094,2332	39,8226	94,2332	54,4105	17,6026	76,6306	0,18	33,41
EDITHBURG	-	137,7500	223	98%	7.209,4709	61,1062	209,4709	148,3647	19,0374	190,4335	0,34	116,33
FREEPORT	28,9483	95,3083	223	98%	7.258,1973	20,3759	258,1973	237,8214	64,8154	323,0127	0,76	312,60
KOCHIIII	33,4992	133,5692	223	98%	6.732,2063	86,7136	267,7937	181,0801	10,1874	277,9811	0,82	187,46
PAPEETE-B,FAREUTEPOINT,SOC.IS.	-	149,5727	223	98%	7.092,5426	59,6037	92,5426	32,9389	19,2707	111,8134	0,59	36,59
SEJINGKAT	1,5828	110,4222	223	98%	6.448,0628	453,3181	551,9372	98,6191	389,3210	162,6162	0,69	247,41
COLONIA	34,4833	57,8500	222	97%	7.152,8514	33,3954	152,8514	119,4559	2,9607	149,8906	0,28	125,69
ROOMPOTBUITEN	51,6197	3,6819	222	97%	7.038,6577	17,7505	38,6577	56,4082	47,4524	86,1100	0,25	100,46
UBIN	1,4194	103,9278	222	97%	6.322,8468	673,3856	677,1532	3,7676	669,5730	7,5801	0,02	678,69
BILLINGA	69,8833	175,7667	221	97%	7.074,1131	3,9170	74,1131	70,1961	21,3764	95,4896	0,16	67,08
ONSLow	21,6497	115,1315	221	97%	7.072,3348	9,7430	72,3348	62,5918	23,4126	95,7475	0,26	77,42
HAKODATEII	41,7667	140,7167	220	96%	6.996,1591	54,5762	3,8409	58,4171	73,7864	77,6273	0,11	105,93
KOZUSIMA	34,2092	139,1317	220	96%	7.033,4182	8,4584	33,4182	41,8766	25,0122	58,4304	0,14	63,34

LALIBERTADII	-	-	220	96%	7.062,2455	47,3296	62,2455	14,9159	-	0,7391	62,9845	0,33	-	5,29
HARWICH	51,9480	1,2921	219	96%	7.143,0046	61,0541	143,0046	81,9504	30,5041	112,5004	0,14	0,52	-	-
LOHM	60,1000	21,6667	219	96%	7.188,6484	13,0557	188,6484	201,7041	55,8857	244,5341	0,33	228,44	-	-
CILACAPB	-	7,7517	218	96%	7.146,7752	116,6972	146,7752	30,0781	93,7312	53,0440	0,17	73,34	-	-
WHANGAREI HARBOUR(MARSDENPOINT)	-	35,7574	218	96%	7.087,7202	38,5023	87,7202	49,2179	19,0043	68,7159	0,15	20,53	-	-
PUERTOPLATA	19,8167	-	217	95%	7.235,8018	99,9045	235,8018	135,8973	59,6203	176,1816	0,32	56,90	-	-
ABASHIRI	44,0194	144,2858	216	95%	7.042,6806	1,0148	42,6806	41,6658	16,0810	58,7615	0,12	42,74	-	-
ASTORIA(TONGUEPOINT)	46,2067	-	216	95%	7.047,0926	35,5655	47,0926	11,5271	33,7802	13,3124	0,12	36,10	-	-
BACKEVIK	58,3667	11,2500	216	95%	6.928,0833	284,1538	71,9167	- 356,0704	344,1387	416,0554	0,53	695,14	-	-
BARMOUTH	52,7193	-	216	95%	7.121,2824	83,8702	121,2824	37,4122	61,7389	59,5435	0,17	32,22	-	-
BARSEBACK	55,7564	12,9033	216	95%	7.097,4676	43,9486	97,4676	53,5190	4,2420	93,2256	0,33	42,53	-	-
BAYWAVELANDYACHTCLUB	30,3250	-	216	95%	6.988,5231	81,2429	11,4769	69,7660	121,0842	109,6074	0,33	185,90	-	-
BENOAB	-	8,7467	216	95%	6.989,0648	28,9023	10,9352	17,9671	42,8229	31,8877	0,13	61,43	-	-
BOUCAU	-	43,5273	216	95%	6.853,8241	44,3152	146,1759	- 101,8608	14,8298	161,0057	0,52	113,93	-	-
BYKOV MYS(BYKOV MYS)	72,0000	129,1167	216	95%	7.019,2870	21,1035	19,2870	- 1,8164	23,1997	3,9127	0,00	20,78	-	-
CABOSANLUCAS	22,8833	-	216	95%	7.083,4907	35,3384	83,4907	48,1523	12,8759	70,6148	0,18	28,75	-	-
CASEY	-	66,2667	216	95%	6.860,0833	121,4953	139,9167	- 18,4214	110,9630	28,9536	0,12	85,97	-	-
CHIMBOTE	-	9,0833	216	95%	7.030,8704	24,9211	30,8704	55,7915	51,2932	82,1635	0,24	110,10	-	-
CIVITAVECCHIA	42,0500	11,8167	216	95%	6.619,2500	33,3067	380,7500	- 414,0567	104,8591	485,6091	0,64	522,84	-	-
COX'SBAZAAR	21,4500	91,8333	216	95%	6.986,6204	80,0305	13,3796	66,6508	113,3719	99,9922	0,28	175,30	-	-
DALIAN	38,8667	121,6833	216	95%	7.044,9722	48,0498	44,9722	- 3,0776	49,7295	4,7573	0,03	61,57	-	-
DAUGAVGRIVA	57,0500	24,0333	216	95%	6.991,1065	135,3392	8,8935	126,4457	153,9379	145,0444	0,14	256,30	-	-
DAYTONABEACHSHORES	29,1467	-	216	95%	7.050,0417	18,4478	50,0417	31,5938	5,6781	44,3636	0,16	39,36	-	-
DENHELDER	52,9644	4,7450	216	95%	6.941,6620	190,9803	58,3380	132,6424	209,0144	150,6765	0,12	304,32	-	-
DIEGOGARCIAD	-	7,2900	216	95%	7.091,4907	76,1778	91,4907	15,3130	69,0701	22,4207	0,14	44,19	-	-
DUNEDIN	-	45,8787	216	95%	7.080,4259	39,3966	80,4259	41,0294	30,9019	49,5240	0,09	15,34	-	-
DUNKERQUE	51,0481	2,3667	216	95%	7.077,0370	61,9584	77,0370	15,0786	58,2310	18,8060	0,03	48,06	-	-
EASTERISLAND-D	-	27,1500	216	95%	6.832,0139	130,1813	167,9861	- 37,8048	112,0042	55,9820	0,11	92,02	-	-

ESASHI	41,8667	140,1333	216	95%	7.051,7083	3,6852	51,7083	48,0231	-	21,6673	73,3757	0,19	-	57,76
FELIXSTOWE	51,9577	1,3466	216	95%	6.995,1111	53,7315	4,8889	-	58,6204	66,4336	71,3225	0,12	-	131,50
GANDIA	38,9952	0,1514	216	95%	7.033,7546	18,1142	33,7546	15,6405	5,9439	27,8107	0,07	-	-	2,23
GETING	6,2264	102,1067	216	95%	7.116,3148	71,3666	116,3148	44,9482	46,5937	69,7211	0,18	-	-	13,02
GOLDCOASTSEAWAY2	27,9500	153,4167	216	95%	7.110,3565	53,1178	110,3565	57,2387	22,0658	88,2907	0,27	-	-	33,16
GRINDSTONE	47,3833	61,8667	216	95%	7.218,3287	116,2186	218,3287	102,1101	72,2198	146,1089	0,42	-	-	37,54
HALIFAX	44,6667	63,5833	216	95%	6.828,4722	25,0365	171,5278	-	196,5643	58,2220	229,7497	0,31	-	269,84
HARLINGEN	53,1756	5,4094	216	95%	6.962,6852	204,7119	37,3148	167,3971	227,9321	190,6173	0,20	-	-	390,40
HELIGMAN	60,2000	19,3000	216	95%	7.016,9444	72,1775	16,9444	-	55,2330	83,6698	66,7254	0,15	-	166,47
KAPINGAMARANGI	1,1000	154,7833	216	95%	7.020,9583	4,0885	20,9583	16,8698	45,9569	66,9153	0,40	-	-	59,19
KATSUURA	35,1294	140,2494	216	95%	7.067,7593	41,0396	67,7593	26,7197	29,2743	38,4850	0,04	-	-	27,80
KOLUCHIN	67,4833	174,6500	216	95%	6.994,4167	82,9202	5,5833	77,3368	108,1942	102,6109	0,20	-	-	178,96
KOSICHANG	13,1500	100,8167	216	95%	6.946,1019	22,3460	53,8981	-	31,5522	14,5173	39,3808	0,08	-	19,92
LANAISLAND,KAUMALAPAU	20,7800	156,9000	216	95%	6.989,3565	12,5429	10,6435	-	23,1864	31,6438	42,2873	0,19	-	58,30
LAUNION	13,3333	87,8167	216	95%	7.076,6296	34,3594	76,6296	42,2703	22,2577	54,3720	0,08	-	-	4,84
LIEPAJA	56,5333	20,9833	216	95%	6.951,7222	156,4063	48,2778	108,1286	171,5607	123,2829	0,12	-	-	271,00
LIVERPOOLGEORGESANDPRINCESPIERS	53,4000	3,0000	216	95%	7.052,2778	81,4749	52,2778	133,7527	98,7247	151,0025	0,13	-	-	205,78
LLANDUDNO	53,3317	3,8252	216	95%	7.105,5046	72,9017	105,5046	32,6029	46,7743	58,7303	0,20	-	-	20,36
LORNE	38,5472	143,9888	216	95%	7.022,9120	16,4924	22,9120	6,4196	12,2666	10,6454	0,04	-	-	4,83
LYOKKI	60,8500	21,1833	216	95%	6.963,7037	79,7042	36,2963	-	116,0005	97,6498	133,9460	0,19	-	236,14
MAASSLUIS	51,9175	4,2497	216	95%	7.146,9537	19,0090	146,9537	165,9627	38,9550	185,9087	0,18	-	-	204,90
MALAGA	36,7127	4,4155	216	95%	7.122,9213	81,9948	122,9213	40,9265	65,5807	57,3406	0,09	-	-	47,95
MANTYLUOTO	61,5944	21,4634	216	95%	7.121,3657	21,4215	121,3657	99,9442	20,9156	142,2814	0,32	-	-	95,88
MASIRAH	20,6833	58,8667	216	95%	7.074,7731	47,2431	74,7731	27,5300	29,8716	44,9016	0,12	-	-	13,01
MATARANIB	17,0017	72,1083	216	95%	7.125,4769	67,1186	125,4769	58,3583	10,3566	115,1203	0,48	-	-	41,43
MELILLA	35,2906	2,9285	216	95%	6.419,0231	395,5013	580,9769	-	185,4756	265,0303	315,9466	1,23	-	60,08
MIYAKOII	39,6431	141,9753	216	95%	6.956,8148	33,7946	43,1852	-	9,3905	28,8522	14,3330	0,04	-	19,59
MOURILYANHARBOUR	17,5833	146,0833	216	95%	7.077,7037	47,5136	77,7037	30,1901	31,2902	46,4135	0,12	-	-	9,54

MUSCATB	23,6283	58,5650	216	95%	7,069,5787	13,5356	69,5787	56,0431	-	40,3525	109,9312	0,45	-	90,00
NEWCASTLEIII	-	32,9167	151,8000	216	95%	6,690,4722	2,6119	309,5278	-	312,1397	71,9398	381,4676	0,66	409,81
NEWPORT	-	41,5050	71,3267	216	95%	6,851,1620	14,5531	148,8380	-	134,2848	17,4613	166,2992	0,30	158,52
NICE	43,6956	7,2855	216	95%	7,089,7685	77,8363	89,7685	11,9322	71,7124	18,0562	0,05	61,24		
NOME,ALASKA	64,5000	165,4300	216	95%	7,055,4537	3,3431	55,4537	58,7968	-	36,0261	91,4798	0,25	80,53	
NORTHSALAMINOS	37,9796	23,5417	216	95%	7,090,6435	41,2665	90,6435	49,3770	14,6766	75,9669	0,19	20,91		
ONAHAMA	36,9375	140,8919	216	95%	6,998,7685	2,1517	1,2315	-	3,3832	4,4016	5,6331	0,01	4,21	
OOSTENDE	51,2333	2,9167	216	95%	6,762,4815	7,2885	237,5185	-	230,2300	51,0163	288,5348	0,53	289,27	
OSKARSHAMN	57,2750	16,4781	216	95%	7,065,5231	23,2486	65,5231	42,2746	-	8,2152	73,7384	0,27	47,65	
OWASE	34,0764	136,2072	216	95%	6,911,8426	57,7988	88,1574	-	30,3586	43,7952	44,3622	0,08	28,31	
PADANGB	-	0,9967	100,3750	216	95%	7,272,2500	173,4075	272,2500	98,8425	65,5951	206,6549	0,95	31,88	
POINTLARUE	-	4,6667	55,5333	216	95%	7,058,6019	56,7482	58,6019	1,8537	57,4978	1,1040	0,06	74,95	
POINTSAPIN	46,9667	64,8333	216	95%	7,058,4352	7,4369	58,4352	50,9983	-	14,4537	72,8889	0,19	60,95	
POLYARNIY	69,2000	33,4833	216	95%	6,834,4722	146,4436	165,5278	-	19,0841	132,7139	32,8139	0,16	101,23	
PORTALBERNI	49,2333	124,8167	216	95%	6,753,4954	93,8984	246,5046	-	152,6063	51,6747	194,8299	0,38	100,93	
PORTMACQUARIE	-	31,4268	152,9110	216	95%	7,081,9815	57,7889	81,9815	24,1926	34,9683	47,0131	0,20	11,96	
PORTMORESBYII	-	9,4833	147,1333	216	95%	7,134,6759	47,8366	134,6759	86,8393	2,6155	132,0605	0,42	88,10	
PORTPIRIE	-	33,1776	138,0117	216	95%	6,996,1852	57,3597	3,8148	53,5449	68,0483	64,2335	0,09	119,10	
PORTSAID	31,2500	32,3000	216	95%	6,692,4537	11,9515	307,5463	-	295,5948	52,3637	359,9099	0,59	360,52	
PUERTOSOBERANIA	-	62,4833	59,6333	216	95%	7,104,9954	34,6765	104,9954	70,3189	-	3,6467	108,6420	0,31	64,43
RAROTONGAB	-	21,2048	159,7848	216	95%	7,012,8981	18,8385	12,8981	-	5,9403	23,8089	10,9108	0,00	17,75
REPOSAARI	61,6167	21,4500	216	95%	6,929,4398	14,7316	70,5602	-	55,8285	5,4767	65,0834	0,09	56,61	
RESOLUTE	74,6833	94,8833	216	95%	7,113,8981	63,5221	113,8981	50,3760	42,7631	71,1350	0,20	10,77		
RIMOUSKI	48,4833	68,5167	216	95%	7,112,8657	62,2841	112,8657	50,5817	35,3447	77,5211	0,20	1,48		
RIOHACHA	11,5500	72,9167	216	95%	7,280,0741	56,3789	280,0741	223,6951	-	23,2740	303,3481	0,74	261,60	
RUSSARO	59,7667	22,9500	216	95%	6,992,7037	113,3069	7,2963	106,0106	-	128,0839	120,7876	0,12	223,10	
SANDYHOOK	40,4667	74,0083	216	95%	6,835,4167	19,5030	164,5833	-	145,0803	15,9597	180,5430	0,31	155,54	
SANFRANCISCO	37,8067	122,4650	216	95%	7,091,6111	27,5658	91,6111	119,1770	42,1076	133,7187	0,12	149,62		
SANJOSE	13,9167	90,8333	216	95%	6,943,3380	23,4302	56,6620	-	33,2319	9,5926	47,0694	0,13	28,54	

SASEBOII	33,1581	129,7239	216	95%	7.024,4259	-	30,4947	24,4259	54,9206	-	55,4788	79,9047	0,19	-	96,89
SEMBAWANG	1,4667	103,8333	216	95%	7.155,7176	-	90,4402	155,7176	65,2774	-	68,5199	87,1977	0,18	-	12,58
SETTLEMENTPOINTA	26,6833	78,9833	216	95%	7.011,0139	-	21,9488	11,0139	32,9627	-	42,4469	53,4608	0,15	-	64,48
SIBONEY	23,1000	82,4667	216	95%	7.041,7407	-	33,6316	41,7407	8,1091	-	31,0680	10,6727	0,01	-	31,03
SIMRISHAMN	55,5575	14,3578	216	95%	7.074,2176	-	15,4579	74,2176	58,7597	-	27,7649	101,9825	0,37	-	82,85
SKANOR	55,4167	12,8294	216	95%	7.028,6528	-	6,5567	28,6528	22,0960	-	9,3535	38,0063	0,11	-	22,10
SPLIT-GRADSKALUKA	43,5067	16,4417	216	95%	6.708,5139	-	18,5533	291,4861	272,9328	-	46,8853	338,3714	0,55	-	302,03
SUCURAJ	43,1333	17,2000	216	95%	7.004,8657	-	5,7433	4,8657	10,6090	-	10,4623	15,3280	0,01	-	9,19
SURIGAO	9,7833	125,5000	216	95%	6.995,3426	-	11,1467	4,6574	6,4893	-	14,2044	9,5469	0,07	-	30,09
SURSARI	60,0833	26,9833	216	95%	7.110,7037	-	80,0171	110,7037	30,6866	-	74,1629	36,5408	0,04	-	55,31
SWANAGEPIER	50,6093	1,9492	216	95%	7.039,2037	-	19,9713	39,2037	19,2324	-	2,8635	36,3402	0,16	-	18,10
TAJIRI	35,5936	134,3158	216	95%	7.037,3380	-	16,8887	37,3380	54,2266	-	39,8901	77,2281	0,15	-	70,78
TANJUNGSEDI	1,9317	104,1150	216	95%	6.862,2778	-	121,9698	137,7222	15,7524	-	114,1330	23,5892	0,08	-	96,05
TILBURY	51,4667	0,3667	216	95%	6.968,0926	-	94,6037	31,9074	62,6963	-	109,2782	77,3708	0,10	-	153,11
TOKUYAMAI	34,0333	131,8000	216	95%	7.078,6620	-	7,2217	78,6620	71,4403	-	15,9320	94,5940	0,18	-	76,47
TRAVEMUNDE	53,9581	10,8722	216	95%	7.119,5463	-	10,2282	119,5463	109,3181	-	3,8421	123,3884	0,10	-	92,94
TUAPSE	44,1000	39,0667	216	95%	7.020,3519	-	12,8766	20,3519	33,2284	-	19,2423	39,5942	0,06	-	54,78
UTO	59,7833	21,3667	216	95%	6.938,0648	-	199,2256	61,9352	137,2904	-	218,3892	156,4540	0,15	-	334,40
VALDEZ	61,1250	146,3617	216	95%	7.000,3981	-	35,8109	0,3981	36,2091	-	53,2985	53,6966	0,14	-	85,35
VIKEN	56,1422	12,5792	216	95%	7.230,9769	-	121,9417	230,9769	109,0351	-	44,2233	186,7535	0,67	-	54,02
VILLASANJURJO	35,2500	3,9167	216	95%	7.065,9907	-	75,3740	65,9907	141,3647	-	113,8925	179,8833	0,32	-	245,31
VILSANDI	58,3833	21,8167	216	95%	6.685,8148	-	46,2341	314,1852	267,9511	-	16,0081	330,1933	0,57	-	289,96
WANDO	34,3153	126,7597	216	95%	7.052,1019	-	61,7021	52,1019	9,6002	-	68,2407	16,1389	0,04	-	74,43
WARNEMUNDEZ	54,1697	12,1033	216	95%	6.945,6898	-	189,2778	54,3102	134,9677	-	206,0116	151,7014	0,14	-	332,40
WAVELAND,GULFOFMEX.,MS	30,2817	89,3667	216	95%	7.254,6620	-	131,4880	254,6620	123,1740	-	54,9384	199,7236	0,66	-	62,95
WESTPORTHARBOUR	41,7456	171,5947	216	95%	6.887,4815	-	125,0291	112,5185	12,5106	-	129,6812	17,1627	0,05	-	104,02
WIDO	35,6181	126,3019	216	95%	7.118,1852	-	74,7275	118,1852	43,4577	-	42,2413	75,9439	0,29	-	1,28
WINTERHARBOUR	50,5167	128,0333	216	95%	7.066,4907	-	1,1160	66,4907	65,3748	-	35,2805	101,7713	0,29	-	88,91
YAKUTAT	59,5483	139,7333	216	95%	7.126,7685	-	18,4868	126,7685	145,2553	-	54,6228	181,3913	0,30	-	183,72

YKSPIHLAJA	63,8333	23,0333	216	95%	7.048,4259	36,0398	48,4259	12,3862	34,3301	14,0958	0,00	34,33
YOSIOKA	41,4500	140,2500	216	95%	6.906,0000	76,3439	94,0000	17,6561	68,4747	25,5253	0,10	44,06
YSTAD	55,4167	13,8167	216	95%	6.718,0185	139,6712	281,9815	- 421,6527	205,7625	487,7439	0,58	607,75
ALOTAU	-	10,3167	215	94%	7.040,4186	5,9998	40,4186	46,4184	31,2686	71,6872	0,20	69,75
BALBOA	8,9667	79,5667	215	94%	6.764,4186	122,6325	235,5814	- 112,9489	100,4105	135,1709	0,04	95,10
BEACHPORT	-	37,5000	215	94%	6.959,4326	105,6638	40,5674	65,0964	126,9134	86,3460	0,09	148,78
BOMBAY(PRINCESDOCK)	18,9500	72,8333	215	94%	7.134,8605	66,0257	134,8605	68,8348	52,4492	82,4113	0,12	14,29
BREST	48,3829	4,4948	215	94%	7.130,4419	5,2863	130,4419	135,7281	18,5897	149,0316	0,08	107,84
CHOSHI-GYOKO	35,7444	140,8583	215	94%	7.154,7628	157,0326	154,7628	- 2,2698	168,3464	13,5836	0,02	163,97
CRISTOBAL	9,3500	79,9167	215	94%	7.057,7395	30,9005	57,7395	26,8390	23,1178	34,6217	0,01	27,93
ERDEK	40,3833	27,8500	215	94%	6.907,8465	74,2980	92,1535	17,8555	65,4690	26,6845	0,08	49,24
GANII	-	0,6833	215	94%	7.078,4698	38,2337	78,4698	40,2361	16,4627	62,0071	0,19	20,39
GEIBERGA(GEIBERGAOSTROV)	77,6000	101,5167	215	94%	7.119,1023	97,6051	119,1023	21,4972	81,4011	37,7012	0,13	64,07
GISBORNE	-	38,6755	215	94%	7.055,5488	2,9990	55,5488	52,5499	24,6014	80,1502	0,23	71,63
KAGOSHIMAI	31,6000	130,5667	215	94%	7.043,3488	3,2660	43,3488	40,0828	9,8293	53,1782	0,09	33,11
LEWES(BREAKWATERHARBOR)	38,7817	-	215	94%	6.792,0698	39,8590	207,9302	- 247,7892	91,2496	299,1798	0,47	348,88
LUCINDA	-	18,5167	215	94%	7.155,1256	121,6854	155,1256	33,4401	82,4103	72,7153	0,35	48,10
MAKURAZAKII	31,2667	130,3000	215	94%	7.141,7163	72,0240	141,7163	69,6922	41,7876	99,9287	0,20	2,49
MIAMIBEACH	25,7683	80,1317	215	94%	7.142,6326	34,5768	142,6326	108,0557	9,1058	133,5268	0,20	80,78
MOZAMBIQUEISLAND	-	15,0333	215	94%	7.041,8651	0,5329	41,8651	42,3980	18,3863	60,2514	0,10	39,76
NAGOYAI	35,0914	136,8808	215	94%	7.071,4744	29,1125	71,4744	42,3619	7,3505	64,1239	0,19	33,28
RAFFLESLIGHTHOUSE	1,1667	103,7500	215	94%	6.717,7674	278,0496	282,2326	- 4,1830	275,0190	7,2136	0,07	304,08
SALERNO	40,6766	14,7508	215	94%	6.940,5302	84,9289	59,4698	25,4592	134,3220	74,8522	0,28	133,94
SANJUAN	18,4583	66,1150	215	94%	7.035,0791	22,1086	35,0791	12,9705	15,9864	19,0927	0,06	2,45
SASEBOI	33,1667	129,7167	215	94%	7.055,3814	5,4349	55,3814	60,8163	24,4702	79,8516	0,10	50,67
SHIRAHAMA	33,6836	135,3753	215	94%	7.056,1488	6,0440	56,1488	50,1049	14,9069	71,0558	0,16	54,65
TRIBENI	22,9833	88,4000	215	94%	7.205,8326	94,6376	205,8326	111,1949	48,4896	157,3430	0,39	55,62
WEIPA	-	12,6667	215	94%	7.121,0605	43,7503	121,0605	77,3102	10,4727	110,5878	0,27	54,35

YARMOUTH	43,8333	-	66,1333	215	94%	7.062,6093	26,2047	62,6093	36,4046	-	2,2018	64,8111	0,27	-	41,53
CAMBRIDGEII	38,5733	-	76,0683	214	94%	6.972,0140	49,2312	27,9860	21,2453	-	58,5786	30,5926	0,11	-	89,66
CAPAUXMEULES	47,3789	-	61,8573	214	94%	7.018,4860	48,5767	18,4860	-	30,0908	65,8053	47,3193	0,12	-	88,52
HONNGU	18,8000	-	105,7667	214	94%	7.099,9065	29,8102	99,9065	70,0963	-	1,6705	98,2361	0,19	-	45,66
KAVIENG	-	2,5833	150,8000	214	94%	7.024,2617	21,6986	24,2617	45,9603	-	44,9439	69,2056	0,16	-	74,05
KERGUELEN	-	49,3515	70,2555	214	94%	6.966,1869	97,2746	33,8131	63,4615	-	135,2893	101,4762	0,37	-	206,76
KEYWEST	24,5550	-	81,8067	214	94%	6.479,7664	469,9564	520,2336	-	50,2773	459,4983	60,7353	0,01	-	480,42
KOCHIII	33,5000	-	133,5833	214	94%	6.893,0607	145,4907	106,9393	38,5514	-	163,6823	56,7431	0,14	-	198,80
KRASNOFLOTSKIE(KRASNOFLOTSKIEOSTROVA)	78,6000	-	98,8333	214	94%	7.191,2664	7,6819	191,2664	183,5845	-	57,0748	248,3411	0,49	-	202,79
LOMBRUM	-	2,0421	147,3738	214	94%	7.114,9626	79,2254	114,9626	35,7372	-	58,6265	56,3361	0,17	-	27,59
MANUSISLAND	-	2,0167	147,2667	214	94%	7.110,4112	53,4558	110,4112	56,9554	-	24,8015	85,6097	0,25	-	27,06
MARDEAJO	-	36,7000	56,6667	214	94%	7.321,7196	67,1988	321,7196	254,5208	-	57,5921	379,3118	0,60	-	132,33
NEDRENYKOPING	58,7500	-	17,0167	214	94%	6.946,0654	64,0816	53,9346	10,1471	-	66,3036	12,3691	0,02	-	55,70
PRINCERUPERT	54,3167	-	130,3333	214	94%	7.145,8692	3,7064	145,8692	142,1628	-	34,0062	179,8753	0,31	-	159,95
RINGHALS	57,2497	-	12,1125	214	94%	7.013,3131	25,4443	13,3131	38,7574	-	57,3643	70,6774	0,28	-	99,82
SANDNESSJOEN	66,0167	-	12,6333	214	94%	7.548,9206	414,3154	548,9206	134,6051	-	356,1624	192,7581	0,48	-	235,66
SCOTTBASE	-	77,8501	166,7690	214	94%	7.079,0000	74,4708	79,0000	4,5292	-	71,7131	7,2869	0,06	-	58,94
SHEDIACBAY	46,2500	-	64,5333	214	94%	7.058,7383	6,2000	58,7383	52,5383	-	17,9001	76,6384	0,20	-	67,23
SPLITRTMARJANA	43,5083	-	16,3917	214	94%	7.005,9907	17,7996	5,9907	23,7903	-	25,1986	31,1893	0,06	-	43,96
SUVA-A	-	18,1357	178,4228	214	94%	7.028,2336	27,6870	28,2336	55,9206	-	52,0321	80,2657	0,20	-	101,34
TOKYOIII	35,6486	-	139,7700	214	94%	6.948,2430	66,5342	51,7570	14,7772	-	73,2459	21,4889	0,02	-	72,59
UDDEVALLA	58,3475	-	11,8947	214	94%	7.012,5748	4,7824	12,5748	17,3572	-	41,3814	53,9562	0,33	-	59,67
VERAVAL	20,9000	-	70,3667	214	94%	7.080,6075	46,6581	80,6075	33,9494	-	26,1033	54,5042	0,20	-	7,97
VICTORIADOCK	1,2667	-	103,8500	214	94%	7.061,5701	53,7896	61,5701	7,7805	-	42,2590	19,3111	0,13	-	27,80
WANGANUI	-	39,9446	174,9932	214	94%	7.071,4206	37,5470	71,4206	33,8736	-	19,6425	51,7780	0,13	-	5,00
GUIRIA	10,5667	-	62,2833	213	93%	7.096,3146	18,3323	96,3146	77,9823	-	14,2444	110,5590	0,36	-	118,40
LAGOMERA	28,0878	-	17,1083	213	93%	7.122,8732	95,4904	122,8732	27,3829	-	76,3691	46,5042	0,11	-	64,42
LASPALMASD	28,1406	-	15,4118	213	93%	6.986,5117	20,5222	13,4883	7,0340	-	23,8001	10,3118	0,00	-	21,80

MANZANILLO	20,3333	- 77,1500	213	93%	7.125,7606	60,0598	125,7606	65,7007	22,0150	103,7456	0,32	- 35,15
MARATHONSHORES	24,7333	- 81,0333	213	93%	6.944,4977	- 87,7247	- 55,5023	32,2224	- 128,7593	73,2569	0,26	- 140,04
PORTOGRANDE(ST.VINCENT)2	16,8833	- 25,0000	213	93%	7.127,4131	39,7005	127,4131	87,7126	- 9,2103	136,6234	0,36	- 70,86
PUERTODEHIERRO	10,6167	- 62,0833	213	93%	6.961,1831	- 35,0230	- 38,8169	- 3,7939	- 35,0413	- 3,7756	0,04	- 52,95
QIKIQTARJUAQ	67,8667	- 64,1167	213	93%	7.004,0423	1,1430	4,0423	2,8992	- 24,2782	28,3205	0,32	- 37,79
SANTACRUZDETENERIFEI	28,4772	- 16,2412	213	93%	7.190,5164	74,7290	190,5164	115,7875	49,0064	141,5100	0,20	- 48,65
STORNOWAY	58,2078	- 6,3890	213	93%	7.127,5164	- 40,2940	127,5164	87,2224	11,1368	116,3796	0,22	- 58,82
SYDNEYPORTJACKSON	- 33,8255	151,2585	213	93%	7.121,3850	73,1077	121,3850	48,2773	24,7051	96,6799	0,41	- 17,11
ZADAR	44,1233	15,2350	213	93%	7.008,3521	- 33,4699	8,3521	41,8220	- 60,4535	68,8056	0,18	- 86,71
ALERTBAY	50,5833	- 126,9500	212	93%	7.055,3491	- 30,1488	55,3491	85,4979	- 54,1233	109,4723	0,22	- 142,79
FORTPHRACHULACHOMKLAO(POMPHRACHUN)	13,5500	100,5833	212	93%	7.015,5708	0,2697	15,5708	15,3011	- 18,2613	33,8320	0,16	- 30,91
JAMESTOWNLANDINGSTEPS	- 15,9209	- 5,7180	212	93%	7.032,0094	19,9007	32,0094	12,1087	12,8362	19,1732	0,02	- 26,00
JEJU	33,5275	126,5431	212	93%	7.145,2972	95,0881	145,2972	50,2091	74,6414	70,6558	0,13	- 45,61
KAOHSIUNGII	22,5333	120,3167	212	93%	7.009,2689	- 31,9109	9,2689	41,1798	- 50,5973	59,8662	0,11	- 69,48
KEYCOLONYBEACH	24,7183	- 81,0167	212	93%	7.065,8774	59,2271	65,8774	6,6503	56,3052	9,5721	0,03	- 47,59
LAMUB	- 2,2717	40,9033	212	93%	7.042,1509	17,6218	42,1509	24,5292	- 1,0581	43,2090	0,18	- 28,85
LIMHAMN	55,5833	12,9333	212	93%	6.996,8962	- 39,4441	- 3,1038	36,3404	- 59,9378	56,8340	0,16	- 90,93
LORDHOWEISLAND	- 31,5167	159,0667	212	93%	7.146,6509	3,4438	146,6509	143,2072	- 47,8454	194,4963	0,35	- 143,41
NAHA	26,2133	127,6653	212	93%	7.026,6887	20,1876	26,6887	6,5011	- 1,0304	27,7191	0,13	- 1,54
PALINURO	40,0299	15,2753	212	93%	7.143,0896	108,3023	143,0896	34,7873	84,0508	59,0388	0,22	- 49,09
PENSACOLA	30,4033	- 87,2100	212	93%	7.238,8962	188,0169	238,8962	50,8794	158,7243	80,1719	0,18	- 131,88
SEOGWIPO	33,2400	126,5617	212	93%	7.103,4906	52,7492	103,4906	50,7413	25,7428	77,7478	0,23	- 21,90
TIKSI(TIKSIBUKHTA)	71,5833	128,9167	212	93%	6.979,8774	- 33,3109	- 20,1226	13,1883	- 37,5326	17,4100	0,02	- 25,37
AKKO	32,9193	35,0702	211	93%	7.134,7204	86,1891	134,7204	48,5313	50,2271	84,4933	0,28	- 15,16
BARHARBOR,FRENCHMANBAY,ME	44,3917	- 68,2050	211	93%	6.994,6540	- 12,0535	- 5,3460	6,7075	- 14,5033	9,1574	0,01	- 14,71
BUGRINO	68,8000	49,3333	211	93%	7.017,1090	- 18,7588	17,1090	35,8678	- 42,0457	59,1547	0,17	- 68,02
INVERGORDON	- 57,6833	- 4,1667	211	93%	7.099,3128	- 26,0086	99,3128	73,3042	- 3,3287	102,6415	0,21	- 59,59

PALMADEMALLORCA2	39,5602	2,6375	211	93%	7.009,6825	-	17,5394	9,6825	27,2218	-	37,2673	46,9498	0,18	-	66,22	
PANAMACITY,ST.ANDREWSBAY,FL	30,1517	-	211	93%	6.926,5545	-	121,2517	-	73,4455	47,8062	-	182,6567	109,2112	0,46	-	216,25
PIRAMIDE	-	-	211	93%	7.122,6066	4,6612	122,6066	117,9454	-	37,6021	160,2087	0,37	-	144,83	-	
PORTOEMPEDOCLE,SICILY	37,2858	13,5268	211	93%	6.981,5166	-	29,9467	-	18,4834	11,4633	39,0882	20,6048	0,06	-	46,59	
PORTORFORD	42,7383	-	211	93%	6.938,8910	-	109,8723	-	61,1090	48,7633	-	138,1051	76,9961	0,22	-	178,42
PORTSANLUIS	35,1767	-	211	93%	7.059,1469	-	64,2802	-	59,1469	123,4271	-	95,8950	155,0419	0,27	-	206,82
PORTVENDRES	42,5201	3,1073	211	93%	7.180,4645	90,0723	180,4645	90,3922	-	45,6364	134,8281	0,38	-	35,56	-	
SUVA-B	-	-	211	93%	7.057,2322	43,0767	57,2322	14,1555	-	27,8124	29,4199	0,10	-	21,04	-	
ANCHORAGE	61,2383	-	210	92%	7.093,6095	69,5067	93,6095	24,1029	-	59,0130	34,5965	0,06	-	45,84	-	
MAKAR,GENERALSANTOSCITY	6,1000	125,1500	210	92%	6.962,1857	-	46,0376	-	37,8143	8,2233	-	53,5923	15,7780	0,02	-	50,27
MALYITAIMYR(MALYITAIMYROSTROV)	78,0833	106,8167	210	92%	6.905,7619	189,9447	-	94,2381	-	284,1828	276,2433	-	370,4814	-	0,75	543,83
MARIIPRONCHISHEVOI(BUKHTA)	75,5333	113,4333	210	92%	6.896,8095	-	152,0275	-	103,1905	48,8370	-	167,8789	64,6884	0,17	-	229,62
NUKUHIVA	-	-	210	92%	6.979,0048	-	50,5967	-	20,9952	29,6014	-	67,3470	46,3517	0,12	-	89,36
STLAWRENCE	46,9168	-	210	92%	7.078,1524	46,3199	78,1524	31,8325	-	14,8756	63,2768	0,31	-	22,17	-	
AVEIRO	40,6500	-	209	92%	6.935,3301	-	132,5248	-	64,6699	67,8549	-	163,0275	98,3576	0,30	-	235,50
CHERRYPOINT	48,8633	-	209	92%	7.107,8947	75,0169	107,8947	32,8778	-	58,3738	49,5210	0,11	-	39,67	-	
CHITTAGONGA	22,2467	91,8250	209	92%	7.038,8947	10,8360	38,8947	28,0587	-	11,4213	50,3161	0,25	-	54,66	-	
CULEBRA	18,3017	-	209	92%	7.153,4306	122,7371	153,4306	30,6935	-	100,3817	53,0489	0,21	-	67,90	-	
KUNGSVIK	58,9967	11,1272	209	92%	7.071,4785	35,8860	71,4785	35,5925	-	12,2469	59,2316	0,19	-	16,02	-	
SAGUNTO	39,6339	-	209	92%	7.150,0335	99,9074	150,0335	50,1261	-	65,8021	84,2314	0,40	-	10,77	-	
ZHELANIAII(ZHELANIAMYS)	76,9500	68,5500	209	92%	7.001,9665	-	60,9194	1,9665	62,8859	-	80,6662	82,6327	0,16	-	134,89	
ALCUDIA	39,8346	3,1390	208	91%	7.114,9808	67,7077	114,9808	47,2731	-	37,7263	77,2544	0,26	-	3,53	-	
GDYNIA	54,5333	18,5500	208	91%	7.427,8798	290,5536	427,8798	137,3262	-	258,0702	169,8096	0,18	-	187,58	-	
NORTHSOUND	19,3000	-	208	91%	7.121,6731	89,9748	121,6731	31,6983	-	76,2759	45,3972	0,11	-	52,02	-	
PUERTOARMUELLES	8,2667	-	208	91%	7.105,0913	33,3077	105,0913	71,7836	-	10,9193	94,1721	0,20	-	58,36	-	
AMBARCIK	69,6167	162,3000	207	91%	7.024,6570	-	4,9122	24,6570	29,5692	-	13,3987	38,0557	0,09	-	48,48	

KINGBAY	-													
	20,6236	116,7491	207	91%	7.142,9372	36,6970	142,9372	106,2402	-	15,3028	158,2400	0,43	-	105,40
NAGOYA	35,0833	136,8833	207	91%	6.937,9130	99,4627	62,0870	37,3757	-	110,6946	48,6077	0,04	-	115,87
NEWHAVEN	50,7818	0,0570	207	91%	7.093,5894	13,4183	93,5894	80,1711	-	28,8558	122,4452	0,37	-	108,08
SOLENZARA	41,8569	9,4038	207	91%	7.136,0966	103,3813	136,0966	32,7153	-	81,3403	54,7564	0,19	-	55,59
TOKEPOINT,WILLIPABAY,WA	46,7067	123,9667	207	91%	7.143,4010	47,7550	143,4010	95,6460	-	6,9801	136,4209	0,31	-	62,31
TURKEYPOINT	29,9150	84,5117	207	91%	7.044,9420	34,3396	44,9420	79,2817	-	72,5346	117,4766	0,32	-	138,76
WAKKANAI	45,4078	141,6853	207	91%	6.999,1304	15,7677	0,8696	14,8981	-	21,1351	20,2655	0,00	-	16,60
AUCKLANDII	36,8431	174,7695	206	90%	6.586,9515	521,9342	413,0485	108,8857	-	541,0624	128,0139	0,13	-	612,92
MUSCAT	23,6333	58,5667	206	90%	7.066,0971	6,1672	66,0971	72,2643	-	42,2146	108,3117	0,31	-	106,33
BAHIADELOSANGELES	28,9667	113,5500	205	90%	7.020,5415	1,3487	20,5415	21,8902	-	35,3694	55,9108	0,27	-	53,88
IRAKLION	35,3485	25,1527	205	90%	7.090,2341	26,2312	90,2341	64,0030	-	7,0212	83,2129	0,13	-	39,02
MUOSTAH(MUOSTAHOSTROV)	71,5500	130,0333	205	90%	6.996,9756	64,7109	3,0244	61,6865	-	83,9377	80,9133	0,19	-	150,56
PORT-ALFRED	48,3333	70,8667	205	90%	7.077,7317	33,7036	77,7317	111,4353	-	83,0428	160,7745	0,41	-	177,42
BINTULU	3,2622	113,0639	204	89%	7.063,8284	46,6786	63,8284	17,1498	-	38,3416	25,4868	0,12	-	12,25
CORRAL	39,8667	73,4333	204	89%	7.105,7892	34,5648	105,7892	71,2244	-	7,2253	98,5640	0,20	-	43,51
HERNEBAY	51,3820	1,1156	204	89%	7.078,7549	33,9875	78,7549	44,7674	-	2,9012	81,6561	0,31	-	40,37
LAMADDALENA	41,2333	9,3667	204	89%	6.957,7500	37,1690	42,2500	5,0810	-	36,5156	5,7344	0,01	-	41,46
LUSI	32,1333	121,6167	204	89%	7.109,8333	57,5742	109,8333	52,2591	-	38,1697	71,6637	0,16	-	6,44
MONBETUI	44,3500	143,3667	204	89%	7.007,3627	12,5513	7,3627	19,9141	-	47,3527	54,7154	0,29	-	60,68
MOSULPO	33,2144	126,2511	204	89%	6.988,8578	71,1231	11,1422	59,9810	-	110,0159	98,8738	0,26	-	144,58
NEDREGAVLE	60,6833	17,1667	204	89%	7.101,3578	26,8428	101,3578	74,5150	-	14,9885	86,3693	0,09	-	43,55
PALERMO	38,1333	13,3333	204	89%	7.071,0196	73,5099	71,0196	2,4903	-	73,8512	2,8316	0,02	-	86,41
PORTOTORRES	40,8422	8,4039	204	89%	6.955,2157	56,7981	44,7843	12,0138	-	67,0310	22,2467	0,05	-	70,76
SALVADOR	12,9667	38,5167	204	89%	7.072,9412	6,1055	72,9412	66,8357	-	12,7734	85,7146	0,14	-	63,84
SAUMLAKI	7,9817	131,2900	204	89%	7.029,7941	24,9337	29,7941	4,8604	-	21,5963	8,1979	0,08	-	6,22
SKURU	60,1000	23,5500	204	89%	7.076,3824	26,3551	76,3824	50,0273	-	17,6431	58,7392	0,07	-	23,36
SLIPSHAVN	55,2883	10,8278	204	89%	7.113,1667	27,7411	113,1667	85,4255	-	13,8824	99,2842	0,10	-	52,97
TUKIZI	35,6667	139,7667	204	89%	7.140,6078	74,6479	140,6078	65,9599	-	53,9258	86,6821	0,17	-	3,74

ACAPULCO	16,8333	-99,9167	203	89%	6.994,2315	16,7595	-5,7685	-22,5280	23,8958	-29,6642	-0,09	57,19
APIAB	-13,8268	-171,7613	203	89%	7.171,9704	59,1004	171,9704	112,8701	0,2377	172,2081	0,49	87,90
LIVORNOII	43,5463	10,2993	203	89%	7.402,0788	191,8090	402,0788	210,2699	61,1085	340,9703	1,20	132,97
SANJOSE	12,3333	121,0833	203	89%	7.006,3596	-16,8605	6,3596	23,2201	-29,4011	35,7607	0,12	55,74
WHYALLA	-33,0167	137,5667	203	89%	7.092,0493	53,5213	92,0493	38,5279	35,9528	56,0964	0,14	5,76
AJACCIO	41,9228	8,7629	202	89%	7.098,0198	54,2261	98,0198	43,7937	27,3927	70,6271	0,23	12,21
KLAIPEDA	55,7000	21,1333	202	89%	7.033,1040	75,2904	33,1040	108,3944	93,3912	126,4952	0,15	187,22
RATMANOVA	65,8500	-169,1333	202	89%	7.428,0347	-31,8558	428,0347	459,8905	-164,2057	592,2404	1,19	594,35
SHOALBAY	-32,7197	152,1757	202	89%	7.084,6535	52,1123	84,6535	32,5411	24,6321	60,0214	0,23	0,30
TRIESTE	45,6474	13,7585	202	89%	7.077,3020	25,1958	77,3020	52,1062	16,9695	60,3325	0,03	0,12
FUNAFUTIB	-8,5025	179,1952	201	88%	7.091,1642	51,7294	91,1642	39,4348	30,8270	60,3371	0,14	8,71
HONOLULU	21,3067	-157,8667	201	88%	7.035,9701	42,6133	35,9701	78,5835	-54,9831	90,9533	0,10	117,97
PATRICIABAY	48,6500	-123,4500	201	88%	7.092,6766	47,1549	92,6766	45,5217	29,9361	62,7405	0,10	9,42
TERIBERKA	69,2000	35,1167	201	88%	7.079,0498	32,5356	79,0498	46,5142	6,2470	72,8028	0,21	28,78
IWASAKI	40,5833	139,9167	200	88%	7.089,2200	17,8590	89,2200	71,3610	6,1270	83,0930	0,09	45,83
NY-ALESUND	78,9285	11,9380	200	88%	7.040,7800	9,2266	40,7800	31,5534	-3,7895	44,5695	0,13	39,54
PUERTOLIMON	10,0000	83,0333	200	88%	7.062,0500	3,5919	62,0500	65,6419	-30,2188	92,2688	0,22	84,64
USTKARA	69,2500	64,5167	200	88%	7.088,7500	64,5138	88,7500	153,2638	-94,7284	183,4784	0,27	241,13
MILNERBAY(GROOTEYLANDT)	-13,8601	136,4156	199	87%	7.025,9095	15,9466	25,9095	9,9629	13,9213	11,9882	0,04	1,57
SAPPI	61,4833	21,3333	199	87%	7.053,1156	-17,5585	53,1156	70,6741	-35,7582	88,8738	0,09	58,10
TENERIFE	28,4772	16,2411	199	87%	7.066,5176	37,4174	66,5176	29,1002	22,8684	43,6491	0,08	11,45
DANANG	16,1000	108,2167	198	87%	6.933,2172	76,1054	66,7828	9,3226	-101,8121	35,0292	0,22	108,75
HANSTHOLM	57,1189	8,5956	198	87%	7.006,4040	25,5997	6,4040	-19,1957	31,8560	25,4519	0,07	56,23
PORThEDLAND	-20,3176	118,5744	198	87%	7.508,9596	40,0686	508,9596	549,0282	-135,5548	644,5144	0,65	502,70
SEWARD	60,1200	149,4267	198	87%	7.136,7374	43,4788	136,7374	93,2586	24,7558	111,9816	0,15	49,57
TONOURA	34,9000	132,0667	198	87%	7.082,7980	23,7486	82,7980	59,0494	14,7645	68,0335	0,05	17,46
DUBLAT(SAUGORIS.)	21,6333	88,1333	197	86%	7.088,3401	-376,0760	88,3401	464,4161	-439,4657	527,8058	0,56	858,88
MANGALORE(PANAMBURU)	12,9167	74,8000	197	86%	7.098,0254	16,5689	98,0254	81,4565	-18,6879	116,7133	0,27	74,19

PORTROYAL	17,9333	-	197	86%	6.936,7005	0,1668	-	63,4662	23,6055	-	0,21	89,20	
BUKOM	1,2256	103,7785	196	86%	7.191,5102	98,4585	191,5102	93,0517	44,8525	146,6577	0,40	14,63	
MAJURO-C	7,1060	171,3728	196	86%	7.025,4337	7,8207	25,4337	33,2544	23,9894	49,4231	0,06	26,70	
NORFOLKISLAND	-	167,9536	196	86%	7.059,0816	2,0000	59,0816	57,0817	13,8273	72,9089	0,13	52,79	
CAPEMAY	38,9683	-	195	86%	7.067,4513	40,9430	67,4513	26,5083	19,7848	47,6665	0,17	0,11	
SANJOSEII	13,9167	-	195	86%	7.032,6974	30,2694	32,6974	2,4280	12,7073	19,9901	0,01	31,55	
BERGENPOINT,STATENIS.	40,6367	-	194	85%	7.157,0825	141,5085	157,0825	15,5740	129,4909	27,5916	0,16	104,58	
GRONSKAR	59,2833	19,0333	194	85%	7.016,6186	-	69,6295	16,6186	86,2480	82,2448	98,8634	0,10	151,08
VENEZIA(PUNTADELLASALUTE)	45,4333	12,3333	194	85%	7.474,9897	175,2422	474,9897	299,7475	62,8842	412,1055	0,89	151,93	
FORMENTERA	38,7347	1,4190	193	85%	7.523,2798	301,7499	523,2798	221,5299	173,2874	349,9924	1,22	32,39	
JACKSONVILLE	30,3500	-	193	85%	7.194,6166	80,9047	194,6166	113,7119	46,3973	148,2193	0,26	33,12	
SANDPOINT,POPOFIS.,AK	55,3367	-	193	85%	6.999,7772	30,0714	0,2228	29,8486	44,1359	43,9131	0,11	64,63	
SHEKPIK	22,2203	113,8944	193	85%	6.994,4093	8,4409	5,5907	14,0316	16,8116	22,4023	0,03	16,04	
DEAL	51,2238	1,4092	192	84%	6.996,1354	23,9388	3,8646	20,0743	44,5630	40,6984	0,19	59,06	
HEUKSANDO	34,6839	125,4364	192	84%	7.054,2500	5,0957	54,2500	49,1543	16,3056	70,5556	0,20	58,40	
LALIBERTAD	-	80,9167	192	84%	7.054,7604	-	11,2399	54,7604	66,0003	28,8002	83,5606	0,11	68,67
PRIGI	8,2800	111,7300	192	84%	7.112,9479	70,3382	112,9479	42,6097	43,2756	69,6723	0,26	4,70	
SAIPAN	15,2333	145,7500	192	84%	6.945,8177	74,3648	54,1823	20,1825	82,2657	28,0834	0,19	136,38	
HILO,HAWAIIISLAND	19,7300	-	191	84%	7.130,6754	27,5672	130,6754	103,1082	5,3212	125,3542	0,13	54,52	
ILETLAMERE	4,8938	-	191	84%	7.055,3141	22,2516	55,3141	33,0626	0,8993	56,2135	0,22	32,12	
KIPTOPEKEBEACH	37,1650	-	191	84%	7.069,2094	50,5139	69,2094	18,6955	45,1037	24,1057	0,02	59,12	
CHARLOTTEAMALIE	18,3350	-	190	83%	7.035,4684	8,9695	35,4684	26,4989	1,3724	36,8408	0,07	16,47	
CRESCENTCITY	41,7450	-	190	83%	6.997,1895	52,8141	2,8105	50,0035	87,5553	84,7448	0,30	126,15	
EASTLONDON	-	27,9317	190	83%	6.913,2368	99,5675	86,7632	12,8044	115,4244	28,6613	0,17	130,86	
OKHA	22,4667	69,0833	190	83%	7.080,9421	46,3761	80,9421	34,5661	31,0103	49,9318	0,16	8,84	
ST.MARYS	49,9179	-	190	83%	7.051,0053	2,5066	51,0053	53,5118	30,5310	81,5363	0,27	81,65	
VARDO	70,3750	31,1040	190	83%	7.061,6526	-	10,5189	61,6526	72,1715	47,7830	109,4356	0,31	103,11
DALHOUSIE	48,0667	-	189	83%	6.949,3757	75,7817	50,6243	25,1574	118,1386	67,5143	0,37	136,06	

FORTMYERS	26,6467	-	189	83%	7.077,2804	55,3543	77,2804	21,9261	47,9992	29,2812	0,05	35,58	
SANTIAGODECUBA	20,0205	-	189	83%	7.059,3122	20,5022	59,3122	38,8099	0,1207	59,1915	0,14	16,44	
CUXHAVEN2	53,8667	8,7167	188	82%	7.058,9309	26,9457	58,9309	85,8765	-	49,9492	108,8801	0,17	109,76
PORTVILAB	-	17,7553	188	82%	7.138,0160	77,4241	138,0160	60,5919	47,7664	90,2496	0,22	11,25	
TWEEDENTRANCESOUTH	-	28,1706	188	82%	7.061,6968	47,9364	61,6968	13,7604	32,5755	29,1214	0,17	17,88	
DAESAN	37,0075	126,3528	187	82%	6.987,3850	53,6480	12,6150	41,0331	-	96,9455	84,3305	0,36	126,59
INCEPOINT	-	10,5083	187	82%	7.064,7594	0,8336	64,7594	63,9258	-	21,4417	86,2011	0,18	63,64
MARDELPLATA(NAVALBASE)	-	38,0333	187	82%	7.072,5668	0,5944	72,5668	71,9725	-	21,2972	93,8640	0,16	64,29
SANDAKAN	5,8100	118,0672	186	82%	6.976,4892	2,0060	23,5108	25,5167	-	15,6522	39,1629	0,19	59,48
GENOVAII	44,4101	8,9255	185	81%	7.042,4973	20,6591	42,4973	21,8382	8,9014	33,5959	0,10	5,33	
VANCOUVER	49,2833	-	185	81%	6.809,3514	139,3873	190,6486	51,2614	-	115,9602	74,6885	0,05	157,63
OURA	32,9767	130,2206	184	81%	7.094,8043	42,5524	94,8043	52,2519	24,5133	70,2911	0,13	8,08	
SYDNEY,FORTDENISON	-	33,8500	184	81%	6.971,4457	164,0851	28,5543	135,5308	-	181,3063	152,7520	0,14	281,70
KOPER	45,5481	13,7246	183	80%	7.008,3607	2,5992	8,3607	5,7615	0,4522	7,9084	0,03	7,34	
PORTAUGUSTA	-	32,5500	183	80%	7.115,4918	90,3388	115,4918	25,1530	81,8419	33,6499	0,00	89,87	
VILLAGARCIA	42,6007	-	183	80%	7.042,3880	36,0979	42,3880	6,2901	32,3506	10,0374	0,01	39,93	
GARIBALDI	45,5533	-	182	80%	7.049,1099	24,2468	49,1099	73,3567	-	48,7277	97,8376	0,13	70,94
PORTOCORSINI	44,5000	12,2833	182	80%	7.045,0824	10,6176	45,0824	55,7000	-	18,5418	63,6242	0,05	45,75
NAOSISLAND2	8,9183	-	181	79%	7.114,3702	79,1477	114,3702	35,2225	63,6923	50,6779	0,16	31,73	
PORTADELAIDE(OUTERHARBOR)	-	34,7798	181	79%	7.064,3812	25,3837	64,3812	38,9976	0,9298	63,4514	0,19	22,30	
BOLVANSKIINOS(FEDOROVA)	70,4500	59,0833	180	79%	7.076,1833	5,8542	76,1833	82,0376	-	28,9575	105,1409	0,20	94,38
MONTAUK	41,0483	-	180	79%	7.138,4389	46,7142	138,4389	91,7247	26,6355	111,8034	0,17	43,33	
VENEZIA(ARSENALE)	45,4167	12,3500	180	79%	6.901,4778	43,8542	98,5222	142,3765	-	62,4674	160,9896	0,20	201,27
WESTCOAST	1,3000	103,7667	180	79%	7.089,3389	54,4807	89,3389	34,8582	34,5139	54,8250	0,21	4,00	
AMHERST	16,0833	97,5667	179	79%	7.136,0503	54,7398	136,0503	81,3105	28,6741	107,3762	0,32	74,34	
ASAMUSHI	40,8975	140,8592	179	79%	7.305,0559	134,7413	305,0559	170,3145	84,1775	220,8783	0,42	44,56	
GWANGYANG	34,9036	127,7547	179	79%	7.114,0670	79,4604	114,0670	34,6067	55,1543	58,9127	0,17	39,24	
CALDERA	-	27,0667	178	78%	7.231,6517	128,7036	231,6517	102,9480	-	103,0719	128,5797	0,14	62,08

MIYAKESIMA	34,0672	139,4808	178	78%	7.089,2528	60,9622	89,2528	28,2906	47,1170	42,1358	0,12	24,53	
PREOBRAZHENIA(PREOBRAZHENIAOSTROV)	74,6667	112,9333	178	78%	7.065,8989	45,0223	65,8989	110,9212	-	77,4888	143,3877	0,31	187,71
BANGOR	54,6648	-	176	77%	7.096,4375	64,1888	96,4375	32,2487	48,7452	47,6923	0,13	27,00	
CARTAGENA	10,4000	75,5500	176	77%	7.009,0909	34,3468	9,0909	43,4377	-	54,1588	63,2497	0,06	52,95
ALESUND	62,4694	6,1519	173	76%	7.067,8671	18,3828	67,8671	49,4843	7,5558	60,3112	0,07	18,93	
BETIO	1,3651	172,9330	173	76%	7.036,5434	3,1092	36,5434	39,6525	-	32,3313	68,8746	0,22	49,63
SABANG	5,8883	95,3167	172	75%	7.078,9477	67,3904	78,9477	11,5573	60,2307	18,7169	0,07	48,67	
NIKISKI,ALASKA	60,6833	151,3967	171	75%	7.064,2339	7,1667	64,2339	57,0672	-	12,1603	76,3942	0,16	48,70
TAN-NOWA	34,3389	135,1781	171	75%	7.019,9942	21,6422	19,9942	41,6363	-	32,5123	52,5065	0,08	57,49
DAYTONABEACH	29,2333	81,0000	170	75%	7.018,1882	17,1453	18,1882	35,3336	-	23,7400	41,9283	0,05	47,49
OCEANCITYINLET	38,3283	75,0917	170	75%	7.248,8824	152,9265	248,8824	95,9559	84,9419	163,9405	0,56	25,08	
RUSSKII(RUSSKIIOSTROV)	77,1667	96,4333	170	75%	7.096,9765	30,0184	96,9765	126,9949	-	66,7105	163,6870	0,30	147,99
SELDOVIA	59,4400	151,7200	170	75%	7.099,4294	47,4574	99,4294	51,9720	32,4277	67,0017	0,11	4,30	
DOVER	51,1144	1,3227	169	74%	7.063,5148	34,5729	63,5148	98,0877	-	48,7541	112,2689	0,16	153,34
PUNTAARENAS	-	70,9000	168	74%	7.100,7143	47,9044	100,7143	52,8099	36,7933	63,9210	0,09	5,26	
BUNDABERG,BURNETTHEADS	24,7667	152,3833	167	73%	7.031,4910	8,5479	31,4910	22,9431	-	35,0921	66,5831	0,81	94,09
MIKUNI	36,2547	136,1489	167	73%	7.015,5749	31,3465	15,5748	46,9213	-	46,9939	62,5688	0,13	75,22
PORTIRENE	18,3833	122,1000	167	73%	7.128,1198	77,9314	128,1198	50,1883	56,2020	71,9177	0,19	18,52	
BROOME	18,0008	122,2186	165	72%	7.094,1212	30,8575	94,1212	63,2637	11,2756	82,8456	0,14	20,61	
IBIZA	38,9112	1,4498	161	71%	7.081,7019	6,7578	81,7019	88,4597	-	46,3181	128,0199	0,29	90,49
KAVALLA	40,9346	24,4121	161	71%	7.075,3975	30,8008	75,3975	44,5967	14,7727	60,6248	0,15	22,56	
UNO	34,4886	133,9494	159	70%	6.938,2516	88,2944	61,7484	26,5460	-	94,4813	32,7328	0,04	104,45
KANTONISLAND-B	2,8167	171,7167	158	69%	7.031,5886	39,1317	31,5886	70,7203	63,6596	95,2482	0,17	100,86	
MANZANILLO	19,0500	104,3333	158	69%	7.152,9873	107,2459	152,9873	45,7415	96,4495	56,5378	0,18	29,80	
FRENCHFRIGATESHOALS	23,8683	166,2883	157	69%	6.926,2420	61,8916	73,7580	11,8664	-	53,2468	20,5111	0,07	45,32
PORTCHALMERS	45,8147	170,6241	157	69%	7.059,4140	40,6151	59,4140	18,7990	24,1140	35,3000	0,15	14,06	
CAPETOWN(GRANGERBAY)	-	18,4347	156	68%	7.013,0897	31,0256	13,0897	44,1153	-	45,1847	58,2745	0,18	91,68
CENTURI	42,9658	9,3498	156	68%	7.044,9103	40,7359	44,9103	4,1744	37,9052	7,0050	0,03	34,02	

HAIKOU	20,0167	110,2833	156	68%	6.926,8462	87,5167	-	73,1538	-	160,6706	146,4211	-	219,5749	-	0,50	242,36
INCHEONSONGDO	37,3381	126,5861	156	68%	7.021,4103	19,7454	21,4103	41,1557	-	45,2643	66,6745	0,28	-	-	-	81,35
LYMINGTON	50,7403	1,5071	156	68%	7.064,5897	32,2216	64,5897	32,3681	10,2022	54,3876	0,31	-	-	-	-	33,63
PORTISABEL	26,0600	97,2150	156	68%	7.116,1410	61,5922	116,1410	54,5488	50,3555	65,7856	0,10	-	-	-	-	11,68
GANGHWADAEGYO	37,7319	126,5222	154	68%	7.085,0000	34,3434	85,0000	50,6566	4,7165	80,2835	0,19	-	-	-	-	12,10
ISLAY(PORTELEN)	55,6276	6,1899	153	67%	6.949,9216	80,7915	50,0784	30,7130	91,0769	40,9985	0,04	-	-	-	-	92,96
REYKJAVIK	64,1506	21,9399	153	67%	7.128,9804	64,6301	128,9804	64,3503	50,5170	78,4633	0,10	-	-	-	-	17,06
LEAVA	14,2960	178,1602	152	67%	7.019,3355	29,9022	19,3355	49,2378	58,0721	77,4076	0,28	-	-	-	-	89,68
VISAKHAPATNAM	17,6833	83,2833	152	67%	7.053,4803	48,9919	53,4803	4,4884	47,1417	6,3385	0,05	-	-	-	-	31,33
SOLOMON'SISLAND(BIOL.LAB.)	38,3167	76,4517	151	66%	7.030,0464	0,2591	30,0464	29,7873	-	10,4547	40,5011	0,10	-	-	-	27,92
BURNIE	41,0501	145,9150	150	66%	6.994,4933	66,3156	5,5067	60,8089	-	80,1923	74,6857	0,04	-	-	-	81,22
RABAU	4,2000	152,1833	150	66%	7.058,9867	31,8276	58,9867	27,1591	25,2715	33,7152	0,02	-	-	-	-	22,59
KANTONISLAND	2,8000	171,7167	148	65%	7.082,9054	13,0363	82,9054	69,8691	-	17,2692	100,1746	0,29	-	-	-	72,37
LINAKHAMARI	69,6500	31,3667	144	63%	7.115,6250	86,7475	115,6250	28,8775	65,7132	49,9118	0,25	-	-	-	-	40,26
OFUNATOI	39,0667	141,7167	144	63%	7.064,1042	7,5356	64,1042	71,6398	28,8044	92,9086	0,22	-	-	-	-	81,72
TALCAHUANO	36,6833	73,1000	144	63%	6.984,6667	78,0900	15,3333	62,7567	-	102,7565	87,4231	0,27	-	-	-	155,08
BUSANNEWPORT	35,0775	128,7869	143	63%	6.959,4406	6,4948	40,5594	34,0646	18,1344	58,6938	0,46	-	-	-	-	90,77
GEOJEDO	34,8014	128,6992	142	62%	7.084,4930	51,6193	84,4930	32,8736	40,2124	44,2805	0,08	-	-	-	-	28,37
HORNBAEK	56,0911	12,4583	142	62%	7.040,5493	124,6733	40,5493	165,2226	-	144,9861	185,5354	0,25	-	-	-	302,86
KALININGRAD	54,7000	20,4833	142	62%	7.045,7887	4,3114	45,7887	50,1002	-	20,4454	66,2341	0,15	-	-	-	50,70
KETCHIKAN	55,3317	131,6250	142	62%	6.907,0986	68,9968	92,9014	23,9046	65,4209	27,4805	0,00	-	-	-	-	71,91
KINLOCHBERVIE	58,4566	5,0504	142	62%	6.982,1831	37,1236	17,8169	19,3067	43,2442	25,4273	0,05	-	-	-	-	52,30
PORTKEMBLA	34,4738	150,9119	141	62%	7.013,7589	0,2107	13,7589	13,5481	-	2,4182	16,1771	0,09	-	-	-	35,65
STENUNGSUND	58,0933	11,8325	140	61%	7.044,1429	61,2906	44,1429	17,1478	69,3113	25,1684	0,07	-	-	-	-	79,32
KASHIWAZAKI	37,3567	138,5083	138	61%	6.943,8406	5,3551	56,1594	61,5145	22,6056	78,7650	0,21	-	-	-	-	88,74
CHRISTIANSTEDHARBOUR	17,7500	64,7050	136	60%	7.068,5515	49,3364	68,5515	19,2151	41,2785	27,2730	0,07	-	-	-	-	31,21
PORTELIZABETH	33,9511	25,6297	136	60%	7.024,9265	0,5807	24,9265	25,5072	-	8,1183	33,0447	0,10	-	-	-	42,56
NEWPORT	51,5500	2,9874	131	57%	7.094,9771	60,6600	94,9771	34,3171	48,5914	46,3857	0,06	-	-	-	-	44,59

PORTNEUF	46,6833	-	71,8833	131	57%	7.103,0534	1,9439	103,0534	101,1095	-	23,5297	126,5831	0,25	-	89,19	
TOULON	43,1129	5,9147	-	131	57%	6.982,5191	0,1826	-	17,4809	-	17,6635	-	4,3530	21,8339	0,01	2,47
CHETYREHSTOLBOVOI	70,6333	162,4833	-	128	56%	6.999,5938	47,3488	-	0,4063	-	46,9426	-	57,8836	57,4773	0,13	107,55
LAUTOKA	-	17,6049	177,4383	127	56%	7.064,7165	17,7319	64,7165	-	46,9847	-	0,5839	64,1327	0,17	27,90	
PARADIP	20,2667	86,7000	-	126	55%	7.128,0238	5,0421	128,0238	-	133,0659	-	40,0396	168,0634	0,56	187,06	
TABLEBAYHARBOUR	-	33,9167	18,4333	125	55%	7.085,9200	0,0878	85,9200	-	86,0078	-	18,3381	104,2581	0,20	73,84	
SETROIA	38,5000	-	8,9000	124	54%	7.136,9677	54,1556	136,9677	-	82,8121	-	32,1567	104,8111	0,16	0,55	
ACAJUTLA	13,5667	-	89,8333	123	54%	7.009,9187	0,7369	9,9187	-	9,1818	-	1,2139	11,1326	0,04	14,92	
GLADSTONE	-	23,8538	151,3137	120	53%	7.104,3333	0,0624	104,3333	104,2709	-	-	20,1634	124,4967	0,19	73,56	
WACHAPREAGUE	37,6067	-	75,6867	119	52%	6.971,5210	46,7115	-	28,4790	-	18,2325	81,1999	52,7209	0,41	91,21	
PUERTOCASTILLA	16,0167	-	86,0333	118	52%	7.061,1017	2,7898	61,1017	-	58,3119	-	9,0701	70,1718	0,14	47,50	
TAIMIUWAN	22,2697	-	114,2886	118	52%	7.061,7458	17,2725	61,7458	-	44,4733	-	0,2600	61,4857	0,22	36,22	
ULLADULLAHARBOUR	-	35,3577	150,4765	117	51%	7.019,8291	2,5648	19,8291	-	22,3938	-	14,1982	34,0273	0,17	31,83	
DURBAN	-	29,8742	31,0508	115	50%	7.148,3130	103,6991	148,3130	-	44,6139	-	71,1738	77,1392	0,31	50,11	
MACAU	22,2000	-	113,5500	112	49%	7.238,6607	64,0169	238,6607	-	174,6438	-	45,1800	193,4807	0,12	6,23	
RAU-CHUA	69,5000	-	166,5833	107	47%	7.100,1869	30,3640	100,1869	-	130,5509	-	49,5577	149,7447	0,12	81,93	
BUCKSPORT,WACCAMAWR.	33,6467	-	79,0950	105	46%	7.183,2476	105,0000	183,2476	-	78,2476	-	88,8996	94,3480	0,16	53,30	
POINTREYES	37,9950	-	122,9767	105	46%	6.974,0286	5,7424	25,9714	-	20,2291	-	2,5487	23,4228	0,03	14,05	
DIKSON	73,5000	-	80,4000	104	46%	6.962,5000	91,6273	37,5000	-	54,1273	-	99,6546	62,1546	0,10	137,17	
MATI,DAVAORIENTAL	6,9500	-	126,2167	100	44%	7.130,9300	80,9440	130,9300	-	49,9860	-	70,2733	60,6567	0,13	48,80	
SHUTEHARBOUR2	-	20,2833	148,7833	97	43%	7.110,5258	76,6688	110,5258	-	33,8569	-	70,3244	40,2014	0,03	68,66	
ST.PETERSBURG	27,7600	-	82,6267	97	43%	7.300,2371	69,7431	300,2371	-	230,4941	-	43,7658	256,4713	0,46	159,47	
BRIDGEPORT	41,1733	-	73,1817	96	42%	7.097,2188	45,0739	97,2188	-	52,1449	-	37,4818	59,7369	0,07	20,22	
RIODEJANEIRO	-	22,9333	43,1333	96	42%	7.135,3542	78,8320	135,3542	-	56,5221	-	70,8833	64,4709	0,08	42,70	
TREGDE	58,0064	-	7,5548	96	42%	6.902,3958	110,0036	-	97,6042	-	12,3994	114,5379	16,9338	0,02	107,06	
GRANDISLE	29,2633	-	89,9567	94	41%	6.779,0851	99,7838	220,9149	-	121,1311	-	66,7287	154,1862	0,58	45,79	
BELYNOS	69,6000	-	60,2167	93	41%	7.161,7957	83,6326	161,7957	-	78,1631	-	49,6287	112,1670	0,50	0,63	
LERWICK	60,1540	-	1,1403	92	40%	7.049,2391	1,9955	49,2391	-	47,2436	-	4,2426	53,4817	0,09	34,53	
MATSUYAMAI	33,8667	-	132,7000	92	40%	7.049,2391	1,9955	49,2391	-	47,2436	-	4,2426	53,4817	0,09	34,53	

CHESAPEAKEBAYBR.TUN.	36,9667	-76,1133	90	39%	6.924,2222	-20,5678	-75,7778	-55,2100	-8,5742	-67,2036	-0,05	-4,02
CASCAIS	38,6833	9,4167	89	39%	7.093,7191	0,8932	93,7191	92,8259	4,4969	98,2160	0,05	42,07
SHEERNESS	51,4456	0,7434	89	39%	7.135,9101	72,2755	135,9101	208,1856	84,8782	220,7883	0,11	193,96
TOSASHIMIZU	32,7792	132,9589	89	39%	7.060,7079	27,9934	60,7079	32,7145	23,3136	37,3943	0,11	15,61
VIGOII	42,2431	8,7260	88	39%	7.057,1023	6,2945	57,1023	50,8077	2,4083	59,5106	0,06	10,49
VIRGINIABEACH	36,8500	75,9667	88	39%	7.051,0227	18,2226	51,0227	32,8001	12,4985	38,5242	0,05	1,16
LECONQUET	48,3594	4,7808	87	38%	7.053,2529	0,1703	53,2529	53,4231	10,4565	63,7094	0,16	48,61
LIVERPOOL(GLADSTONEDOCK)	53,4497	3,0180	87	38%	7.065,1149	38,9979	65,1149	26,1171	31,9331	33,1818	0,12	10,48
ROTHERA	67,5713	68,1298	87	38%	7.067,6322	1,0655	67,6322	66,5667	14,7471	82,3792	0,07	13,51
TWEEDHEADS	28,1695	153,5496	87	38%	7.168,3333	126,7483	168,3333	41,5850	107,9374	60,3959	0,36	68,60
URAKAWAII	42,1667	142,7667	87	38%	6.992,6552	49,4059	7,3448	42,0610	55,7329	48,3880	0,05	67,67
CHAMPLAIN	46,4333	72,4000	86	38%	7.042,2907	102,5403	42,2907	144,8310	127,2627	169,5534	0,74	341,23
DARWIN	12,4718	130,8459	86	38%	7.059,7326	6,5117	59,7326	66,2442	17,7295	77,4620	0,21	78,46
MONTEREY	36,6050	121,8867	86	38%	7.030,7907	10,2329	30,7907	41,0236	19,1203	49,9110	0,13	48,46
PORTLAND	38,3434	141,6132	86	38%	7.018,0465	21,6107	18,0465	39,6572	31,3403	49,3868	0,16	63,02
SAINTPIERREETMIQUELON	46,7788	56,1683	86	38%	7.051,4884	42,7525	51,4884	8,7359	37,9300	13,5583	0,08	28,40
PORTDOUGLAS2	16,4833	145,4667	85	37%	6.989,4824	12,1702	10,5176	1,6526	11,0242	0,5066	0,16	32,55
OITAI	33,2661	131,6867	82	36%	6.998,3902	61,3220	1,6098	59,7122	69,8352	68,2254	0,11	100,53
TVARMINNE	59,8500	23,2500	80	35%	7.107,9875	65,6693	107,9875	42,3182	58,1419	49,8456	0,07	45,23
NAURU-B	0,5294	166,9101	72	32%	7.021,0556	8,2011	21,0556	12,8545	5,4191	15,6365	0,02	13,55
SALAMANDER	33,0667	18,0000	72	32%	7.715,0417	521,9682	715,0417	193,0735	475,2644	239,7772	1,95	5,27
PROGRESO	21,3000	89,6667	71	31%	7.082,8732	21,6475	82,8732	61,2258	14,2643	68,6090	0,15	35,93
PRUDHOEBAY,ALASKA	70,4000	148,5267	71	31%	7.227,9718	19,3034	227,9718	208,6684	26,1091	254,0810	1,29	275,35
LEMSTROM	60,1000	20,0167	68	30%	6.870,7206	47,4659	129,2794	176,7453	57,2941	186,5735	0,24	223,19
VIESTE	41,8881	16,1770	65	29%	6.994,1538	28,8397	5,8462	22,9936	36,8785	31,0323	0,14	57,26
NAPOLI	40,8414	14,2692	62	27%	6.969,5323	65,8206	30,4677	35,3529	74,7577	44,2899	0,14	93,14
TALARA	4,6167	81,2833	61	27%	7.079,9180	13,6997	79,9180	66,2183	9,2897	70,6283	0,06	17,83
APALACHICOLA	29,7267	84,9817	59	26%	7.054,4915	5,6075	54,4915	60,0990	13,0925	67,5841	0,15	50,15

GRINDAVIK	63,8333	-	59	26%	7.081,3559	16,4831	81,3559	64,8729	11,3619	69,9941	0,04	0,23
WESTTUAS	1,3444	103,6340	59	26%	6.926,4068	49,9771	73,5932	- 23,6162	44,0114	29,5818	0,22	2,25
PESCHANYI(PESCHANYIMYS)	79,4333	102,4833	54	24%	7.051,3519	67,7816	51,3519	119,1334	80,7567	132,1086	0,32	168,10
FYNHAV	54,9950	9,9869	53	23%	6.845,6792	75,6418	154,3208	- 78,6790	66,0697	88,2511	0,32	27,68
KNYSNA	-	34,0494	53	23%	7.333,8113	137,7035	333,8113	196,1078	110,9845	222,8268	0,40	26,70
PETROPAVLOVSK-KAMCHATSKY	52,9833	158,6500	52	23%	7.176,3462	1,9880	176,3462	174,3581	12,0850	188,4311	0,08	30,83
CAGLIARIIII	39,2102	9,1143	48	21%	7.186,4375	153,3240	186,4375	33,1135	143,6707	42,7668	0,15	125,95
WONSAN	39,1667	127,4500	46	20%	7.055,4565	10,4019	55,4565	45,0546	5,4831	49,9734	0,10	18,92
MOKUOLOEISLAND	21,4317	-	43	19%	7.187,9070	1,8408	187,9070	186,0661	11,4341	199,3410	0,19	72,47
PLOCE	43,0500	17,4167	39	17%	7.004,9744	22,7952	4,9744	- 17,8208	24,5756	19,6013	0,03	30,97
ARUNPLATFORM	50,7698	-	38	17%	7.031,4474	12,3416	31,4474	43,7889	18,5077	49,9551	0,18	43,27
STJEANDELUZ(SOCA)	43,3952	-	38	17%	7.161,1316	13,9958	161,1316	147,1357	8,0869	153,0447	0,05	40,87
ESPERANZA,VIEQUES	18,0933	-	36	16%	7.128,0833	57,2077	128,0833	70,8756	37,9969	90,0864	0,38	8,89
GALVESTONI,PLEASUREPIER,TX	29,2850	-	35	15%	7.085,7143	0,4071	85,7143	86,1214	6,9804	92,6947	0,13	44,04
WAKAYAMA	34,2217	135,1456	32	14%	7.078,7813	6,0801	78,7813	84,8613	12,3442	91,1255	0,29	97,65
QUEENCHARLOTTECITY	53,2500	-	24	11%	7.252,9167	9,9764	252,9167	262,8931	25,0544	277,9711	0,17	70,81
SIMONSBAY	-	34,1878	22	10%	7.155,0000	3,8001	155,0000	151,1999	2,3463	157,3463	0,21	69,66
ONAGAWA	38,4333	141,4667	20	9%	6.989,2000	46,4456	10,8000	35,6456	47,6178	36,8178	0,03	57,66
UGORSKIISHAR(UGORSKIISHARPROLIV)	69,8167	60,7500	19	8%	7.027,6842	-	68,2368	27,6842	95,9210	70,8088	0,06	89,94
BELLEDUNE	47,9000	-	18	8%	6.975,5556	19,5674	24,4444	- 4,8770	18,7739	5,6706	0,06	29,90
NORTHSYDNEY	46,2167	-	17	7%	6.972,8235	83,4438	27,1765	- 110,6203	89,3201	116,4965	0,10	109,95
KRENKELIA(HEISAOSTROV)	80,6167	58,0500	15	7%	7.231,3333	3,7739	231,3333	227,5595	2,1999	233,5332	0,09	23,77
NAGAEVO	59,5500	150,7167	14	6%	7.407,1429	1,9971	407,1429	405,1458	8,1621	415,3050	0,20	70,26
MOKPO	34,7797	126,3756	11	5%	7.090,0000	-	3,6986	90,0000	93,6986	5,3400	0,08	34,13
MURORAN	42,3500	140,9500	11	5%	7.010,1818	18,4028	10,1818	28,5846	19,6438	29,8256	0,07	31,34
MONAISLAND	18,0900	-	10	4%	7.052,0000	5,1745	52,0000	46,8255	3,2976	48,7024	0,09	10,69
TANGGU	39,0000	117,7167	6	3%	7.160,3333	53,9185	160,3333	214,2518	57,5520	217,8853	0,03	60,41

MURMANSKII	68,9667	33,0500	5	2%	7.081,2000	-	10,1870	81,2000	91,3870	-	12,3653	93,5653	0,17	-	67,28
RICHARDSBAY	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	28,8119	32,0786	5	2%	6.956,2000	72,2109	43,8000	28,4109	73,8059	30,0059	0,20	119,63			
BRISBANE(WESTINNERBAR)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	27,3667	153,1667	2	1%	7.055,0000	1,0585	55,0000	53,9415	1,4164	53,5836	0,05	14,08			
ABERDEENII	57,1500	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	90,3009	-	-	90,3009	90,3009	-	-	0,25	206,57	
ABURATSUBO	35,1603	139,6153	-	0%	7.000,0000	37,4864	-	-	37,4864	37,4864	-	-	0,08	40,57	
ACAJUTLA2	13,5833	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	30,9781	-	30,9781	30,9781	30,9781	0,24	78,11			
ADEN	12,7883	44,9742	-	0%	7.000,0000	86,4664	-	86,4664	86,4664	86,4664	0,09	122,56			
AION	69,9333	167,9833	-	0%	7.000,0000	27,0621	-	27,0621	27,0621	27,0621	0,26	10,01			
ALAMEDA(NAVALAIRSTATION)	37,7717	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	22,2000	-	22,2000	22,2000	22,2000	-	-	0,34	11,96	
ALBANY	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	35,0337	117,8926	-	0%	7.000,0000	28,8864	-	-	28,8864	28,8864	0,37	55,74			
ALERT	82,4900	62,3200	-	0%	7.000,0000	79,8034	-	-	79,8034	79,8034	0,16	46,15			
ALEXANDROUPOLIS	40,8441	25,8783	-	0%	7.000,0000	50,2039	-	-	50,2039	50,2039	0,43	15,84			
ALGECIRAS2	36,1770	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	21,6281	-	-	21,6281	21,6281	0,02	20,97			
	-	5,3984	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ALICANTE(INNERHARBOUR)	38,3389	0,4812	-	0%	7.000,0000	32,1903	-	32,1903	32,1903	32,1903	0,16	9,36			
AMASRA	41,4333	32,2333	-	0%	7.000,0000	11,5387	-	11,5387	11,5387	11,5387	0,62	29,12			
AMRUM(WITTDUEN)	54,6167	8,3833	-	0%	7.000,0000	9,1859	-	9,1859	9,1859	9,1859	0,75	58,19			
ANCONA	43,5833	13,4833	-	0%	7.000,0000	48,7109	-	48,7109	48,7109	48,7109	0,09	19,08			
ANCLUD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	41,8669	73,8319	-	0%	7.000,0000	41,0596	-	-	41,0596	41,0596	0,41	22,88			
ANGRADOHEROISMO	38,6500	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	38,0534	-	-	38,0534	38,0534	0,00	38,07			
	-	27,2333	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ANHEUNG	36,6736	126,1322	-	0%	7.000,0000	57,7834	-	57,7834	57,7834	57,7834	1,06	89,97			
ANTALYAI	36,8333	30,6167	-	0%	7.000,0000	34,9738	-	-	34,9738	34,9738	0,12	42,17			
ANTIFER	49,6500	0,1500	-	0%	7.000,0000	24,2640	-	24,2640	24,2640	24,2640	0,02	22,52			
ANTOFAGASTA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	23,6500	70,4167	-	0%	7.000,0000	14,1624	-	-	14,1624	14,1624	0,19	42,43			
ANTOFAGASTA2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	23,6531	70,4044	-	0%	7.000,0000	57,7029	-	-	57,7029	57,1015	0,19	21,10			
ARGENTIA	47,3000	53,9833	-	0%	7.000,0000	20,3379	-	20,3379	20,3379	20,3379	0,49	38,88			
ARGENTINEISLANDS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	65,2462	64,2574	-	0%	7.000,0000	47,8894	-	47,8894	47,8894	47,8894	0,01	49,47			
ARINAGA	27,8469	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	12,9066	-	-	12,9066	12,9066	0,04	9,20			
	-	15,4015	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ARRECIFE	28,9719	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	6,0963	-	6,0963	6,0963	6,0963	0,74	29,41			
	-	13,5301	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

ASHDODII	31,8313	34,6405	-	0%	7,000,000	47,2106	-	- 47,2106	47,2106	-	47,2106	0,28	24,45
ATLANTICCITY	39,3550	74,4183	-	0%	7,000,000	92,6975	-	- 92,6975	92,6975	-	92,6975	0,15	155,56
AUCKLAND-WAITEMATAHARBOUR	36,8431	174,7695	-	0%	7,000,000	44,0447	-	- 44,0447	42,8631	-	42,8631	0,21	69,65
AYUKAWA	38,2967	141,5053	-	0%	7,000,000	36,5729	-	36,5729	-	-	36,5729	0,15	70,22
BAHIAESPERANZA	63,3000	56,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	44,0888	-	- 44,0888	44,0888	-	44,0888	0,16	22,99
BAIECOMEAU	49,2333	68,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	32,5900	-	- 32,5900	32,5900	-	32,5900	0,12	48,95
BALANACAN,MARINDUQUE	13,5333	121,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5114	-	3,5114	-	-	3,5114	0,19	28,50
BALINTANG,QUEZON,PALAWAN	9,3500	118,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	19,7150	-	19,7150	-	-	19,7150	0,15	38,15
BALLINA	28,8667	153,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	150,7088	-	- 150,7088	150,7088	-	150,7088	0,61	216,10
BAMFIELD	48,8500	125,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	12,0487	-	12,0487	-	-	12,0487	0,94	85,53
BAR	42,0833	19,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	62,3208	-	- 62,3208	62,3208	-	62,3208	0,18	34,14
BARAHONA	18,2000	71,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	68,4097	-	- 68,4097	68,4097	-	68,4097	0,08	58,34
BARENTSBURG	78,0667	14,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	16,9499	-	16,9499	-	-	16,9499	0,19	22,74
BARENTSBURGII(SPITSBERGEN)	78,0667	14,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	247,3216	-	247,3216	-	-	247,3216	0,45	356,70
BATUMI	41,6333	41,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	12,3962	-	- 12,3962	12,3962	-	12,3962	0,11	43,76
BEDFORDINSTITUTE	44,6833	63,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	51,7918	-	51,7918	-	-	51,7918	2,55	83,65
BELEM	1,4500	48,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	34,0657	-	34,0657	-	-	34,0657	0,43	59,95
BELFAST2	54,6000	5,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	31,5755	-	31,5755	-	-	31,5755	0,12	82,92
BELLABELLA	52,1667	128,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	2,0749	-	- 2,0749	2,0749	-	2,0749	0,15	36,94
BIRKENHEAD(ALFREDDOCK)	53,4000	3,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	48,3741	-	48,3741	-	-	48,3741	0,27	81,27
BJORN	60,6333	17,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	40,1333	-	40,1333	-	-	40,1333	0,04	42,28
BLUFF(SOUTHLANDHARBOUR)	46,5977	168,3454	-	0%	7,000,000	45,5319	-	- 45,5319	45,5319	-	45,5319	0,03	42,52
BODRUMII	37,0333	27,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5262	-	1,5262	-	-	1,5262	0,51	33,94
BONANZA	36,8022	6,3381	-	0%	7,000,000	24,1836	-	24,1836	-	-	24,1836	0,47	38,11
BONAVISTA	48,6510	53,1150	-	0%	7,000,000	63,3969	-	63,3969	-	-	63,3969	0,19	48,48
BORKUM(FISCHERBAJIE)	53,5575	6,7478	-	0%	7,000,000	37,3255	-	- 37,3255	37,3255	-	37,3255	0,38	12,74
BOULOGNE	50,7275	1,5775	-	0%	7,000,000	59,1310	-	59,1310	-	-	59,1310	0,31	163,76

BOURNEMOUTH	50,7143	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	13,3206	-	-	-	-
BRIGHTON	35,0333	138,5167	-	0%	7,000,000	9,8091	-	9,8091	9,8091	9,8091	0,22	21,01
BUENAVENTURA	3,9000	77,1000	-	0%	7,000,000	30,5220	-	30,5220	30,5220	30,5220	0,67	7,29
BUENOSAIRES	34,6000	58,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	22,7801	-	22,7801	22,7801	22,7801	0,25	42,36
BUNBURY	33,3234	115,6600	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5298	-	3,5298	3,5298	3,5298	0,23	57,14
CABOCRUZ	19,8333	77,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	32,0981	-	32,0981	32,0981	32,0981	0,11	20,45
CADIZIII	36,5401	6,2862	-	0%	7,000,000	19,8385	-	19,8385	19,8385	19,8385	0,22	74,48
CAGLIARI	39,2000	9,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	187,0510	-	187,0510	187,0510	187,0510	0,55	306,82
CAIRNS	16,9167	145,7833	-	0%	7,000,000	91,7591	-	91,7591	91,7591	91,7591	0,05	80,87
CALAIS	50,9694	1,8677	-	0%	7,000,000	16,3719	-	16,3719	16,3719	16,3719	0,10	25,24
CANANEIA	25,0167	47,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	31,4461	-	31,4461	31,4461	31,4461	0,10	61,08
CAPOPASSERO	36,6667	15,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9587	-	2,9587	2,9587	2,9587	0,02	7,55
CARLOFORTE	39,1480	8,3095	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8668	-	61,8668	61,8668	61,8668	0,10	52,95
CATANIA	37,5000	15,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	208,0487	-	208,0487	208,0487	208,0487	0,37	315,37
CATANIAII	37,4981	15,0938	-	0%	7,000,000	168,3154	-	168,3154	168,3154	168,3154	0,01	170,17
CEBU	10,3000	123,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	49,2431	-	49,2431	49,2431	49,2431	0,14	86,55
CHABAHARII	25,2958	60,6033	-	0%	7,000,000	48,1839	-	48,1839	48,1839	48,1839	0,06	51,88
CHAMPERICO	14,2833	91,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	18,0296	-	18,0296	18,0296	18,0296	0,27	39,26
CHARCHANGA	22,2167	91,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	13,8827	-	13,8827	13,8827	13,8827	0,03	9,40
CHARLESTONI	32,7817	79,9250	-	0%	7,000,000	7,7272	-	7,7272	7,7272	7,7272	0,18	15,95
CHATHAMISLAND	43,9463	176,5612	-	0%	7,000,000	38,8166	-	38,8166	38,8166	38,8166	0,47	68,78
CHENNAI	13,1000	80,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	2,1766	-	2,1766	2,1766	2,1766	0,13	66,70
CHIMAWAN,LANTAUISLAND	22,2333	114,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	4,9571	-	4,9571	4,9571	4,9571	0,07	12,26
CHOSHII	35,7333	140,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	1,8902	-	1,8902	1,8902	1,8902	0,11	26,10
CHRISTMASISLAND	1,9833	157,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	81,0771	-	81,0771	81,0771	81,0771	2,00	211,98
CHRISTMASISLANDII	1,9833	157,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	22,5516	-	22,5516	22,5516	22,5516	0,01	20,72
CHUJADO	33,9617	126,3003	-	0%	7,000,000	16,7858	-	16,7858	16,7858	16,7858	0,09	9,06
CIUDADMADERO	22,2500	97,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	29,8444	-	29,8444	29,8444	29,8444	0,40	124,92
COCOSISLAND(HOMEIS.)	12,1167	96,8944	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5762	-	3,5762	3,5762	3,5762	0,05	10,18

CONCARNEAU	47,8737	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	123,5019	-	- 123,5019	123,5019	-	123,5019	0,15	94,01
CONSTANTZA	44,1667	28,6667	-	0%	7.000,0000	24,7025	-	24,7025	26,0363	26,0363	-	0,17	104,94
CORPUSCHRISTI,GULFMEXICO, TX	27,5833	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	33,0711	-	- 33,0711	33,0711	-	33,0711	0,08	46,53
CURRIMAOILOCOSNORTE	17,9833	120,4833	-	0%	7.000,0000	40,2826	-	- 40,2826	40,2826	-	40,2826	0,13	29,85
CUTLER	44,6500	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	93,7202	-	- 93,7202	93,7202	-	93,7202	0,51	136,98
CUTLERII	44,6417	67,2967	-	0%	7.000,0000	65,3635	-	- 65,3635	65,3635	-	65,3635	0,31	54,83
DAKAR2	14,6833	17,4167	-	0%	7.000,0000	37,1606	-	37,1606	37,1606	-	37,1606	0,40	63,45
DAVAO,DAVAOGULF	7,0833	125,6333	-	0%	7.000,0000	40,2743	-	40,2743	40,2743	-	40,2743	0,11	81,56
DELFIJUL	53,3264	6,9331	-	0%	7.000,0000	39,0066	-	39,0066	39,0066	-	39,0066	0,05	69,70
DEVONPORT	41,1847	146,3624	-	0%	7.000,0000	55,8984	-	- 55,8984	55,8984	-	55,8984	0,27	29,86
DIEGORAMIREZ	56,5000	68,7167	-	0%	7.000,0000	19,5866	-	- 19,5866	19,5866	-	19,5866	0,17	47,88
DIEPPE	49,9291	1,0838	-	0%	7.000,0000	4,7446	-	4,7446	4,7446	-	4,7446	0,14	24,59
DIGBY	44,6333	65,7500	-	0%	7.000,0000	14,0709	-	14,0709	14,0709	-	14,0709	0,25	16,02
DONGFANG	19,1000	108,6167	-	0%	7.000,0000	31,3329	-	- 31,3329	31,3329	-	31,3329	0,01	32,06
DRAGHALLAN	62,3667	17,5333	-	0%	7.000,0000	190,5133	-	- 190,5133	190,5133	-	190,5133	0,50	464,79
DUBROVNIK	42,6583	18,0633	-	0%	7.000,0000	64,0084	-	64,0084	64,0084	-	64,0084	0,13	39,55
DUNAI(DUNAIOSTROV)	73,9333	124,5000	-	0%	7.000,0000	137,8281	-	- 137,8281	137,8281	-	137,8281	0,01	136,66
DUNBAR	56,0059	2,5169	-	0%	7.000,0000	99,6898	-	99,6898	99,6898	-	99,6898	0,02	106,57
DUTCHHARBOR	53,9000	166,5333	-	0%	7.000,0000	31,8113	-	31,8113	31,8113	-	31,8113	0,18	100,67
EASTPORT	44,9033	66,9817	-	0%	7.000,0000	40,1776	-	- 40,1776	40,1776	-	40,1776	0,16	47,52
EDEN	37,0737	149,9077	-	0%	7.000,0000	86,9419	-	- 86,9419	86,9419	-	86,9419	0,01	83,65
ELFINCOVE,PORTALTHORP	58,1950	136,3467	-	0%	7.000,0000	19,3519	-	19,3519	19,3519	-	19,3519	0,33	16,52
ENSENADA	31,8500	116,6333	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,9833	-	0,9833	0,9833	-	0,9833	0,14	17,91
ESBJERG	55,4608	8,4411	-	0%	7.000,0000	67,6427	-	67,6427	67,6427	-	67,6427	0,24	139,75
ESPERANCE	33,8709	121,8954	-	0%	7.000,0000	35,6404	-	35,6404	35,6404	-	35,6404	0,04	39,03
EVANSHEAD	29,1167	153,4333	-	0%	7.000,0000	125,0919	-	125,0919	125,0919	-	125,0919	0,24	155,10
EXMOUTH	21,9549	114,1409	-	0%	7.000,0000	56,1899	-	56,1899	56,1899	-	56,1899	0,75	96,30
FAMAGUSTA	35,1167	33,9500	-	0%	7.000,0000	29,7112	-	29,7112	29,7112	-	29,7112	0,14	23,25

FANNING-B	3,9000	-	159,3833	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	67,0619	-	67,0619	-	67,0619	-	1,86	-	16,89
FORSMARK	60,4086	-	18,2108	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	8,5385	-	8,5385	-	8,5385	-	0,11	-	14,36
FORTALEZA	-	-	38,4833	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	98,5179	-	98,5179	-	98,5179	-	0,05	-	113,30
FORT-DE-FRANCEII	14,6015	-	61,0632	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	13,8934	-	13,8934	-	13,8934	-	0,02	-	16,17
FORTPULASKI	32,0333	-	80,9017	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	17,0960	-	17,0960	-	17,0960	-	0,01	-	15,48
FREDERICIA	55,5608	-	9,7544	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	33,6620	-	33,6620	-	33,6620	-	0,05	-	65,50
FUERTEVENTURA	28,4925	-	13,8582	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	80,3391	-	80,3391	-	80,3391	-	0,28	-	56,57
FULFORDHARBOUR	48,7667	-	123,4500	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	9,1520	-	9,1520	-	9,3638	-	0,13	-	34,96
FUNAFUTI	-	-	179,2167	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	125,0384	-	125,0384	-	125,0384	-	0,67	-	54,64
FUNCHAL	32,6440	-	16,9131	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	23,4771	-	23,4771	-	23,4771	-	0,17	-	49,55
GADEOKDO	35,0247	-	128,8108	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	60,9431	-	60,9431	-	60,9431	-	0,27	-	13,60
GARDENREACH	22,5500	-	88,3000	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	257,0730	-	257,0730	-	257,0730	-	0,10	-	281,32
GARIBALDIII	45,5550	-	123,9183	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	36,0537	-	36,0537	-	36,0537	-	0,07	-	44,89
GAZENICA	44,0833	-	15,2667	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	40,4672	-	40,4672	-	40,4672	-	0,11	-	22,33
GEDSER	54,5728	-	11,9256	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	57,3578	-	57,3578	-	57,3578	-	0,12	-	82,04
GERALDTON	-	-	114,6019	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	63,8023	-	63,8023	-	63,8023	-	0,09	-	55,44
GIBARA	21,1083	-	76,1250	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	1,0601	-	1,0601	-	1,0601	-	0,12	-	23,83
GINGERVILLECREEK	38,9583	-	76,5550	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	69,4558	-	69,4558	-	69,4558	-	0,19	-	109,23
GIRNE	35,3500	-	33,3333	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	57,4241	-	57,4241	-	57,4241	-	0,34	-	83,24
GOTEBORG-KLIPPAN	57,6833	-	11,9000	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	57,3633	-	57,3633	-	57,3633	-	0,10	-	123,43
GOTEBORG-RINGON	57,7167	-	11,9667	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	11,5459	-	11,5459	-	11,5459	-	0,13	-	27,31
GOTEBORG-TORSHAMNEN	57,6847	-	11,7906	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	25,6941	-	25,6941	-	25,6941	-	0,25	-	48,61
GRANADILLA	28,0853	-	16,4896	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	50,5826	-	50,5826	-	50,5826	-	0,08	-	56,07
GREYMOUTH	-	-	171,2000	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	66,0042	-	66,0042	-	66,0042	-	0,29	-	36,07
GUADALUPEISLANDII	28,8833	-	118,3000	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	3,2559	-	3,2559	-	3,2559	-	1,51	-	26,96
GUANTANAMOBAY	19,9067	-	75,1467	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	66,6276	-	66,6276	-	66,6276	-	0,17	-	128,42
GULEOBDO	37,1944	-	125,9953	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	25,2556	-	25,2556	-	25,2556	-	0,29	-	10,68
HACHINOHEI	40,5333	-	141,5333	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	37,0294	-	37,0294	-	37,0294	-	0,14	-	29,88
HAGI	34,4333	-	131,4167	-	0%	7,000,0000	-	35,9759	-	35,9759	-	35,9759	-	0,19	-	6,29

HAKATA	33,6189	130,4078	-	0%	7,000,000	16,5064	-	-	16,5064	16,5064	-	16,5064	0,26	-	4,59	
HALDIA	22,0333	88,1000	-	0%	7,000,000	26,6553	-	-	26,6553	26,6553	26,6553	26,6553	4,49	-	96,21	
HAMADAI	34,8972	132,0661	-	0%	7,000,000	33,3431	-	-	33,3431	33,3431	33,3431	33,3431	0,00	-	33,95	
HAMMERFEST	70,6646	23,6832	-	0%	7,000,000	12,9481	-	-	12,9481	12,9481	12,9481	12,9481	0,14	-	29,60	
HARRINGTONHBR	50,5000	59,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	6,9222	-	-	6,9222	6,9222	6,9222	6,9222	0,04	-	26,85	
HAYPOINT	-	21,2833	149,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,5209	-	-	57,5209	57,5209	57,5209	57,5209	0,70	-	92,74
HIERRO	27,7841	-	17,9016	-	0%	7,000,000	2,7133	-	-	2,7133	2,7133	2,7133	2,7133	0,05	-	6,35
HINKLEYPPOINT	51,2106	-	3,1313	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5234	-	-	44,5234	44,5234	44,5234	44,5234	0,09	-	35,62
HIRONPOINT	21,7833	89,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	5,7894	-	-	5,7894	5,7894	5,7894	5,7894	0,20	-	17,19	
HIRTSHALS	57,5956	9,9639	-	0%	7,000,000	65,8679	-	-	65,8679	65,8679	65,8679	65,8679	0,07	-	105,98	
HOBART	-	42,8773	147,3410	-	0%	7,000,000	0,4778	-	-	0,4778	0,4778	0,4778	0,4778	0,24	-	60,42
HONDAU	20,6667	106,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7722	-	-	1,7722	1,7722	1,7722	1,7722	0,06	-	16,73	
HONIARA-B	-	9,4289	159,9554	-	0%	7,000,000	58,8020	-	-	58,8020	58,8020	58,8020	58,8020	0,24	-	79,98
HOSOJIMA	32,4286	131,6694	-	0%	7,000,000	42,4342	-	-	42,4342	42,4342	42,4342	42,4342	0,06	-	33,45	
HUELVA	37,1320	-	6,8337	-	0%	7,000,000	17,3544	-	-	17,3544	17,3544	17,3544	17,3544	3,74	-	86,62
IJMUIDEN	52,4622	4,5547	-	0%	7,000,000	126,1608	-	-	126,1608	126,1608	126,1608	126,1608	0,15	-	189,76	
IMMINGHAM	53,6302	-	0,1874	-	0%	7,000,000	68,7721	-	-	68,7721	68,7721	68,7721	68,7721	0,06	-	111,36
INCHEON	37,4519	126,5922	-	0%	7,000,000	26,5849	-	-	26,5849	26,5849	26,5849	26,5849	0,25	-	80,52	
IQUIQUE	-	20,2167	70,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	9,0053	-	-	9,0053	9,0053	9,0053	9,0053	0,03	-	6,34
IRAKLIONII	35,3485	25,1527	-	0%	7,000,000	11,6774	-	-	11,6774	11,6774	11,6774	11,6774	0,13	-	28,53	
ISABELADESAGUA	22,9333	-	80,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	42,1282	-	-	42,1282	42,1282	42,1282	42,1282	0,07	-	50,13
ISHIGAKI	24,3333	124,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	14,4178	-	-	14,4178	14,4178	14,4178	14,4178	1,51	-	45,43	
ISLADECEDROS	28,1000	-	115,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	28,5312	-	-	28,5312	28,5312	28,5312	28,5312	0,44	-	0,66
ISLAMARTINGARCIA	-	34,1833	58,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8967	-	-	61,8967	61,8967	61,8967	61,8967	0,14	-	76,06
ITOI	34,9667	139,1167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7726	-	-	1,7726	1,7726	1,7726	1,7726	0,11	-	27,34	
ITOI	34,8956	139,1331	-	0%	7,000,000	26,7185	-	-	26,7185	26,7185	26,7185	26,7185	0,25	-	7,74	
JANGHANG	36,0069	126,6878	-	0%	7,000,000	82,0034	-	-	82,0034	82,0034	82,0034	82,0034	0,29	-	122,26	
JUNGRUSUND	59,9500	22,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	233,2875	-	-	233,2875	233,2875	233,2875	233,2875	0,45	-	445,54	
KALIX	65,6969	23,0961	-	0%	7,000,000	0,7872	-	-	0,7872	0,7872	0,7872	0,7872	0,20	-	11,15	

KARIYA	33,4731	129,8492	-	0%	7.000,0000	-	2,9416	-	2,9416	-	0,15	10,52
KARUMBA	17,5000	140,8333	-	0%	7.000,0000	1,0715	-	1,0715	1,0715	1,0715	0,15	38,86
KATAKOLON	37,6448	21,3197	-	0%	7.000,0000	26,8531	-	26,8531	26,8531	26,8531	0,09	33,93
KAWAIHAE,HAWAIIISLAND	20,0367	155,8300	-	0%	7.000,0000	-	8,9232	-	8,9232	8,9232	0,19	31,28
KEELUNGII	25,1333	121,7333	-	0%	7.000,0000	18,7760	-	18,7760	18,7760	18,7760	0,38	153,80
KEPPELHARBOUR	1,2667	103,8167	-	0%	7.000,0000	7,5833	-	7,5833	7,5833	7,5833	0,90	18,84
KHALKISNORTH	38,4723	23,5926	-	0%	7.000,0000	26,2642	-	26,2642	26,2642	26,2642	0,04	30,12
KHALKISSOUTH	38,4609	23,5895	-	0%	7.000,0000	15,2607	-	15,2607	15,2607	15,2607	0,00	15,95
KIGILIAH	73,3333	139,8667	-	0%	7.000,0000	23,6992	-	23,6992	23,6992	23,6992	0,35	46,89
KINGSTON	36,8333	139,8500	-	0%	7.000,0000	-	3,8692	-	3,8692	3,8692	0,28	11,08
KLAGSHAMN	55,5222	12,8936	-	0%	7.000,0000	73,5050	-	73,5050	73,5050	73,5050	0,57	130,27
KOBBAKLINTAR	60,0333	19,8833	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,4405	-	0,4405	0,4405	0,4405	2,64	79,75
KOBE	34,6833	135,1833	-	0%	7.000,0000	291,5005	-	291,5005	291,5005	291,5005	2,00	620,72
KOBEII	34,6822	135,1903	-	0%	7.000,0000	166,5524	-	166,5524	166,5524	166,5524	0,68	198,64
KOBENHAVN	55,7050	12,6000	-	0%	7.000,0000	20,7575	-	20,7575	20,7575	20,7575	0,18	43,63
KOLOBRZEG	54,1833	15,5500	-	0%	7.000,0000	83,2483	-	83,2483	83,2483	83,2483	0,03	87,50
KOMATSUSHIMA	34,0092	134,5878	-	0%	7.000,0000	54,2808	-	54,2808	54,2808	54,2808	3,37	109,89
KORSOR	55,3322	11,1422	-	0%	7.000,0000	20,0103	-	20,0103	20,0103	20,0103	0,03	35,36
KOTELNYI(KOTELNYIOSTROV)	76,0000	137,8667	-	0%	7.000,0000	17,3734	-	17,3734	17,3734	17,3734	0,17	48,19
KUCHINOTSU	32,6053	130,1953	-	0%	7.000,0000	50,2414	-	50,2414	50,2414	50,2414	0,10	44,42
KUDAT	6,8794	116,8436	-	0%	7.000,0000	44,9089	-	44,9089	44,9089	44,9089	0,19	65,46
KUNSAN	35,9833	126,7167	-	0%	7.000,0000	26,2207	-	26,2207	26,2207	26,2207	0,09	8,54
KUREI	33,3336	133,2433	-	0%	7.000,0000	53,1277	-	53,1277	53,1277	53,1277	0,57	82,45
KUREII	34,2333	132,5333	-	0%	7.000,0000	5,1367	-	5,1367	5,1367	5,1367	0,05	5,85
KUREIII	34,2333	132,5500	-	0%	7.000,0000	3,8657	-	3,8657	3,8657	3,8657	0,57	126,86
KUREIV	34,2406	132,5503	-	0%	7.000,0000	10,3070	-	10,3070	10,3070	10,3070	0,19	47,61
KUSHIMOTO	33,4758	135,7733	-	0%	7.000,0000	55,6726	-	55,6726	55,6726	55,6726	0,06	65,20
KWAJALEIN	8,7317	167,7350	-	0%	7.000,0000	69,8579	-	69,8579	69,8579	69,8579	0,04	78,93
LACORUNAI	43,3643	8,3989	-	0%	7.000,0000	44,2341	-	44,2341	44,2341	44,2341	0,77	141,59

LACORUNAIH	43,3573	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	84,1211	-	84,1211	-	-
		8,3893				84,1211			84,1211		0,42	25,36
LAE	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,7500	147,0000				65,1851		65,1851	65,1851	65,1851	0,39	1,16
LAHATDATU	5,0189	118,3461	-	0%	7,000,000	75,5954	-	-	75,5954	75,5954	0,02	74,08
LAJESDASFLORES	39,3785	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	17,1448	-	17,1448	0,57	-
		31,1686				17,1448			17,1448			82,33
LANDSORTNORRA	58,7689	17,8589	-	0%	7,000,000	23,9859	-	-	23,9859	23,9859	0,39	-
												3,99
LANGARAPPOINT	54,2500	-	-	0%	7,000,000	2,0634	-	-	2,0634	2,0634	0,23	-
		133,0333										56,44
LAPALOMA	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	34,6500	54,1500				10,2039		-	10,2039	10,2039	0,08	0,15
LAPAZ	24,1667	-	-	0%	7,000,000	21,6761	-	-	21,6761	21,6761	0,48	-
		110,3500										4,28
LAPUSH	47,9133	-	-	0%	7,000,000	340,5379	-	-	340,5379	340,5379	3,03	-
		124,6367										686,24
LARKHARBOUR	49,1000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	5,4945	-	-	5,4945	5,4945	0,26	-
		58,3667										6,00
LASPALMAS,PUERTODELALUZ	28,1363	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		15,4257				185,5025			185,5025	185,5025	1,59	-
												368,02
LEHAVRE	49,4819	0,1060	-	0%	7,000,000	59,8143	-	-	59,8143	58,4707	0,20	-
												29,45
LEITHII	55,9898	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		3,1817				3,6518			3,6518	3,6518	1,92	-
												62,29
LEIXOES	41,1833	-	-	0%	7,000,000	76,5118	-	-	76,5118	76,5118	0,18	-
		8,7000										98,44
LESKINA(LESKINAMYS)	72,3167	79,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	15,1494	-	-	15,1494	15,1494	0,50	-
												4,41
LEVERDON	45,5500	-	-	0%	7,000,000	131,7989	-	-	131,7989	131,7989	0,21	-
		1,0667										117,84
LEVKAS	38,8345	20,7121	-	0%	7,000,000	19,2284	-	-	19,2284	19,2284	0,05	-
												15,28
LIANYUNGANG	34,7500	119,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	88,2545	-	-	88,2545	88,2545	0,18	-
												123,90
LIMETREEBAY,STCROIX	17,6933	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		64,7533				154,5260			154,5260	154,5260	0,18	-
												176,27
LOKONPAI	22,3667	114,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	88,4967	-	-	88,4967	88,4967	0,37	-
												66,25
LOWESTOFT	52,4731	1,7501	-	0%	7,000,000	55,9640	-	-	55,9640	55,9640	0,10	-
												30,10
LOWHEAD	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	41,0644	146,7947				48,0154			48,0154	48,0154	0,22	-
												25,80
LUDERITZ	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	26,6433	15,1550				0,1970			0,1970	0,1970	0,08	-
												11,04
LUMUT	4,2400	100,6133	-	0%	7,000,000	45,4249	-	-	45,4249	45,4249	2,79	-
												6,11
LYPYRTTI	60,6000	21,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	129,0534	-	-	129,0534	129,0534	0,09	-
												197,48
LYTTELTONII	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	43,6056	172,7219				19,9147			19,9147	19,9147	0,05	-
												23,38
MACKAY	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	21,1000	149,2333				3,3836			3,3836	3,3836	0,59	-
												21,30
MAISAKA	34,6819	137,6089	-	0%	7,000,000	28,6020	-	-	28,6020	28,6020	0,15	-
												9,19

MAJURO-B	7,1000	171,3667	-	0%	7,000,0000	8,7452	-	- 8,7452	8,7452	-	8,7452	0,08	- 2,46
MALAKAL-B	7,3333	134,4667	-	0%	7,000,0000	28,6166	-	28,6166	28,6166	28,6166	-	0,09	25,88
MALINHEAD	55,3667	7,3333	-	0%	7,000,0000	19,5413	-	19,5413	19,5413	19,5413	-	0,04	25,17
MALYEKARMAKULY	72,3667	52,7000	-	0%	7,000,0000	4,245,1482	-	4,245,1482	4,245,1482	4,245,1482	-	2,58	4,281,21
MAMBAJAOCAMGUIN	9,2500	124,7333	-	0%	7,000,0000	16,3598	-	- 16,3598	16,3598	16,3598	-	0,06	12,29
MAPUTO	25,9667	32,5667	-	0%	7,000,0000	4,1144	-	- 4,1144	4,1144	4,1144	-	0,05	16,60
MASAN	35,2100	128,5889	-	0%	7,000,0000	0,6718	-	0,6718	0,6718	0,6718	-	0,14	17,58
MATARANI	17,0000	72,1167	-	0%	7,000,0000	26,4999	-	- 26,4999	26,4999	26,4999	-	0,37	50,82
MAYPORT	30,3933	81,4317	-	0%	7,000,0000	39,0719	-	39,0719	39,0719	39,0719	-	0,07	65,30
MILFORDHAVEN(NEWTONNOYES)	51,7000	5,0167	-	0%	7,000,0000	71,6129	-	71,6129	71,6129	71,6129	-	0,11	142,81
MILLPORT	55,7498	4,9063	-	0%	7,000,0000	91,8847	-	- 91,8847	91,8847	91,8847	-	0,03	84,69
MIYAZU	35,5333	135,1833	-	0%	7,000,0000	2,8598	-	- 2,8598	2,8598	2,8598	-	0,26	73,29
MOBILESTATEDOCKS,ALABAMA	30,7050	88,0400	-	0%	7,000,0000	42,2099	-	- 42,2099	42,2099	42,2099	-	0,57	13,32
MOMMARK	54,9333	10,0667	-	0%	7,000,0000	149,5602	-	149,5602	149,5602	149,5602	-	0,15	192,32
MONACO(FONTVIEILLE)	43,7288	7,4215	-	0%	7,000,0000	36,9026	-	36,9026	36,9026	36,9026	-	0,09	50,51
MORMUGAO	15,4167	73,8000	-	0%	7,000,0000	19,9490	-	- 19,9490	19,9490	19,9490	-	1,81	91,30
MOTRIL2	36,7202	3,5236	-	0%	7,000,0000	47,8764	-	47,8764	47,8764	47,8764	-	0,10	53,89
MOULMEIN	16,4833	97,6167	-	0%	7,000,0000	0,5821	-	- 0,5821	0,5821	0,5821	-	0,08	22,92
MOZI	33,9500	130,9667	-	0%	7,000,0000	23,8867	-	23,8867	23,8867	23,8867	-	2,56	635,11
MUKHO	37,5503	129,1164	-	0%	7,000,0000	62,4817	-	- 62,4817	62,4817	62,4817	-	0,39	85,97
MYSSHMIDTA	68,9000	179,3667	-	0%	7,000,0000	118,1043	-	118,1043	118,1043	118,1043	-	1,14	145,92
NAGAPATTINAM	10,7667	79,8500	-	0%	7,000,0000	109,1069	-	- 109,1069	109,1069	109,1069	-	0,95	172,42
NAKANOSIMA	29,8419	129,8478	-	0%	7,000,0000	1,7483	-	- 1,7483	1,7483	1,7483	-	0,19	47,24
NANOOSEBAY	49,2667	124,1333	-	0%	7,000,0000	0,1519	-	0,1519	0,1519	0,1519	-	1,11	18,65
NANSHA	9,5500	112,8800	-	0%	7,000,0000	196,7377	-	- 196,7377	196,7377	196,7377	-	0,22	237,82
NANTUCKETISLAND	41,2850	70,0967	-	0%	7,000,0000	52,4086	-	- 52,4086	52,4086	52,4086	-	0,25	3,07
NAPLES	26,1317	81,8067	-	0%	7,000,0000	1,3103	-	- 1,3103	1,3103	1,3103	-	0,29	63,15
NAPOLI(ARSENALE)	40,8667	14,2667	-	0%	7,000,0000	22,8679	-	- 22,8679	22,8679	22,8679	-	0,20	37,69

NAPOLI(MANDRACCHIO)	40,8429	14,2575	-	0%	7,000,000	6,2031	-	- 6,2031	6,2031	-	6,2031	0,20	-	24,49
NARVIK	68,4283	17,4258	-	0%	7,000,000	65,4685	-	- 65,4685	65,4685	-	65,4685	0,01	-	69,36
NASEI	28,3833	129,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,9819	-	- 1,9819	1,9819	-	1,9819	0,23	-	49,94
NASEIII	28,5000	129,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	68,9825	-	- 68,9825	68,9825	-	68,9825	0,32	-	92,33
NAURU	0,5333	166,9000	-	0%	7,000,000	16,5429	-	- 16,5429	16,5429	-	16,5429	0,44	-	61,78
NEDRESODERTALJE	59,2000	17,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	155,3188	-	- 155,3188	155,3188	-	155,3188	0,23	-	252,66
NELSON	41,2613	173,2728	-	0%	7,000,000	22,2706	-	- 22,2706	22,2706	-	22,2706	1,61	-	61,69
NEMKOVA(NEMKOVAOSTROV)	71,4167	150,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5655	-	- 44,5655	44,5655	-	44,5655	0,90	-	113,56
NETTEN	66,9667	171,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	68,5527	-	- 68,5527	68,5527	-	68,5527	0,66	-	210,16
NEWCASTLEI	32,9167	151,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	72,8619	-	- 72,8619	72,8619	-	72,8619	0,41	-	115,71
NEWCASTLEII	32,9167	151,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,4534	-	- 57,4534	57,4534	-	57,4534	0,37	-	30,00
NEWCASTLEV	32,9240	151,7886	-	0%	7,000,000	99,7645	-	- 99,7645	99,7645	-	99,7645	0,10	-	123,36
NEWROCHELLE	40,8933	73,7817	-	0%	7,000,000	50,7768	-	- 50,7768	50,7768	-	50,7768	0,05	-	51,61
NEWESTMINSTER	49,2000	122,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3075	-	- 0,3075	0,3075	-	0,3075	0,06	-	3,85
NEZUGASEKI	38,5633	139,5458	-	0%	7,000,000	10,4047	-	- 10,4047	10,4047	-	10,4047	0,21	-	67,67
NISINOOMOTE	30,7350	130,9922	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8141	-	- 61,8141	61,8141	-	61,8141	0,05	-	59,47
NORTHSALAMINOSII	37,9796	23,5342	-	0%	7,000,000	51,4595	-	- 51,4595	51,4595	-	51,4595	0,21	-	32,07
NORTHSHIELDS	55,0074	1,4398	-	0%	7,000,000	84,8574	-	- 84,8574	84,8574	-	84,8574	0,27	-	157,50
NOSY-BE	13,4000	48,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	18,9728	-	- 18,9728	18,9728	-	18,9728	0,32	-	38,51
NOUMEA-CHALEIX	22,3000	166,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	7,4247	-	- 7,4247	7,4247	-	7,4247	0,41	-	15,79
ODOMARI	31,0236	130,6892	-	0%	7,000,000	7,2272	-	- 7,2272	7,2272	-	7,2272	0,12	-	1,24
OFUNATOII	39,0197	141,7533	-	0%	7,000,000	66,7426	-	- 66,7426	66,7426	-	66,7426	0,01	-	68,77
OGI	37,8147	138,2811	-	0%	7,000,000	51,9532	-	- 51,9532	51,9532	-	51,9532	0,49	-	84,97
OKADA	34,7894	139,3914	-	0%	7,000,000	24,8077	-	- 24,8077	24,8077	-	24,8077	0,36	-	3,16
OMINATO	41,2500	141,1500	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5664	-	- 44,5664	44,5664	-	44,5664	1,60	-	19,71
ONISAKI	34,9039	136,8236	-	0%	7,000,000	59,6229	-	- 59,6229	59,6229	-	59,6229	0,23	-	18,97
OSCARSBORG	59,6781	10,6049	-	0%	7,000,000	286,2251	-	- 286,2251	286,2251	-	286,2251	0,52	-	504,89
OSHOROI	43,2094	140,8581	-	0%	7,000,000	1,9610	-	- 1,9610	1,9610	-	1,9610	0,18	-	34,77

OSLO	59,9086	10,7345	-	0%	7,000,000	139,7704	-	- 139,7704	139,7704	-	0,37	251,42
PADREISLAND	26,0683	97,1517	-	0%	7,000,000	64,6946	-	- 64,6946	64,6946	64,6946	0,02	62,92
PAGETISLAND	32,3667	64,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	4,4368	-	- 4,4368	4,4368	4,4368	0,18	35,50
PAGOBAY,GUAM	13,4283	144,7967	-	0%	7,000,000	34,7041	-	- 34,7041	34,7041	34,7041	0,15	17,07
PALERMO	34,5667	58,4000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,3200	-	- 1,3200	1,3200	1,3200	0,16	43,39
PALERMOII	38,1214	13,3713	-	0%	7,000,000	260,5215	-	- 260,5215	260,5215	260,5215	0,49	320,26
PALMEIRA	16,7500	22,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	7,0056	-	- 7,0056	7,0056	7,0056	0,43	38,03
PASAIHARBOUR,SANSEBASTIAN	43,3218	1,9315	-	0%	7,000,000	37,3756	-	- 37,3756	37,3756	37,3756	4,99	25,05
PASAJES	43,3266	1,9218	-	0%	7,000,000	111,0209	-	111,0209	111,0209	111,0209	0,31	207,83
PATRAI	38,4167	21,7287	-	0%	7,000,000	15,1186	-	15,1186	15,1186	15,1186	0,20	7,54
PELABUHANKELANG	3,0500	101,3583	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7836	-	- 1,7836	1,7836	1,7836	1,08	18,79
PENRHYN	9,0167	158,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	49,2339	-	- 49,2339	49,2339	49,2339	0,65	25,01
PEVEK	69,7000	170,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	23,5339	-	- 23,5339	23,5339	23,5339	0,11	4,76
PHILADELPHIA(PIER9N)	39,9333	75,1417	-	0%	7,000,000	17,9134	-	17,9134	17,9134	17,9134	0,13	38,17
PICTOU	45,6833	62,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	33,3504	-	33,3504	33,3504	33,3504	0,55	71,62
PINEYPOINT,MARYLAND	38,1333	76,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	30,4654	-	- 30,4654	30,4654	30,4654	0,31	8,21
PLUMISLAND	41,1667	72,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5074	-	- 1,5074	1,5074	1,5074	0,25	65,29
POINTTUPPER	45,6000	61,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	21,5424	-	21,5424	21,5424	21,5424	0,78	7,49
PORTALLEN,HANAPEPEBAY,KAUAIISLAND	21,9033	159,5917	-	0%	7,000,000	100,6504	-	100,6504	100,6504	100,6504	0,55	167,33
PORTALMA	23,5833	150,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	13,9729	-	- 13,9729	13,9729	13,9729	0,38	25,09
PORTANGELES,WASHINGTON	48,1250	123,4400	-	0%	7,000,000	16,7873	-	- 16,7873	16,7873	16,7873	0,35	24,85
PORTARANSAS,H.CALDWELLPIER	27,8267	97,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	8,1350	-	- 8,1350	8,1350	8,1350	0,11	15,47
PORTAUPRINCE	18,5667	72,3500	-	0%	7,000,000	153,4086	-	153,4086	153,4086	153,4086	0,18	96,92
PORTBLOC	45,5685	1,0616	-	0%	7,000,000	64,1075	-	64,1075	64,1075	64,1075	0,78	29,36
PORTBURY	51,5000	2,7285	-	0%	7,000,000	32,0313	-	32,0313	32,0313	32,0313	0,07	29,73
PORTCHICAGO,CALIFORNIA	38,0550	122,0400	-	0%	7,000,000	45,1550	-	45,1550	45,1550	45,1550	2,50	110,15
PORTERIN	54,0854	4,7681	-	0%	7,000,000	38,6308	-	38,6308	38,6308	38,6308	1,51	102,86

PORTFERREOL	43,3591	6,7176	-	0%	7,000,000	7,3360	-	-	7,3360	7,3360	-	-	1,30	65,13
PORTHARDY	50,7167	127,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	81,5493	-	-	81,5493	81,5493	-	-	0,15	65,77
PORTLAND(MAINE)	43,6567	70,2467	-	0%	7,000,000	31,9248	-	-	31,9248	31,9248	-	-	0,07	46,46
PORTLYTTELTON	43,6056	172,7219	-	0%	7,000,000	42,8562	-	-	42,8562	42,8562	-	-	0,04	51,33
PORTMACDONNELLI	38,0000	140,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	45,3894	-	-	45,3894	45,3894	-	-	0,21	106,22
PORTNOLLOTH	29,2567	16,8678	-	0%	7,000,000	2,8586	-	-	2,8586	2,8586	-	-	0,06	12,14
PORTMAURIZIO	43,8667	8,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	137,4834	-	-	137,4834	137,4834	-	-	0,51	396,96
PORTRUSH	55,2068	6,6568	-	0%	7,000,000	48,2639	-	-	48,2639	48,2639	-	-	0,16	19,91
PORT-SAINT-FRANCOIS	46,2667	72,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	7,8673	-	-	7,8673	7,8673	-	-	0,13	21,84
PORTSMOUTH	50,8023	1,1113	-	0%	7,000,000	117,6770	-	-	117,6770	117,6770	-	-	0,66	181,50
PORTTARNAKI	39,0562	174,0344	-	0%	7,000,000	65,3335	-	-	65,3335	65,3335	-	-	0,02	63,24
POTI	42,1667	41,6833	-	0%	7,000,000	109,3595	-	-	109,3595	109,3595	-	-	0,06	94,08
PRAVDY(PRAVDYOSTROV)	76,2667	94,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	122,6270	-	-	122,6270	122,6270	-	-	0,83	150,70
PUERTOANGEL	15,5000	96,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	4,2541	-	-	4,2541	4,2541	-	-	0,08	14,44
PUERTOPRINCESA,PALAWAN	9,7500	118,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	35,4133	-	-	35,4133	35,4133	-	-	0,02	39,79
PUERTOWILLIAMS	54,9167	67,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9035	-	-	19,9035	19,9035	-	-	0,59	15,99
PULAU LANGKAWI	6,4308	99,7642	-	0%	7,000,000	29,0371	-	-	29,0371	29,0371	-	-	0,10	18,61
PYEONGTAEK	36,9667	126,8228	-	0%	7,000,000	41,8445	-	-	41,8445	41,8445	-	-	0,00	41,39
RAFINA	38,0333	24,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	62,7181	-	-	62,7181	62,7181	-	-	1,40	134,20
RANGIROA	14,9458	147,7060	-	0%	7,000,000	12,7620	-	-	12,7620	21,7273	21,7273	-	1,11	173,09
RANGOON	16,7667	96,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	17,8843	-	-	17,8843	17,8843	-	-	0,09	33,38
RATAN	63,9861	20,8950	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5605	-	-	1,5605	1,5605	-	-	0,05	27,03
REALQUEZON	14,6667	121,6000	-	0%	7,000,000	17,8391	-	-	17,8391	17,8391	-	-	0,48	89,71
REGGIOCALABRIAI	38,1217	15,6489	-	0%	7,000,000	18,5389	-	-	18,5389	18,5389	-	-	0,17	6,78
RHODOS	36,4417	28,2364	-	0%	7,000,000	56,1171	-	-	56,1171	56,1171	-	-	0,35	81,89
RHODOSII	36,4417	28,2364	-	0%	7,000,000	35,6773	-	-	35,6773	35,6773	-	-	0,22	10,60
RIKITEA	23,1223	134,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	89,9012	-	-	89,9012	89,9012	-	-	1,24	51,99
RINCONISLAND	34,3483	119,4417	-	0%	7,000,000	45,8475	-	-	45,8475	45,8475	-	-	0,01	43,83
RIVIERE-AU-RENARD	49,0000	64,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	58,2292	-	-	58,2292	58,2292	-	-	0,25	29,95

ROCKPORT	28,0217	-	-	0%	7,000,000	51,2580	-	-	51,2580	51,2580	-	0,17	30,14
RODBYHAVN	54,6558	11,3486	-	0%	7,000,000	30,6832	-	30,6832	-	30,6832	30,6832	0,02	28,00
RODRIGUESIS	-	19,6667	63,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	3,7153	-	3,7153	3,7153	3,7153	0,51	78,11
RONNSKAR	63,0667	20,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	122,3281	-	-	122,3281	122,3281	122,3281	0,22	217,21
RORVIK	64,8595	11,2301	-	0%	7,000,000	14,5248	-	-	14,5248	14,5248	14,5248	0,45	46,62
ROSALES	-	38,9333	62,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	11,9508	-	11,9508	-	11,9508	0,15	54,79
ROSYTH	56,0167	-	3,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	4,4048	-	4,4048	4,4048	4,4048	0,24	54,25
ROVINJ	45,0833	13,6283	-	0%	7,000,000	67,5669	-	-	67,5669	67,5669	67,5669	0,21	40,54
RUSSKAIAGAVANII	76,1833	62,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	30,0834	-	-	30,0834	30,0834	30,0834	0,43	14,40
RUSSKAYAGAVAN	76,2000	62,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	38,7201	-	38,7201	-	38,7201	38,7201	0,83	70,32
RUSTICO	46,4667	63,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	4,5125	-	-	4,5125	4,5125	4,5125	0,19	34,94
SABINEPASS	29,7050	93,8533	-	0%	7,000,000	6,2144	-	6,2144	-	6,2144	6,2144	0,16	10,56
SAGYLLAH-ARY	73,1500	128,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	2,3963	-	-	2,3963	2,3963	2,3963	0,29	68,15
SAINTJOHN,N.B.	45,2667	66,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	19,0209	-	19,0209	-	19,3786	19,3786	0,11	80,63
SALALAH	16,9333	54,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	76,3133	-	-	76,3133	76,3133	76,3133	0,29	45,63
SALGRUND	62,3333	21,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	8,5217	-	-	8,5217	8,5217	8,5217	0,03	23,71
SANCLEMENTEISLAND	33,0000	118,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	0,6366	-	-	0,6366	0,6366	0,6366	0,35	85,11
SANCRISTOBAL	0,9000	89,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	7,9251	-	7,9251	-	7,9251	7,9251	0,52	35,28
SANDIEGO(QUARANTINESTATION)	32,7133	117,1733	-	0%	7,000,000	269,0285	-	-	269,0285	269,0285	269,0285	0,67	549,10
SANFELIX	26,2922	80,1086	-	0%	7,000,000	1,1905	-	1,1905	-	1,1905	1,1905	1,16	125,99
SANFERNANDO,LAUNION	16,6167	120,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	54,7567	-	-	54,7567	54,7567	54,7567	0,10	42,04
SANJUAN	-	15,3667	75,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	73,9596	-	-	73,9596	73,9596	0,04	70,29
SANTABARBARA,CALIFORNIA	34,4083	119,6850	-	0%	7,000,000	68,1843	-	-	68,1843	68,1843	68,1843	0,08	78,78
SANTACRUZDELAPALMA	28,6797	17,7664	-	0%	7,000,000	29,3744	-	29,3744	-	29,3744	29,3744	0,14	59,42
SANTAMONICA(MUNICIPALPIER)	34,0083	118,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	31,4410	-	-	31,4410	25,1976	25,1976	0,45	7,21
SANTANDERIII	43,4613	3,7908	-	0%	7,000,000	83,1271	-	83,1271	-	83,1271	83,1271	0,21	122,63
SANTOTOMASDECASTILLA	15,7000	88,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	23,3602	-	23,3602	-	23,3602	23,3602	0,02	19,61

SEATTLE	47,6017	-	122,3383	-	0%	7,000,000	38,9975	-	-	38,9975	38,9975	-	38,9975	-	0,56	60,97
SEAVEYISLAND	43,0800	-	70,7417	-	0%	7,000,000	-	140,4123	-	140,4123	140,4123	140,4123	140,4123	0,24	-	208,54
SE-LAHA	70,1500	-	72,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	11,5806	-	11,5806	11,5806	11,5806	11,5806	0,03	-	4,77
SETTLEMENTPOINT	26,7100	-	78,9967	-	0%	7,000,000	-	12,6967	-	12,6967	12,6967	12,6967	12,6967	0,22	-	27,72
SEWELLSPPOINT,HAMPTONROADS	36,9467	-	76,3300	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,2169	-	7,2169	7,2169	7,2169	7,2169	0,99	-	37,43
SHIJIUSUO	35,3833	-	119,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	155,3188	-	155,3188	155,3188	155,3188	155,3188	0,07	-	170,97
SHIMIZU-MINATO	35,0117	-	138,5175	-	0%	7,000,000	-	10,6205	-	10,6205	10,6205	10,6205	10,6205	0,34	-	23,64
SHIMONOSEKIII	33,9667	-	130,9500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	90,4834	-	90,4834	90,4834	90,4834	90,4834	0,41	-	18,92
SHIMONOSEKIII	33,9250	-	130,9278	-	0%	7,000,000	-	16,6297	-	16,6297	16,6297	16,6297	16,6297	3,74	-	69,05
SIBAURA	35,6333	-	139,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	0,4506	-	0,4506	0,4506	0,4506	0,4506	0,01	-	2,98
SINES	37,9500	-	8,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	21,0833	-	21,0833	21,0833	21,0833	21,0833	1,65	-	81,47
SIROS	37,4400	-	24,9458	-	0%	7,000,000	-	47,4903	-	47,4903	47,4903	47,4903	47,4903	0,03	-	49,91
SMOGEN	58,3536	-	11,2178	-	0%	7,000,000	-	12,3912	-	12,3912	12,3912	12,3912	12,3912	0,87	-	94,49
SODERSKAR	60,1167	-	25,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	8,2718	-	8,2718	8,2718	8,2718	8,2718	0,07	-	37,06
SOLNECHNAIA(SOLNECHNAIABUKHTA)	78,2000	-	103,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	42,8632	-	42,8632	42,8632	42,8632	42,8632	0,08	-	29,91
SOOKE	48,3667	-	123,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	71,5390	-	71,5390	71,5390	71,5390	71,5390	0,12	-	84,16
SOUDHAS	35,4875	-	24,0825	-	0%	7,000,000	-	73,4175	-	73,4175	73,4175	73,4175	73,4175	0,42	-	120,98
SOUTHBEACH	44,6250	-	124,0417	-	0%	7,000,000	-	15,7004	-	15,7004	15,7004	15,7004	15,7004	0,11	-	11,53
SOUTHISLANDPLANTATION,WINYAHBAY	33,2350	-	79,2033	-	0%	7,000,000	-	52,3304	-	52,3304	52,3304	52,3304	52,3304	0,72	-	78,78
SOUTHPASS	28,9900	-	89,1400	-	0%	7,000,000	-	3,5037	-	3,5037	3,5037	3,5037	3,5037	0,12	-	17,81
SOUTHPORT	33,9150	-	78,0183	-	0%	7,000,000	-	50,5014	-	50,5014	50,5014	50,5014	50,5014	0,37	-	123,39
SPRINGMAIDPIER	33,6550	-	78,9183	-	0%	7,000,000	-	1,8922	-	1,8922	1,8922	1,8922	1,8922	0,18	-	43,94
ST.JOHN'S,NFLD.	47,5667	-	52,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	27,1809	-	27,1809	27,1809	27,1809	27,1809	0,02	-	18,30
ST.MALO	48,6411	-	2,0282	-	0%	7,000,000	-	3,3573	-	3,3573	3,3573	3,3573	3,3573	0,14	-	61,53
ST.NAZAIRE	47,2700	-	2,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	49,3948	-	49,3948	49,3948	49,3948	49,3948	0,40	-	130,31
STANLEY	51,6903	-	57,8649	-	0%	7,000,000	-	11,7170	-	11,7170	11,7170	11,7170	11,7170	0,17	-	11,37
STAVANGER	58,9743	-	5,7301	-	0%	7,000,000	-	95,6363	-	95,6363	95,6363	95,6363	95,6363	0,22	-	158,67

STE-ANNE-DES-MONTS	49,1333	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	30,6100	-	30,6100	-	0,38	0,04
STERLEGOVA(STERLEGOVAMYS)	75,4167	88,9000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	26,6536	-	26,6536	-	1,02	40,43
ST-FRANCOIS	47,0000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	21,4182	-	21,4182	-	0,04	19,31
ST-JEAN-PORT-JOLI	47,2167	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	18,2488	-	18,2488	-	0,68	107,58
ST-JOSEPH-DE-LA-RIVE	47,4500	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	16,1539	-	16,1539	-	0,30	36,78
STOMPNEUSBAY	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	3,9375	-	3,9375	-	0,01	1,46
STONYPOINT	-	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	30,8888	-	30,8888	-	0,06	36,14
SULTANSHOAL	1,2333	103,6500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	7,5760	-	7,5760	-	0,85	23,39
SUMOTO	34,3406	134,9067	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	35,8741	-	35,8741	-	0,28	44,87
SVIATOINOS(SVIATOINOSMYS)	72,8333	140,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	1,7493	-	1,7493	-	0,08	9,18
SWINOUSCIE	53,9167	14,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	133,7383	-	133,7383	-	0,06	207,07
TACLOBAN,LEYTE	11,2500	125,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	13,5429	-	13,5429	-	0,63	47,13
TADIBE-IAHA	70,3667	72,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	79,1024	-	79,1024	-	0,35	113,14
TADOUSSAC	48,1333	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	14,5618	-	14,5618	-	0,19	12,04
TAEAN	36,9131	126,2389	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	63,2616	-	66,6251	-	0,32	106,38
TAGO	34,8069	138,7642	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	0,2407	-	0,2407	-	0,34	63,54
TAIPOKAU,TOLOHARBOUR	22,4425	114,1839	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	19,3355	-	19,3355	-	0,14	32,49
TAKAMATSUII	34,3514	134,0569	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	1,4119	-	1,4119	-	0,17	27,88
TALLINN	59,4500	24,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	72,0437	-	72,0437	-	0,90	123,60
TANDAG,SURIGAODELSUR	9,0833	126,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	31,2562	-	31,2562	-	0,12	16,28
TANGACHCHIMADAM	9,2833	79,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	103,0480	-	103,0480	-	0,90	76,82
TANJUNGGELANG	3,9750	103,4300	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	589,0359	-	589,0359	-	0,17	578,90
TAPPI	41,2425	140,3814	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	19,9846	-	19,9846	-	0,12	5,13
TARANTO	40,4333	17,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	92,1012	-	92,1012	-	0,34	120,78
TARAWA-A,BETIO	1,3667	172,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	1,8082	-	1,8082	-	0,44	38,64
TEIGNMOUTHPIER	50,5439	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	9,0201	-	9,0201	-	1,05	116,47
TEJN	55,2497	14,8378	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	70,9422	-	70,9422	-	0,18	86,28
TERPIAI-TUMSA	73,5500	118,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	57,1673	-	57,1673	-	0,28	91,73

THESSALONIKI	40,6325	22,9349	-	0%	7,000,000	-	20,1265	-	20,1265	-	20,1265	0,42	-	80,76
TOKYOI	35,6667	139,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	39,2152	-	-	39,2152	-	39,2152	0,30	-	113,87
TOKYOII	35,6500	139,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	9,8786	-	-	9,8786	-	9,8786	0,59	-	95,50
TOLCHESTERBEACH,MARYLAND	39,2133	-	-	0%	7,000,000	54,1228	-	-	54,1228	-	54,1228	0,25	-	62,35
TOPOLOBAMPO	25,6000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	68,2460	-	-	68,2460	-	68,2460	0,00	-	68,30
TORSHAVN	62,0167	6,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	2,1626	-	-	2,1626	-	2,1626	0,23	-	55,35
TOWERPIER	51,5000	0,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	82,5961	-	-	82,5961	-	82,5961	0,65	-	8,53
TOWNSVILLEI	-	19,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	63,6123	-	-	63,6123	-	63,6123	0,10	-	46,46
TROIS-RIVIERES	46,3333	-	-	0%	7,000,000	25,0358	-	-	25,0358	-	25,0358	0,59	-	39,28
TROMSO	69,6474	18,9613	-	0%	7,000,000	40,6503	-	-	40,6503	-	40,6503	0,43	-	50,21
TRONDHEIM	63,4333	10,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	137,4191	-	-	137,4191	-	137,4191	0,29	-	312,45
TUBUJAI	-	23,3418	-	0%	7,000,000	51,5614	-	-	51,5614	-	51,5614	0,02	-	49,21
TUMACO	1,8333	-	-	0%	7,000,000	73,7007	-	-	73,7007	-	73,7007	0,09	-	89,34
TUTICORIN	8,7500	78,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	19,1316	-	-	19,1316	-	19,1316	0,14	-	11,70
TUXPAN	21,0000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9585	-	-	2,9585	-	2,9585	0,09	-	13,60
ULLAPOOL	57,8953	-	-	0%	7,000,000	5,1579	-	-	2,4049	-	3,4246	0,04	-	12,10
ULLEUNG	37,4914	130,9136	-	0%	7,000,000	16,2226	-	-	16,2226	-	16,2226	0,17	-	51,48
ULSAN	35,5019	129,3872	-	0%	7,000,000	40,9394	-	-	40,9394	-	40,9394	0,71	-	93,82
URAGAMI	33,5583	135,8964	-	0%	7,000,000	24,2477	-	-	24,2477	-	24,2477	0,03	-	28,78
URAKAWAI	42,1667	142,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3758	-	-	0,3758	-	0,3758	0,11	-	31,96
URANGANII	-	25,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	33,0801	-	-	33,0801	-	33,0801	0,19	-	12,15
USHUAIAI	54,8167	-	-	0%	7,000,000	68,2167	-	-	2,0183	-	2,0183	0,23	-	57,92
USTKA	54,5833	16,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	34,5105	-	34,5105	0,49	-	108,56
VADSO	70,0667	29,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	38,1765	-	-	38,1765	-	38,1765	1,97	-	89,42
VALENCIA	39,4420	-	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3113	-	-	30,4814	-	30,4814	0,26	-	13,23
VALKARKAI	70,0833	170,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	-	-	0,3146	-	0,3146	0,09	-	10,36
VANKAREM	67,8333	-	-	0%	7,000,000	175,8333	-	-	7,9316	-	7,9316	0,25	-	36,28
VICTORHARBOUR	-	35,5625	-	0%	7,000,000	138,6354	-	-	28,9835	-	28,9835	0,04	-	18,28

VICTORIA	48,4167	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	65,1943	-	- 65,1943	65,1943	-	65,1943	0,23	32,40	
VIKER	59,0360	10,9498	-	0%	7.000,0000	75,5357	-	75,5357	75,5357	-	75,5357	0,40	41,87	
VIS-CESKAVILA	43,0667	16,2000	-	0%	7.000,0000	33,5412	-	33,5412	33,5412	-	33,5412	0,15	61,16	
VISE(VISEOSTROV)	79,5000	76,9833	-	0%	7.000,0000	38,2527	-	- 38,2527	38,2527	-	38,2527	0,10	66,09	
VLISSINGEN	51,4422	3,5961	-	0%	7.000,0000	224,0138	-	- 224,0138	224,0138	-	224,0138	0,42	424,04	
VRANGELIA(VRANGELIAOSTROV)	70,9833	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	79,5077	-	- 79,5077	79,5077	-	79,5077	0,02	74,30	
WAGLANISLAND	22,1831	114,3028	-	0%	7.000,0000	35,5964	-	- 35,5964	35,5964	-	35,5964	0,81	11,97	
WAJIMA	37,4058	136,9003	-	0%	7.000,0000	3,1470	-	- 3,1470	3,1470	-	3,1470	0,21	29,42	
WALTONNTHENAZE	51,8500	1,2667	-	0%	7.000,0000	- 3,6099	-	3,6099	-	-	3,6099	0,01	2,33	
WALVISBAY	-	22,9493	14,4985	-	0%	7.000,0000	- 9,4848	-	9,4848	-	9,4848	0,03	5,12	
WELLINGTONHARBOUR	-	41,2843	174,7798	-	0%	7.000,0000	78,0882	-	- 78,0882	78,0882	-	78,0882	0,56	116,19
WESTBAYHARBOUR	-	50,7089	2,7641	-	0%	7.000,0000	87,8042	-	87,8042	-	93,7480	0,73	184,32	
WEWAK	-	3,5500	143,6333	-	0%	7.000,0000	25,7504	-	25,7504	-	25,7504	0,06	16,40	
WLADYSLAWOWO	-	54,8000	18,4167	-	0%	7.000,0000	50,5576	-	- 50,5576	50,5576	-	50,5576	0,49	26,73
WYNDHAM	-	15,4533	128,1010	-	0%	7.000,0000	46,8236	-	- 46,8236	46,8236	-	46,8236	0,34	80,22
XIAMEN	-	24,4500	118,0667	-	0%	7.000,0000	-	-	69,1788	-	69,1788	0,03	77,93	
YAIZU	-	34,8706	138,3272	-	0%	7.000,0000	60,1396	-	60,1396	-	60,1396	0,12	82,74	
YAMBA	-	29,4297	153,3619	-	0%	7.000,0000	34,9220	-	34,9220	-	34,9220	0,09	77,27	
ZEMLIABUNGE	-	74,8833	142,1167	-	0%	7.000,0000	21,9388	-	- 21,9388	21,9388	-	21,9388	0,23	12,01

Table 2. Results for B1 – 2005 – 2019

Station	latitude	longitude	sample	completeness	psmsl mean	mean tot (realigned val)	mean (baseline)	R1	mean non base	R2	Coef RR	offset RO
BOURGAS	42,4833	27,4833	168	100%	7.177,2440	-	177,2440	177,3876	-	216,0751	0,30	-
ARKO	58,4842	16,9606	168	100%	7.085,9286	65,6339	85,9286	20,2947	31,6595	54,2691	0,25	24,17
MALYSHEVA(MALYSHEVAOSTROV)	72,0667	129,8333	168	100%	7.176,3452	17,4711	176,3452	158,8742	-	206,4121	0,32	-
JOHNSTONISLAND	16,7383	-	168	100%	7.028,4286	55,5977	28,4286	-	65,2351	-	0,06	86,71
MACABALANPORT,CAGAYANDEORO	8,5000	124,6667	168	100%	6.821,1369	-	178,8631	-	34,3652	-	0,43	23,87
TANJONGCHANGI	1,3903	103,9989	168	100%	7.030,8155	1,0011	30,8155	29,8144	-	43,3835	0,15	-
ANABAR	73,2167	113,5000	168	100%	7.071,4226	35,1369	71,4226	36,2857	20,2752	51,1475	0,15	-
MURMANSK	68,9667	33,0500	168	100%	7.203,8036	62,7012	203,8036	141,1024	16,8990	186,9046	0,34	93,51
LAJOLLA(SCRIPPSPIER)	32,8667	-	168	100%	7.047,5714	-	47,5714	61,5461	26,6222	74,1936	0,09	-
CHUUK,MOENISLAND	7,4467	151,8467	168	100%	7.056,7202	5,9196	56,7202	62,6398	-	77,8420	0,13	-
KAINAN	34,1442	135,1914	168	100%	6.978,4286	-	21,5714	27,4955	58,0216	36,4502	0,06	-
VARNA	43,1833	27,9167	168	100%	7.030,4762	62,6125	30,4762	-	69,4269	38,9507	0,03	82,12
YAKUTAT	59,5483	-	168	100%	7.138,9524	18,4866	138,9524	157,4390	54,6228	193,5751	0,30	-
MOREHEADCITY	34,7167	-	168	100%	7.063,6190	1,0722	63,6190	62,5469	-	84,2230	0,19	-
PUERTOCORTES	15,8333	-	168	100%	7.203,5000	101,6373	203,5000	101,8627	76,4433	127,0567	0,21	-
YEOSU	34,7472	127,7656	168	100%	7.322,1250	278,1560	322,1250	43,9690	260,7453	61,3797	0,08	251,55
HANASAKI	43,2833	145,5833	168	100%	6.822,9583	298,0695	177,0417	121,0278	318,0271	140,9855	0,14	402,35
DALIAN	38,8667	121,6833	168	100%	7.041,0536	48,0496	41,0536	-	49,7293	8,6757	0,03	61,57
MARSEILLE	43,2788	5,3539	168	100%	6.976,0238	52,2666	23,9762	28,2904	59,0515	35,0753	0,03	72,25
CLEARWATERBEACH	27,9783	-	168	100%	6.999,0536	29,8605	0,9464	-	45,6079	46,5544	0,16	81,09
KOTAPHAONOI	7,8333	98,4333	168	100%	6.986,4048	61,0076	13,5952	-	80,2228	93,8180	0,16	150,10
MINAMIIZU	34,6167	138,8833	168	100%	6.966,2202	52,7172	33,7798	18,9374	61,6913	27,9116	0,07	77,59
VARBERG	57,1000	12,2167	168	100%	6.975,0357	41,0964	24,9643	16,1321	44,3746	19,4103	0,00	42,68
NUKU'ALOFAB	21,1368	175,1807	168	100%	6.944,2440	34,3368	55,7560	21,4192	22,7081	33,0479	0,09	8,57
WILLETSPPOINT	40,7933	-	168	100%	7.101,8274	47,5437	101,8274	54,2836	36,2570	65,5703	0,09	2,54

ULUKHAKTOK(FORMERLYHOLMAN)	70,7363	-	168	100%	7.144,3512	65,5383	144,3512	78,8129	24,5806	119,7706	0,34	-	34,90	
HELSINKI	60,1536	24,9562	168	100%	7.143,3631	98,3518	143,3631	241,7149	-	129,1249	272,4880	0,24	-	338,47
PORTBLAIR	11,6833	92,7667	168	100%	7.152,3155	30,2845	152,3155	122,0310	8,3943	143,9212	0,18	-	94,89	
KOTKA	60,4500	26,9500	168	100%	7.170,4048	59,5871	170,4048	110,8177	40,0799	130,3249	0,17	-	64,77	
HAULOVERPIER	25,9033	-	168	100%	7.024,0060	19,0626	24,0060	43,0685	-	88,2784	112,2844	0,48	-	100,51
AMDERMA	69,7500	61,7000	168	100%	6.897,2381	2,3435	102,7619	100,4184	24,1168	126,8787	0,21	-	100,26	
BERGEN	60,3980	5,3205	168	100%	6.853,4464	120,4022	146,5536	26,1514	110,4566	36,0970	0,08	-	86,70	
CAPELAMBERT	20,5880	117,1860	168	100%	7.117,2381	72,9138	117,2381	44,3243	10,0274	107,2107	0,45	-	5,07	
SKAGWAY	59,4500	-	168	100%	7.203,6964	84,0533	203,6964	119,6432	54,3474	149,3491	0,23	-	41,72	
GRONDINES	46,5833	72,0333	168	100%	6.948,8095	56,8916	51,1905	5,7011	54,4939	3,3034	0,01	-	49,40	
NEWLYN	50,1030	5,5428	168	100%	7.093,9940	16,7241	93,9940	110,7182	32,7801	126,7742	0,12	-	117,08	
HEYSHAM	54,0318	2,9203	168	100%	7.005,7679	14,3411	5,7679	8,5733	17,6718	11,9040	0,04	-	29,66	
VENEZIA(S.STEFANO)	45,4167	12,3333	168	100%	6.952,3452	101,8395	47,6548	149,4942	124,3373	171,9920	0,16	-	240,18	
IMBITUBA	28,2333	48,6500	168	100%	7.074,5536	27,1017	74,5536	47,4518	16,1261	58,4275	0,10	-	24,68	
DOUGLAS	54,1500	4,4667	168	100%	7.022,2738	3,9085	22,2738	18,3653	1,1317	23,4055	0,02	-	9,52	
MYRTLEBEACH	33,6833	78,8850	168	100%	7.002,3036	64,9939	2,3036	67,2974	87,0334	89,3370	0,17	-	127,78	
ZHOHOVA(ZHOHOVAOSTROV)	76,1500	152,8333	168	100%	6.987,2262	0,9832	12,7738	13,7570	6,5953	19,3691	0,06	-	26,74	
FURUOGRUND	64,9158	21,2306	168	100%	7.106,0476	29,5827	106,0476	76,4649	14,8950	91,1526	0,13	-	57,04	
EVENSKJAER	68,5833	16,5500	168	100%	7.047,8214	82,3706	47,8214	34,5491	92,0705	44,2491	0,06	-	114,15	
ARRECIFE-D	28,9658	13,5379	168	100%	6.783,9524	274,6396	216,0476	58,5920	295,9799	79,9323	0,16	-	327,63	
DIAMONDHARBOUR	22,2000	88,1667	168	100%	6.937,8988	4,9706	62,1012	67,0718	25,5240	87,6252	0,15	-	79,65	
ST.PAUL'SHARBOR,KODIAK	57,7450	152,4817	168	100%	7.138,7024	116,1425	138,7024	22,5599	76,1846	62,5178	0,29	-	66,72	
DUBLIN	53,3500	6,2167	168	100%	7.270,7976	71,0352	270,7976	199,7624	22,1656	248,6321	0,39	-	145,56	
USTOLENEK	73,0000	119,8667	168	100%	7.086,7976	56,1686	86,7976	30,6290	48,8800	37,9176	0,07	-	20,48	
KODIAKISLAND,WOMENS BAY	57,7317	152,5117	168	100%	6.345,2024	168,2281	654,7976	486,5695	29,7398	625,0578	1,12	-	397,88	
POINTENOIRE	4,7833	11,8333	168	100%	7.013,9702	18,5161	13,9702	4,5459	21,3704	7,4001	0,05	-	40,15	
ARRECIFE2	28,9719	13,5301	168	100%	7.051,0298	25,6016	51,0298	25,4282	13,4863	37,5435	0,14	-	13,01	
QUEBEC(LAUZON)	46,8333	71,1667	168	100%	7.079,8869	108,0649	79,8869	187,9518	141,9393	221,8262	0,25	-	288,47	

SANDWICHMARINA, CAPECODCANALENTRANCE	41,7667	- 70,5000	168	100%	7.135,6845	99,7328	135,6845	35,9518	74,9335	60,7511	0,30	0,33
WEST-TERSCHELLING	53,3631	5,2200	168	100%	7.166,1190	70,2446	166,1190	95,8745	51,9338	114,1852	0,16	- 31,31
NORTHPOINT	22,3000	114,2000	168	100%	7.179,9464	30,2527	179,9464	149,6937	2,9596	182,9060	0,28	- 134,83
BITUNGII	1,4333	125,2000	168	100%	7.241,2083	138,2246	241,2083	102,9837	90,2070	151,0014	0,39	- 11,79
ALVARADO	18,7667	- 95,7667	168	100%	6.975,3274	13,9550	24,6726	- 38,6276	27,3935	52,0661	0,15	- 75,63
REGGIOCALABRIA	38,1000	15,6500	168	100%	6.954,2202	83,0369	45,7798	37,2571	94,0321	48,2524	0,06	- 111,29
FISHGUARD	52,0132	- 4,9838	168	100%	7.057,5119	38,5571	57,5119	18,9548	4,7940	52,7179	0,24	- 1,22
SOUDHASII	35,4875	24,0825	168	100%	6.826,4821	56,8030	173,5179	116,7148	6,0165	179,5343	0,44	- 67,89
PALMADEMALLORCA	39,5524	2,6389	168	100%	7.059,9643	40,5875	59,9643	19,3768	28,4371	31,5272	0,12	- 5,95
TURKEYPOINT	29,9150	- 84,5117	168	100%	7.053,5119	34,3396	53,5119	87,8515	72,5347	126,0466	0,32	- 138,76
DUCKPIEROUTSIDE	36,1833	- 75,7467	167	99%	7.164,3353	75,0447	164,3353	89,2907	36,5816	127,7537	0,31	- 28,72
ALAMITOSBAYENTRANCE	33,7500	- 118,1167	167	99%	7.205,0359	106,8524	205,0359	98,1836	76,7425	128,2934	0,24	- 1,37
BILBAO	43,3515	- 3,0451	167	99%	7.177,8563	153,3357	177,8563	24,5206	114,1239	63,7324	0,30	- 102,14
TUAS(WESTJURONG)	1,2833	103,6667	167	99%	7.050,1018	33,5212	50,1018	16,5806	26,7974	23,3044	0,09	- 6,00
STROMSTAD	58,9500	11,1833	167	99%	7.292,7186	158,6427	292,7186	134,0758	134,9824	157,7362	0,18	- 24,16
ARICA	18,4667	- 70,3333	167	99%	6.453,3772	183,6856	546,6228	362,9371	82,3323	464,2905	0,70	- 151,68
YOKOSUKA	35,2881	139,6514	167	99%	7.051,8802	17,0438	51,8802	68,9241	40,0163	91,8965	0,12	- 70,21
CHURCHILL	58,7667	- 94,1833	167	99%	6.989,4192	25,1425	10,5808	- 35,7233	35,1204	45,7012	0,11	- 87,03
POINTATKINSON	49,3333	- 123,2500	167	99%	7.180,5389	1,0910	180,5389	179,4480	31,5461	212,0850	0,27	- 187,15
BELFAST	54,6000	- 5,9167	167	99%	7.094,4491	14,5539	94,4491	109,0030	51,9054	146,3545	0,31	- 142,48
PORTSANLUIS	35,1767	- 120,7600	167	99%	7.073,4611	64,2802	73,4611	137,7413	95,8949	169,3560	0,27	- 206,82
CADIZII	36,5278	- 6,3114	167	99%	7.432,2216	108,8539	432,2216	323,3677	44,2766	387,9449	0,54	- 253,57
MATSUYAMAI	33,8589	132,7122	167	99%	6.809,3713	88,0398	190,6287	102,5890	45,2833	145,3454	0,39	- 64,50
FORCADOS	5,3500	5,3500	167	99%	7.008,5928	86,5786	8,5928	77,9858	119,6457	111,0529	0,24	- 165,88
SANNIKOVA(SANNIKOVAPROLIV)	74,6667	138,9000	167	99%	7.155,4731	42,8496	155,4731	112,6235	12,2765	143,1966	0,22	- 66,56
STOCKHOLM	59,3242	18,0817	167	99%	6.973,9940	143,7072	26,0060	169,7131	172,1729	198,1789	0,24	- 335,56
SANDOWNPIER	50,6511	- 1,1532	166	99%	7.245,9880	212,0338	245,9880	33,9541	170,6599	75,3280	0,37	- 149,52
WEYMOUTH	50,6085	- 2,4479	166	99%	6.982,1084	76,5538	17,8916	58,6623	102,1754	84,2838	0,22	- 147,01

N.SPIT,HUMBOLDTBAY	40,7667	-	124,2167	166	99%	7.102,2410	72,7866	102,2410	29,4543	23,4591	78,7818	0,34	18,10
NEWYORK(THEBATTERY)	40,7000	-	74,0133	166	99%	7.107,3735	21,1490	107,3735	128,5225	37,1964	144,5699	0,12	143,91
ALGECIRASB	36,1214	-	5,4371	166	99%	7.113,3916	81,1949	113,3916	32,1967	63,4551	49,9365	0,18	31,63
RECIFE	8,0500	-	34,8667	166	99%	7.234,3373	103,8713	234,3373	130,4661	70,3126	164,0247	0,27	36,41
KRISTIANSUND	63,1139	-	7,7344	166	99%	6.898,1145	540,6564	101,8855	- 642,5420	746,5992	848,4848	1,51	1.226,14
LOSANGELES	33,7200	-	118,2717	166	99%	7.257,0181	123,8781	257,0181	133,1399	97,8405	159,1776	0,20	7,61
LAPALMA	28,6778	-	17,7680	166	99%	6.598,9096	173,0111	401,0904	- 228,0792	33,1686	367,9218	1,03	118,23
LOHM	60,1000	-	21,6667	166	99%	7.200,8072	13,0555	200,8072	213,8628	55,8855	256,6927	0,33	228,44
UBLI	42,7500	-	16,8333	166	99%	7.119,6807	87,2976	119,6807	32,3831	32,3418	87,3389	0,30	39,17
FEDOROVA(CHELUSKINMYS)	77,7167	-	104,3000	166	99%	7.104,3614	4,1620	104,3614	100,1995	19,9474	124,3089	0,17	80,26
BUZZARDSBAY	41,7417	-	70,6167	166	99%	6.743,5602	155,1470	256,4398	101,2928	65,0889	191,3509	0,76	5,88
CANAVIEIRAS	15,6667	-	38,9667	165	98%	7.080,2485	47,0915	80,2485	33,1570	38,6095	41,6390	0,08	10,76
DAUPHINISLAND	30,2500	-	88,0750	165	98%	7.008,8121	36,4410	8,8121	45,2531	53,6222	62,4343	0,14	87,96
SEMBAWANG	1,4667	-	103,8333	165	98%	7.167,5030	90,4403	167,5030	77,0627	68,5201	98,9830	0,18	12,58
CROMER	52,9344	-	1,3016	165	98%	7.119,4848	46,9076	119,4848	72,5773	16,6046	102,8802	0,25	34,67
ZEEBRUGGE	51,3500	-	3,2000	165	98%	7.105,7576	9,8548	105,7576	95,9028	12,0574	117,8149	0,18	87,09
SOUTHEND	51,5145	-	0,7238	165	98%	7.215,8121	77,5995	215,8121	138,2126	48,0858	167,7263	0,23	61,09
PORTGILES	35,0218	-	137,7683	165	98%	7.036,4485	91,4863	36,4485	55,0378	113,6595	77,2110	0,16	145,73
SHALAUROVA(SHALAUROVAMYS)	73,1833	-	143,2333	165	98%	7.132,3455	32,2972	132,3455	100,0483	5,4903	126,8551	0,20	63,70
FUKUE	32,6961	-	128,8494	165	98%	7.136,4606	92,3631	136,4606	44,0975	52,8427	83,6179	0,36	15,98
KUSHIRO	42,9756	-	144,3714	164	98%	7.141,2378	11,1961	141,2378	130,0417	20,8023	162,0401	0,24	115,70
SOUTHSOUND	19,2667	-	81,3833	164	98%	7.135,2317	79,2649	135,2317	55,9668	56,3396	78,8921	0,18	16,94
KOZUSIMA	34,2092	-	139,1317	164	98%	7.042,2988	8,4561	42,2988	50,7549	25,0098	67,3086	0,14	63,34
MIAMIBEACH	25,7683	-	80,1317	163	97%	7.156,0184	34,5768	156,0184	121,4416	9,1058	146,9126	0,20	80,78
KOCHIII	33,4992	-	133,5692	163	97%	6.705,3252	86,7137	294,6748	207,9611	10,1873	304,8622	0,82	187,46
ABURATSU	31,5769	-	131,4094	163	97%	7.101,1166	39,8226	101,1166	61,2939	17,6025	83,5140	0,18	33,41
SEJINGKAT	1,5828	-	110,4222	163	97%	6.466,6442	453,3182	533,3558	- 80,0376	389,3210	144,0348	0,69	247,41
HARWICH	51,9480	-	1,2921	163	97%	7.154,7485	61,0540	154,7485	93,6945	30,5036	124,2448	0,14	0,52

FREEPORT	28,9483	-	163	97%	7.282,8098	20,3758	282,8098	262,4340	-	64,8155	347,6253	0,76	-	312,60	
PAPEETE-B,FAREUTEPOINT,SOC.IS.	-	-	163	97%	7.104,0614	59,6038	104,0613	44,4576	-	19,2704	123,3318	0,59	-	36,59	
EDITHBURG	35,0833	137,7500	163	97%	7.226,3252	61,1063	226,3252	165,2189	19,0375	207,2876	0,34	-	-	116,33	
ROOMPOTBUITEN	51,6197	3,6819	162	96%	7.051,7160	-	17,7505	51,7160	69,4666	-	47,4524	99,1685	0,25	-	100,46
UBIN	1,4194	103,9278	162	96%	6.319,0617	673,3856	680,9383	7,5527	669,5732	11,3650	0,02	-	-	678,69	
ONSLow	21,6497	115,1315	162	96%	7.085,9383	9,7430	85,9383	76,1953	23,4127	109,3510	0,26	-	-	77,42	
COLONIA	34,4833	57,8500	162	96%	7.155,1111	33,3955	155,1111	121,7156	2,9608	152,1503	0,28	-	-	125,69	
BILLINGA	69,8833	175,7667	161	96%	7.085,2112	3,9167	85,2112	81,2944	21,3767	106,5878	0,16	-	-	67,08	
HAKODATEII	41,7667	140,7167	160	95%	6.990,5375	54,5762	9,4625	-	64,0387	73,7864	83,2489	0,11	-	105,93	
LALIBERTADII	2,2000	80,9167	160	95%	7.072,8500	47,3296	72,8500	25,5204	0,7395	73,5895	0,33	-	-	5,29	
CILACAPB	7,7517	109,0167	158	94%	7.153,7342	116,6974	153,7342	37,0368	93,7314	60,0028	0,17	-	-	73,34	
WHANGAREIHARBOUR(MARSDENPOINT)	35,7574	174,3500	158	94%	7.098,1646	38,5022	98,1646	59,6624	19,0040	79,1606	0,15	-	-	20,53	
PUERTOPLATA	19,8167	70,7000	157	93%	7.255,9936	99,9045	255,9936	156,0892	59,6201	196,3736	0,32	-	-	56,90	
MATARANIB	17,0017	72,1083	156	93%	7.120,6474	67,1185	120,6474	53,5290	10,3563	110,2911	0,48	-	-	41,43	
TRAVEMUNDE	53,9581	10,8722	156	93%	7.121,1090	10,2281	121,1090	110,8808	3,8422	124,9512	0,10	-	-	92,94	
PUERTOSOBERANIA	62,4833	59,6333	156	93%	7.106,6987	34,6765	106,6987	72,0222	3,6466	110,3453	0,31	-	-	64,43	
PORTALBERNI	49,2333	124,8167	156	93%	6.746,6218	93,8984	253,3782	159,4798	51,6748	201,7034	0,38	-	-	100,93	
GRINDSTONE	47,3833	61,8667	156	93%	7.227,8846	116,2186	227,8846	111,6660	72,2198	155,6648	0,42	-	-	37,54	
PADANGB	0,9967	100,3750	156	93%	7.283,8590	173,4075	283,8590	110,4515	65,5952	218,2637	0,95	-	-	31,88	
RUSSARO	59,7667	22,9500	156	93%	6.999,4038	113,3068	0,5962	112,7107	128,0839	127,4877	0,12	-	-	223,10	
POLYARNIY	69,2000	33,4833	156	93%	6.828,5000	146,4437	171,5000	-	25,0563	132,7139	38,7861	0,16	-	101,23	
SANFRANCISCO	37,8067	122,4650	156	93%	7.099,7628	27,5658	99,7628	127,3286	42,1075	141,8704	0,12	-	-	149,62	
LYOKKI	60,8500	21,1833	156	93%	6.963,8718	79,7043	36,1282	-	115,8325	97,6498	133,7780	0,19	-	236,14	
LAUNION	13,3333	87,8167	156	93%	7.080,7821	34,3595	80,7821	46,4226	22,2578	58,5243	0,08	-	-	4,84	
SETTLEMENTPOINTA	26,6833	78,9833	156	93%	7.015,3141	21,9488	15,3141	37,2629	42,4468	57,7609	0,15	-	-	64,48	
ALOTAU	10,3167	150,4500	156	93%	7.046,1090	5,9998	46,1090	52,1088	31,2687	77,3777	0,20	-	-	69,75	
DENHELDER	52,9644	4,7450	156	93%	6.944,2628	190,9804	55,7372	135,2432	209,0145	153,2773	0,12	-	-	304,32	
MELILLA	35,2906	2,9285	156	93%	6.410,9808	395,5012	589,0192	193,5180	265,0303	323,9889	1,23	-	-	60,08	

SHIRAHAMA	33,6836	135,3753	156	93%	7.060,1026	6,0439	60,1026	54,0586	-	14,9069	75,0095	0,16	-	54,65
KOSICHANG	13,1500	100,8167	156	93%	6.948,0577	22,3460	51,9423	- 29,5963	-	14,5173	37,4250	0,08	-	19,92
BOUCAU	43,5273	1,5148	156	93%	6.840,0321	44,3150	159,9679	115,6529	14,8298	174,7978	0,52	-	-	113,93
TANJUNGSEDILI	1,9317	104,1150	156	93%	6.858,1538	121,9697	141,8462	19,8764	114,1329	27,7133	0,08	-	-	96,05
LLANDUDNO	53,3317	3,8252	156	93%	7.108,7244	72,9016	108,7244	35,8228	46,7741	61,9503	0,20	-	-	20,36
WINTERHARBOUR	50,5167	128,0333	156	93%	7.071,4615	1,1158	71,4615	70,3458	35,2808	106,7424	0,29	-	-	88,91
NEWPORT	41,5050	71,3267	156	93%	6.847,1410	14,5531	152,8590	138,3059	17,4612	170,3202	0,30	-	-	158,52
OWASE	34,0764	136,2072	156	93%	6.902,3397	57,7987	97,6603	39,8615	43,7952	53,8651	0,08	-	-	28,31
UTO	59,7833	21,3667	156	93%	6.942,7244	199,2257	57,2756	141,9501	218,3893	161,1137	0,15	-	-	334,40
WESTPORTHARBOUR	41,7456	171,5947	156	93%	6.899,0513	125,0290	100,9487	24,0803	129,6811	28,7324	0,05	-	-	104,02
SWANAGEPIER	50,6093	1,9492	156	93%	7.048,9551	19,9713	48,9551	28,9838	2,8634	46,0917	0,16	-	-	18,10
LEWES(BREAKWATERHARBOR)	38,7817	75,1200	156	93%	6.783,9808	39,8590	216,0192	255,8782	91,2496	307,2688	0,47	-	-	348,88
WARNEMUNDE2	54,1697	12,1033	156	93%	6.950,2115	189,2779	49,7885	139,4894	206,0116	156,2232	0,14	-	-	332,40
RESOLUTE	74,6833	94,8833	156	93%	7.120,6474	63,5223	120,6474	57,1251	42,7634	77,8841	0,20	-	-	10,77
RAROTONGAB	21,2048	159,7848	156	93%	7.013,5641	18,8383	13,5641	5,2742	23,8087	10,2446	0,00	-	-	17,75
DUNEDIN	45,8787	170,5134	156	93%	7.088,0256	39,3963	88,0256	48,6293	30,9016	57,1240	0,09	-	-	15,34
MIYAKOII	39,6431	141,9753	156	93%	6.956,0962	33,7945	43,9038	10,1093	28,8521	15,0518	0,04	-	-	19,59
NOME,ALASKA	64,5000	165,4300	156	93%	7.067,4103	3,3431	67,4103	70,7533	36,0260	103,4362	0,25	-	-	80,53
GETING	6,2264	102,1067	156	93%	7.126,0000	71,3666	126,0000	54,6334	46,5936	79,4064	0,18	-	-	13,02
LIVERPOOLGEORGESANDPRINCESPIERS	53,4000	3,0000	156	93%	7.053,7500	81,4749	53,7500	135,2249	98,7247	152,4747	0,13	-	-	205,78
NICE	43,6956	7,2855	156	93%	7.090,1474	77,8362	90,1474	12,3112	71,7122	18,4352	0,05	-	-	61,24
SKANOR	55,4167	12,8294	156	93%	7.030,2885	6,5567	30,2885	23,7317	9,3536	39,6420	0,11	-	-	22,10
DIEGOGARCIAD	7,2900	72,3933	156	93%	7.044,3397	76,1778	44,3397	31,8381	69,0701	24,7304	0,14	-	-	44,19
GANDIA	38,9952	0,1514	156	93%	7.027,1731	18,1141	27,1731	9,0589	5,9441	21,2290	0,07	-	-	2,23
SPLIT-GRADSKALUKA	43,5067	16,4417	156	93%	6.696,3077	18,5534	303,6923	285,1389	46,8852	350,5775	0,55	-	-	302,03
REPOSAARI	61,6167	21,4500	156	93%	6.929,0256	14,7317	70,9744	- 56,2427	5,4768	65,4976	0,09	-	-	56,61
BARMOUTH	52,7193	4,0450	156	93%	7.123,7821	83,8700	123,7821	39,9121	61,7387	62,0434	0,17	-	-	32,22
CIVITAVECCHIA	42,0500	11,8167	156	93%	6.606,6731	33,3066	393,3269	- 426,6335	104,8591	498,1860	0,64	-	-	522,84

POINTSAPIN	46,9667	-	64,8333	156	93%	7.060,0833	7,4368	60,0833	52,6465	-	14,4539	74,5372	0,19	-	60,95
NORTHSALAMINOS	37,9796	23,5417		156	93%	7.100,2564	41,2664	100,2564	58,9900	14,6763	85,5801	0,19	20,91		
YKSPIHLAJA	63,8333	23,0333		156	93%	7.056,3462	36,0398	56,3462	20,3063	34,3302	22,0159	0,00	34,33		
HARLINGEN	53,1756	5,4094		156	93%	6.965,4359	204,7119	34,5641	170,1478	227,9321	193,3680	0,20	390,40		
TAJIRI	35,5936	134,3158		156	93%	7.043,6603	16,8886	43,6603	60,5489	39,8901	83,5503	0,15	70,78		
VILLASANJURJO	35,2500	3,9167		156	93%	7.073,5641	75,3740	73,5641	148,9381	113,8926	187,4567	0,32	245,31		
POINTLARUE	4,6667	55,5333		156	93%	7.072,1026	56,7491	72,1026	15,3535	57,4987	14,6039	0,06	74,95		
EASTERISLAND-D	27,1500	109,4500		156	93%	6.820,6282	130,1813	179,3718	49,1905	112,0042	67,3676	0,11	92,02		
BARSEBACK	55,7564	12,9033		156	93%	7.101,8077	43,9485	101,8077	57,8592	4,2419	97,5658	0,33	42,53		
RIMOUSKI	48,4833	68,5167		156	93%	7.122,8974	62,2841	122,8974	60,6133	35,3448	87,5527	0,20	1,48		
PORTSAID	31,2500	32,3000		156	93%	6.679,8718	11,9515	320,1282	308,1767	52,3637	372,4919	0,59	360,52		
MAKURAZAKII	31,2667	130,3000		156	93%	7.152,6410	72,0240	152,6410	80,6170	41,7876	110,8534	0,20	2,49		
DEAL	51,2238	1,4092		156	93%	7.000,6090	23,9388	0,6090	24,5478	44,5632	45,1721	0,19	59,06		
ABASHIRI	44,0194	144,2858		156	93%	7.046,4038	1,0150	46,4038	45,3889	16,0808	62,4847	0,12	42,74		
ESASHI	41,8667	140,1333		156	93%	7.060,4231	3,6853	60,4231	56,7378	21,6674	82,0904	0,19	57,76		
LANAIISLAND,KAUMALAPAU	20,7800	156,9000		156	93%	6.982,4615	12,5429	17,5385	30,0814	31,6440	49,1825	0,19	58,30		
PORTMACQUARIE	31,4268	152,9110		156	93%	7.083,8077	57,7890	83,8077	26,0187	34,9684	48,8393	0,20	11,96		
VENEZIA(ARSENALE)	45,4167	12,3500		156	93%	6.896,6346	43,8545	103,3654	147,2198	62,4677	165,8331	0,20	201,27		
LIEPAJA	56,5333	20,9833		156	93%	6.953,3462	156,4064	46,6538	109,7526	171,5608	124,9070	0,12	271,00		
SASEBOII	33,1581	129,7239		156	93%	7.030,1667	30,4949	30,1667	60,6616	55,4790	85,6457	0,19	96,89		
VIKEN	56,1422	12,5792		156	93%	7.249,4423	121,9416	249,4423	127,5007	44,2233	205,2190	0,67	54,02		
YOSIOKA	41,4500	140,2500		156	93%	6.897,5577	76,3440	102,4423	26,0984	68,4748	33,9675	0,10	44,06		
SURSARI	60,0833	26,9833		156	93%	7.121,2949	80,0170	121,2949	41,2778	74,1628	47,1321	0,04	55,31		
WANDO	34,3153	126,7597		156	93%	7.054,5769	61,7031	54,5769	7,1262	68,2418	13,6649	0,04	74,43		
HALIFAX	44,6667	63,5833		156	93%	6.826,2179	25,0365	173,7821	198,8186	58,2221	232,0041	0,31	269,84		
VALDEZ	61,1250	146,3617		156	93%	7.011,8269	35,8111	11,8269	47,6381	53,2988	65,1257	0,14	85,35		
SIBONEY	23,1000	82,4667		156	93%	7.045,1667	33,6321	45,1667	11,5345	31,0686	14,0981	0,01	31,03		
SUCURAJ	43,1333	17,2000		156	93%	7.008,5064	5,7434	8,5064	14,2498	10,4623	18,9687	0,01	9,19		
MUSCATB	23,6283	58,5650		156	93%	7.078,6923	13,5358	78,6923	65,1565	40,3525	119,0448	0,45	90,00		

MAASSLUIS	51,9175	4,2497	156	93%	7.150,3718	-	19,0090	150,3718	169,3808	-	38,9549	189,3267	0,18	-	204,90
TOKUYAMAI	34,0333	131,8000	156	93%	7.086,5513	7,2219	86,5513	79,3294	-	15,9318	102,4831	0,18	-	76,47	
MARATHONSHORES	24,7333	81,0333	156	93%	6.952,8718	87,7249	47,1282	40,5967	-	128,7593	81,6311	0,26	-	140,04	
NEWCASTLEIII	32,9167	151,8000	156	93%	6.677,8462	2,6119	322,1538	324,7658	-	71,9398	394,0937	0,66	-	409,81	
PORTMORESBYII	9,4833	147,1333	156	93%	7.142,2051	47,8364	142,2051	94,3687	-	2,6153	139,5899	0,42	-	88,10	
CASEY	66,2667	110,5167	156	93%	6.851,4808	121,4951	148,5192	27,0241	-	110,9629	37,5563	0,12	-	85,97	
CHOSHI-GYOKO	35,7444	140,8583	156	93%	7.371,4808	157,0326	371,4808	214,4481	-	168,3465	203,1343	0,02	-	163,97	
FELIXSTOWE	51,9577	1,3466	156	93%	6.999,2564	53,7314	0,7436	-	54,4749	66,4334	67,1770	0,12	-	131,50	
HELIGMAN	60,2000	19,3000	156	93%	7.014,3013	72,1775	14,3013	57,8762	-	83,6698	69,3685	0,15	-	166,47	
CHIMBOTE	9,0833	78,6333	156	93%	7.044,8590	24,9213	44,8590	69,7803	-	51,2934	96,1524	0,24	-	110,10	
LORNE	38,5472	143,9888	156	93%	7.024,0577	16,4923	24,0577	7,5654	-	12,2664	11,7913	0,04	-	4,83	
BENOAB	8,7467	115,2117	156	93%	6.994,7628	28,9020	5,2372	23,6648	-	42,8227	37,5855	0,13	-	61,43	
BACKEVIK	58,3667	11,2500	156	93%	6.917,0641	284,1539	82,9359	367,0898	-	344,1388	427,0747	0,53	-	695,14	
SYDNEY,FORTDENISON	33,8500	151,2333	156	93%	6.977,9103	164,0852	22,0897	141,9955	-	181,3064	159,2166	0,14	-	281,70	
KOLUCHIN	67,4833	174,6500	156	93%	7.003,2051	82,9201	3,2051	86,1252	-	108,1941	111,3993	0,20	-	178,96	
TILBURY	51,4667	0,3667	156	93%	6.979,7885	94,6038	20,2115	74,3923	-	109,2783	89,0668	0,10	-	153,11	
GANII	0,6833	73,1500	156	93%	7.083,6474	38,2338	83,6474	45,4137	-	16,4627	67,1847	0,19	-	20,39	
PUERTOARMUELLES	8,2667	82,8667	156	93%	7.120,8526	33,3078	120,8526	87,5448	-	10,9193	109,9333	0,20	-	58,36	
WIDO	35,6181	126,3019	156	93%	7.121,1795	74,7276	121,1795	46,4519	-	42,2414	78,9380	0,29	-	1,28	
ONAHAMA	36,9375	140,8919	156	93%	7.002,4615	2,1528	2,4615	0,3087	-	4,4039	1,9424	0,01	-	4,21	
DAUGAVGRIVA	57,0500	24,0333	156	93%	6.990,4103	135,3391	9,5897	125,7494	-	153,9378	144,3481	0,14	-	256,30	
LAGOMERA	28,0878	17,1083	156	93%	7.133,7179	95,4904	133,7179	38,2276	-	76,3692	57,3488	0,11	-	64,42	
MASIRAH	20,6833	58,8667	156	93%	7.081,9679	47,2429	81,9679	34,7251	-	29,8715	52,0965	0,12	-	13,01	
MANUSISLAND	2,0167	147,2667	156	93%	7.113,3654	53,4557	113,3654	59,9096	-	24,8014	88,5640	0,25	-	27,06	
OOSTENDE	51,2333	2,9167	156	93%	6.752,3077	7,2886	247,6923	240,4037	-	51,0161	298,7084	0,53	-	289,27	
MARDEAJO	36,7000	56,6667	156	93%	7.267,4808	67,1988	267,4808	200,2820	-	57,5921	325,0729	0,60	-	132,33	
GOLDCOASTSEAWAY2	27,9500	153,4167	156	93%	7.123,3141	53,1177	123,3141	70,1964	-	22,0657	101,2484	0,27	-	33,16	
SANDYHOOK	40,4667	74,0083	156	93%	6.830,1923	19,5030	169,8077	150,3047	-	15,9597	185,7674	0,31	-	155,54	
SIMRISHAMN	55,5575	14,3578	156	93%	7.083,9551	15,4579	83,9551	68,4972	-	27,7649	111,7200	0,37	-	82,85	

JACKSONVILLE	30,3500	- 81,6167	156	93%	7.206,4679	80,9048	206,4679	125,5631	46,3975	160,0705	0,26	- 33,12
WAVELAND,GULFOFMEX.,MS	30,2817	- 89,3667	156	93%	7.270,1410	131,4879	270,1410	138,6531	54,9382	215,2028	0,66	- 62,95
SURIGAO	9,7833	125,5000	156	93%	7.001,9487	11,1468	1,9487	13,0955	- 14,2042	16,1530	0,07	- 30,09
GISBORNE	- 38,6755	178,0224	156	93%	7.067,4872	2,9991	67,4872	64,4881	- 24,6012	92,0884	0,23	- 71,63
KATSUURA	35,1294	140,2494	156	93%	7.075,1731	41,0396	75,1731	34,1335	29,2741	45,8990	0,04	27,80
VILSANDI	58,3833	21,8167	156	93%	6.674,2051	46,2342	325,7949	279,5606	16,0080	341,8029	0,57	289,96
PRINCERUPERT	54,3167	- 130,3333	156	93%	7.153,2949	3,7063	153,2949	149,5885	- 34,0062	187,3011	0,31	- 159,95
COX'SBAZAAR	21,4500	91,8333	156	93%	6.996,7308	80,0305	3,2692	76,7612	- 113,3718	110,1026	0,28	- 175,30
ASTORIA(TONGUEPOINT)	46,2067	- 123,7683	156	93%	7.098,3462	35,5656	98,3462	62,7806	33,7803	64,5658	0,12	- 36,10
BAYWAVELANDYACHTCLUB	30,3250	- 89,3250	156	93%	7.008,4872	81,2427	8,4872	89,7299	- 121,0841	129,5713	0,33	- 185,90
BYKOVMY(SBYKOVMY)	72,0000	129,1167	156	93%	7.022,1538	21,1034	22,1538	1,0504	23,1997	- 1,0459	0,00	20,78
PORTPIRIE	- 33,1776	138,0117	156	93%	6.997,2821	57,3595	2,7179	54,6415	- 68,0481	65,3301	0,09	- 119,10
YSTAD	55,4167	13,8167	156	93%	6.705,8013	139,6712	294,1987	- 433,8699	205,7625	499,9612	0,58	607,75
KAPINGAMARANGI	1,1000	154,7833	156	93%	7.043,6795	4,0885	43,6795	39,5909	45,9567	89,6362	0,40	- 59,19
DAYTONABEACHSHORES	29,1467	- 80,9633	156	93%	7.068,7436	18,4478	68,7436	50,2958	5,6779	63,0657	0,16	- 39,36
DUNKERQUE	51,0481	2,3667	156	93%	7.081,5321	61,9582	81,5321	19,5738	58,2308	23,3013	0,03	48,06
RIOHACHA	11,5500	72,9167	156	93%	7.282,9808	56,3790	282,9808	226,6018	23,2740	306,2548	0,74	261,60
OSKARSHAMN	57,2750	16,4781	156	93%	7.074,0128	23,2487	74,0128	50,7641	- 8,2149	82,2277	0,27	- 47,65
MOZAMBIQUEISLAND	- 15,0333	40,7333	156	93%	7.043,5256	0,5329	43,5256	44,0585	- 18,3863	61,9119	0,10	- 39,76
BOMBAY(PRINCESDOCK)	18,9500	72,8333	156	93%	7.120,6795	66,0256	120,6795	54,6539	52,4492	68,2303	0,12	- 14,29
WANGANUI	- 39,9446	174,9932	156	93%	7.076,7308	37,5469	76,7308	39,1839	19,6424	57,0884	0,13	- 5,00
MALAGA	36,7127	- 4,4155	156	93%	7.126,6795	81,9949	126,6795	44,6846	65,5807	61,0988	0,09	47,94
SANJOSE	13,9167	- 90,8333	156	93%	6.939,6859	23,4302	60,3141	- 36,8839	- 9,5927	50,7214	0,13	- 28,54
TOKYOIII	35,6486	139,7700	156	93%	6.944,8526	66,5343	55,1474	11,3869	- 73,2461	18,0986	0,02	- 72,59
TUAPSE	44,1000	39,0667	156	93%	7.028,1795	12,8770	28,1795	41,0564	19,2428	47,4223	0,06	- 54,78
CABOSANLUCAS	22,8833	- 109,9000	156	93%	7.091,6987	35,3383	91,6987	56,3604	12,8758	78,8230	0,18	- 28,75
MANTYLUOTO	61,5944	21,4634	156	93%	7.137,1282	21,4214	137,1282	115,7068	20,9158	158,0440	0,32	- 95,88
MOURILYANHARBOUR	- 17,5833	146,0833	156	93%	7.078,0256	47,5135	78,0256	30,5121	31,2900	46,7357	0,12	- 9,54
LOMBRUM	- 2,0421	147,3738	156	93%	7.122,7885	79,2254	122,7885	43,5631	58,6266	64,1619	0,17	- 27,59

FORTPHRACHULACHOMKLAO(POMPHRACHUN)	13,5500	100,5833	155	92%	7.020,7806	0,2696	20,7806	20,5110	-	18,2609	39,0416	0,16	-	30,91
KAGOSHIMAI	31,6000	130,5667	155	92%	7.052,1935	3,2661	52,1935	48,9274	-	9,8293	62,0228	0,09	-	33,11
PALMADEMALLORCAZ	39,5602	2,6375	155	92%	7.015,8710	17,5393	15,8710	33,4103	-	37,2673	53,1383	0,18	-	66,22
KAVIENG	2,5833	150,8000	155	92%	7.031,2258	21,6986	31,2258	52,9244	-	44,9440	76,1698	0,16	-	74,05
SANJUAN	18,4583	66,1150	155	92%	7.026,5161	22,1086	26,5161	4,4076	-	15,9864	10,5297	0,06	-	2,45
MAKAR,GENERALSANTOSCITY	6,1000	125,1500	155	92%	6.969,8129	46,0371	30,1871	15,8500	-	53,5917	23,4046	0,02	-	50,26
WEIPA	12,6667	141,8667	155	92%	7.136,5677	43,7500	136,5677	92,8178	-	10,4724	126,0953	0,27	-	54,35
JAMESTOWNLANDINGSTEPS	15,9209	5,7180	155	92%	7.038,8710	19,9009	38,8710	18,9701	-	12,8363	26,0347	0,02	-	26,00
PORTHEDLAND	20,3176	118,5744	155	92%	7.540,1290	40,0685	540,1290	580,1975	-	135,5547	675,6838	0,65	-	502,70
ERDEK	40,3833	27,8500	155	92%	6.905,6452	74,2980	94,3548	20,0569	-	65,4690	28,8859	0,08	-	49,24
SASEBOI	33,1667	129,7167	155	92%	7.062,2516	5,4349	62,2516	67,6865	-	24,4701	86,7217	0,10	-	50,67
BALBOA	8,9667	79,5667	155	92%	6.834,9677	122,6324	165,0323	42,3999	-	100,4104	64,6219	0,04	-	95,10
TRIBENI	22,9833	88,4000	155	92%	7.212,2065	94,6374	212,2065	117,5691	-	48,4894	163,7171	0,39	-	55,62
YARMOUTH	43,8333	66,1333	155	92%	7.078,5677	26,2048	78,5677	52,3630	-	2,2016	80,7694	0,27	-	41,53
CAPAUXMEULES	47,3789	61,8573	155	92%	7.022,7419	48,5767	22,7419	25,8348	-	65,8053	43,0634	0,12	-	88,52
SANDNESSJOEN	66,0167	12,6333	155	92%	7.560,4452	414,3155	560,4452	146,1296	-	356,1625	204,2827	0,48	-	235,66
BEACHPORT	37,5000	140,0000	155	92%	6.969,9355	105,6638	30,0645	75,5993	-	126,9134	96,8489	0,09	-	148,78
HONNGU	18,8000	105,7667	155	92%	7.105,7742	29,8102	105,7742	75,9640	-	1,6705	104,1037	0,19	-	45,66
SALERNO	40,6766	14,7508	155	92%	6.953,5806	84,9290	46,4194	38,5096	-	134,3218	87,9024	0,28	-	133,94
MANZANILLO	20,3333	77,1500	155	92%	7.141,0000	60,0597	141,0000	80,9403	-	22,0148	118,9852	0,32	-	35,15
NAGOYAI	35,0914	136,8808	155	92%	7.062,1935	29,1120	62,1935	33,0815	-	7,3496	54,8439	0,19	-	33,28
CRISTOBAL	9,3500	79,9167	155	92%	7.059,9677	30,9005	59,9677	29,0673	-	23,1178	36,8499	0,01	-	27,93
VANCOUVER	49,2833	123,1167	155	92%	6.868,7742	139,3872	131,2258	8,1614	-	115,9603	15,2655	0,05	-	157,63
SUVA-A	18,1357	178,4228	155	92%	7.042,4516	27,6871	42,4516	70,1387	-	52,0321	94,4837	0,20	-	101,34
SPLITRTMARJANA	43,5083	16,3917	155	92%	7.011,4645	17,7996	11,4645	29,2641	-	25,1986	36,6631	0,06	-	43,96
PORT-ALFRED	48,3333	70,8667	155	92%	7.086,9355	33,7037	86,9355	120,6392	-	83,0427	169,9782	0,41	-	177,41
RAFFLESLIGHTHOUSE	1,1667	103,7500	155	92%	6.753,4839	278,0496	246,5161	31,5335	-	275,0190	28,5029	0,07	-	304,08
AKKO	32,9193	35,0702	155	92%	7.146,6774	86,1888	146,6774	60,4886	-	50,2268	96,4506	0,28	-	15,16

PORTOEMPEDOCLE,SICILY	37,2858	13,5268	155	92%	6.994,0000	-	29,9467	-	6,0000	23,9467	-	39,0880	33,0880	0,06	-	46,59
LUCINDA	-	18,5167	146,3833	155	92%	7.163,6452	121,6857	163,6452	41,9595	82,4107	81,2345	0,35	48,10			
ZADAR	44,1233	15,2350	155	92%	7.031,8194	33,4700	31,8194	65,2894	-	60,4535	92,2729	0,18	86,71			
GEIBERGA(GEIBERGAOSTROV)	77,6000	101,5167	155	92%	7.123,8452	97,6050	123,8452	26,2402	81,4008	42,4444	0,13	64,07				
SHEDIACBAY	46,2500	-	64,5333	155	92%	7.066,9677	6,2002	66,9677	60,7675	-	17,8999	84,8676	0,20	67,23		
BREST	48,3829	-	4,4948	155	92%	7.137,3419	5,2862	137,3419	142,6281	18,5896	155,9316	0,08	107,84			
KERGUELEN	-	49,3515	70,2555	154	92%	6.987,9221	97,2751	12,0779	85,1972	135,2900	123,2121	0,37	206,76			
STORNOWAY	58,2078	-	6,3890	154	92%	7.136,2857	40,2940	136,2857	95,9917	11,1369	125,1488	0,22	58,82			
CAMBRIDGEII	38,5733	-	76,0683	154	92%	6.972,3442	49,2312	27,6558	21,5754	-	58,5786	30,9227	0,11	89,66		
KRASNOFLOTSKIE(KRASNOFLOTSKIEOSTROVA)	78,6000	98,8333	154	92%	7.207,4870	7,6820	207,4870	199,8051	-	57,0748	264,5618	0,49	202,79			
PORTAUGUSTA	-	32,5500	137,7833	154	92%	7.119,6948	90,3392	119,6948	29,3556	81,8421	37,8527	0,00	89,87			
RATMANOVA	65,8500	-	169,1333	154	92%	7.447,8766	-	31,8559	447,8766	479,7326	164,2060	612,0826	1,19	594,35		
PIRAMIDE	-	42,5833	-	64,2833	154	92%	7.134,4156	4,6611	134,4156	129,7544	-	37,6021	172,0177	0,37	144,83	
SCOTTBASE	-	77,8501	166,7690	154	92%	7.078,1558	74,4704	78,1558	3,6855	71,7128	6,4430	0,06	58,94			
PANAMACITY,ST.ANDEWSBAY,FL	30,1517	-	85,6667	154	92%	6.941,4740	-	121,2517	58,5260	62,7257	-	182,6565	124,1305	0,46	216,25	
RINGHALS	57,2497	12,1125	154	92%	7.012,8701	-	25,4442	12,8701	38,3144	-	57,3643	70,2344	0,28	99,82		
PUERTODEHIERRO	10,6167	-	62,0833	154	92%	6.932,9675	-	35,0231	67,0325	-	32,0094	35,0414	31,9911	0,04	52,95	
KEYWEST	24,5550	-	81,8067	154	92%	6.542,2727	-	469,9565	457,7273	12,2293	459,4986	1,7713	0,01	480,42		
TIKSI(TIKSIBUKHTA)	71,5833	128,9167	154	92%	6.983,8377	33,3107	16,1623	17,1484	-	37,5324	21,3701	0,02	25,37			
UDDEVALLA	58,3475	11,8947	154	92%	7.019,7143	4,7821	19,7143	24,4964	-	41,3810	61,0953	0,33	59,67			
KOCHIII	33,5000	133,5833	154	92%	6.909,3701	-	145,4905	90,6299	54,8606	-	163,6821	73,0522	0,14	198,80		
NEDRENYKOPING	58,7500	17,0167	154	92%	6.950,7273	64,0819	49,2727	14,8092	-	66,3039	17,0311	0,02	55,70			
PORTVENDRES	42,5201	3,1073	154	92%	7.189,0195	90,0724	189,0195	98,9471	45,6365	143,3829	0,38	35,56				
VERAVAL	20,9000	70,3667	154	92%	7.088,3442	46,6576	88,3442	41,6865	26,1029	62,2412	0,20	7,97				
VICTORIADOCK	1,2667	103,8500	154	92%	7.070,9870	53,7895	70,9870	17,1975	42,2588	28,7282	0,13	27,80				
SANTACRUZDETENERIFEI	28,4772	-	16,2412	153	91%	7.191,2418	74,7291	191,2418	116,5127	49,0066	142,2352	0,20	48,65			
ALERTBAY	-	50,5833	126,9500	153	91%	7.059,0588	30,1482	59,0588	89,2070	-	54,1226	113,1814	0,22	142,79		

SYDNEYPORTJACKSON	-	33,8255	151,2585	153	91%	7.125,5882	73,1076	125,5882	52,4807	24,7050	100,8832	0,41	-	17,11
LAMUB	-	2,2717	40,9033	153	91%	7.047,9477	17,6220	47,9477	30,3258	-	1,0578	49,0055	0,18	28,85
BARHARBOR,FRENCHMANBAY,ME	-	44,3917	68,2050	153	91%	7.006,6275	12,0540	6,6275	18,6815	-	14,5038	21,1312	0,01	14,71
FORTMYERS	-	26,6467	81,8700	153	91%	7.078,0000	55,3544	78,0000	22,6456	47,9992	30,0008	0,05	35,58	
SUVA-B	-	18,1325	178,4275	153	91%	7.055,6863	43,0767	55,6863	12,6095	27,8127	27,8736	0,10	21,04	
SAPPI	-	61,4833	21,3333	153	91%	7.082,7190	17,5585	82,7190	100,2774	-	35,7581	118,4771	0,09	58,10
PORTOGRANDE(ST.VINCENT)2	-	16,8833	25,0000	153	91%	7.134,8954	39,7007	134,8954	95,1947	-	9,2102	144,1056	0,36	70,86
LASPALMASD	-	28,1406	15,4118	153	91%	6.987,9673	20,5221	12,0327	8,4894	-	23,8000	11,7673	0,00	21,80
LORDHOWEISLAND	-	31,5167	159,0667	153	91%	7.151,5033	3,4436	151,5033	148,0597	-	47,8455	199,3487	0,35	143,41
NEWHAVEN	-	50,7818	0,0570	153	91%	7.100,4510	13,4188	100,4510	87,0322	-	28,8549	129,3059	0,37	108,08
GUIRIA	-	10,5667	62,2833	153	91%	7.098,1634	18,3324	98,1634	79,8310	-	14,2443	112,4077	0,36	118,40
AMBARCIK	-	69,6167	162,3000	153	91%	7.032,4837	4,9120	32,4837	37,3956	-	13,3986	45,8822	0,09	48,48
LIMHAMN	-	55,5833	12,9333	153	91%	7.002,2680	39,4442	2,2680	41,7122	-	59,9378	62,2058	0,16	90,93
QIKIQTARJUAQ	-	67,8667	64,1167	153	91%	7.021,7124	1,1428	21,7124	20,5696	-	24,2790	45,9914	0,32	37,79
AVEIRO	-	40,6500	8,7500	153	91%	6.942,3987	132,5247	57,6013	74,9234	-	163,0276	105,4262	0,30	235,50
KEYCOLONYBEACH	-	24,7183	81,0167	153	91%	7.083,0000	59,2268	83,0000	23,7732	-	56,3050	26,6950	0,03	47,59
NUKUHIVA	-	8,9333	140,0833	152	90%	6.987,9211	50,5967	12,0789	38,5177	-	67,3470	55,2681	0,12	89,36
PENSACOLA	-	30,4033	87,2100	152	90%	7.258,4474	188,0171	258,4474	70,4303	-	158,7246	99,7228	0,18	131,89
MUSCAT	-	23,6333	58,5667	152	90%	7.082,7763	6,1672	82,7763	88,9435	-	42,2147	124,9910	0,31	106,33
TENERIFE	-	28,4772	16,2411	152	90%	7.072,4737	37,4176	72,4737	35,0561	-	22,8688	49,6048	0,08	11,45
SEOGWIPO	-	33,2400	126,5617	152	90%	7.107,0263	52,7493	107,0263	54,2770	-	25,7428	81,2835	0,23	21,90
ALCUDIA	-	39,8346	3,1390	152	90%	7.131,6711	67,7074	131,6711	63,9636	-	37,7261	93,9450	0,26	3,53
KAOHSIUNGII	-	22,5333	120,3167	152	90%	7.017,9803	31,9109	17,9803	49,8912	-	50,5973	68,5775	0,11	69,48
NAHA	-	26,2133	127,6653	152	90%	7.024,9013	20,1877	24,9013	4,7136	-	1,0303	25,9316	0,13	1,54
PALINURO	-	40,0299	15,2753	152	90%	7.152,8092	108,3025	152,8092	44,5067	-	84,0512	68,7580	0,22	49,09
INVERGORDON	-	57,6833	4,1667	152	90%	7.068,2303	26,0086	68,2303	42,2217	-	3,3288	71,5591	0,21	59,59
JEJU	-	33,5275	126,5431	152	90%	7.152,3750	95,0883	152,3750	57,2867	-	74,6416	77,7334	0,13	45,61
KINGBAY	-	20,6236	116,7491	152	90%	7.151,8289	36,6968	151,8289	115,1321	-	15,3025	167,1315	0,43	105,40

BUGRINO	68,8000	49,3333	152	90%	7.023,5855	-	18,7587	23,5855	42,3443	-	42,0455	65,6310	0,17	-	68,02
MARIIPRONCHISHEVOI(BUKHTA)	75,5333	113,4333	152	90%	6.891,2829	-	152,0274	108,7171	43,3103	-	167,8788	59,1617	0,17	-	229,62
PORTORFORD	42,7383	-	151	90%	6.962,0265	-	109,8723	37,9735	71,8988	-	138,1052	100,1317	0,22	-	178,42
FUNAFUTIB	-	8,5025	151	90%	7.090,2252	-	51,7296	90,2252	38,4956	-	30,8272	59,3979	0,14	-	8,71
CHITTAGONGA	22,2467	91,8250	151	90%	7.053,7285	-	10,8358	53,7285	42,8926	-	11,4215	65,1500	0,25	-	54,66
GDYNIA	54,5333	18,5500	150	89%	7.441,5667	-	290,5540	441,5667	151,0126	-	258,0708	183,4959	0,18	-	187,58
APIAB	-	13,8268	150	89%	7.189,5333	-	59,1003	189,5333	130,4330	-	0,2378	189,7711	0,49	-	87,90
KUNGSVIK	58,9967	11,1272	150	89%	7.081,7533	-	35,8862	81,7533	45,8672	-	12,2470	69,5063	0,19	-	16,02
CHERRYPOINT	48,8633	-	150	89%	7.115,5600	-	75,0168	115,5600	40,5432	-	58,3736	57,1864	0,11	-	39,67
MALYITAIMYR(MALYITAIMYROSTROV)	78,0833	106,8167	150	89%	6.896,8000	-	189,9449	103,2000	293,1449	-	276,2435	379,4435	0,75	-	543,83
DUBLAT(SAUGORIS.)	21,6333	88,1333	150	89%	7.091,2667	-	376,0760	91,2667	467,3426	-	439,4657	530,7324	0,56	-	858,88
PORTROYAL	17,9333	-	150	89%	6.929,8200	-	0,1668	70,1800	70,3468	-	23,6055	93,7855	0,21	-	89,20
NORTHSOUND	19,3000	-	150	89%	7.132,4200	-	89,9749	132,4200	42,4451	-	76,2760	56,1440	0,11	-	52,02
STLAWRENCE	46,9168	-	150	89%	7.094,3667	-	46,3198	94,3667	48,0469	-	14,8756	79,4911	0,31	-	22,17
NY-ALESUND	78,9285	11,9380	150	89%	7.034,7133	-	9,2265	34,7133	25,4868	-	3,7896	38,5029	0,13	-	39,54
BINTULU	3,2622	113,0639	150	89%	7.073,2200	-	46,6787	73,2200	26,5413	-	38,3415	34,8785	0,12	-	12,25
ANCHORAGE	61,2383	-	150	89%	7.094,4733	-	69,5066	94,4733	24,9667	-	59,0129	35,4604	0,06	-	45,84
AUCKLANDII	-	36,8431	150	89%	6.584,7333	-	521,9346	415,2667	106,6679	-	541,0628	125,7961	0,13	-	612,92
PORTOTORRES	40,8422	8,4039	150	89%	6.960,0133	-	56,7982	39,9867	16,8115	-	67,0313	27,0446	0,05	-	70,76
CULEBRA	18,3017	-	149	89%	7.159,7248	-	122,7373	159,7248	36,9876	-	100,3818	59,3430	0,21	-	67,90
TWEEDENTRANCESOUTH	-	28,1706	149	89%	7.072,9664	-	47,9367	72,9664	25,0298	-	32,5759	40,3906	0,17	-	17,88
HERNEBAY	51,3820	1,1156	149	89%	7.092,1141	-	33,9884	92,1141	58,1256	-	2,9001	95,0142	0,31	-	40,37
SAUMLAKI	-	7,9817	149	89%	7.032,0805	-	24,9338	32,0805	7,1467	-	21,5965	10,4840	0,08	-	6,22
SAGUNTO	39,6339	-	149	89%	7.155,6644	-	99,9071	155,6644	55,7574	-	65,8018	89,8626	0,40	-	10,77
ZHELANII(ZHELANIAMYS)	76,9500	68,5500	149	89%	7.008,9262	-	60,9194	8,9262	69,8455	-	80,6661	89,5923	0,16	-	134,89
GARIBALDI	45,5533	-	148	88%	7.066,4257	-	24,2467	66,4257	90,6724	-	48,7276	115,1533	0,13	-	70,94
SOLENZARA	41,8569	9,4038	148	88%	7.132,6959	-	103,3811	132,6959	29,3149	-	81,3401	51,3559	0,19	-	55,59
TOKEPOINT,WILLIPABAY,WA	46,7067	-	148	88%	7.152,6351	-	47,7551	152,6351	104,8801	-	6,9801	145,6550	0,31	-	62,31

MANGALORE(PANAMBURU)	12,9167	74,8000	148	88%	7.116,7838	16,5691	116,7838	100,2147	-	18,6877	135,4715	0,27	-	74,19
VILLAGARCIA	42,6007	8,7700	147	88%	7.026,0884	36,0977	26,0884	-	10,0093	32,3506	6,2621	0,01	-	39,93
HANSTHOLM	57,1189	8,5956	147	88%	6.995,0748	25,5999	4,9252	-	30,5250	31,8561	36,7813	0,07	-	56,23
WAKKANAI	45,4078	141,6853	147	88%	7.006,1156	15,7673	6,1156	21,8830	-	21,1346	27,2502	0,00	-	16,60
SHOALBAY	32,7197	152,1757	147	88%	7.099,9116	52,1123	99,9116	47,7992	-	24,6317	75,2798	0,23	-	0,30
PATRICIABAY	48,6500	123,4500	147	88%	7.096,0068	47,1549	96,0068	48,8519	-	29,9362	66,0706	0,10	-	9,42
NAGOYA	35,0833	136,8833	147	88%	6.998,0068	99,4625	1,9932	97,4693	-	110,6945	108,7013	0,04	-	115,87
ACAPULCO	16,8333	99,9167	146	87%	6.982,6370	16,7602	17,3630	-	34,1232	23,8965	41,2595	0,09	-	57,19
AJACCIO	41,9228	8,7629	145	86%	7.104,0552	54,2264	104,0552	49,8288	-	27,3929	76,6622	0,23	-	12,21
MUOSTAH(MUOSTAHOSTROV)	71,5500	130,0333	145	86%	6.997,2069	64,7107	2,7931	61,9176	-	83,9374	81,1443	0,19	-	150,56
NORFOLKISLAND	29,0583	167,9536	145	86%	7.061,3103	2,0001	61,3103	59,3103	-	13,8271	75,1375	0,13	-	52,79
SANJOSE	12,3333	121,0833	145	86%	7.012,0207	16,8607	12,0207	28,8813	-	29,4012	41,4219	0,12	-	55,74
BAHIADELOSANGELES	28,9667	113,5500	145	86%	7.036,5034	1,3486	36,5034	37,8520	-	35,3693	71,8727	0,27	-	53,88
IRAKLION	35,3485	25,1527	145	86%	7.093,3793	26,2312	93,3793	67,1481	-	7,0212	86,3581	0,13	-	39,02
TONOURA	34,9000	132,0667	144	86%	7.085,1736	23,7486	85,1736	61,4250	-	14,7644	70,4092	0,05	-	17,46
LAMADDALENA	41,2333	9,3667	144	86%	6.955,3750	37,1689	44,6250	7,4561	-	36,5156	8,1094	0,01	-	41,46
SALVADOR	12,9667	38,5167	144	86%	7.073,0694	6,1055	73,0694	66,9639	-	12,7733	85,8428	0,14	-	63,84
TUKIZI	35,6667	139,7667	144	86%	7.139,0486	74,6478	139,0486	64,4008	-	53,9255	85,1231	0,17	-	3,74
PALERMO	38,1333	13,3333	144	86%	7.070,6250	73,5099	70,6250	2,8849	-	73,8511	3,2261	0,02	-	86,41
SKURU	60,1000	23,5500	144	86%	7.079,2153	26,3550	79,2153	52,8603	-	17,6430	61,5722	0,07	-	23,36
KLAIPEDA	55,7000	21,1333	144	86%	7.029,8333	75,2905	29,8333	105,1238	-	93,3913	123,2246	0,15	-	187,22
SLIPSHAVN	55,2883	10,8278	144	86%	7.120,6806	27,7412	120,6806	92,9394	-	13,8825	106,7981	0,10	-	52,97
NEDREGAVLE	60,6833	17,1667	144	86%	7.102,8333	26,8427	102,8333	75,9907	-	14,9883	87,8450	0,09	-	43,55
WHYALLA	33,0167	137,5667	144	86%	7.098,2153	53,5210	98,2153	44,6943	-	35,9523	62,2630	0,14	-	5,76
LUSI	32,1333	121,6167	144	86%	7.112,7083	57,5742	112,7083	55,1341	-	38,1697	74,5387	0,16	-	6,44
CORRAL	39,8667	73,4333	144	86%	7.109,0833	34,5648	109,0833	74,5185	-	7,2253	101,8580	0,20	-	43,51
MONBETUI	44,3500	143,3667	144	86%	7.014,0139	12,5513	14,0139	26,5651	-	47,3527	61,3666	0,29	-	60,68
MOSULPO	33,2144	126,2511	144	86%	6.994,2778	71,1217	5,7222	65,3995	-	110,0137	104,2915	0,26	-	144,58

PRIGI	-	8,2800	111,7300	143	85%	7.130,4406	70,3382	130,4406	60,1024	43,2756	87,1650	0,26	4,70
LEAVA	-	14,2960	178,1602	143	85%	7.021,2517	29,9019	21,2517	51,1537	58,0717	79,3235	0,28	89,68
LIVORNOII	-	43,5463	10,2993	143	85%	7.515,7203	191,8091	515,7203	323,9112	61,1088	454,6115	1,20	132,97
IBIZA	-	38,9112	1,4498	142	85%	7.074,7535	6,7580	74,7535	81,5115	46,3183	121,0718	0,29	90,49
TERIBERKA	-	69,2000	35,1167	142	85%	7.089,0704	32,5360	89,0704	56,5344	6,2472	82,8233	0,21	28,78
NIKISKI,ALASKA	-	60,6833	151,3967	142	85%	7.079,9085	7,1664	79,9085	72,7420	12,1605	92,0689	0,16	48,70
TRIESTE	-	45,6474	13,7585	142	85%	7.072,2183	25,1958	72,2183	47,0225	16,9695	55,2488	0,03	0,12
PUERTOLIMON	-	10,0000	83,0333	141	84%	7.078,7092	3,5907	78,7092	82,2999	30,2169	108,9262	0,22	84,64
INCEPOINT	-	10,5083	142,3100	141	84%	7.053,5461	0,8335	53,5461	52,7126	21,4418	74,9879	0,18	63,64
MILNERBAY(GROOTEELYLANDT)	-	13,8601	136,4156	141	84%	7.074,3546	15,9468	74,3546	58,4079	13,9214	60,4333	0,04	1,57
HONOLULU	-	21,3067	157,8667	141	84%	7.045,5887	42,6134	45,5887	88,2021	54,9832	100,5719	0,10	117,97
MONTAUK	-	41,0483	71,9600	141	84%	7.139,5461	46,7143	139,5461	92,8318	26,6356	112,9105	0,17	43,33
HILO,HAWAIIISLAND	-	19,7300	155,0550	141	84%	7.133,5745	27,5673	133,5745	106,0071	5,3214	128,2531	0,13	54,52
REYKJAVIK	-	64,1506	21,9399	141	84%	7.128,5177	64,6297	128,5177	63,8880	50,5166	78,0011	0,10	17,06
USTKARA	-	69,2500	64,5167	140	83%	7.106,2143	64,5139	106,2143	170,7282	94,7284	200,9427	0,27	241,13
SANJOSEII	-	13,9167	90,8167	140	83%	7.023,9000	30,2694	23,9000	6,3694	12,7074	11,1926	0,01	31,55
IWASAKI	-	40,5833	139,9167	140	83%	7.093,0357	17,8589	93,0357	75,1768	6,1269	86,9088	0,09	45,83
SEWARD	-	60,1200	149,4267	139	83%	7.144,6115	43,4788	144,6115	101,1327	24,7557	119,8558	0,15	49,57
MAJURO-C	-	7,1060	171,3728	139	83%	7.031,9424	7,8200	31,9424	39,7625	23,9889	55,9313	0,06	26,70
DANANG	-	16,1000	108,2167	138	82%	6.940,6812	76,1054	59,3188	16,7866	101,8117	42,4929	0,22	108,75
BERGENPOINT,STATENIS.	-	40,6367	74,1417	137	82%	7.170,1460	141,5085	170,1460	28,6375	129,4907	40,6552	0,16	104,58
SHEKPIK	-	22,2203	113,8944	137	82%	7.002,3650	8,4407	2,3650	6,0758	16,8113	14,4464	0,03	16,04
BUKOM	-	1,2256	103,7785	136	81%	7.216,0000	98,4585	216,0000	117,5415	44,8526	171,1474	0,40	14,63
CAPEMAY	-	38,9683	74,9600	136	81%	7.064,8897	40,9431	64,8897	23,9466	19,7850	45,1048	0,17	0,11
PORTVILAB	-	17,7553	168,3077	136	81%	7.142,6250	77,4241	142,6250	65,2009	47,7663	94,8587	0,22	11,25
OKHA	-	22,4667	69,0833	136	81%	7.088,9044	46,3757	88,9044	42,5287	31,0099	57,8945	0,16	8,84
BETIO	-	1,3651	172,9330	135	80%	7.042,1556	3,1081	42,1556	45,2637	32,3301	74,4857	0,22	49,63
GRONSKAR	-	59,2833	19,0333	135	80%	7.027,1111	69,6294	27,1111	96,7406	82,2448	109,3559	0,10	151,08

ST.MARYS	49,9179	-	6,3172	135	80%	7.065,1037	-	2,5068	65,1037	67,6105	-	30,5314	95,6351	0,27	-	81,65
SANDPOINT,POPOFIS.,AK	55,3367	-	160,5017	134	80%	7.000,1642	-	30,0713	0,1642	30,2355	-	44,1358	44,3000	0,11	-	64,63
GWANGYANG	34,9036	-	127,7547	134	80%	7.127,8582	-	79,4605	127,8582	48,3977	-	55,1545	72,7037	0,17	-	39,24
CRESCENTCITY	41,7450	-	124,1817	134	80%	7.013,9776	-	52,8141	13,9776	66,7917	-	87,5554	101,5330	0,30	-	126,15
MARDELPLATA(NAVALBASE)	-	-	-	134	80%	7.098,5821	-	0,5943	98,5821	97,9878	-	21,2973	119,8794	0,16	-	64,29
VENEZIA(PUNTADELLASALUTE)	45,4333	-	12,3333	134	80%	7.610,0522	-	175,2424	610,0522	434,8099	-	62,8844	547,1678	0,89	-	151,93
FORMENTERA	38,7347	-	1,4190	133	79%	7.620,5564	-	301,7500	620,5564	318,8064	-	173,2875	447,2689	1,22	-	32,39
EASTLONDON	-	-	-	133	79%	6.929,2707	-	99,5671	70,7293	28,8378	-	115,4244	44,6951	0,17	-	130,86
CALDERA	-	-	-	132	79%	7.258,0303	-	128,7037	258,0303	129,3266	-	103,0721	154,9583	0,14	-	62,08
PREOBRAZHENIA(PREOBRAZHENIAOSTROV)	74,6667	-	112,9333	132	79%	7.069,1515	-	45,0222	69,1515	114,1737	-	77,4886	146,6401	0,31	-	187,71
LALIBERTAD	-	-	-	132	79%	7.074,0455	-	11,2398	74,0455	85,2852	-	28,8002	102,8456	0,11	-	68,67
KIPTOPEKEBEACH	37,1650	-	75,9883	132	79%	7.077,7045	-	50,5140	77,7045	27,1906	-	45,1037	32,6008	0,02	-	59,12
HEUKSANDO	34,6839	-	125,4364	132	79%	7.059,6515	-	5,0959	59,6515	54,5556	-	16,3053	75,9568	0,20	-	58,40
SAIPAN	15,2333	-	145,7500	132	79%	6.967,8636	-	74,3646	32,1364	42,2282	-	82,2655	50,1292	0,19	-	136,38
ILETLAMERE	4,8938	-	52,1905	131	78%	7.069,1908	-	22,2518	69,1908	46,9390	-	0,8990	70,0898	0,22	-	32,12
CUXHAVEN2	53,8667	-	8,7167	131	78%	7.068,1221	-	26,9460	68,1221	95,0681	-	49,9497	118,0718	0,17	-	109,76
VARDO	70,3750	-	31,1040	130	77%	7.073,7231	-	10,5191	73,7231	84,2422	-	47,7832	121,5063	0,31	-	103,11
SANTIAGODECUBA	20,0205	-	75,8367	130	77%	7.077,9308	-	20,5022	77,9308	57,4285	-	0,1206	77,8102	0,14	-	16,44
OURA	32,9767	-	130,2206	130	77%	7.119,1308	-	42,5521	119,1308	76,5787	-	24,5128	94,6180	0,13	-	8,08
CHARLOTTEAMALIE	18,3350	-	64,9200	130	77%	7.048,4846	-	8,9697	48,4846	39,5149	-	1,3721	49,8567	0,07	-	16,47
DALHOUSIE	48,0667	-	66,3833	129	77%	6.964,1628	-	75,7816	35,8372	39,9444	-	118,1385	82,3013	0,37	-	136,06
RUSSKII(RUSSKIIOSTROV)	77,1667	-	96,4333	129	77%	7.107,4109	-	30,0185	107,4109	137,4294	-	66,7107	174,1216	0,30	-	147,99
TAN-NOWA	34,3389	-	135,1781	129	77%	7.022,1085	-	21,6422	22,1085	43,7508	-	32,5124	54,6210	0,08	-	57,49
SANDAKAN	5,8100	-	118,0672	129	77%	6.980,3023	-	2,0060	19,6977	21,7037	-	15,6523	35,3500	0,19	-	59,48
GENOVAII	44,4101	-	8,9255	127	76%	7.039,1732	-	20,6592	39,1732	18,5141	-	8,9016	30,2716	0,10	-	5,33
MIYAKESIMA	34,0672	-	139,4808	127	76%	7.096,5748	-	60,9624	96,5748	35,6124	-	47,1172	49,4576	0,12	-	24,53
DAESAN	37,0075	-	126,3528	127	76%	7.009,9449	-	53,6480	9,9449	63,5929	-	96,9455	106,8904	0,36	-	126,59
PORTOCORSINI	44,5000	-	12,2833	126	75%	7.041,1190	-	10,6177	41,1190	51,7368	-	18,5420	59,6611	0,05	-	45,75

MANZANILLO	19,0500	-	125	74%	7.170,2000	107,2455	170,2000	62,9545	96,4493	73,7507	0,18	29,80
SABANG	5,8883	95,3167	123	73%	7.090,1382	67,3903	90,1382	22,7480	60,2306	29,9076	0,07	48,67
PORTADELAIDE(OUTERHARBOR)	-	34,7798	123	73%	7.074,2195	25,3837	74,2195	48,8358	0,9298	73,2897	0,19	-
KOPER	45,5481	13,7246	123	73%	7.011,7073	2,5991	11,7073	9,1083	0,4522	11,2552	0,03	7,34
ISLAY(PORTELEN)	55,6276	-	122	73%	6.943,2869	80,7914	-	24,0783	91,0769	34,3638	0,04	92,96
NAOSISLAND2	8,9183	-	121	72%	7.119,8843	79,1474	119,8843	40,7369	63,6920	56,1923	0,16	31,73
BROOME	-	18,0008	120	71%	7.107,5000	30,8577	107,5000	76,6423	11,2758	96,2242	0,14	20,61
AMHERST	16,0833	97,5667	120	71%	7.150,7000	54,7398	150,7000	95,9602	28,6741	122,0259	0,32	74,34
WESTCOAST	1,3000	103,7667	120	71%	7.095,9000	54,4808	95,9000	41,4192	34,5140	61,3860	0,21	4,00
BOLVANSKIINOS(FEDOROVA)	70,4500	59,0833	120	71%	7.079,3583	5,8541	79,3583	85,2124	28,9575	108,3158	0,20	94,38
RABAU	-	4,2000	120	71%	7.062,8583	31,8276	62,8583	31,0307	25,2715	37,5869	0,02	22,59
MIKUNI	36,2547	136,1489	120	71%	7.029,0250	31,3467	29,0250	60,3717	46,9941	76,0191	0,13	75,22
ASAMUSHI	40,8975	140,8592	119	71%	7.326,5966	134,7418	326,5966	191,8548	84,1780	242,4186	0,42	44,56
PUNTAARENAS	-	53,1667	119	71%	7.104,7647	47,9045	104,7647	56,8602	36,7935	67,9712	0,09	5,26
PORTKEMBLA	-	34,4738	117	70%	7.030,7692	0,2108	30,7692	30,5584	2,4181	33,1873	0,09	35,65
BANGOR	54,6648	-	117	70%	7.120,0769	64,1889	120,0769	55,8880	48,7454	71,3315	0,13	27,00
CARTAGENA	10,4000	-	116	69%	7.021,9828	34,3472	21,9828	56,3299	54,1592	76,1420	0,06	52,95
SELDOVIA	59,4400	-	116	69%	7.105,6121	47,4572	105,6121	58,1549	32,4273	73,1848	0,11	4,30
SOLOMON'SISLAND(BIOL.LAB.)	38,3167	-	116	69%	7.040,5603	0,2591	40,5603	40,3013	-	10,4547	0,10	-
BUNDABERG,BURNETTHEADS	-	24,7667	114	68%	7.073,2281	8,5479	73,2281	64,6801	35,0923	108,3204	0,81	94,09
KALININGRAD	54,7000	20,4833	114	68%	7.051,2719	-	4,3114	51,2719	55,5834	20,4454	0,15	50,70
ALESUND	62,4694	6,1519	114	68%	7.068,2982	18,3830	68,2982	49,9153	7,5560	60,7422	0,07	18,93
DOVER	51,1144	1,3227	113	67%	7.082,3717	34,5727	82,3717	116,9444	48,7540	131,1257	0,16	153,34
OCEANCITYINLET	38,3283	-	113	67%	7.282,4513	152,9267	282,4513	129,5246	84,9420	197,5093	0,56	25,08
GEOJEDO	34,8014	128,6992	113	67%	7.082,7080	51,6192	82,7080	31,0887	40,2124	42,4955	0,08	28,37
MACAU	22,2000	113,5500	112	67%	7.238,6607	64,0169	238,6607	174,6438	45,1800	193,4807	0,12	6,23
DAYTONABEACH	29,2333	-	112	67%	7.025,9107	-	17,1455	25,9107	43,0562	23,7402	0,05	47,49

CHETYREHSTOLBOVOI	70,6333	162,4833	109	65%	7.003,8991	-	47,3484	3,8991	51,2474	-	57,8831	61,7822	0,13	-	107,55
UNO	34,4886	133,9494	107	64%	6.945,5701	-	88,2945	54,4299	33,8646	-	94,4814	40,0515	0,04	-	104,45
PORTIRENE	18,3833	122,1000	107	64%	7.132,1682	77,9315	132,1682	54,2367	56,2021	75,9661	0,19	18,52			
FRENCHFRIGATESHOALS	23,8683	166,2883	105	63%	6.939,2952	61,8916	60,7048	1,1868	53,2470	7,4578	0,07	45,32			
KANTONISLAND	2,8000	171,7167	104	62%	7.089,8077	13,0364	89,8077	76,7713	17,2693	107,0769	0,29	72,37			
KANTONISLAND-B	2,8167	171,7167	103	61%	7.022,4466	39,1318	22,4466	61,5784	63,6597	86,1063	0,17	100,86			
KAVALLA	40,9346	24,4121	101	60%	7.078,2772	30,8008	78,2772	47,4764	14,7727	63,5045	0,15	22,56			
MATI,DAVAORIENTAL	6,9500	126,2167	100	60%	7.130,9300	80,9440	130,9300	49,9860	70,2733	60,6567	0,13	48,80			
KINLOCHBERVIE	58,4566	5,0504	98	58%	6.997,2755	37,1236	2,7245	34,3991	43,2440	40,5195	0,05	52,30			
PORTCHALMERS	45,8147	170,6241	98	58%	7.067,0408	40,6156	67,0408	26,4252	24,1147	42,9261	0,15	14,06			
CAPTOWN(GRANGERBAY)	33,9053	18,4347	96	57%	7.019,6042	31,0255	19,6042	50,6297	45,1846	64,7888	0,18	91,68			
LYMINGTON	50,7403	1,5071	96	57%	7.078,1875	32,2219	78,1875	45,9656	10,2022	67,9853	0,31	33,63			
INCHEONSONGDO	37,3381	126,5861	96	57%	7.032,2917	19,7457	32,2917	52,0374	45,2644	77,5561	0,28	81,35			
HAIKOU	20,0167	110,2833	96	57%	6.939,2500	87,5167	60,7500	148,2667	146,4211	207,1711	0,50	242,36			
CENTURI	42,9658	9,3498	96	57%	7.061,5208	40,7356	61,5208	20,7852	37,9050	23,6159	0,03	34,02			
SETROIA	38,5000	8,9000	96	57%	7.134,4375	54,1556	134,4375	80,2819	32,1566	102,2809	0,16	0,55			
POINTREYES	37,9950	122,9767	96	57%	6.972,7083	5,7426	27,2917	21,5491	2,5489	24,7428	0,03	14,05			
PORTISABEL	26,0600	97,2150	96	57%	7.120,2500	61,5922	120,2500	58,6578	50,3554	69,8946	0,10	11,68			
BRIDGEPORT	41,1733	73,1817	96	57%	7.097,2188	45,0739	97,2188	52,1449	37,4818	59,7369	0,07	20,22			
TALCAHUANO	36,6833	73,1000	94	56%	6.989,9362	78,0901	10,0638	68,0263	102,7566	92,6928	0,27	155,08			
GANGHWADAEGYO	37,7319	126,5222	94	56%	7.093,1809	34,3432	93,1809	58,8376	4,7163	88,4646	0,19	12,10			
DURBAN	29,8742	31,0508	93	55%	7.160,1720	103,6994	160,1720	56,4726	71,1740	88,9981	0,31	50,11			
LERWICK	60,1540	1,1403	92	55%	7.049,2391	1,9955	49,2391	47,2436	4,2426	53,4817	0,09	34,53			
BUSANNEWPORT	35,0775	128,7869	92	55%	6.984,0543	6,4956	15,9457	9,4500	18,1334	34,0791	0,46	90,77			
VISAKHAPATNAM	17,6833	83,2833	92	55%	7.066,2283	48,9919	66,2283	17,2363	47,1418	19,0865	0,05	31,33			
MATSUYAMAI	33,8667	132,7000	92	55%	7.049,2391	1,9955	49,2391	47,2436	4,2426	53,4817	0,09	34,53			
HORNBAEK	56,0911	12,4583	91	54%	7.061,5275	124,6736	61,5275	186,2011	144,9865	206,5139	0,25	302,86			
KASHIWAZAKI	37,3567	138,5083	91	54%	6.936,7033	5,3549	63,2967	68,6516	22,6055	85,9022	0,21	88,74			
BURNIE	41,0501	145,9150	90	54%	6.992,5111	66,3157	7,4889	58,8269	80,1924	72,7036	0,04	81,22			

LINAKHAMARI	69,6500	31,3667	90	54%	7.131,4333	86,7473	131,4333	44,6860	65,7128	65,7205	0,25	40,26
SHUTEHARBOUR2	-	148,7833	87	52%	7.115,7701	76,6687	115,7701	39,1014	70,3243	45,4458	0,03	68,66
STENUNGSUND	58,0933	11,8325	87	52%	7.053,6782	61,2907	53,6782	7,6125	69,3114	15,6332	0,07	79,32
URAKAWAI	42,1667	142,7667	87	52%	6.992,6552	49,4059	7,3448	42,0610	55,7329	48,3880	0,05	67,67
ST.PETERSBURG	27,7600	82,6267	86	51%	7.307,4767	69,7431	307,4767	237,7337	43,7658	263,7109	0,46	159,47
OFUNATOI	39,0667	141,7167	84	50%	7.074,4286	7,5353	74,4286	81,9639	28,8043	103,2329	0,22	81,72
KETCHIKAN	55,3317	131,6250	82	49%	6.933,2683	68,9968	66,7317	2,2651	65,4210	1,3107	0,00	71,91
CASCAIS	38,6833	9,4167	82	49%	7.098,5610	0,8932	98,5610	97,6678	4,4968	103,0578	0,05	42,07
OITAI	33,2661	131,6867	82	49%	6.998,3902	61,3220	1,6098	59,7122	69,8352	68,2254	0,11	100,53
GLADSTONE	-	151,3137	81	48%	7.090,2469	0,0626	90,2469	90,1843	20,1632	110,4101	0,19	73,56
PORTELIZABETH	33,9511	25,6297	79	47%	7.003,9241	0,5809	3,9241	4,5049	8,1184	12,0425	0,10	42,56
TOSASHIMIZU	32,7792	132,9589	78	46%	7.068,6795	27,9934	68,6795	40,6861	23,3137	45,3658	0,11	15,61
RIODEJANEIRO	-	43,1333	77	46%	7.136,1039	78,8321	136,1039	57,2718	70,8834	65,2205	0,08	42,70
CHRISTIANSTEDHARBOUR	17,7500	64,7050	76	45%	7.076,1184	49,3365	76,1184	26,7819	41,2786	34,8398	0,07	31,21
TOULON	43,1129	5,9147	73	43%	6.992,3288	0,1825	7,6712	7,8537	4,3530	12,0242	0,01	2,47
NEWPORT	51,5500	2,9874	72	43%	7.105,7500	60,6604	105,7500	45,0896	48,5917	57,1583	0,06	44,59
PORTNEUF	46,6833	71,8833	72	43%	7.061,8056	1,9437	61,8056	59,8619	23,5299	85,3355	0,25	89,19
VIGOII	42,2431	8,7260	71	42%	7.068,0845	6,2944	68,0845	61,7901	2,4084	70,4929	0,06	10,49
LAUTOKA	-	177,4383	68	40%	7.077,8676	17,7319	77,8676	60,1357	0,5841	77,2836	0,17	27,90
BELYNOS	69,6000	60,2167	68	40%	7.175,1765	83,6322	175,1765	91,5443	49,6280	125,5485	0,50	0,63
PARADIP	20,2667	86,7000	66	39%	7.128,0152	5,0421	128,0152	133,0572	40,0396	168,0548	0,56	187,06
ACAJUTLA	13,5667	89,8333	66	39%	6.992,4242	0,7369	7,5758	8,3126	1,2139	6,3618	0,04	14,92
TABLEBAYHARBOUR	-	18,4333	65	39%	7.090,0000	0,0883	90,0000	90,0883	18,3386	108,3386	0,20	73,84
TVARMINNE	59,8500	23,2500	65	39%	7.122,0154	65,6692	122,0154	56,3462	58,1418	63,8736	0,07	45,23
TALARA	4,6167	81,2833	61	36%	7.079,9180	13,6997	79,9180	66,2183	9,2897	70,6283	0,06	17,83
TAIMIUWAN	22,2697	114,2886	61	36%	7.064,9508	17,2723	64,9508	47,6785	0,2598	64,6910	0,22	36,22
WACHAPREAGUE	37,6067	75,6867	59	35%	6.976,4407	46,7117	23,5593	23,1523	81,1997	57,6403	0,41	91,21
GRINDAVIK	63,8333	22,4333	59	35%	7.081,3559	16,4831	81,3559	64,8729	11,3619	69,9941	0,04	0,23
ULLADULLAHARBOUR	-	150,4765	58	35%	7.039,1724	2,5649	39,1724	41,7374	14,1984	53,3708	0,17	31,83

PUERTOCASTILLA	16,0167	-86,0333	58	35%	7,058,7931	2,7900	58,7931	56,0032	-9,0699	67,8630	0,14	-47,50
CHESAPEAKEBAYBR.TUN.	36,9667	76,1133	55	33%	6,922,3636	20,5676	77,6364	-57,0688	8,5739	69,0624	0,05	4,02
DIKSON	73,5000	80,4000	55	33%	6,974,8909	91,6273	25,1091	66,5182	99,6546	74,5455	0,10	137,17
GRANDISLE	29,2633	89,9567	49	29%	6,769,9796	99,7833	230,0204	130,2371	66,7283	163,2921	0,58	45,79
RAU-CHUA	69,5000	166,5833	47	28%	7,140,1489	30,3643	140,1489	170,5132	49,5580	189,7070	0,12	81,93
BUCKSPORT,WACCAMAWR.	33,6467	79,0950	47	28%	7,221,8511	105,0001	221,8511	116,8509	88,8999	132,9512	0,16	53,30
KNYSNA	34,0494	23,0456	43	26%	7,385,5116	137,7032	385,5116	247,8084	110,9842	274,5275	0,40	26,70
PLOCE	43,0500	17,4167	39	23%	7,004,9744	22,7952	4,9744	17,8208	24,5756	19,6013	0,03	30,97
TREGDE	58,0064	7,5548	38	23%	6,919,6579	110,0034	80,3421	29,6613	114,5378	34,1957	0,02	107,06
STJEANDELUZ(SOCAA)	43,3952	1,6816	38	23%	7,161,1316	13,9958	161,1316	147,1357	8,0869	153,0447	0,05	40,87
FYNHAV	54,9950	9,9869	37	22%	6,843,1892	75,6420	156,8108	81,1688	66,0699	90,7409	0,32	27,68
SHEERNESS	51,4456	0,7434	34	20%	7,135,6176	72,2756	135,6176	207,8932	84,8783	220,4959	0,11	193,96
NAURU-B	0,5294	166,9101	32	19%	7,011,4375	8,2004	11,4375	3,2371	5,4185	6,0190	0,02	13,55
PORTDOUGLAS2	16,4833	145,4667	29	17%	6,995,8966	12,1698	4,1034	8,0664	11,0237	6,9202	0,16	32,55
VIRGINIABEACH	36,8500	75,9667	28	17%	7,039,1071	18,2228	39,1071	20,8844	12,4986	26,6085	0,05	1,16
LECONQUET	48,3594	4,7808	27	16%	7,040,4074	0,1705	40,4074	40,5779	10,4567	50,8641	0,16	48,61
ROTHERA	67,5713	68,1298	27	16%	7,135,3333	1,0654	135,3333	134,2679	14,7470	150,0803	0,07	13,51
TWEEDHEADS	28,1695	153,5496	27	16%	7,157,1111	126,7484	157,1111	30,3627	107,9375	49,1736	0,36	68,60
LIVERPOOL(GLADSTONEDOCK)	53,4497	3,0180	27	16%	7,064,2222	38,9979	64,2222	25,2243	31,9332	32,2890	0,12	10,48
SAINTPIERREETMIQUELON	46,7788	56,1683	27	16%	7,033,0370	42,7522	33,0370	9,7152	37,9298	4,8928	0,08	28,40
MONTEREY	36,6050	121,8867	27	16%	7,004,2593	10,2329	4,2593	14,4922	19,1203	23,3796	0,13	48,46
CHAMPLAIN	46,4333	72,4000	26	15%	7,038,0385	102,5415	38,0385	140,5799	127,2638	165,3023	0,74	341,23
PORTLAND	38,3434	141,6132	26	15%	6,991,2692	21,6107	8,7308	12,8799	31,3403	22,6096	0,16	63,02
DARWIN	12,4718	130,8459	26	15%	7,052,1154	6,5117	52,1154	58,6271	17,7296	69,8450	0,21	78,46
MOKUOLOEISLAND	21,4317	157,7900	26	15%	7,152,6923	1,8404	152,6923	150,8519	11,4345	164,1268	0,19	72,47
PETROPAVLOVSK-KAMCHATSKY	52,9833	158,6500	24	14%	7,234,1667	1,9877	234,1667	232,1789	12,0853	246,2519	0,08	30,83
ARUNPLATFORM	50,7698	0,4921	16	10%	7,047,6250	12,3416	47,6250	59,9666	18,5078	66,1328	0,18	43,27
QUEENCHARLOTTECITY	53,2500	132,0667	12	7%	7,287,5000	9,9766	287,5000	297,4766	25,0546	312,5546	0,17	70,81

VIESTE	41,8881	16,1770	12	7%	6.966,5833	- 28,8394	- 33,4167	- 4,5772	- 36,8782	3,4615	0,14	- 57,26
APALACHICOLA	29,7267	84,9817	12	7%	7.075,0000	5,6073	75,0000	80,6073	13,0923	88,0923	0,15	50,14
SALAMANDER	33,0667	18,0000	12	7%	7.677,0000	521,9682	677,0000	155,0318	475,2645	201,7355	1,95	5,27
PRUDHOEBAY,ALASKA	70,4000	148,5267	12	7%	7.246,0000	19,3031	246,0000	226,6969	26,1094	272,1094	1,29	275,35
MOKPO	34,7797	126,3756	11	7%	7.090,0000	- 3,6986	90,0000	93,6986	5,3400	95,3400	0,08	34,13
PROGRESO	21,3000	89,6667	11	7%	7.103,8182	21,6477	103,8182	82,1705	14,2645	89,5537	0,15	35,93
NAGAEVO	59,5500	150,7167	8	5%	7.506,2500	1,9973	506,2500	504,2527	8,1619	514,4119	0,20	70,26
LEMSTROM	60,1000	20,0167	8	5%	6.746,5000	47,4659	253,5000	- 300,9659	57,2941	310,7941	0,24	223,19
PESCHANYI(PESCHANYIMYS)	79,4333	102,4833	7	4%	7.072,0000	67,7816	72,0000	139,7816	80,7568	152,7568	0,32	168,10
SIMONSBAY	34,1878	18,4401	7	4%	7.335,7143	3,8003	335,7143	331,9140	2,3461	338,0603	0,21	69,66
NAPOLIII	40,8414	14,2692	6	4%	6.997,1667	65,8205	2,8333	62,9871	74,7576	71,9242	0,14	93,14
KRENKELIA(HEISAOSTROV)	80,6167	58,0500	3	2%	7.300,0000	3,7739	300,0000	296,2261	2,1998	302,1998	0,09	23,77
WESTTUAS	1,3444	103,6340	2	1%	6.954,0000	49,9771	46,0000	3,9771	44,0115	1,9885	0,22	2,25
KHALKISNORTH	38,4723	23,5926	-	0%	7.000,0000	26,2642	-	- 26,2642	26,2642	26,2642	0,04	30,12
TAEAN	36,9131	126,2389	-	0%	7.000,0000	63,2616	-	63,2616	66,6251	66,6251	0,32	106,38
SHIMONOSEKIII	33,9667	130,9500	-	0%	7.000,0000	90,4834	-	- 90,4834	90,4834	90,4834	0,41	18,92
BUENOSAIRE	34,6000	58,3667	-	0%	7.000,0000	22,7801	-	22,7801	22,7801	22,7801	0,25	42,36
BEDFORDINSTITUTE	44,6833	63,6167	-	0%	7.000,0000	51,7918	-	51,7918	51,7918	51,7918	2,55	83,65
CHIMAWAN,LANTAUISLAND	22,2333	114,0000	-	0%	7.000,0000	4,9571	-	4,9571	4,9571	4,9571	0,07	12,26
PORTSMOUTH	50,8023	1,1113	-	0%	7.000,0000	117,6770	-	117,6770	117,6770	117,6770	0,66	181,50
STAVANGER	58,9743	5,7301	-	0%	7.000,0000	95,6363	-	95,6363	95,6363	95,6363	0,22	158,67
ALBANY	35,0337	117,8926	-	0%	7.000,0000	28,8864	-	- 28,8864	28,8864	28,8864	0,37	55,74
PORT-SAINT-FRANCOIS	46,2667	72,6167	-	0%	7.000,0000	7,8673	-	7,8673	7,8673	7,8673	0,13	21,84
NORTSHIELDS	55,0074	1,4398	-	0%	7.000,0000	84,8574	-	- 84,8574	84,8574	84,8574	0,27	157,50
LASPALMAS,PUERTODELALUZ	28,1363	15,4257	-	0%	7.000,0000	185,5025	-	185,5025	185,5025	185,5025	1,59	368,02
SEAVEYISLAND	43,0800	70,7417	-	0%	7.000,0000	140,4123	-	140,4123	140,4123	140,4123	0,24	208,54
OKADA	34,7894	139,3914	-	0%	7.000,0000	24,8077	-	- 24,8077	24,8077	24,8077	0,36	3,16
URAKAWAI	42,1667	142,7667	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,3758	-	0,3758	0,3758	0,3758	0,11	31,96

BONAVISTA	48,6510	-	-	0%	7,000,000	63,3969	-	63,3969	-	63,3969	63,3969	-	-	48,48
MURORAN	42,3500	140,9500	-	0%	7,000,000	18,4026	-	18,4026	-	19,6436	19,6436	0,07	-	31,34
NEZUGASEKI	38,5633	139,5458	-	0%	7,000,000	10,4047	-	10,4047	-	10,4047	10,4047	0,21	-	67,67
RICHARDSBAY	-	28,8119	32,0786	-	7,000,000	72,2110	-	72,2110	-	73,8060	73,8060	0,20	-	119,63
KARIYA	33,4731	129,8492	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9416	-	2,9416	-	2,9416	2,9416	0,15	-	10,52
DONGFANG	19,1000	108,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	31,3329	-	31,3329	-	31,3329	31,3329	0,01	-	32,06
ISLAMARTINGARCIA	-	34,1833	58,2500	-	7,000,000	61,8967	-	61,8967	-	61,8967	61,8967	0,14	-	76,06
RHODOS	36,4417	28,2364	-	0%	7,000,000	56,1171	-	56,1171	-	56,1171	56,1171	0,35	-	81,89
MUKHO	37,5503	129,1164	-	0%	7,000,000	62,4817	-	62,4817	-	62,4817	62,4817	0,39	-	85,97
ANHEUNG	36,6736	126,1322	-	0%	7,000,000	57,7834	-	57,7834	-	57,7834	57,7834	1,06	-	89,97
BALANACAN,MARINDUQUE	13,5333	121,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5114	-	3,5114	-	3,5114	3,5114	0,19	-	28,50
MYSSHMIDTA	68,9000	-	179,3667	-	7,000,000	118,1043	-	118,1043	-	118,1043	118,1043	1,14	-	145,92
FANNING-B	3,9000	159,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	67,0619	-	67,0619	-	67,0619	67,0619	1,86	-	16,89
FUNAFUTI	-	8,5333	179,2167	-	7,000,000	125,0384	-	125,0384	-	125,0384	125,0384	0,67	-	54,64
GREYMOUTH	-	42,4500	171,2000	-	7,000,000	66,0042	-	66,0042	-	66,0042	66,0042	0,29	-	36,07
TORSHAVN	62,0167	-	6,7667	-	7,000,000	2,1626	-	2,1626	-	2,1626	2,1626	0,23	-	55,35
TROMSO	69,6474	18,9613	-	0%	7,000,000	40,6503	-	40,6503	-	40,6503	40,6503	0,43	-	50,21
TERPIAI-TUMSA	73,5500	118,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	57,1673	-	57,1673	-	57,1673	57,1673	0,28	-	91,73
MIYAZU	35,5333	135,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	2,8598	-	2,8598	-	2,8598	2,8598	0,26	-	73,29
MATARANI	-	17,0000	72,1167	-	7,000,000	26,4999	-	26,4999	-	26,4999	26,4999	0,37	-	50,82
SE-LAHA	70,1500	72,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	11,5806	-	11,5806	-	11,5806	11,5806	0,03	-	4,77
WISE(VISEOSTROV)	79,5000	76,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	38,2527	-	38,2527	-	38,2527	38,2527	0,10	-	66,09
PORTLAND(MAINE)	43,6567	-	70,2467	-	7,000,000	31,9248	-	31,9248	-	31,9248	31,9248	0,07	-	46,46
RATAN	63,9861	20,8950	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5605	-	1,5605	-	1,5605	1,5605	0,05	-	27,03
ALICANTE(INNERHARBOUR)	38,3389	-	0,4812	-	7,000,000	32,1903	-	32,1903	-	32,1903	32,1903	0,16	-	9,36
TARAWA-A,BETIO	1,3667	172,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	1,8082	-	1,8082	-	1,8082	1,8082	0,44	-	38,64
STANLEY	-	51,6903	57,8649	-	7,000,000	11,7170	-	11,7170	-	11,7170	11,7170	0,17	-	11,37
NAGAPATTINAM	10,7667	79,8500	-	0%	7,000,000	109,1069	-	109,1069	-	109,1069	109,1069	0,95	-	172,42

STERLEGOVA(STERLEGOVAMYS)	75,4167	88,9000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	26,6536	-	26,6536	-	26,6536	1,02	-	40,43
ZEMLIABUNGE	74,8833	142,1167	-	0%	7,000,000	21,9388	-	-	21,9388	-	21,9388	0,23	-	12,01
IMMINGHAM	53,6302	0,1874	-	0%	7,000,000	68,7721	-	68,7721	68,7721	68,7721	68,7721	0,06	-	111,36
TEIGNMOUTHPIER	50,5439	3,4921	-	0%	7,000,000	9,0201	-	9,0201	9,0201	9,0201	9,0201	1,05	-	116,47
EDEN	37,0737	149,9077	-	0%	7,000,000	86,9419	-	-	86,9419	86,9419	86,9419	0,01	-	83,65
PYEONGTAEK	36,9667	126,8228	-	0%	7,000,000	41,8445	-	-	41,8445	41,8445	41,8445	0,00	-	41,39
TOKYOII	35,6500	139,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	9,8786	-	9,8786	9,8786	9,8786	9,8786	0,59	-	95,50
SANJUAN	15,3667	75,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	73,9596	-	-	73,9596	73,9596	73,9596	0,04	-	70,29
KATAKOLON	37,6448	21,3197	-	0%	7,000,000	26,8531	-	26,8531	26,8531	26,8531	26,8531	0,09	-	33,93
NANTUCKETISLAND	41,2850	70,0967	-	0%	7,000,000	52,4086	-	-	52,4086	52,4086	52,4086	0,25	-	3,07
HARRINGTONHBR	50,5000	59,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	6,9222	-	-	6,9222	6,9222	6,9222	0,04	-	26,85
OGI	37,8147	138,2811	-	0%	7,000,000	51,9532	-	51,9532	51,9532	51,9532	51,9532	0,49	-	84,97
SALGRUND	62,3333	21,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	8,5217	-	-	8,5217	8,5217	8,5217	0,03	-	23,71
AMRUM(WITTDUEN)	54,6167	8,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	9,1859	-	9,1859	9,1859	9,1859	9,1859	0,75	-	58,19
BELLABELLA	52,1667	128,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	2,0749	-	-	2,0749	2,0749	2,0749	0,15	-	36,94
ALEXANDROUPOLIS	40,8441	25,8783	-	0%	7,000,000	50,2039	-	-	50,2039	50,2039	50,2039	0,43	-	15,84
PALERMOII	38,1214	13,3713	-	0%	7,000,000	260,5215	-	-	260,5215	260,5215	260,5215	0,49	-	320,26
MAPUTO	25,9667	32,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	4,1144	-	4,1144	4,1144	4,1144	4,1144	0,05	-	16,60
DUNBAR	56,0059	2,5169	-	0%	7,000,000	99,6898	-	99,6898	99,6898	99,6898	99,6898	0,02	-	106,57
ARRECIFE	28,9719	13,5301	-	0%	7,000,000	6,0963	-	6,0963	6,0963	6,0963	6,0963	0,74	-	29,41
PHILADELPHIA(PIER9N)	39,9333	75,1417	-	0%	7,000,000	17,9134	-	17,9134	17,9134	17,9134	17,9134	0,13	-	38,17
INCHEON	37,4519	126,5922	-	0%	7,000,000	26,5849	-	26,5849	26,5849	26,5849	26,5849	0,25	-	80,52
OSHOROI	43,2094	140,8581	-	0%	7,000,000	1,9610	-	1,9610	1,9610	1,9610	1,9610	0,18	-	34,77
URAGAMI	33,5583	135,8964	-	0%	7,000,000	24,2477	-	24,2477	24,2477	24,2477	24,2477	0,03	-	28,78
LOKONPAI	22,3667	114,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	88,4967	-	88,4967	88,4967	88,4967	88,4967	0,37	-	66,25
REGGIOCALABRIAI	38,1217	15,6489	-	0%	7,000,000	18,5389	-	18,5389	18,5389	18,5389	18,5389	0,17	-	6,78
RUSSKAIAGAVANII	76,1833	62,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	30,0834	-	30,0834	30,0834	30,0834	30,0834	0,43	-	14,40
KUREI	33,3336	133,2433	-	0%	7,000,000	53,1277	-	53,1277	53,1277	53,1277	53,1277	0,57	-	82,45

LESKINA(LESKINAMYS)	72,3167	79,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	15,1494	-	15,1494	-	15,1494	-	0,50	4,41
WAKAYAMA	34,2217	135,1456	-	0%	7,000,000	6,0801	-	6,0801	-	12,3442	12,3442	-	0,29	97,65
IQUIQUE	-	20,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	9,0053	-	9,0053	-	9,0053	-	0,03	6,34
ULLEUNG	37,4914	130,9136	-	0%	7,000,000	-	16,2226	-	16,2226	-	16,2226	-	0,17	51,48
LAPUSH	47,9133	124,6367	-	0%	7,000,000	-	340,5379	-	340,5379	-	340,5379	-	3,03	686,24
BATUMI	41,6333	41,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	12,3962	-	-	12,3962	-	12,3962	-	0,11	43,76
BELEM	-	1,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	34,0657	-	34,0657	-	34,0657	-	0,43	59,95
GERALDTON	-	28,7760	-	0%	7,000,000	-	63,8023	-	-	63,8023	63,8023	-	0,09	55,44
TANDAG,SURIGAODELSUR	9,0833	126,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	31,2562	-	-	31,2562	-	31,2562	-	0,12	16,28
WAGLANISLAND	22,1831	114,3028	-	0%	7,000,000	35,5964	-	-	35,5964	-	35,5964	-	0,81	11,97
NAPLES	26,1317	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	1,3103	-	-	1,3103	1,3103	-	0,29	63,15
ST-JOSEPH-DE-LA-RIVE	47,4500	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	16,1539	-	-	16,1539	16,1539	-	0,30	36,78
NORTHSYDNEY	46,2167	60,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	83,4440	-	-	83,4440	-	89,3202	-	0,10	109,95
LYPYRTTI	60,6000	21,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	129,0534	-	-	129,0534	129,0534	-	0,09	197,48
PRAVDY(PRAVDYOSTROV)	76,2667	94,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	122,6270	-	-	122,6270	122,6270	-	0,83	150,70
HIERRO	27,7841	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	2,7133	-	-	2,7133	2,7133	-	0,05	6,35
LIANYUNGANG	34,7500	119,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	88,2545	-	-	88,2545	-	88,2545	-	0,18	123,90
OMINATO	41,2500	141,1500	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5664	-	-	44,5664	-	44,5664	-	1,60	19,71
LANGARAPOINT	54,2500	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	2,0634	-	-	2,0634	2,0634	-	0,23	56,44
GALVESTONI,PLEASUREPIER,TX	29,2850	-	-	0%	7,000,000	-	0,4070	-	-	0,4070	6,9804	-	0,13	44,04
ST.NAZAIRE	47,2700	2,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	49,3948	-	-	49,3948	-	49,3948	-	0,40	130,31
DAKAR2	14,6833	17,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	37,1606	-	-	37,1606	-	37,1606	-	0,40	63,45
CAPOPASSERO	36,6667	15,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9587	-	-	2,9587	-	2,9587	-	0,02	7,55
STE-ANNE-DES-MONTS	49,1333	66,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	30,6100	-	-	30,6100	-	30,6100	-	0,38	0,04
NAURU	-	0,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	16,5429	-	-	16,5429	16,5429	-	0,44	61,78
KHALKISSOUTH	38,4609	23,5895	-	0%	7,000,000	15,2607	-	-	15,2607	-	15,2607	-	0,00	15,95
HIRTSHALS	57,5956	9,9639	-	0%	7,000,000	65,8679	-	-	65,8679	-	65,8679	-	0,07	105,98
SVIATOINOS(SVIATOINOSMYS)	72,8333	140,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7493	-	-	1,7493	-	1,7493	-	0,08	9,18

DELFIJIL	53,3264	6,9331	-	0%	7,000,000	-	39,0066	-	39,0066	39,0066	0,05	-	69,70
LIMETREEBAY,STCROIX	17,6933	64,7533	-	0%	7,000,000	154,5260	-	154,5260	154,5260	154,5260	0,18	-	176,27
HAGI	34,4333	131,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	35,9759	-	35,9759	35,9759	35,9759	0,19	-	6,29
WESTBAYHARBOUR	50,7089	2,7641	-	0%	7,000,000	87,8042	-	87,8042	93,7480	93,7480	0,73	-	184,32
BUNBURY	33,3234	115,6600	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5298	-	3,5298	3,5298	3,5298	0,23	-	57,14
GOTEBORG-RINGON	57,7167	11,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	11,5459	-	11,5459	11,5459	11,5459	0,13	-	27,31
BARAHONA	18,2000	71,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	68,4097	-	68,4097	68,4097	68,4097	0,08	-	58,34
SETTLEMENTPOINT	26,7100	78,9967	-	0%	7,000,000	12,6967	-	12,6967	12,6967	12,6967	0,22	-	27,72
TADOUSSAC	48,1333	69,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	14,5618	-	14,5618	14,5618	14,5618	0,19	-	12,04
NOSY-BE	13,4000	48,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	18,9728	-	18,9728	18,9728	18,9728	0,32	-	38,51
GUADALUPEISLANDII	28,8833	118,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	3,2559	-	3,2559	3,2559	3,2559	1,51	-	26,96
GEDSER	54,5728	11,9256	-	0%	7,000,000	57,3578	-	57,3578	57,3578	57,3578	0,12	-	82,04
ULLAPOOL	57,8953	5,1579	-	0%	7,000,000	2,4049	-	2,4049	3,4246	3,4246	0,04	-	12,10
LEVKAS	38,8345	20,7121	-	0%	7,000,000	19,2284	-	19,2284	19,2284	19,2284	0,05	-	15,28
SMOGEN	58,3536	11,2178	-	0%	7,000,000	12,3912	-	12,3912	12,3912	12,3912	0,87	-	94,49
ITOI	34,8956	139,1331	-	0%	7,000,000	26,7185	-	26,7185	26,7185	26,7185	0,25	-	7,74
CADIZIII	36,5401	6,2862	-	0%	7,000,000	19,8385	-	19,8385	19,8385	19,8385	0,22	-	74,48
BORKUM(FISCHERBALJE)	53,5575	6,7478	-	0%	7,000,000	37,3255	-	37,3255	37,3255	37,3255	0,38	-	12,74
KOBE	34,6833	135,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	291,5005	-	291,5005	291,5005	291,5005	2,00	-	620,72
SABINEPASS	29,7050	93,8533	-	0%	7,000,000	6,2144	-	6,2144	6,2144	6,2144	0,16	-	10,56
CAGLIARI	39,2102	9,1143	-	0%	7,000,000	153,3243	-	153,3243	143,6709	143,6709	0,15	-	125,95
SANFERNANDO,LAUNION	16,6167	120,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	54,7567	-	54,7567	54,7567	54,7567	0,10	-	42,04
URANGANII	25,3000	152,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	33,0801	-	33,0801	33,0801	33,0801	0,19	-	12,15
MAISAKA	34,6819	137,6089	-	0%	7,000,000	28,6020	-	28,6020	28,6020	28,6020	0,15	-	9,19
SEWELLSPPOINT,HAMPTONROADS	36,9467	76,3300	-	0%	7,000,000	7,2169	-	7,2169	7,2169	7,2169	0,99	-	37,43
POINTTUPPER	45,6000	61,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	21,5424	-	21,5424	21,5424	21,5424	0,78	-	7,49
SOUTHBEACH	44,6250	124,0417	-	0%	7,000,000	15,7004	-	15,7004	15,7004	15,7004	0,11	-	11,53
LAPALOMA	34,6500	54,1500	-	0%	7,000,000	10,2039	-	10,2039	10,2039	10,2039	0,08	-	0,15

RUSSKAYAGAVAN	76,2000	62,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	38,7201	-	38,7201	38,7201	0,83	-	70,32
TEJN	55,2497	14,8378	-	0%	7,000,000	70,9422	-	70,9422	70,9422	70,9422	0,18	-	86,28
MOULMEIN	16,4833	97,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	0,5821	-	0,5821	0,5821	0,5821	0,08	-	22,92
PALERMO	-	34,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	1,3200	-	1,3200	1,3200	1,3200	0,16	-	43,39
WONSAN	39,1667	127,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	10,4017	-	10,4017	5,4829	5,4829	0,10	-	18,92
PUERTOPRINCESA,PALAWAN	9,7500	118,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	35,4133	-	35,4133	35,4133	35,4133	0,02	-	39,79
GADEOKDO	35,0247	128,8108	-	0%	7,000,000	60,9431	-	60,9431	60,9431	60,9431	0,27	-	13,60
RONNSKAR	63,0667	20,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	122,3281	-	122,3281	122,3281	122,3281	0,22	-	217,21
BALLINA	-	28,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	150,7088	-	150,7088	150,7088	150,7088	0,61	-	216,10
FUNCHAL	32,6440	-	-	0%	7,000,000	23,4771	-	23,4771	23,4771	23,4771	0,17	-	49,55
TUMACO	1,8333	78,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	73,7007	-	73,7007	73,7007	73,7007	0,09	-	89,34
GAZENICA	44,0833	15,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	40,4672	-	40,4672	40,4672	40,4672	0,11	-	22,33
IRAKLIONII	35,3485	25,1527	-	0%	7,000,000	11,6774	-	11,6774	11,6774	11,6774	0,13	-	28,53
NEUWESTMINSTER	49,2000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3075	-	0,3075	0,3075	0,3075	0,06	-	3,85
LAHATDATU	5,0189	118,3461	-	0%	7,000,000	75,5954	-	75,5954	75,5954	75,5954	0,02	-	74,08
PORTTARANAKI	-	39,0562	-	0%	7,000,000	65,3335	-	65,3335	65,3335	65,3335	0,02	-	63,24
FORTPULASKI	32,0333	-	-	0%	7,000,000	17,0960	-	17,0960	17,0960	17,0960	0,01	-	15,48
AUCKLAND-WAITEMATAHARBOUR	-	36,8431	-	0%	7,000,000	44,0447	-	44,0447	42,8631	42,8631	0,21	-	69,65
JUNGFRUSUND	59,9500	22,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	233,2875	-	233,2875	233,2875	233,2875	0,45	-	445,54
MONACO(FONTVIEILLE)	43,7288	7,4215	-	0%	7,000,000	36,9026	-	36,9026	36,9026	36,9026	0,09	-	50,51
BRIGHTON	-	35,0333	-	0%	7,000,000	9,8091	-	9,8091	9,8091	9,8091	0,22	-	21,01
HONDAU	20,6667	106,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7722	-	1,7722	1,7722	1,7722	0,06	-	16,73
GUANTANAMOBAY	19,9067	-	-	0%	7,000,000	66,6276	-	66,6276	66,6276	66,6276	0,17	-	128,42
GINGERVILLECREEK	38,9583	-	-	0%	7,000,000	69,4558	-	69,4558	69,4558	69,4558	0,19	-	109,23
PORTLYTTTELTON	-	43,6056	-	0%	7,000,000	42,8562	-	42,8562	42,8562	42,8562	0,04	-	51,33
HACHINOHEI	40,5333	141,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	37,0294	-	37,0294	37,0294	37,0294	0,14	-	29,88
ROSALES	-	38,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	11,9508	-	11,9508	11,9508	11,9508	0,15	-	54,79
PORTBURY	51,5000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	32,0313	-	32,0313	32,0313	32,0313	0,07	-	29,73
YAMBA	-	29,4297	-	0%	7,000,000	34,9220	-	34,9220	34,9220	34,9220	0,09	-	77,27

HALDIA	22,0333	88,1000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	26,6553	-	26,6553	-	26,6553	4,49	-	96,21
SANTOTOMASDECASTILLA	15,7000	88,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	23,3602	-	23,3602	-	23,3602	23,3602	0,02	-	19,61
CONSTANTZA	44,1667	28,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	24,7025	-	24,7025	-	26,0363	26,0363	0,17	-	104,94
KUCHINOTSU	32,6053	130,1953	-	0%	7,000,000	50,2414	-	50,2414	-	50,2414	50,2414	0,10	-	44,42
ATLANTICCITY	39,3550	74,4183	-	0%	7,000,000	92,6975	-	92,6975	-	92,6975	92,6975	0,15	-	155,56
CHARCHANGA	22,2167	91,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	13,8827	-	13,8827	-	13,8827	13,8827	0,03	-	9,40
ALGECIRAS2	36,1770	5,3984	-	0%	7,000,000	21,6281	-	21,6281	-	21,6281	21,6281	0,02	-	20,97
SOLNECHNAIA(SOLNECHNAIABUKHTA)	78,2000	103,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	42,8632	-	42,8632	-	42,8632	42,8632	0,08	-	29,91
SIBAURA	35,6333	139,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	0,4506	-	0,4506	-	0,4506	0,4506	0,01	-	2,98
WEWAK	3,5500	143,6333	-	0%	7,000,000	25,7504	-	25,7504	-	25,7504	25,7504	0,06	-	16,40
SOUTHISLANDPLANTATION,WINYAHBAY	33,2350	79,2033	-	0%	7,000,000	52,3304	-	52,3304	-	52,3304	52,3304	0,72	-	78,78
CORPUSCHRISTI,GULFMEXICO,TX	27,5833	97,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	33,0711	-	33,0711	-	33,0711	33,0711	0,08	-	46,53
KARUMBA	17,5000	140,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	1,0715	-	1,0715	-	1,0715	1,0715	0,15	-	38,86
NASEI	28,3833	129,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,9819	-	1,9819	-	1,9819	1,9819	0,23	-	49,94
BAMFIELD	48,8500	125,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	12,0487	-	12,0487	-	12,0487	12,0487	0,94	-	85,53
CANANEIA	25,0167	47,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	31,4461	-	31,4461	-	31,4461	31,4461	0,10	-	61,08
SOOKE	48,3667	123,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	71,5390	-	71,5390	-	71,5390	71,5390	0,12	-	84,16
ST.MALO	48,6411	2,0282	-	0%	7,000,000	3,3573	-	3,3573	-	3,3573	3,3573	0,14	-	61,53
KORSOR	55,3322	11,1422	-	0%	7,000,000	20,0103	-	20,0103	-	20,0103	20,0103	0,03	-	35,36
STONYPOINT	38,3721	145,2247	-	0%	7,000,000	30,8888	-	30,8888	-	30,8888	30,8888	0,06	-	36,14
MAYPORT	30,3933	81,4317	-	0%	7,000,000	39,0719	-	39,0719	-	39,0719	39,0719	0,07	-	65,30
REALQUEZON	14,6667	121,6000	-	0%	7,000,000	17,8391	-	17,8391	-	17,8391	17,8391	0,48	-	89,71
BARENTSBURGII(SPITSBERGEN)	78,0667	14,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	247,3216	-	247,3216	-	247,3216	247,3216	0,45	-	356,70
PADREISLAND	26,0683	97,1517	-	0%	7,000,000	64,6946	-	64,6946	-	64,6946	64,6946	0,02	-	62,92
BAHIAESPERANZA	63,3000	56,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	44,0888	-	44,0888	-	44,0888	44,0888	0,16	-	22,99
SANDIEGO(QUARANTINESTATION)	32,7133	117,1733	-	0%	7,000,000	269,0285	-	269,0285	-	269,0285	269,0285	0,67	-	549,10

PASAIHARBOUR,SANSEBASTIAN	43,3218	- 1,9315	-	0%	7,000,000	37,3756	-	- 37,3756	37,3756	- 37,3756	4,99	- 25,05
SHIMIZU-MINATO	35,0117	138,5175	-	0%	7,000,000	- 10,6205	-	10,6205	- 10,6205	10,6205	0,34	- 23,64
BJORN	60,6333	17,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	40,1333	-	40,1333	40,1333	40,1333	0,04	42,28
NEWCASTLEII	- 32,9167	151,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,4534	-	57,4534	57,4534	57,4534	0,37	30,00
GULEOBDO	37,1944	125,9953	-	0%	7,000,000	- 25,2556	-	25,2556	- 25,2556	25,2556	0,29	- 10,68
BIRKENHEAD(ALFREDDOCK)	53,4000	- 3,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	48,3741	-	48,3741	48,3741	48,3741	0,27	81,27
VALENCIA	39,4420	0,3113	-	0%	7,000,000	30,4814	-	30,4814	30,4814	30,4814	0,26	13,23
KUREII	34,2333	132,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	5,1367	-	5,1367	5,1367	5,1367	0,05	5,85
BAR	42,0833	19,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	- 62,3208	-	- 62,3208	62,3208	62,3208	0,18	34,14
SODERSKAR	60,1167	25,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 8,2718	-	8,2718	- 8,2718	8,2718	0,07	- 37,06
SPRINGMAIDPIER	33,6550	78,9183	-	0%	7,000,000	1,8922	-	1,8922	1,8922	1,8922	0,18	43,94
ST.JOHN'S,NFLD.	47,5667	52,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	27,1809	-	27,1809	27,1809	27,1809	0,02	18,30
NEWCASTLEI	- 32,9167	151,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	72,8619	-	72,8619	72,8619	72,8619	0,41	115,71
WELLINGTONHARBOUR	- 41,2843	174,7798	-	0%	7,000,000	78,0882	-	- 78,0882	78,0882	78,0882	0,56	116,19
VIS-CESKAVILA	43,0667	16,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	33,5412	-	33,5412	33,5412	33,5412	0,15	61,16
PORTAUPRINCE	18,5667	72,3500	-	0%	7,000,000	- 153,4086	-	153,4086	- 153,4086	153,4086	0,18	- 96,92
ELFINCOVE,PORTALTHORP	58,1950	136,3467	-	0%	7,000,000	19,3519	-	19,3519	19,3519	19,3519	0,33	16,52
DUNAI(DUNAIOSTROV)	73,9333	124,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	137,8281	-	137,8281	137,8281	137,8281	0,01	136,66
HAYPOINT	- 21,2833	149,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,5209	-	57,5209	57,5209	57,5209	0,70	92,74
NAKANOSIMA	29,8419	129,8478	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7483	-	1,7483	1,7483	1,7483	0,19	47,24
RAFINA	38,0333	24,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	62,7181	-	62,7181	62,7181	62,7181	1,40	134,20
RHODOSII	36,4417	28,2364	-	0%	7,000,000	35,6773	-	35,6773	35,6773	35,6773	0,22	10,60
ISHIGAKI	24,3333	124,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	- 14,4178	-	14,4178	- 14,4178	14,4178	1,51	- 45,43
SANCRISTOBAL	- 0,9000	89,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	7,9251	-	7,9251	7,9251	7,9251	0,52	35,28
SANTANDERIII	43,4613	3,7908	-	0%	7,000,000	83,1271	-	83,1271	83,1271	83,1271	0,21	122,63
BOURNEMOUTH	50,7143	1,8749	-	0%	7,000,000	13,3206	-	13,3206	13,3206	13,3206	0,08	7,81
PORTOMAURIZIO	43,8667	8,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	137,4834	-	137,4834	137,4834	137,4834	0,51	396,96
CATANIAII	37,4981	15,0938	-	0%	7,000,000	168,3154	-	168,3154	168,3154	168,3154	0,01	170,17

CEBU	10,3000	123,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	49,2431	-	49,2431	49,2431	0,14	-	86,55
ULSAN	35,5019	129,3872	-	0%	7,000,000	40,9394	-	40,9394	40,9394	40,9394	0,71	-	93,82
NETTEN	66,9667	171,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	68,5527	-	68,5527	68,5527	68,5527	0,66	-	210,16
VLISSINGEN	51,4422	3,5961	-	0%	7,000,000	224,0138	-	224,0138	224,0138	224,0138	0,42	-	424,04
SINES	37,9500	8,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	21,0833	-	21,0833	21,0833	21,0833	1,65	-	81,47
GOTEBORG-KLIPPAN	57,6833	11,9000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,3633	-	57,3633	57,3633	57,3633	0,10	-	123,43
BELFAST2	54,6000	5,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	31,5755	-	31,5755	31,5755	31,5755	0,12	-	82,92
NELSON	41,2613	173,2728	-	0%	7,000,000	22,2706	-	22,2706	22,2706	22,2706	1,61	-	61,69
ONAGAWA	38,4333	141,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	46,4458	-	46,4458	47,6180	47,6180	0,03	-	57,66
CHAMPERICO	14,2833	91,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	18,0296	-	18,0296	18,0296	18,0296	0,27	-	39,26
PORTMACDONNELLI	38,0000	140,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	45,3894	-	45,3894	45,3894	45,3894	0,21	-	106,22
LEVERDON	45,5500	1,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	131,7989	-	131,7989	131,7989	131,7989	0,21	-	117,84
CUTLER	44,6500	67,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	93,7202	-	93,7202	93,7202	93,7202	0,51	-	136,98
KUNSAN	35,9833	126,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	26,2207	-	26,2207	26,2207	26,2207	0,09	-	8,54
ANTIFER	49,6500	0,1500	-	0%	7,000,000	24,2640	-	24,2640	24,2640	24,2640	0,02	-	22,52
KOMATSUSHIMA	34,0092	134,5878	-	0%	7,000,000	54,2808	-	54,2808	54,2808	54,2808	3,37	-	109,89
LAE	6,7500	147,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	65,1851	-	65,1851	65,1851	65,1851	0,39	-	1,16
CAIRNS	16,9167	145,7833	-	0%	7,000,000	91,7591	-	91,7591	91,7591	91,7591	0,05	-	80,87
PORTNOLLOTH	29,2567	16,8678	-	0%	7,000,000	2,8586	-	2,8586	2,8586	2,8586	0,06	-	12,14
BALINTANG,QUEZON,PALAWAN	9,3500	118,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	19,7150	-	19,7150	19,7150	19,7150	0,15	-	38,15
RORVIK	64,8595	11,2301	-	0%	7,000,000	14,5248	-	14,5248	14,5248	14,5248	0,45	-	46,62
ALERT	82,4900	62,3200	-	0%	7,000,000	79,8034	-	79,8034	79,8034	79,8034	0,16	-	46,15
LEHAVRE	49,4819	0,1060	-	0%	7,000,000	59,8143	-	59,8143	58,4707	58,4707	0,20	-	29,45
PORTARANSAS,H.CALDWELLPIER	27,8267	97,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	8,1350	-	8,1350	8,1350	8,1350	0,11	-	15,47
TAIPOKAU,TOLOHARBOUR	22,4425	114,1839	-	0%	7,000,000	19,3355	-	19,3355	19,3355	19,3355	0,14	-	32,49
KINGSTON	36,8333	139,8500	-	0%	7,000,000	3,8692	-	3,8692	3,8692	3,8692	0,28	-	11,08
ESPERANZA,VIEQUES	18,0933	65,4717	-	0%	7,000,000	57,2075	-	57,2075	37,9966	37,9966	0,38	-	8,89
ROVINJ	45,0833	13,6283	-	0%	7,000,000	67,5669	-	67,5669	67,5669	67,5669	0,21	-	40,54

BODRUMII	37,0333	27,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5262	-	1,5262	-	1,5262	0,51	-	33,94
WYNDHAM	15,4533	128,1010	-	0%	7,000,000	46,8236	-	- 46,8236	46,8236	46,8236	0,34	-	80,22
KIGILIAH	73,3333	139,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	23,6992	-	- 23,6992	23,6992	23,6992	0,35	-	46,89
HOSOJIMA	32,4286	131,6694	-	0%	7,000,000	42,4342	-	- 42,4342	42,4342	42,4342	0,06	-	33,45
BELLEDUNE	47,9000	65,8500	-	0%	7,000,000	19,5674	-	19,5674	18,7739	18,7739	0,06	-	29,90
KUREIII	34,2333	132,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	3,8657	-	3,8657	3,8657	3,8657	0,57	-	126,86
CHRISTMASISLAND	1,9833	157,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	81,0771	-	81,0771	81,0771	81,0771	2,00	-	211,98
UGORSKIISHAR(UGORSKIISHARPROLIV)	69,8167	60,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	68,2367	-	68,2367	70,8087	70,8087	0,06	-	89,95
TOWERPIER	51,5000	0,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	82,5961	-	82,5961	82,5961	82,5961	0,65	-	8,53
WALVISBAY	22,9493	14,4985	-	0%	7,000,000	- 9,4848	-	9,4848	9,4848	9,4848	0,03	-	5,12
FAMAGUSTA	35,1167	33,9500	-	0%	7,000,000	29,7112	-	29,7112	29,7112	29,7112	0,14	-	23,25
GOTEBORG-TORSHAMNEN	57,6847	11,7906	-	0%	7,000,000	25,6941	-	25,6941	25,6941	25,6941	0,25	-	48,61
PORTRUSH	55,2068	6,6568	-	0%	7,000,000	48,2639	-	- 48,2639	48,2639	48,2639	0,16	-	19,91
TADIBE-IAHA	70,3667	72,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	79,1024	-	79,1024	79,1024	79,1024	0,35	-	113,14
HAMADAI	34,8972	132,0661	-	0%	7,000,000	33,3431	-	33,3431	33,3431	33,3431	0,00	-	33,95
CHATHAMISLAND	43,9463	176,5612	-	0%	7,000,000	38,8166	-	- 38,8166	38,8166	38,8166	0,47	-	68,78
CARLOFORTE	39,1480	8,3095	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8668	-	- 61,8668	61,8668	61,8668	0,10	-	52,95
PEVEK	69,7000	170,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	23,5339	-	- 23,5339	23,5339	23,5339	0,11	-	4,76
ESBJERG	55,4608	8,4411	-	0%	7,000,000	67,6427	-	67,6427	67,6427	67,6427	0,24	-	139,75
PORTCHICAGO,CALIFORNIA	38,0550	122,0400	-	0%	7,000,000	45,1550	-	45,1550	45,1550	45,1550	2,50	-	110,15
CHRISTMASISLANDII	1,9833	157,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	22,5516	-	22,5516	22,5516	22,5516	0,01	-	20,72
RIKITEA	23,1223	134,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	89,9012	-	89,9012	89,9012	89,9012	1,24	-	51,99
ITOI	34,9667	139,1167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7726	-	1,7726	1,7726	1,7726	0,11	-	27,34
DAVAO,DAVAOGULF	7,0833	125,6333	-	0%	7,000,000	40,2743	-	40,2743	40,2743	40,2743	0,11	-	81,56
TAPPI	41,2425	140,3814	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9846	-	19,9846	19,9846	19,9846	0,12	-	5,13
MILLPORT	55,7498	4,9063	-	0%	7,000,000	91,8847	-	91,8847	91,8847	91,8847	0,03	-	84,69
MONAISLAND	18,0900	67,9383	-	0%	7,000,000	5,1743	-	5,1743	3,2974	3,2974	0,09	-	10,69
PORTANGELES,WASHINGTON	48,1250	123,4400	-	0%	7,000,000	16,7873	-	16,7873	16,7873	16,7873	0,35	-	24,85

NANSHA	9,5500	112,8800	-	0%	7,000,000	196,7377	-	-	196,7377	-	0,22	237,82
PINEYPOINT,MARYLAND	38,1333	76,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	30,4654	-	-	30,4654	-	0,31	8,21
ABURATSUBO	35,1603	139,6153	-	0%	7,000,000	37,4864	-	-	37,4864	-	0,08	40,57
YAIZU	34,8706	138,3272	-	0%	7,000,000	60,1396	-	60,1396	60,1396	60,1396	0,12	82,74
WLADYSLAWOWO	54,8000	18,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	50,5576	-	-	50,5576	-	0,49	26,73
SOUTHPASS	28,9900	89,1400	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5037	-	3,5037	3,5037	3,5037	0,12	17,81
TOPOLOBAMPO	25,6000	109,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	68,2460	-	-	68,2460	-	0,00	68,30
PLUMISLAND	41,1667	72,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5074	-	-	1,5074	-	0,25	65,29
PUERTOWILLIAMS	54,9167	67,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9035	-	-	19,9035	-	0,59	15,99
RANGIROA	14,9458	147,7060	-	0%	7,000,000	12,7620	-	-	12,7620	-	1,11	173,09
LUDERITZ	26,6433	15,1550	-	0%	7,000,000	0,1970	-	-	0,1970	-	0,08	11,04
TANGGU	39,0000	117,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	53,9189	-	-	53,9189	-	0,03	60,41
TARANTO	40,4333	17,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	92,1012	-	-	92,1012	-	0,34	120,78
LEIXOES	41,1833	8,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	76,5118	-	-	76,5118	-	0,18	98,44
EVANSHEAD	29,1167	153,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	125,0919	-	-	125,0919	-	0,24	155,10
MACKAY	21,1000	149,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	3,3836	-	-	3,3836	-	0,59	21,30
FORTALEZA	3,7167	38,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	98,5179	-	-	98,5179	-	0,05	113,30
CONCARNEAU	47,8737	3,9074	-	0%	7,000,000	123,5019	-	-	123,5019	-	0,15	94,01
ARINAGA	27,8469	15,4015	-	0%	7,000,000	12,9066	-	-	12,9066	-	0,04	9,20
GIRNE	35,3500	33,3333	-	0%	7,000,000	57,4241	-	-	57,4241	-	0,34	83,24
KOBBAKLINTAR	60,0333	19,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	0,4405	-	-	0,4405	-	2,64	79,75
ANGRADOHEROISMO	38,6500	27,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	38,0534	-	-	38,0534	-	0,00	38,07
DIEGORAMIREZ	56,5000	68,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	19,5866	-	-	19,5866	-	0,17	47,88
COCOSISLAND(HOMEIS.)	12,1167	96,8944	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5762	-	-	3,5762	-	0,05	10,18
LARKHARBOUR	49,1000	58,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	5,4945	-	-	5,4945	-	0,26	6,00
DRAGHALLAN	62,3667	17,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	190,5133	-	-	190,5133	-	0,50	464,79
SWINOUJSIE	53,9167	14,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	133,7383	-	-	133,7383	-	0,06	207,07
CHABAHARII	25,2958	60,6033	-	0%	7,000,000	48,1839	-	-	48,1839	-	0,06	51,88
ESPERANCE	33,8709	121,8954	-	0%	7,000,000	35,6404	-	-	35,6404	-	0,04	39,03

CHARLESTONI	32,7817	-79,9250	-	0%	7,000,000	7,7272	-	-	7,7272	7,7272	-	0,18	-	15,95
ISABELADESAGUA	22,9333	80,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	42,1282	-	42,1282	42,1282	42,1282	-	0,07	-	50,13
STOMPNEUSBAY	32,7167	17,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	3,9375	-	3,9375	3,9375	3,9375	-	0,01	-	1,46
PAGOBAY, GUAM	13,4283	144,7967	-	0%	7,000,000	34,7041	-	34,7041	34,7041	34,7041	-	0,15	-	17,07
MAJURO-B	7,1000	171,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	8,7452	-	8,7452	8,7452	8,7452	-	0,08	-	2,46
MALYEKARMAKULY	72,3667	52,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	4.245,1482	-	4.245,1482	4.245,1482	4.245,1482	-	2,58	-	4.281,21
VADSO	70,0667	29,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	38,1765	-	38,1765	38,1765	38,1765	-	1,97	-	89,42
MOMMARK	54,9333	10,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	149,5602	-	149,5602	149,5602	149,5602	-	0,15	-	192,32
LYTTTELTONII	43,6056	172,7219	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9147	-	19,9147	19,9147	19,9147	-	0,05	-	23,38
BRISBANE(WESTINNERBAR)	27,3667	153,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	1,0586	-	1,0586	1,4166	1,4166	-	0,05	-	14,08
KWAJALEIN	8,7317	167,7350	-	0%	7,000,000	69,8579	-	69,8579	69,8579	69,8579	-	0,04	-	78,93
SANFELIX	26,2922	80,1086	-	0%	7,000,000	1,1905	-	1,1905	1,1905	1,1905	-	1,16	-	125,99
ANTALYAI	36,8333	30,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	34,9738	-	34,9738	34,9738	34,9738	-	0,12	-	42,17
DUBROVNIK	42,6583	18,0633	-	0%	7,000,000	64,0084	-	64,0084	64,0084	64,0084	-	0,13	-	39,55
KUSHIMOTO	33,4758	135,7733	-	0%	7,000,000	55,6726	-	55,6726	55,6726	55,6726	-	0,06	-	65,20
KOTELNYI(KOTELNYIOSTROV)	76,0000	137,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	17,3734	-	17,3734	17,3734	17,3734	-	0,17	-	48,19
ADEN	12,7883	44,9742	-	0%	7,000,000	86,4664	-	86,4664	86,4664	86,4664	-	0,09	-	122,56
HAKATA	33,6189	130,4078	-	0%	7,000,000	16,5064	-	16,5064	16,5064	16,5064	-	0,26	-	4,59
ONISAKI	34,9039	136,8236	-	0%	7,000,000	59,6229	-	59,6229	59,6229	59,6229	-	0,23	-	18,97
MASAN	35,2100	128,5889	-	0%	7,000,000	0,6718	-	0,6718	0,6718	0,6718	-	0,14	-	17,58
MALINHEAD	55,3667	7,3333	-	0%	7,000,000	19,5413	-	19,5413	19,5413	19,5413	-	0,04	-	25,17
SIROS	37,4400	24,9458	-	0%	7,000,000	47,4903	-	47,4903	47,4903	47,4903	-	0,03	-	49,91
NISINOOMOTE	30,7350	130,9922	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8141	-	61,8141	61,8141	61,8141	-	0,05	-	59,47
HONIARA-B	9,4289	159,9554	-	0%	7,000,000	58,8020	-	58,8020	58,8020	58,8020	-	0,24	-	79,98
ROCKPORT	28,0217	97,0467	-	0%	7,000,000	51,2580	-	51,2580	51,2580	51,2580	-	0,17	-	30,14
AMASRA	41,4333	32,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	11,5387	-	11,5387	11,5387	11,5387	-	0,62	-	29,12
NASEIII	28,5000	129,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	68,9825	-	68,9825	68,9825	68,9825	-	0,32	-	92,33
ARGENTIA	47,3000	53,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	20,3379	-	20,3379	20,3379	20,3379	-	0,49	-	38,88
FREDERICIA	55,5608	9,7544	-	0%	7,000,000	33,6620	-	33,6620	33,6620	33,6620	-	0,05	-	65,50

PORTHARDY	50,7167	-	-	0%	7,000,000	81,5493	-	-	81,5493	81,5493	-	0,15	65,77
MALAKAL-B	7,3333	134,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	28,6166	-	28,6166	28,6166	28,6166	-	0,09	25,88
FORT-DE-FRANCEII	14,6015	61,0632	-	0%	7,000,000	13,8934	-	13,8934	13,8934	13,8934	-	0,02	16,17
CHUJADO	33,9617	126,3003	-	0%	7,000,000	16,7858	-	16,7858	16,7858	16,7858	-	0,09	9,06
LAPAZ	24,1667	110,3500	-	0%	7,000,000	21,6761	-	21,6761	21,6761	21,6761	-	0,48	4,28
SANTABARBARA,CALIFORNIA	34,4083	119,6850	-	0%	7,000,000	68,1843	-	68,1843	68,1843	68,1843	-	0,08	78,78
RIVIERE-AU-RENARD	49,0000	64,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	58,2292	-	58,2292	58,2292	58,2292	-	0,25	29,95
LOWESTOFT	52,4731	1,7501	-	0%	7,000,000	55,9640	-	55,9640	55,9640	55,9640	-	0,10	30,10
TAGO	34,8069	138,7642	-	0%	7,000,000	0,2407	-	0,2407	0,2407	0,2407	-	0,34	63,54
NAPOLI(ARSENALE)	40,8667	14,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	22,8679	-	22,8679	22,8679	22,8679	-	0,20	37,69
PUERTOANGEL	15,5000	96,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	4,2541	-	4,2541	4,2541	4,2541	-	0,08	14,44
ENSENADA	31,8500	116,6333	-	0%	7,000,000	0,9833	-	0,9833	0,9833	0,9833	-	0,14	17,91
USHUAIAI	54,8167	68,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	2,0183	-	2,0183	2,0183	2,0183	-	0,23	57,92
TUBUAI	23,3418	149,4755	-	0%	7,000,000	51,5614	-	51,5614	51,5614	51,5614	-	0,02	49,21
PULAU LANGKAWI	6,4308	99,7642	-	0%	7,000,000	29,0371	-	29,0371	29,0371	29,0371	-	0,10	18,61
KALIX	65,6969	23,0961	-	0%	7,000,000	0,7872	-	0,7872	0,7872	0,7872	-	0,20	11,15
CATANIA	37,5000	15,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	208,0487	-	208,0487	208,0487	208,0487	-	0,37	315,37
SHIJIUSUO	35,3833	119,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	155,3188	-	155,3188	155,3188	155,3188	-	0,07	170,97
PORTERIN	54,0854	4,7681	-	0%	7,000,000	38,6308	-	38,6308	38,6308	38,6308	-	1,51	102,86
DIGBY	44,6333	65,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	14,0709	-	14,0709	14,0709	14,0709	-	0,25	16,02
VALKARKAI	70,0833	170,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3146	-	0,3146	0,3146	0,3146	-	0,09	10,36
BLUFF(SOUTHLANDHARBOUR)	46,5977	168,3454	-	0%	7,000,000	45,5319	-	45,5319	45,5319	45,5319	-	0,03	42,52
ACAJUTLAZ	13,5833	89,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	30,9781	-	30,9781	30,9781	30,9781	-	0,24	78,11
PASAJES	43,3266	1,9218	-	0%	7,000,000	111,0209	-	111,0209	111,0209	111,0209	-	0,31	207,83
GRANADILLA	28,0853	16,4896	-	0%	7,000,000	50,5826	-	50,5826	50,5826	50,5826	-	0,08	56,07
EASTPORT	44,9033	66,9817	-	0%	7,000,000	40,1776	-	40,1776	40,1776	40,1776	-	0,16	47,52
VIKER	59,0360	10,9498	-	0%	7,000,000	75,5357	-	75,5357	75,5357	75,5357	-	0,40	41,87
OSLO	59,9086	10,7345	-	0%	7,000,000	139,7704	-	139,7704	139,7704	139,7704	-	0,37	251,42

PALMEIRA	16,7500	-	22,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,0056	-	7,0056	0,43	-	38,03
TACLOBAN,LEYTE	11,2500	-	125,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	13,5429	-	13,5429	0,63	-	47,13
BOULOGNE	50,7275	-	1,5775	-	0%	7,000,000	-	59,1310	-	59,1310	0,31	-	163,76
TOKYOI	35,6667	-	139,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	39,2152	-	39,2152	0,30	-	113,87
CABOCRUZ	19,8333	-	77,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	32,0981	-	32,0981	0,11	-	20,45
PELABUHANKELANG	3,0500	-	101,3583	-	0%	7,000,000	-	1,7836	-	1,7836	1,08	-	18,79
BAIECOMEAU	49,2333	-	68,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	32,5900	-	32,5900	0,12	-	48,95
LANDSORTNORRA	58,7689	-	17,8589	-	0%	7,000,000	-	23,9859	-	23,9859	0,39	-	3,99
LEITHII	55,9898	-	3,1817	-	0%	7,000,000	-	3,6518	-	3,6518	1,92	-	62,29
SAINTJOHN,N.B.	45,2667	-	66,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	19,0209	-	19,3786	0,11	-	80,63
NORTHSALAMINOSII	37,9796	-	23,5342	-	0%	7,000,000	-	51,4595	-	51,4595	0,21	-	32,07
TANGACHCHIMADAM	9,2833	-	79,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	103,0480	-	103,0480	0,90	-	76,82
PICTOU	45,6833	-	62,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	33,3504	-	33,3504	0,55	-	71,62
LACORUNAI	43,3643	-	8,3989	-	0%	7,000,000	-	44,2341	-	44,2341	0,77	-	141,59
SAGYLLAH-ARY	73,1500	-	128,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	2,3963	-	2,3963	0,29	-	68,15
THESSALONIKI	40,6325	-	22,9349	-	0%	7,000,000	-	20,1265	-	20,1265	0,42	-	80,76
PORTALMA	23,5833	-	150,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	13,9729	-	13,9729	0,38	-	25,09
AYUKAWA	38,2967	-	141,5053	-	0%	7,000,000	-	36,5729	-	36,5729	0,15	-	70,22
USTKA	54,5833	-	16,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	34,5105	-	34,5105	0,49	-	108,56
POTI	42,1667	-	41,6833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	109,3595	-	109,3595	0,06	-	94,08
RUSTICO	46,4667	-	63,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	4,5125	-	4,5125	0,19	-	34,94
SALALAH	16,9333	-	54,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	76,3133	-	76,3133	0,29	-	45,63
MILFORDHAVEN(NEWTONNOYES)	51,7000	-	5,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	71,6129	-	71,6129	0,11	-	142,81
RANGOON	16,7667	-	96,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	17,8843	-	17,8843	0,09	-	33,38
ODOMARI	31,0236	-	130,6892	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,2272	-	7,2272	0,12	-	1,24
AION	69,9333	-	167,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	27,0621	-	27,0621	0,26	-	10,01
SULTANSHOAL	1,2333	-	103,6500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,5760	-	7,5760	0,85	-	23,39
BONANZA	36,8022	-	6,3381	-	0%	7,000,000	-	24,1836	-	24,1836	0,47	-	38,11

KUDAT	6,8794	116,8436	-	0%	7,000,000	44,9089	-	- 44,9089	44,9089	-	44,9089	-	0,19	65,46
DUTCHHARBOR	53,9000	166,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	31,8113	-	31,8113	31,8113	31,8113	31,8113	0,18	100,67	
BARENTSBURG	78,0667	14,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	16,9499	-	16,9499	16,9499	16,9499	16,9499	0,19	22,74	
TUTICORIN	8,7500	78,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	19,1316	-	19,1316	19,1316	19,1316	19,1316	0,14	11,70	
PATRAI	38,4167	21,7287	-	0%	7,000,000	15,1186	-	15,1186	15,1186	15,1186	15,1186	0,20	7,54	
NEDRESODERTALJE	59,2000	17,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	155,3188	-	155,3188	155,3188	155,3188	155,3188	0,23	252,66	
KOBENHAVN	55,7050	12,6000	-	0%	7,000,000	20,7575	-	20,7575	20,7575	20,7575	20,7575	0,18	43,63	
RODRIGUESIS	19,6667	63,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	3,7153	-	3,7153	3,7153	3,7153	3,7153	0,51	78,11	
TANJUNGGELANG	3,9750	103,4300	-	0%	7,000,000	589,0359	-	589,0359	589,0359	589,0359	589,0359	0,17	578,90	
CHOSHII	35,7333	140,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	1,8902	-	1,8902	1,8902	1,8902	1,8902	0,11	26,10	
DIEPPE	49,9291	1,0838	-	0%	7,000,000	4,7446	-	4,7446	4,7446	4,7446	4,7446	0,14	24,59	
RINCONISLAND	34,3483	119,4417	-	0%	7,000,000	45,8475	-	45,8475	45,8475	45,8475	45,8475	0,01	43,83	
TRONDHEIM	63,4333	10,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	137,4191	-	137,4191	137,4191	137,4191	137,4191	0,29	312,45	
SOUTHPORT	33,9150	78,0183	-	0%	7,000,000	50,5014	-	50,5014	50,5014	50,5014	50,5014	0,37	123,39	
SEATTLE	47,6017	122,3383	-	0%	7,000,000	38,9975	-	38,9975	38,9975	38,9975	38,9975	0,56	60,97	
HAMMERFEST	70,6646	23,6832	-	0%	7,000,000	12,9481	-	12,9481	12,9481	12,9481	12,9481	0,14	29,60	
KUREIV	34,2406	132,5503	-	0%	7,000,000	10,3070	-	10,3070	10,3070	10,3070	10,3070	0,19	47,61	
ANTOFAGASTA2	23,6531	70,4044	-	0%	7,000,000	57,7029	-	57,7029	57,1015	57,1015	57,1015	0,19	21,10	
CURRIMAOILOCOSNORTE	17,9833	120,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	40,2826	-	40,2826	40,2826	40,2826	40,2826	0,13	29,85	
ST-JEAN-PORT-JOLI	47,2167	70,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	18,2488	-	18,2488	18,2488	18,2488	18,2488	0,68	107,58	
NAPOLI(MANDRACCHIO)	40,8429	14,2575	-	0%	7,000,000	6,2031	-	6,2031	6,2031	6,2031	6,2031	0,20	24,49	
ARGENTINEISLANDS	65,2462	64,2574	-	0%	7,000,000	47,8894	-	47,8894	47,8894	47,8894	47,8894	0,01	49,47	
ALAMEDA(NAVALAIRSTATION)	37,7717	122,2983	-	0%	7,000,000	22,2000	-	22,2000	22,2000	22,2000	22,2000	0,34	11,96	
TAKAMATSUII	34,3514	134,0569	-	0%	7,000,000	1,4119	-	1,4119	1,4119	1,4119	1,4119	0,17	27,88	
EXMOUTH	21,9549	114,1409	-	0%	7,000,000	56,1899	-	56,1899	56,1899	56,1899	56,1899	0,75	96,30	
ST-FRANCOIS	47,0000	70,8167	-	0%	7,000,000	21,4182	-	21,4182	21,4182	21,4182	21,4182	0,04	19,31	
VICTORIA	48,4167	123,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	65,1943	-	65,1943	65,1943	65,1943	65,1943	0,23	32,40	
PORTBLOC	45,5685	1,0616	-	0%	7,000,000	64,1075	-	64,1075	64,1075	64,1075	64,1075	0,78	29,36	

XIAMEN	24,4500	118,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	69,1788	-	69,1788	69,1788	0,03	-	77,93
PORTFERREOL	43,3591	6,7176	-	0%	7,000,000	7,3360	-	-	7,3360	7,3360	1,30	-	65,13
NEWROCHELLE	40,8933	73,7817	-	0%	7,000,000	50,7768	-	-	50,7768	50,7768	0,05	-	51,61
CALAIS	50,9694	1,8677	-	0%	7,000,000	16,3719	-	-	16,3719	16,3719	0,10	-	25,24
MURMANSKII	68,9667	33,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	10,1869	-	-	10,1869	12,3651	0,17	-	67,28
KAWAIHAE,HAWAIIISLAND	20,0367	155,8300	-	0%	7,000,000	-	8,9232	-	8,9232	8,9232	0,19	-	31,28
PAGETISLAND	32,3667	64,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	4,4368	-	-	4,4368	4,4368	0,18	-	35,50
HOBART	42,8773	147,3410	-	0%	7,000,000	0,4778	-	-	0,4778	0,4778	0,24	-	60,42
LUMUT	4,2400	100,6133	-	0%	7,000,000	45,4249	-	-	45,4249	45,4249	2,79	-	6,11
VICTORHARBOUR	35,5625	138,6354	-	0%	7,000,000	28,9835	-	-	28,9835	28,9835	0,04	-	18,28
TOLCHESTERBEACH,MARYLAND	39,2133	76,2450	-	0%	7,000,000	54,1228	-	-	54,1228	54,1228	0,25	-	62,35
VANKAREM	67,8333	175,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	7,9316	-	-	7,9316	7,9316	0,25	-	36,28
KEPPELHARBOUR	1,2667	103,8167	-	0%	7,000,000	7,5833	-	-	7,5833	7,5833	0,90	-	18,84
HIRONPOINT	21,7833	89,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	5,7894	-	-	5,7894	5,7894	0,20	-	17,19
OFUNATOII	39,0197	141,7533	-	0%	7,000,000	66,7426	-	-	66,7426	66,7426	0,01	-	68,77
GARIBALDI	45,5550	123,9183	-	0%	7,000,000	36,0537	-	-	36,0537	36,0537	0,07	-	44,89
RODBYHAVN	54,6558	11,3486	-	0%	7,000,000	30,6832	-	-	30,6832	30,6832	0,02	-	28,00
DEVONPORT	41,1847	146,3624	-	0%	7,000,000	55,8984	-	-	55,8984	55,8984	0,27	-	29,86
HUELVA	37,1320	6,8337	-	0%	7,000,000	17,3544	-	-	17,3544	17,3544	3,74	-	86,62
LOWHEAD	41,0644	146,7947	-	0%	7,000,000	48,0154	-	-	48,0154	48,0154	0,22	-	25,80
GARDENREACH	22,5500	88,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	257,0730	-	-	257,0730	257,0730	0,10	-	281,32
CIUDADMADERO	22,2500	97,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	29,8444	-	-	29,8444	29,8444	0,40	-	124,92
ANCUD	41,8669	73,8319	-	0%	7,000,000	41,0596	-	-	41,0596	41,0596	0,41	-	22,88
KOLOBRZEG	54,1833	15,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	83,2483	-	-	83,2483	83,2483	0,03	-	87,50
WAJIMA	37,4058	136,9003	-	0%	7,000,000	3,1470	-	-	3,1470	3,1470	0,21	-	29,42
JANGHANG	36,0069	126,6878	-	0%	7,000,000	82,0034	-	-	82,0034	82,0034	0,29	-	122,26
HINKLEYPPOINT	51,2106	3,1313	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5234	-	-	44,5234	44,5234	0,09	-	35,62
SUMOTO	34,3406	134,9067	-	0%	7,000,000	35,8741	-	-	35,8741	35,8741	0,28	-	44,87

SOUHDAS	35,4875	24,0825	-	0%	7,000,000	73,4175	-	-	73,4175	73,4175	-	0,42	120,98
ANCONA	43,5833	13,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	48,7109	-	48,7109	48,7109	48,7109	-	0,09	19,08
TUXPAN	21,0000	97,3333	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9585	-	2,9585	2,9585	2,9585	-	0,09	13,60
LAJESDASFLORES	39,3785	31,1686	-	0%	7,000,000	17,1448	-	17,1448	17,1448	17,1448	-	0,57	82,33
LACORUNAI	43,3573	8,3893	-	0%	7,000,000	84,1211	-	84,1211	84,1211	84,1211	-	0,42	25,36
TALLINN	59,4500	24,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	72,0437	-	72,0437	72,0437	72,0437	-	0,90	123,60
TOWNSVILLE	19,2500	146,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	63,6123	-	63,6123	63,6123	63,6123	-	0,10	46,46
SANTACRUZDELAPALMA	28,6797	17,7664	-	0%	7,000,000	29,3744	-	29,3744	29,3744	29,3744	-	0,14	59,42
MOTRIL2	36,7202	3,5236	-	0%	7,000,000	47,8764	-	47,8764	47,8764	47,8764	-	0,10	53,89
MORMUGAO	15,4167	73,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9490	-	19,9490	19,9490	19,9490	-	1,81	91,30
ROSYTH	56,0167	3,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	4,4048	-	4,4048	4,4048	4,4048	-	0,24	54,25
MOBILESTATEDOCKS,ALABAMA	30,7050	88,0400	-	0%	7,000,000	42,2099	-	42,2099	42,2099	42,2099	-	0,57	13,32
CHENNAI	13,1000	80,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	2,1766	-	2,1766	2,1766	2,1766	-	0,13	66,70
CUTLERII	44,6417	67,2967	-	0%	7,000,000	65,3635	-	65,3635	65,3635	65,3635	-	0,31	54,83
IJMUIDEN	52,4622	4,5547	-	0%	7,000,000	126,1608	-	126,1608	126,1608	126,1608	-	0,15	189,76
SHIMONOSEKI	33,9250	130,9278	-	0%	7,000,000	16,6297	-	16,6297	16,6297	16,6297	-	3,74	69,05
NEMKOVA(NEMKOVAOSTROV)	71,4167	150,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5655	-	44,5655	44,5655	44,5655	-	0,90	113,56
NARVIK	68,4283	17,4258	-	0%	7,000,000	65,4685	-	65,4685	65,4685	65,4685	-	0,01	69,36
SANTAMONICA(MUNICIPALPIER)	34,0083	118,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	31,4410	-	31,4410	25,1976	25,1976	-	0,45	7,21
TROIS-RIVIERES	46,3333	72,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	25,0358	-	25,0358	25,0358	25,0358	-	0,59	39,28
ISLADECEDROS	28,1000	115,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	28,5312	-	28,5312	28,5312	28,5312	-	0,44	0,66
OSCARSBORG	59,6781	10,6049	-	0%	7,000,000	286,2251	-	286,2251	286,2251	286,2251	-	0,52	504,89
FORSMARK	60,4086	18,2108	-	0%	7,000,000	8,5385	-	8,5385	8,5385	8,5385	-	0,11	14,36
ASHDODII	31,8313	34,6405	-	0%	7,000,000	47,2106	-	47,2106	47,2106	47,2106	-	0,28	24,45
ANTOFAGASTA	23,6500	70,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	14,1624	-	14,1624	14,1624	14,1624	-	0,19	42,43
NANOOSEBAY	49,2667	124,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	0,1519	-	0,1519	0,1519	0,1519	-	1,11	18,65
WALTONONTHEHAZE	51,8500	1,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	3,6099	-	3,6099	3,6099	3,6099	-	0,01	2,33

MAMBAJAOCAMGUIN	9,2500	124,7333	-	0%	7,000,0000	16,3598	-	-	16,3598	16,3598	-	16,3598	0,06	12,29
KOBEI	34,6822	135,1903	-	0%	7,000,0000	166,5524	-	166,5524	166,5524	166,5524	-	166,5524	0,68	198,64
MOZI	33,9500	130,9667	-	0%	7,000,0000	23,8867	-	23,8867	23,8867	23,8867	-	23,8867	2,56	635,11
CAGLIARI	39,2000	9,1667	-	0%	7,000,0000	187,0510	-	187,0510	187,0510	187,0510	-	187,0510	0,55	306,82
KLASHAMN	55,5222	12,8936	-	0%	7,000,0000	73,5050	-	73,5050	73,5050	73,5050	-	73,5050	0,57	130,27
FUERTEVENTURA	28,4925	13,8582	-	0%	7,000,0000	80,3391	-	80,3391	80,3391	80,3391	-	80,3391	0,28	56,57
GIBARA	21,1083	76,1250	-	0%	7,000,0000	1,0601	-	1,0601	1,0601	1,0601	-	1,0601	0,12	23,83
ABERDEENII	57,1500	2,0833	-	0%	7,000,0000	90,3009	-	90,3009	90,3009	90,3009	-	90,3009	0,25	206,57
KEELUNGII	25,1333	121,7333	-	0%	7,000,0000	18,7760	-	18,7760	18,7760	18,7760	-	18,7760	0,38	153,80
BUENAVENTURA	3,9000	77,1000	-	0%	7,000,0000	30,5220	-	30,5220	30,5220	30,5220	-	30,5220	0,67	7,29
NOUMEA-CHALEIX	22,3000	166,4333	-	0%	7,000,0000	7,4247	-	7,4247	7,4247	7,4247	-	7,4247	0,41	15,79
PORTALLEN,HANAPEPEBAY,KAUAIISLAND	21,9033	159,5917	-	0%	7,000,0000	100,6504	-	100,6504	100,6504	100,6504	-	100,6504	0,55	167,33
FULFORDHARBOUR	48,7667	123,4500	-	0%	7,000,0000	9,1520	-	9,1520	9,3638	9,3638	-	9,3638	0,13	34,96
NEWCASTLEV	32,9240	151,7886	-	0%	7,000,0000	99,7645	-	99,7645	99,7645	99,7645	-	99,7645	0,10	123,36
SANCLEMENTEISLAND	33,0000	118,5500	-	0%	7,000,0000	0,6366	-	0,6366	0,6366	0,6366	-	0,6366	0,35	85,11
PENRHYN	9,0167	158,0667	-	0%	7,000,0000	49,2339	-	49,2339	49,2339	49,2339	-	49,2339	0,65	25,01
VRANGELIA(VRANGELIAOSTROV)	70,9833	178,4833	-	0%	7,000,0000	79,5077	-	79,5077	79,5077	79,5077	-	79,5077	0,02	74,30

Table 3. Results for B1 – 2005 – 2019

	latitude	longitude	sample	completeness	psmsl mean	mean tot (realigned val)	mean (baseline)	R1	mean non base	R2	RR	R0
CANAVIEIRAS	15,6667	38,9667	108	100%	7,098,3796	47,0914	98,3796	51,2882	38,6094	59,7702	0,08	10,76
WEYMOUTH	50,6085	2,4479	108	100%	7,008,5185	76,5536	8,5185	85,0721	102,1750	110,6936	0,22	147,00
BOURGAS	42,4833	27,4833	108	100%	7,191,3241	0,1441	191,3241	191,4682	38,8318	230,1558	0,30	184,67
ALAMITOSBAYENTRANCE	33,7500	118,1167	108	100%	7,226,8704	106,8525	226,8704	120,0179	76,7426	150,1277	0,24	1,37
ARKO	58,4842	16,9606	108	100%	7,095,0185	65,6340	95,0185	29,3846	31,6597	63,3588	0,25	24,17
MALYSHEVA(MALYSHEVAOSTROV)	72,0667	129,8333	108	100%	7,228,2315	17,4712	228,2315	210,7603	30,0666	258,2981	0,32	119,15
DAUPHINISLAND	30,2500	88,0750	108	100%	7,019,4259	36,4410	19,4259	55,8669	53,6224	73,0483	0,14	87,96

JOHNSTONISLAND	16,7383	-	108	100%	7.035,2685	55,5976	35,2685	-	20,3291	65,2350	-	29,9665	-	0,06	86,71	
MACABALANPORT,CAGAYANDEORO	8,5000	124,6667	108	100%	6.799,9167	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	23,87	
TANJONGCHANGI	1,3903	103,9989	108	100%	7.043,7685	1,0013	43,7685	42,7672	-	12,5675	56,3360	0,15	-	-	42,85	
ANABAR	73,2167	113,5000	108	100%	7.086,7593	35,1369	86,7593	51,6223	20,2752	66,4841	0,15	-	-	-	11,47	
MURMANSK	68,9667	33,0500	108	100%	7.218,7500	62,7011	218,7500	156,0489	16,8990	201,8510	0,34	-	-	-	93,51	
LAJOLLA(SCRIPPSPIER)	32,8667	-	108	100%	7.061,8333	13,9747	61,8333	75,8081	-	26,6223	88,4556	0,09	-	-	69,73	
CHUUK,MOENISLAND	7,4467	151,8467	108	100%	7.072,4352	5,9196	72,4352	78,3548	-	21,1218	93,5570	0,13	-	-	74,36	
KAINAN	34,1442	135,1914	108	100%	6.982,5926	49,0671	17,4074	31,6596	-	58,0218	40,6144	0,06	-	-	76,30	
VARNA	43,1833	27,9167	108	100%	7.017,6389	62,6128	17,6389	-	44,9739	69,4272	-	51,7883	-	0,03	82,12	
YAKUTAT	59,5483	-	108	100%	7.165,4259	18,4865	165,4259	183,9125	-	54,6226	220,0486	0,30	-	-	183,72	
MOREHEADCITY	34,7167	76,7333	108	100%	7.076,3426	1,0722	76,3426	75,2704	-	20,6040	96,9466	0,19	-	-	80,58	
PUERTOCORTES	15,8333	-	108	100%	7.235,1389	101,6374	235,1389	133,5014	-	76,4434	158,6955	0,21	-	-	3,07	
YEOSU	34,7472	127,7656	108	100%	7.338,7222	278,1561	338,7222	60,5661	-	260,7454	77,9768	0,08	-	-	251,55	
HANASAKI	43,2833	145,5833	108	100%	6.836,6389	-	298,0694	-	-	163,3611	134,7083	318,0271	154,6660	0,14	402,35	
DALIAN	38,8667	121,6833	108	100%	7.043,7963	48,0496	43,7963	-	4,2533	49,7292	5,9329	0,03	-	-	61,57	
MARSEILLE	43,2788	5,3539	108	100%	6.978,1389	-	52,2665	-	21,8611	30,4054	-	59,0514	37,1903	0,03	72,25	
CLEARWATERBEACH	27,9783	-	108	100%	6.997,3241	29,8605	-	-	-	2,6759	32,5365	45,6079	-	48,2838	0,16	81,09
ALGECIRASB	36,1214	-	108	100%	7.132,9352	81,1948	-	-	-	132,9352	51,7404	63,4548	69,4804	0,18	31,63	
KOTAPHAONOI	7,8333	98,4333	108	100%	6.988,5093	61,0079	-	-	11,4907	72,4986	80,2230	-	91,7138	0,16	150,10	
MINAMIIZU	34,6167	138,8833	108	100%	6.973,8889	52,7173	-	-	26,1111	26,6062	61,6915	35,5803	0,07	-	77,59	
VARBERG	57,1000	12,2167	108	100%	6.978,0278	41,0965	-	-	21,9722	19,1243	44,3747	22,4025	0,00	-	42,68	
NUKU'ALOFAB	21,1368	-	108	100%	6.947,5926	34,3369	-	-	-	34,3369	52,4074	18,0705	22,7082	29,6992	0,09	8,57
BILLINGA	69,8833	175,7667	108	100%	7.081,4537	3,9168	-	-	81,4537	77,5369	-	21,3766	102,8303	0,16	67,08	
WILLETSPPOINT	40,7933	-	108	100%	7.117,6204	73,7817	47,5439	117,6204	70,0765	36,2572	81,3632	0,09	-	-	2,54	
KRISTIANSUND	63,1139	7,7344	108	100%	6.840,5648	540,6566	159,4352	700,0918	-	746,5995	906,0347	1,51	-	-	1.226,14	
ULUKHAKTOK(FORMERLYHOLMAN)	70,7363	-	108	100%	7.159,4907	65,5377	159,4907	93,9530	-	24,5798	134,9109	0,34	-	-	34,90	
HELSINKI	60,1536	24,9562	108	100%	7.152,1667	98,3518	152,1667	250,5185	-	129,1250	281,2916	0,24	-	-	338,47	
ARICA	18,4667	-	108	100%	6.406,8704	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		70,3333			6.406,8704	183,6855	593,1296	409,4441		82,3321	510,7975	0,70			151,68	

ABURATSU	31,5769	131,4094	108	100%	7.118,7778	39,8227	118,7778	78,9551	17,6027	101,1751	0,18	-	33,41
PORTBLAIR	11,6833	92,7667	108	100%	7.175,7593	30,2843	175,7593	145,4749	8,3942	167,3651	0,18	-	94,89
YOKOSUKA	35,2881	139,6514	108	100%	7.059,2870	17,0442	59,2870	76,3313	40,0169	99,3039	0,12	-	70,21
KOTKA	60,4500	26,9500	108	100%	7.186,4167	59,5872	186,4167	126,8295	40,0799	146,3367	0,17	-	64,77
HAUOVERPIER	25,9033	80,1200	108	100%	7.030,6574	19,0625	30,6574	49,7200	88,2782	118,9356	0,48	-	100,51
AMDERMA	69,7500	61,7000	108	100%	6.866,0556	2,3436	133,9444	131,6009	24,1167	158,0611	0,21	-	100,26
BERGEN	60,3980	5,3205	108	100%	6.859,4630	120,4020	140,5370	20,1351	110,4565	30,0806	0,08	-	86,70
CAPELAMBERT	20,5880	117,1860	108	100%	7.121,7593	72,9139	121,7593	48,8454	10,0275	111,7318	0,45	-	5,07
SKAGWAY	59,4500	135,3267	108	100%	7.212,5741	84,0531	212,5741	128,5209	54,3472	158,2269	0,23	-	41,72
GRONDINES	46,5833	72,0333	108	100%	6.962,7593	56,8915	37,2407	19,6507	54,4938	17,2531	0,01	-	49,40
NEWLYN	50,1030	5,5428	108	100%	7.096,1204	16,7242	96,1204	112,8445	32,7802	128,9006	0,12	-	117,08
HEYSHAM	54,0318	2,9203	108	100%	7.011,0833	14,3411	11,0833	3,2578	17,6720	6,5886	0,04	-	29,66
VENEZIA(S.STEFANO)	45,4167	12,3333	108	100%	6.951,0093	101,8395	48,9907	150,8303	124,3373	173,3281	0,16	-	240,18
IMBITUBA	28,2333	48,6500	108	100%	7.086,8981	27,1017	86,8981	59,7964	16,1261	70,7720	0,10	-	24,68
CADIZII	36,5278	6,3114	108	100%	7.468,3056	108,8539	468,3056	359,4516	44,2766	424,0289	0,54	-	253,57
DOUGLAS	54,1500	4,4667	108	100%	7.019,4537	3,9086	19,4537	15,5451	1,1315	20,5852	0,02	-	9,52
MYRTLEBEACH	33,6833	78,8850	108	100%	7.017,5278	64,9939	17,5278	82,5217	87,0335	104,5613	0,17	-	127,78
ZHOHOVA(ZHOHOVAOSTROV)	76,1500	152,8333	108	100%	6.991,4907	0,9830	8,5093	9,4923	6,5952	15,1044	0,06	-	26,74
FURUOGRUND	64,9158	21,2306	108	100%	7.117,5926	29,5825	117,5926	88,0100	14,8948	102,6978	0,13	-	57,04
EVENSKJAER	68,5833	16,5500	108	100%	7.051,3981	82,3706	51,3981	30,9725	92,0706	40,6724	0,06	-	114,15
ARRECIFE-D	28,9658	13,5379	108	100%	6.815,6389	274,6396	184,3611	90,2785	295,9800	111,6188	0,16	-	327,63
DIAMONDHARBOUR	22,2000	88,1667	108	100%	6.938,9074	4,9704	61,0926	66,0630	25,5238	86,6164	0,15	-	79,65
ST.PAUL'SHARBOR,KODIAK	57,7450	152,4817	108	100%	7.152,7130	116,1428	152,7130	36,5702	76,1848	76,5281	0,29	-	66,72
LOHM	60,1000	21,6667	108	100%	7.211,0833	13,0555	211,0833	224,1389	55,8855	266,9688	0,33	-	228,44
DUBLIN	53,3500	6,2167	108	100%	7.288,1574	71,0353	288,1574	217,1221	22,1657	265,9917	0,39	-	145,56
USTOLENEK	73,0000	119,8667	108	100%	7.104,0093	56,1684	104,0093	47,8408	48,8798	55,1295	0,07	-	20,48
KUSHIRO	42,9756	144,3714	108	100%	7.148,3148	11,1962	148,3148	137,1187	20,8023	169,1171	0,24	-	115,70
KODIAKISLAND,WOMENS BAY	57,7317	152,5117	108	100%	6.304,9815	168,2282	695,0185	526,7903	29,7399	665,2786	1,12	-	397,88
POINTENOIRE	4,7833	11,8333	108	100%	7.018,1574	18,5162	18,1574	0,3588	21,3703	3,2129	0,05	-	40,15

ARRECIFE2	28,9719	- 13,5301	108	100%	7.067,8611	25,6017	67,8611	42,2594	13,4864	54,3747	0,14	- 13,01
QUEBEC(LAUZON)	46,8333	- 71,1667	108	100%	7.092,6574	108,0650	92,6574	200,7224	141,9394	234,5969	0,25	- 288,47
SANDWICHMARINA,CAPECODCANALENTRANCE	41,7667	- 70,5000	108	100%	7.127,7130	99,7328	127,7130	27,9802	74,9336	52,7794	0,30	- 0,33
WEST-TERSCHELLING	53,3631	5,2200	108	100%	7.171,5741	70,2448	171,5741	101,3293	51,9340	119,6401	0,16	- 31,31
NORTHPOINT	22,3000	114,2000	108	100%	7.208,9537	30,2527	208,9537	178,7010	2,9597	211,9134	0,28	- 134,83
BITUNGII	1,4333	125,2000	108	100%	7.251,7593	138,2246	251,7593	113,5346	90,2069	161,5523	0,39	- 11,79
ALVARADO	18,7667	- 95,7667	108	100%	6.977,4722	13,9552	22,5278	36,4830	27,3937	49,9215	0,15	- 75,63
REGGIOCALABRIA	38,1000	15,6500	108	100%	6.960,0741	83,0368	39,9259	43,1109	94,0321	54,1062	0,06	- 111,29
FISHGUARD	52,0132	- 4,9838	108	100%	7.066,6667	38,5571	66,6667	28,1096	4,7944	61,8723	0,24	- 1,22
SOUDHASII	35,4875	24,0825	108	100%	6.803,5463	56,8030	196,4537	139,6507	6,0166	202,4703	0,44	- 67,89
PALMADEMALLORCA	39,5524	2,6389	108	100%	7.066,8981	40,5877	66,8981	26,3105	28,4371	38,4610	0,12	- 5,95
TURKEYPOINT	29,9150	- 84,5117	108	100%	7.084,5278	34,3397	84,5278	118,8675	72,5347	157,0625	0,32	- 138,76
BUZZARDSBAY	41,7417	- 70,6167	108	100%	6.726,2407	155,1474	273,7593	118,6119	65,0898	208,6695	0,76	- 5,88
STOCKHOLM	59,3242	18,0817	108	100%	6.969,3981	143,7073	30,6019	174,3092	172,1730	202,7749	0,24	- 335,56
DUCKPIEROUTSIDE	36,1833	- 75,7467	107	99%	7.175,8692	75,0450	175,8692	100,8241	36,5820	139,2871	0,31	- 28,72
BILBAO	43,3515	- 3,0451	107	99%	7.189,0374	153,3358	189,0374	35,7016	114,1236	74,9138	0,30	- 102,14
TUAS(WESTJURONG)	1,2833	103,6667	107	99%	7.060,4579	33,5212	60,4579	26,9367	26,7975	33,6605	0,09	- 6,00
STROMSTAD	58,9500	11,1833	107	99%	7.315,6168	158,6428	315,6168	156,9740	134,9824	180,6344	0,18	- 24,16
CHURCHILL	58,7667	- 94,1833	107	99%	6.991,8224	25,1425	8,1776	33,3201	35,1204	43,2980	0,11	- 87,03
FREEPORT	28,9483	95,3083	107	99%	7.318,6729	20,3759	318,6729	298,2970	64,8155	383,4884	0,76	- 312,60
POINTATKINSON	49,3333	- 123,2500	107	99%	7.198,0841	1,0909	198,0841	196,9932	31,5461	229,6302	0,27	- 187,15
BELFAST	54,6000	- 5,9167	107	99%	7.110,1122	14,5538	110,1121	124,6660	51,9052	162,0174	0,31	- 142,48
PORTSANLUIS	35,1767	- 120,7600	107	99%	7.096,2617	64,2802	96,2617	160,5419	95,8949	192,1566	0,27	- 206,82
CROMER	52,9344	1,3016	107	99%	7.142,6355	46,9077	142,6355	95,7279	16,6047	126,0309	0,25	- 34,67
ZEEBRUGGE	51,3500	3,2000	107	99%	7.113,7850	9,8547	113,7850	103,9304	12,0575	125,8425	0,18	- 87,09
SOUTHEND	51,5145	0,7238	107	99%	7.222,3551	77,5996	222,3551	144,7555	48,0860	174,2691	0,23	- 61,09
MATSUYAMAI	33,8589	132,7122	107	99%	6.815,5421	88,0397	184,4579	96,4183	45,2832	139,1748	0,39	- 64,50
FORCADOS	5,3500	5,3500	107	99%	6.997,7196	86,5786	2,2804	88,8589	119,6457	121,9261	0,24	- 165,88

SANNIKOVA(SANNIKOVAPROLIV)	74,6667	138,9000	107	99%	7.161,7009	42,8495	161,7009	118,8514	12,2764	149,4245	0,22	- 66,56
KOZUSIMA	34,2092	139,1317	107	99%	7.054,9626	8,4585	54,9626	63,4211	25,0123	79,9749	0,14	- 63,34
SANDOWNPIER	50,6511	1,1532	106	98%	7.259,2170	212,0338	259,2170	47,1832	170,6595	88,5575	0,37	149,52
N.SPIT,HUMBOLDTBAY	40,7667	124,2167	106	98%	7.113,3208	72,7867	113,3208	40,5341	23,4588	89,8620	0,34	18,10
NEWYORK(THEBATTERY)	40,7000	74,0133	106	98%	7.125,6509	21,1489	125,6509	146,7998	37,1963	162,8472	0,12	- 143,91
RECIFE	8,0500	34,8667	106	98%	7.262,4717	103,8713	262,4717	158,6004	70,3127	192,1590	0,27	- 36,41
LOSANGELES	33,7200	118,2717	106	98%	7.277,2358	123,8782	277,2358	153,3577	97,8405	179,3953	0,20	- 7,61
LAPALMA	28,6778	17,7680	106	98%	6.569,3019	173,0112	430,6981	257,6869	33,1688	397,5293	1,03	118,23
UBLI	42,7500	16,8333	106	98%	7.117,2453	87,2978	117,2453	29,9475	32,3420	84,9033	0,30	39,17
HAKODATEII	41,7667	140,7167	106	98%	6.997,9340	54,5762	2,0660	56,6422	73,7863	75,8523	0,11	105,93
FEDOROVA(CHELUSKINMYS)	77,7167	104,3000	106	98%	7.135,7736	4,1619	135,7736	131,6117	19,9474	155,7210	0,17	- 80,26
SOUTHSOUND	19,2667	81,3833	106	98%	7.147,5849	79,2649	147,5849	68,3200	56,3393	91,2456	0,18	16,94
PORTGILES	35,0218	137,7683	106	98%	7.030,8019	91,4866	30,8019	60,6847	113,6597	82,8578	0,16	145,73
SEMBAWANG	1,4667	103,8333	105	97%	7.174,9524	90,4399	174,9524	84,5125	68,5196	106,4328	0,18	12,58
KOCHIII	33,4992	133,5692	105	97%	6.691,5238	86,7137	308,4762	221,7625	10,1874	318,6636	0,82	187,46
JACKSONVILLE	30,3500	81,6167	105	97%	7.214,4476	80,9047	214,4476	133,5429	46,3973	168,0503	0,26	- 33,12
EDITHBURG	35,0833	137,7500	105	97%	7.237,3238	61,1065	237,3238	176,2173	19,0378	218,2861	0,34	- 116,33
SHALAUROVA(SHALAUROVAMYS)	73,1833	143,2333	105	97%	7.138,4095	32,2971	138,4095	106,1124	5,4903	132,9192	0,20	- 63,70
FUKUE	32,6961	128,8494	105	97%	7.149,1238	92,3630	149,1238	56,7608	52,8427	96,2811	0,36	15,98
ONSLow	21,6497	115,1315	104	96%	7.112,2404	9,7430	112,2404	102,4974	23,4126	135,6530	0,26	- 77,42
COLONIA	34,4833	57,8500	104	96%	7.170,4038	33,3955	170,4038	137,0084	2,9608	167,4430	0,28	- 125,69
MIAMIBEACH	25,7683	80,1317	103	95%	7.183,4563	34,5770	183,4563	148,8793	9,1061	174,3502	0,20	- 80,78
SEJINGKAT	1,5828	110,4222	103	95%	6.461,6214	453,3180	538,3786	85,0607	389,3209	149,0578	0,69	247,41
HARWICH	51,9480	1,2921	103	95%	7.137,5825	61,0541	137,5825	76,5284	30,5038	107,0787	0,14	- 0,52
PAPEETE-B,FAREUTEPOINT,SOC.IS.	17,5331	149,5727	103	95%	7.122,2524	59,6036	122,2524	62,6488	19,2705	141,5229	0,59	- 36,59
UBIN	1,4194	103,9278	103	95%	6.318,9903	673,3857	681,0097	7,6240	669,5733	11,4364	0,02	- 678,69
ROOMPOTBUITEN	51,6197	3,6819	102	94%	7.066,3922	17,7508	66,3922	84,1429	47,4527	113,8448	0,25	- 100,46

WHANGAREIHARBOUR(MARSDENPOINT)	- 35,7574	174,3500	101	94%	7.113,5248	38,5022	113,5248	75,0226	19,0040	94,5207	0,15	- 20,53
CILACAPB	- 7,7517	109,0167	100	93%	7.165,4100	116,6972	165,4100	48,7128	93,7312	71,6788	0,17	73,34
LALIBERTADII	- 2,2000	80,9167	100	93%	7.084,9600	47,3294	84,9600	37,6306	0,7395	85,6995	0,33	- 5,29
KUNGSVIK	58,9967	11,1272	97	90%	7.093,8247	35,8861	93,8247	57,9387	12,2470	81,5777	0,19	- 16,02
PUERTOPLATA	19,8167	70,7000	97	90%	7.277,7732	99,9046	277,7732	177,8686	59,6201	218,1531	0,32	- 56,90
MATARANIB	- 17,0017	72,1083	96	89%	7.141,7083	67,1188	141,7083	74,5896	10,3566	131,3517	0,48	- 41,43
TRAVEMUNDE	53,9581	10,8722	96	89%	7.114,3542	10,2282	114,3542	104,1260	3,8421	118,1963	0,10	- 92,94
PUERTOSBERANIA	- 62,4833	59,6333	96	89%	7.106,4375	34,6765	106,4375	71,7610	3,6467	110,0842	0,31	- 64,43
PORTALBERNI	49,2333	124,8167	96	89%	6.737,3438	93,8986	262,6563	168,7576	51,6750	210,9812	0,38	- 100,93
GRINDSTONE	47,3833	61,8667	96	89%	7.250,1458	116,2185	250,1458	133,9273	72,2198	177,9261	0,42	- 37,54
PADANGB	- 0,9967	100,3750	96	89%	7.314,8021	173,4076	314,8021	141,3945	65,5953	249,2068	0,95	- 31,88
RUSSARO	59,7667	22,9500	96	89%	7.007,2083	113,3068	7,2083	120,5152	128,0839	135,2922	0,12	- 223,10
POLYARNIY	69,2000	33,4833	96	89%	6.827,4583	146,4437	172,5417	26,0980	132,7138	39,8279	0,16	- 101,23
FORTPHRACHULACHOMKLAO(POMPHRACHUN)	13,5500	100,5833	96	89%	7.042,8542	0,2699	42,8542	42,5843	18,2607	61,1149	0,16	- 30,91
SANFRANCISCO	37,8067	122,4650	96	89%	7.101,5000	27,5657	101,5000	129,0657	42,1075	143,6075	0,12	- 149,62
LYOKKI	60,8500	21,1833	96	89%	6.961,4375	79,7041	38,5625	118,2666	97,6497	136,2122	0,19	- 236,14
LAUNION	13,3333	87,8167	96	89%	7.071,0938	34,3593	71,0938	36,7345	22,2575	48,8362	0,08	- 4,84
SETTLEMENTPOINTA	26,6833	78,9833	96	89%	7.026,7500	21,9487	26,7500	48,6987	42,4468	69,1968	0,15	- 64,48
INCEPOINT	- 10,5083	142,3100	96	89%	7.048,2292	0,8334	48,2292	47,3957	21,4419	69,6711	0,18	- 63,64
ALOTAU	- 10,3167	150,4500	96	89%	7.054,6042	5,9997	54,6042	60,6039	31,2686	85,8728	0,20	- 69,75
DENHELDER	52,9644	4,7450	96	89%	6.944,6563	190,9803	55,3438	135,6366	209,0144	153,6707	0,12	- 304,32
MELILLA	35,2906	2,9285	96	89%	6.422,9479	395,5011	577,0521	181,5509	265,0304	312,0217	1,23	- 60,08
APIAB	- 13,8268	171,7613	96	89%	7.194,4792	59,1003	194,4792	135,3789	0,2378	194,7169	0,49	- 87,90
SHIRAHAMA	33,6836	135,3753	96	89%	7.073,4479	6,0440	73,4479	67,4039	14,9069	88,3548	0,16	- 54,65
KOSICHANG	13,1500	100,8167	96	89%	6.948,6354	22,3462	51,3646	29,0184	14,5175	36,8471	0,08	- 19,92
BOUCAU	43,5273	1,5148	96	89%	6.824,3854	44,3151	175,6146	131,2994	14,8297	190,4442	0,52	- 113,92
TANJUNGSEDI	1,9317	104,1150	96	89%	6.869,3854	121,9697	130,6146	8,6449	114,1327	16,4819	0,08	- 96,05
LLANDUDNO	53,3317	3,8252	96	89%	7.104,8333	72,9015	104,8333	31,9318	46,7743	58,0590	0,20	- 20,36

WINTERHARBOUR	50,5167	- 128,0333	96	89%	7.083,0833	1,1158	83,0833	81,9676	- 35,2808	118,3642	0,29	- 88,91
ALERTBAY	50,5833	- 126,9500	96	89%	7.058,5625	30,1488	58,5625	88,7113	54,1233	112,6858	0,22	- 142,79
NEWPORT	41,5050	- 71,3267	96	89%	6.839,8438	14,5531	160,1563	145,6031	17,4612	177,6174	0,30	- 158,52
KAGOSHIMAI	31,6000	- 130,5667	96	89%	7.068,7500	3,2659	68,7500	65,4841	9,8294	78,5794	0,09	- 33,11
OWASE	34,0764	- 136,2072	96	89%	6.881,2083	57,7988	118,7917	60,9929	43,7952	74,9964	0,08	- 28,31
CULEBRA	18,3017	- 65,3033	96	89%	7.176,1875	122,7375	176,1875	53,4500	100,3820	75,8055	0,21	- 67,90
UTO	59,7833	- 21,3667	96	89%	6.955,3646	199,2256	44,6354	154,5902	218,3892	173,7538	0,15	- 334,40
WESTPORTHARBOUR	- 41,7456	- 171,5947	96	89%	6.909,1146	125,0293	90,8854	34,1439	129,6814	38,7960	0,05	- 104,02
PALMADEMALLORCA2	39,5602	- 2,6375	96	89%	7.020,2917	17,5393	20,2917	37,8309	37,2673	57,5590	0,18	- 66,22
SWANAGEPIER	50,6093	- 1,9492	96	89%	7.059,8333	19,9715	59,8333	39,8618	2,8637	56,9696	0,16	- 18,10
LEWES(BREAKWATERHARBOR)	38,7817	- 75,1200	96	89%	6.773,3333	39,8590	226,6667	266,5257	91,2497	317,9163	0,47	- 348,88
WARNEMUNDE2	54,1697	- 12,1033	96	89%	6.952,6979	189,2778	47,3021	141,9757	206,0116	158,7095	0,14	- 332,40
RESOLUTE	74,6833	- 94,8833	96	89%	7.130,7500	63,5222	130,7500	67,2278	42,7632	87,9868	0,20	- 10,77
RAROTONGAB	- 21,2048	- 159,7848	96	89%	7.021,1042	18,8379	21,1042	2,2663	23,8083	2,7041	0,00	- 17,75
DUNEDIN	- 45,8787	- 170,5134	96	89%	7.100,0208	39,3965	100,0208	60,6244	30,9018	69,1190	0,09	- 15,34
KAVIENG	- 2,5833	- 150,8000	96	89%	7.043,5625	21,6985	43,5625	65,2610	44,9438	88,5063	0,16	- 74,05
HANSTHOLM	57,1189	- 8,5956	96	89%	6.995,2917	25,6002	4,7083	30,3085	31,8565	36,5648	0,07	- 56,23
SANJUAN	18,4583	- 66,1150	96	89%	7.005,4688	22,1087	5,4688	16,6400	15,9866	10,5178	0,06	- 2,45
MIYAKOII	39,6431	- 141,9753	96	89%	6.964,5208	33,7946	35,4792	1,6846	28,8521	6,6271	0,04	- 19,59
NOME,ALASKA	64,5000	- 165,4300	96	89%	7.084,2396	- 3,3433	84,2396	87,5828	36,0261	120,2657	0,25	- 80,53
GETING	6,2264	- 102,1067	96	89%	7.137,5208	71,3666	137,5208	66,1542	46,5937	90,9271	0,18	- 13,02
MAKAR,GENERALSANTOSCITY	6,1000	- 125,1500	96	89%	6.977,8229	46,0370	22,1771	23,8600	53,5917	31,4146	0,02	- 50,26
WEIPA	- 12,6667	- 141,8667	96	89%	7.169,7917	43,7500	169,7917	126,0417	10,4724	159,3193	0,27	- 54,35
RATMANOVA	65,8500	- 169,1333	96	89%	7.452,5625	31,8558	452,5625	484,4183	164,2059	616,7684	1,19	- 594,35
LIVERPOOLGEORGESANDPRINCESPIERS	53,4000	- 3,0000	96	89%	7.053,6979	81,4750	53,6979	135,1729	98,7247	152,4226	0,13	- 205,78
NICE	43,6956	- 7,2855	96	89%	7.091,8750	77,8363	91,8750	14,0387	71,7124	20,1626	0,05	- 61,24
SKANOR	55,4167	- 12,8294	96	89%	7.031,2083	6,5569	31,2083	24,6514	9,3535	40,5618	0,11	- 22,10

PIRAMIDE	-	-	96	89%	7,098,7500	4,6612	98,7500	94,0888	-	37,6020	136,3520	0,37	-	144,83
DIEGOGARCIAD	7,2900	72,3933	96	89%	7,063,3333	76,1776	63,3333	12,8443	69,0699	5,7366	0,14	44,19	-	-
GANDIA	38,9952	0,1514	96	89%	6,999,5313	18,1143	0,4688	18,5831	5,9442	6,4130	0,07	2,23	-	-
SPLIT-GRADSKALUKA	43,5067	16,4417	96	89%	6,689,0938	18,5534	310,9063	292,3529	46,8853	357,7916	0,55	302,03	-	-
REPOSAARI	61,6167	21,4500	96	89%	6,923,2292	14,7318	76,7708	62,0391	5,4769	71,2940	0,09	56,61	-	-
SCOTTBASE	77,8501	166,7690	96	89%	7,064,7292	74,4706	64,7292	9,7414	71,7131	6,9840	0,06	58,94	-	-
BARMOUTH	52,7193	4,0450	96	89%	7,123,9583	83,8704	123,9583	40,0880	61,7391	62,2192	0,17	32,22	-	-
EASTLONDON	33,0272	27,9317	96	89%	6,940,6042	99,5676	59,3958	40,1717	115,4249	56,0290	0,17	130,86	-	-
BALBOA	8,9667	79,5667	96	89%	6,858,7917	122,6323	141,2083	18,5760	100,4104	40,7980	0,04	95,10	-	-
MUSCAT	23,6333	58,5667	96	89%	7,091,3125	6,1672	91,3125	97,4797	42,2147	133,5272	0,31	106,33	-	-
CIVITAVECCHIA	42,0500	11,8167	96	89%	6,594,9792	33,3066	405,0208	438,3275	104,8591	509,8800	0,64	522,84	-	-
POINTSAPIN	46,9667	64,8333	96	89%	7,073,5625	7,4371	73,5625	66,1254	14,4537	88,0162	0,19	60,95	-	-
NORTHSALAMINOS	37,9796	23,5417	96	89%	7,113,8229	41,2663	113,8229	72,5566	14,6763	99,1466	0,19	20,91	-	-
YKSPIHLAJA	63,8333	23,0333	96	89%	7,054,2188	36,0399	54,2188	18,1789	34,3302	19,8885	0,00	34,33	-	-
HARLINGEN	53,1756	5,4094	96	89%	6,968,8542	204,7119	31,1458	173,5660	227,9321	196,7862	0,20	390,40	-	-
TAJIRI	35,5936	134,3158	96	89%	7,052,9375	16,8887	52,9375	69,8262	39,8900	92,8275	0,15	70,78	-	-
VILLASANJURJO	35,2500	3,9167	96	89%	7,084,4792	75,3740	84,4792	159,8531	113,8925	198,3717	0,32	245,31	-	-
YARMOUTH	43,8333	66,1333	96	89%	7,099,5833	26,2048	99,5833	73,3786	2,2018	101,7852	0,27	41,53	-	-
POINTLARUE	4,6667	55,5333	96	89%	7,092,6875	56,7482	92,6875	35,9393	57,4976	35,1899	0,06	74,95	-	-
EASTERISLAND-D	27,1500	109,4500	96	89%	6,826,1979	130,1814	173,8021	43,6207	112,0042	61,7978	0,11	92,02	-	-
BARSEBACK	55,7564	12,9033	96	89%	7,107,6354	43,9485	107,6354	63,6869	4,2420	103,3935	0,33	42,53	-	-
RIMOUSKI	48,4833	68,5167	96	89%	7,145,6250	62,2841	145,6250	83,3409	35,3447	110,2803	0,20	1,48	-	-
PORTSAID	31,2500	32,3000	96	89%	6,669,4167	11,9517	330,5833	318,6316	52,3635	382,9468	0,59	360,52	-	-
MAKURAZAKII	31,2667	130,3000	96	89%	7,169,6563	72,0240	169,6563	97,6323	41,7875	127,8687	0,20	2,49	-	-
DEAL	51,2238	1,4092	96	89%	7,006,2813	23,9389	6,2813	30,2202	44,5632	50,8445	0,19	59,06	-	-
CAPAUXMEULES	47,3789	61,8573	96	89%	7,016,0833	48,5767	16,0833	32,4934	65,8053	49,7220	0,12	88,52	-	-
LEAVA	14,2960	178,1602	96	89%	7,019,5938	29,9019	19,5938	49,4957	58,0715	77,6653	0,28	89,68	-	-
ABASHIRI	44,0194	144,2858	96	89%	7,038,0521	1,0148	38,0521	37,0373	16,0809	54,1330	0,12	42,74	-	-
SANDNESSJOEN	66,0167	12,6333	96	89%	7,588,9688	414,3155	588,9688	174,6533	356,1623	232,8065	0,48	235,66	-	-

ESASHI	41,8667	140,1333	96	89%	7.077,9271	3,6850	77,9271	74,2420	-	21,6677	99,5948	0,19	-	57,76
LANAISLAND,KAUMALAPAU	20,7800	156,9000	96	89%	6.989,4896	12,5431	10,5104	23,0535	31,6440	42,1544	0,19	58,30	-	-
BEACHPORT	-	37,5000	96	89%	6.978,6563	105,6639	21,3438	84,3201	126,9134	105,5697	0,09	148,78	-	-
PORTMACQUARIE	-	31,4268	96	89%	7.083,4896	57,7890	83,4896	25,7006	34,9683	48,5213	0,20	11,96	-	-
VENEZIA(ARSENALE)	45,4167	12,3500	96	89%	6.891,4688	43,8542	108,5313	152,3854	62,4674	170,9986	0,20	201,27	-	-
HONNGU	18,8000	105,7667	96	89%	7.117,7083	29,8102	117,7083	87,8981	1,6705	116,0378	0,19	45,66	-	-
LIEPAJA	56,5333	20,9833	96	89%	6.957,3125	156,4064	42,6875	113,7189	171,5608	128,8733	0,12	271,00	-	-
RUSSKII(RUSSKIIOSTROV)	77,1667	96,4333	96	89%	7.114,3125	30,0184	114,3125	144,3309	66,7106	181,0231	0,30	147,99	-	-
SASEBOII	33,1581	129,7239	96	89%	7.043,5521	30,4948	43,5521	74,0469	55,4788	99,0309	0,19	96,89	-	-
VIKEN	56,1422	12,5792	96	89%	7.272,5000	121,9416	272,5000	150,5584	44,2234	228,2766	0,67	54,02	-	-
YOSIOKA	41,4500	140,2500	96	89%	6.913,2500	76,3437	86,7500	10,4063	68,4746	18,2754	0,10	44,06	-	-
LASPALMASD	28,1406	15,4118	96	89%	6.995,0938	20,5224	4,9063	15,6162	23,8003	18,8940	0,00	21,80	-	-
SURSARI	60,0833	26,9833	96	89%	7.139,2917	80,0170	139,2917	59,2747	74,1627	65,1289	0,04	55,31	-	-
WANDO	34,3153	126,7597	96	89%	7.055,7708	61,7030	55,7708	5,9321	68,2415	12,4706	0,04	74,43	-	-
NORFOLKISLAND	-	29,0583	96	89%	7.062,5000	2,0003	62,5000	60,4997	13,8268	76,3268	0,13	52,79	-	-
HALIFAX	44,6667	63,5833	96	89%	6.817,3125	25,0365	182,6875	207,7240	58,2221	240,9096	0,31	269,84	-	-
VALDEZ	61,1250	146,3617	96	89%	7.008,2917	35,8114	8,2917	44,1030	53,2992	61,5908	0,14	85,35	-	-
SIBONEY	23,1000	82,4667	96	89%	7.057,6667	33,6319	57,6667	24,0347	31,0682	26,5985	0,01	31,03	-	-
SUCURAJ	43,1333	17,2000	96	89%	7.016,5625	5,7433	16,5625	22,3058	10,4623	27,0248	0,01	9,19	-	-
MUSCATB	23,6283	58,5650	96	89%	7.101,6875	13,5358	101,6875	88,1517	40,3523	142,0398	0,45	90,00	-	-
MAASSLUIS	51,9175	4,2497	96	89%	7.150,8646	19,0090	150,8646	169,8736	38,9549	189,8195	0,18	204,90	-	-
TOKUYAMAI	34,0333	131,8000	96	89%	7.093,8750	7,2219	93,8750	86,6531	15,9317	109,8067	0,18	76,47	-	-
MARATHONSHORES	24,7333	81,0333	96	89%	6.945,6250	87,7249	54,3750	33,3499	128,7595	74,3845	0,26	140,04	-	-
CRISTOBAL	9,3500	79,9167	96	89%	7.064,2917	30,9005	64,2917	33,3912	23,1178	41,1739	0,01	27,93	-	-
ALCUDIA	39,8346	3,1390	96	89%	7.135,7500	67,7074	135,7500	68,0426	37,7264	98,0236	0,26	3,53	-	-
NEWCASTLEIII	-	32,9167	96	89%	6.668,2604	2,6119	331,7396	334,3515	71,9398	403,6794	0,66	409,81	-	-
BINTULU	3,2622	113,0639	96	89%	7.086,9271	46,6788	86,9271	40,2483	38,3415	48,5856	0,12	12,25	-	-
PORTMORESBYII	-	9,4833	96	89%	7.153,5313	47,8364	153,5313	105,6948	2,6151	150,9161	0,42	88,10	-	-
CASEY	-	66,2667	96	89%	6.840,5000	121,4951	159,5000	38,0049	110,9628	48,5372	0,12	85,97	-	-

CHOSHI-GYOKO	35,7444	140,8583	96	89%	7.466,6979	157,0326	466,6979	309,6653	168,3464	298,3515	-	0,02	163,97
FELIXSTOWE	51,9577	1,3466	96	89%	7.005,0417	53,7314	5,0417	48,6897	66,4335	61,3919	-	0,12	131,50
KAOSHIUNGII	22,5333	120,3167	96	89%	7.025,8646	31,9111	25,8646	57,7756	50,5975	76,4621	-	0,11	69,48
HELIGMAN	60,2000	19,3000	96	89%	7.010,5313	72,1774	10,5313	61,6461	83,6697	73,1384	-	0,15	166,47
VANCOUVER	49,2833	123,1167	96	89%	6.901,7917	139,3872	98,2083	41,1789	115,9601	17,7518	-	0,05	157,63
CHIMBOTE	9,0833	78,6333	96	89%	7.063,0938	24,9212	63,0938	88,0150	51,2934	114,3871	-	0,24	110,10
LORNE	38,5472	143,9888	96	89%	7.028,4063	16,4923	28,4063	11,9140	12,2665	16,1397	-	0,04	4,83
NAHA	26,2133	127,6653	96	89%	7.035,1979	20,1876	35,1979	15,0103	1,0302	36,2281	-	0,13	1,54
BENOAB	8,7467	115,2117	96	89%	6.999,3958	28,9024	0,6042	28,2982	42,8230	42,2188	-	0,13	61,43
SUVA-A	18,1357	178,4228	96	89%	7.065,9167	27,6872	65,9167	93,6039	52,0323	117,9490	-	0,20	101,34
BACKEVIK	58,3667	11,2500	96	89%	6.907,9271	284,1539	92,0729	376,2268	344,1389	436,2118	-	0,53	695,14
SYDNEY,FORTDENISON	33,8500	151,2333	96	89%	6.947,8542	164,0851	52,1458	111,9393	181,3063	129,1605	-	0,14	281,70
KOLUCHIN	67,4833	174,6500	96	89%	7.012,6563	82,9202	12,6563	95,5764	108,1942	120,8505	-	0,20	178,96
TILBURY	51,4667	0,3667	96	89%	6.984,5104	94,6038	15,4896	79,1142	109,2782	93,7886	-	0,10	153,11
ST.MARYS	49,9179	6,3172	96	89%	7.076,1771	2,5069	76,1771	78,6839	30,5313	106,7084	-	0,27	81,65
GANII	0,6833	73,1500	96	89%	7.085,2813	38,2338	85,2813	47,0475	16,4627	68,8186	-	0,19	20,39
PUERTOARMUELLES	8,2667	82,8667	96	89%	7.128,6563	33,3078	128,6563	95,3484	10,9193	117,7370	-	0,20	58,36
WIDO	35,6181	126,3019	96	89%	7.128,1354	74,7275	128,1354	53,4079	42,2413	85,8941	-	0,29	1,28
KOCHIII	33,5000	133,5833	96	89%	6.925,1667	145,4906	74,8333	70,6573	163,6823	88,8489	-	0,14	198,80
ONAHAMA	36,9375	140,8919	96	89%	7.016,9896	2,1524	16,9896	14,8371	4,4032	12,5864	-	0,01	4,21
DAUGAVGRIVA	57,0500	24,0333	96	89%	6.992,1250	135,3392	7,8750	127,4642	153,9379	146,0629	-	0,14	256,30
LAGOMERA	28,0878	17,1083	96	89%	7.147,5417	95,4898	147,5417	52,0518	76,3685	71,1732	-	0,11	64,42
MASIRAH	20,6833	58,8667	96	89%	7.094,4792	47,2429	94,4792	47,2362	29,8716	64,6076	-	0,12	13,01
MANUSISLAND	2,0167	147,2667	96	89%	7.121,4167	53,4556	121,4167	67,9610	24,8012	96,6154	-	0,25	27,06
OOSTENDE	51,2333	2,9167	96	89%	6.740,9583	7,2886	259,0417	251,7530	51,0161	310,0577	-	0,53	289,27
MARDEAJO	36,7000	56,6667	96	89%	7.263,0938	67,1989	263,0938	195,8948	57,5920	320,6858	-	0,60	132,33
GOLDCOASTSEAWAY2	27,9500	153,4167	96	89%	7.144,9688	53,1177	144,9688	91,8510	22,0656	122,9031	-	0,27	33,16
SANDYHOOK	40,4667	74,0083	96	89%	6.820,6250	19,5030	179,3750	159,8720	15,9597	195,3347	-	0,31	155,54
SIMRISHAMN	55,5575	14,3578	96	89%	7.099,7292	15,4580	99,7292	84,2712	27,7647	127,4938	-	0,37	82,85

WAVELAND,GULFOFMEX.,MS	30,2817	-	96	89%	7.302,6979	131,4879	302,6979	171,2100	54,9382	247,7597	0,66	-	62,95
PORT-ALFRED	48,3333	-	96	89%	7.105,5417	33,7035	105,5417	139,2451	83,0426	188,5843	0,41	-	177,41
RAFFLESLIGHTHOUSE	1,1667	103,7500	96	89%	6.769,4375	278,0494	230,5625	47,4869	275,0189	44,4564	0,07	-	304,08
SURIGAO	9,7833	125,5000	96	89%	7.014,6250	11,1467	14,6250	25,7717	14,2042	28,8292	0,07	-	30,09
GISBORNE	-	38,6755	96	89%	7.081,1563	2,9990	81,1563	78,1572	24,6013	105,7575	0,23	-	71,63
KATSUURA	35,1294	140,2494	96	89%	7.090,1250	41,0393	90,1250	49,0857	29,2738	60,8512	0,04	-	27,80
VILSANDI	58,3833	21,8167	96	89%	6.666,3125	46,2343	333,6875	287,4532	16,0080	349,6955	0,57	-	289,96
PRINCERUPERT	54,3167	-	96	89%	7.161,2188	3,7065	161,2188	157,5122	34,0061	195,2248	0,31	-	159,95
COX'SBAZAAR	21,4500	91,8333	96	89%	7.019,7917	-	80,0303	19,7917	99,8220	113,3716	0,28	-	175,30
ASTORIA(TONGUEPOINT)	46,2067	-	96	89%	7.119,7083	35,5654	119,7083	84,1429	33,7801	85,9282	0,12	-	36,10
BAYWAVELANDYACHTCLUB	30,3250	-	96	89%	7.009,3333	81,2430	9,3333	90,5763	121,0844	130,4178	0,33	-	185,90
BYKOVMY(SBYKOVMY)	72,0000	129,1167	96	89%	7.023,9167	21,1033	23,9167	2,8134	23,1996	0,7171	0,00	-	20,78
PORTPIRIE	-	33,1776	96	89%	6.993,0833	-	57,3609	6,9167	50,4442	68,0496	0,09	-	119,11
YSTAD	55,4167	13,8167	96	89%	6.693,4583	139,6712	306,5417	446,2128	205,7624	512,3040	0,58	-	607,75
KAPINGAMARANGI	1,1000	154,7833	96	89%	7.055,0000	4,0887	55,0000	50,9113	45,9568	100,9568	0,40	-	59,19
DAYTONABEACHSHORES	29,1467	-	96	89%	7.083,8125	18,4476	83,8125	65,3649	5,6778	78,1347	0,16	-	39,36
LUCINDA	-	18,5167	96	89%	7.167,1354	121,6855	167,1354	45,4499	82,4102	84,7252	0,35	-	48,10
DUNKERQUE	51,0481	2,3667	96	89%	7.079,9688	61,9581	79,9688	18,0106	58,2307	21,7380	0,03	-	48,06
RIOHACHA	11,5500	-	96	89%	7.290,7083	56,3790	290,7083	234,3294	23,2741	313,9824	0,74	-	261,60
OSKARSHAMN	57,2750	16,4781	96	89%	7.085,2813	23,2486	85,2813	62,0326	8,2151	93,4964	0,27	-	47,65
MOZAMBIQUEISLAND	-	15,0333	96	89%	7.033,7917	-	0,5329	33,7917	34,3246	18,3863	0,10	-	39,76
BOMBAY(PRINCESDOCK)	18,9500	72,8333	96	89%	7.115,1667	66,0258	115,1667	49,1409	52,4493	62,7173	0,12	-	14,29
WANGANUI	-	39,9446	96	89%	7.086,3750	37,5467	86,3750	48,8283	19,6423	66,7327	0,13	-	5,00
MALAGA	36,7127	-	96	89%	7.125,3021	81,9947	125,3021	43,3073	65,5805	59,7216	0,09	-	47,94
SANJOSE	13,9167	-	96	89%	6.943,0938	23,4303	56,9063	33,4760	9,5928	47,3135	0,13	-	28,54
SHEDIACBAY	46,2500	-	96	89%	7.085,7292	6,2001	85,7292	79,5291	17,8999	103,6291	0,20	-	67,23
AVEIRO	40,6500	-	96	89%	6.941,5521	132,5248	58,4479	74,0769	163,0275	104,5796	0,30	-	235,50
TOKYOIII	35,6486	139,7700	96	89%	6.948,4271	66,5342	51,5729	14,9612	73,2458	21,6729	0,02	-	72,59
TUAPSE	44,1000	39,0667	96	89%	7.038,8125	-	12,8769	38,8125	51,6894	19,2427	0,06	-	54,78

CABOSANLUCAS	22,8833	-	109,9000	96	89%	7,098,8854	35,3384	98,8854	63,5470	12,8758	86,0096	0,18	-	28,75
MANTYLUOTO	61,5944	21,4634		96	89%	7,149,4896	21,4215	149,4896	128,0681	20,9157	170,4053	0,32	-	95,88
MOURILYANHARBOUR	-	17,5833	146,0833	96	89%	7,085,7292	47,5135	85,7292	38,2156	31,2901	54,4390	0,12	-	9,54
VICTORIADOCK	1,2667	103,8500		96	89%	7,087,1979	53,7897	87,1979	33,4082	42,2590	44,9389	0,13	-	27,80
LOMBRUM	-	2,0421	147,3738	96	89%	7,136,3229	79,2255	136,3229	57,0974	58,6267	77,6962	0,17	-	27,59
SANTACRUZDETENERIFEI	28,4772	-	16,2412	95	88%	7,194,9368	74,7290	194,9368	120,2078	49,0065	145,9303	0,20	-	48,65
STORNOWAY	58,2078	-	6,3890	95	88%	7,155,1579	40,2943	155,1579	114,8636	11,1371	144,0208	0,22	-	58,82
CAMBRIDGEII	38,5733	-	76,0683	95	88%	6,981,0421	49,2311	18,9579	30,2732	58,5784	39,6205	0,11	-	89,66
SYDNEYPORTJACKSON	-	33,8255	151,2585	95	88%	7,132,6737	73,1078	132,6737	59,5659	24,7054	107,9683	0,41	-	17,11
LAMUB	-	2,2717	40,9033	95	88%	7,057,5368	17,6220	57,5368	39,9148	1,0577	58,5945	0,18	-	28,85
PORTAUGUSTA	-	32,5500	137,7833	95	88%	7,126,6421	90,3390	126,6421	36,3031	81,8422	44,7999	0,00	-	89,87
JAMESTOWNLANDINGSTEPS	-	15,9209	5,7180	95	88%	7,023,6316	19,9007	23,6316	3,7309	12,8362	10,7953	0,02	-	26,00
PORTHEDLAND	-	20,3176	118,5744	95	88%	7,556,8421	40,0684	556,8421	596,9105	135,5546	692,3967	0,65	-	502,70
ERDEK	40,3833	-	27,8500	95	88%	6,916,0211	74,2980	83,9789	9,6809	65,4691	18,5099	0,08	-	49,24
HERNEBAY	51,3820	-	1,1156	95	88%	7,122,2421	33,9876	122,2421	88,2545	2,9011	125,1432	0,31	-	40,37
SASEBOI	33,1667	-	129,7167	95	88%	7,065,8000	5,4351	65,8000	71,2351	24,4703	90,2703	0,10	-	50,67
PANAMACITY,ST.ANDREWSBAY,FL	30,1517	-	85,6667	95	88%	6,949,7895	121,2519	50,2105	71,0414	182,6567	132,4462	0,46	-	216,25
SAUMLAKI	-	7,9817	131,2900	95	88%	7,038,6947	24,9339	38,6947	13,7608	21,5966	17,0982	0,08	-	6,22
TRIBENI	22,9833	-	88,4000	95	88%	7,220,9895	94,6374	220,9895	126,3520	48,4894	172,5000	0,39	-	55,62
SAPPI	61,4833	-	21,3333	95	88%	7,106,0947	17,5586	106,0947	123,6533	35,7582	141,8529	0,09	-	58,10
PUERTODEHIERRO	10,6167	-	62,0833	95	88%	6,920,7789	35,0230	79,2211	44,1980	35,0413	44,1797	0,04	-	52,95
SANJOSEII	13,9167	-	90,8167	95	88%	7,023,1684	30,2692	23,1684	7,1008	12,7076	10,4608	0,01	-	31,55
SALERNO	40,6766	-	14,7508	95	88%	6,936,2632	84,9290	63,7368	21,1922	134,3217	70,5848	0,28	-	133,94
TIKSI(TIKSIBUKHTA)	71,5833	-	128,9167	95	88%	7,002,5158	33,3108	2,5158	35,8266	37,5325	40,0483	0,02	-	25,37
MANZANILLO	20,3333	-	77,1500	95	88%	7,151,1053	60,0599	151,1053	91,0454	22,0150	129,0903	0,32	-	35,15
NAGOYAI	35,0914	-	136,8808	95	88%	7,050,0105	29,1126	50,0105	20,8979	7,3506	42,6599	0,19	-	33,28
SOLENZARA	41,8569	-	9,4038	95	88%	7,151,7263	103,3812	151,7263	48,3451	81,3403	70,3860	0,19	-	55,59
SPLITRTMARJANA	43,5083	-	16,3917	95	88%	7,013,0105	17,7996	13,0105	30,8102	25,1987	38,2092	0,06	-	43,96

NEDRENYKOPING	58,7500	17,0167	95	88%	6.958,7684	-	64,0817	41,2316	22,8501	-	66,3037	25,0721	-	0,02	-	55,70
SANTIAGODECUBA	20,0205	75,8367	95	88%	7.073,6421	20,5020	73,6421	53,1401	0,1204	73,5218	0,14	16,44	-	-	-	-
AKKO	32,9193	35,0702	95	88%	7.150,1158	86,1892	150,1158	63,9266	50,2273	99,8885	0,28	15,16	-	-	-	-
PORTOEMPEDOCLE,SICILY	37,2858	13,5268	95	88%	6.998,8421	29,9467	1,1579	28,7888	-	39,0881	0,06	46,59	-	-	-	-
ZADAR	44,1233	15,2350	95	88%	7.024,7053	33,4699	24,7053	58,1752	-	60,4535	0,18	86,71	-	-	-	-
GEIBERGA(GEIBERGAOSTROV)	77,6000	101,5167	95	88%	7.128,9474	97,6052	128,9474	31,3422	81,4010	47,5463	0,13	64,07	-	-	-	-
MARIIPRONCHISHEVOI(BUKHTA)	75,5333	113,4333	95	88%	6.888,7474	-	152,0275	111,2526	40,7749	-	167,8788	56,6262	0,17	-	-	229,62
BREST	48,3829	4,4948	95	88%	7.143,8737	5,2862	143,8737	149,1599	-	18,5896	0,08	107,84	-	-	-	-
KERGUELEN	-	49,3515	94	87%	7.009,1064	-	97,2740	9,1064	106,3803	135,2883	0,37	206,75	-	-	-	-
GDYNIA	54,5333	18,5500	94	87%	7.461,8298	290,5535	461,8298	171,2763	258,0700	203,7598	0,18	187,58	-	-	-	-
KRASNOFLOTSKIE(KRASNOFLOTSKIEOSTROVA)	78,6000	98,8333	94	87%	7.235,7128	7,6819	235,7128	228,0308	-	57,0748	0,49	202,79	-	-	-	-
FORTMYERS	26,6467	-	94	87%	7.082,5106	55,3543	82,5106	27,1563	47,9991	34,5115	0,05	35,58	-	-	-	-
SUVA-B	-	18,1325	94	87%	7.056,5319	43,0766	56,5319	13,4553	27,8124	28,7195	0,10	21,04	-	-	-	-
RINGHALS	57,2497	12,1125	94	87%	7.014,6277	25,4440	14,6277	40,0717	-	57,3642	0,28	99,82	-	-	-	-
KEYWEST	24,5550	81,8067	94	87%	6.566,4894	469,9566	433,5106	36,4459	459,4986	25,9880	0,01	480,42	-	-	-	-
PREOBRAZHENIA(PREOBRAZHENIAOSTROV)	74,6667	112,9333	94	87%	7.085,8298	-	45,0223	85,8298	130,8521	-	77,4888	163,3186	0,31	-	-	187,71
CHITTAGONGA	22,2467	91,8250	94	87%	7.082,0106	10,8358	82,0106	71,1748	-	11,4215	0,25	54,66	-	-	-	-
ACAPULCO	16,8333	99,9167	94	87%	6.997,9255	16,7585	2,0745	18,8330	23,8946	25,9690	0,09	57,19	-	-	-	-
UDDEVALLA	58,3475	11,8947	94	87%	7.031,9468	4,7822	31,9468	36,7290	41,3811	73,3279	0,33	59,67	-	-	-	-
TAN-NOWA	34,3389	135,1781	94	87%	7.025,7021	21,6423	25,7021	47,3444	-	32,5125	0,08	57,49	-	-	-	-
PALINURO	40,0299	15,2753	94	87%	7.165,9894	108,3023	165,9894	57,6871	84,0510	81,9384	0,22	49,09	-	-	-	-
KINGBAY	-	20,6236	94	87%	7.150,7447	36,6968	150,7447	114,0479	-	15,3026	0,43	105,40	-	-	-	-
PORTVENDRES	42,5201	3,1073	94	87%	7.205,8617	90,0724	205,8617	115,7893	45,6365	160,2252	0,38	35,56	-	-	-	-
VERAVAL	20,9000	70,3667	94	87%	7.114,2766	46,6577	114,2766	67,6189	26,1030	88,1736	0,20	7,97	-	-	-	-
REYKJAVIK	64,1506	-	94	87%	7.125,3511	64,6300	125,3511	60,7210	50,5169	74,8341	0,10	17,06	-	-	-	-
OURA	32,9767	130,2206	94	87%	7.143,7872	42,5522	143,7872	101,2351	24,5130	119,2743	0,13	8,08	-	-	-	-

LIMHAMN	55,5833	12,9333	94	87%	7.006,4681	-	39,4442	6,4681	45,9123	-	59,9378	66,4059	0,16	-	90,93
QIKIQTARJUAQ	67,8667	64,1167	94	87%	7.026,5106	1,1430	26,5106	25,3676	24,2774	50,7880	0,32	37,79			
BARHARBOR,FRENCHMANBAY,ME	44,3917	68,2050	93	86%	7.012,8387	-	12,0535	12,8387	24,8922	-	14,5033	27,3420	0,01	-	14,71
TENERIFE	28,4772	16,2411	93	86%	7.071,7097	37,4178	71,7097	34,2919	22,8689	48,8408	0,08	11,45			
PORTOGRANDE(ST.VINCENT)2	16,8833	25,0000	93	86%	7.132,6882	39,7006	132,6882	92,9876	-	9,2103	141,8984	0,36	-	70,86	
SEOGWIPO	33,2400	126,5617	93	86%	7.112,2796	52,7491	112,2796	59,5305	25,7426	86,5370	0,23	-	21,90		
KIPTOPEKEBEACH	37,1650	75,9883	93	86%	7.078,7527	50,5139	78,7527	28,2388	45,1037	33,6490	0,02	59,12			
LORDHOWEISLAND	31,5167	159,0667	93	86%	7.160,4301	3,4436	160,4301	156,9865	47,8456	208,2757	0,35	143,41			
NEWHAVEN	50,7818	0,0570	93	86%	7.130,6452	13,4186	130,6452	117,2265	-	28,8553	159,5005	0,37	-	108,08	
PATRICIABAY	48,6500	123,4500	93	86%	7.120,4194	47,1550	120,4194	73,2644	29,9362	90,4832	0,10	9,42			
GUIRIA	10,5667	62,2833	93	86%	7.107,2043	18,3322	107,2043	88,8721	-	14,2445	121,4488	0,36	-	118,40	
AMBARCHIK	69,6167	162,3000	93	86%	7.035,3763	4,9121	35,3763	40,2884	13,3986	48,7749	0,09	48,48			
NIKISKI,ALASKA	60,6833	151,3967	93	86%	7.087,7312	7,1666	87,7312	80,5646	-	12,1604	99,8915	0,16	-	48,70	
KEYCOLONYBEACH	24,7183	81,0167	93	86%	7.076,6559	59,2268	76,6559	17,4291	56,3049	20,3510	0,03	47,59			
CHERRYPOINT	48,8633	122,7567	92	85%	7.122,9239	75,0168	122,9239	47,9071	58,3738	64,5501	0,11	39,67			
TERIBERKA	69,2000	35,1167	92	85%	7.096,7174	32,5358	96,7174	64,1816	6,2472	90,4702	0,21	28,78			
NUKUHIVA	8,9333	140,0833	92	85%	7.001,6413	50,5965	1,6413	52,2378	-	67,3468	68,9881	0,12	-	89,36	
PENSACOLA	30,4033	87,2100	92	85%	7.258,9457	188,0171	258,9457	70,9286	158,7245	100,2211	0,18	131,88			
NY-ALESUND	78,9285	11,9380	92	85%	7.060,2500	9,2267	60,2500	51,0233	-	3,7894	64,0394	0,13	-	39,54	
MANZANILLO	19,0500	104,3333	92	85%	7.172,5870	107,2452	172,5870	65,3418	96,4488	76,1382	0,18	29,80			
MAJURO-C	7,1060	171,3728	92	85%	7.029,0761	7,8205	29,0761	36,8966	-	23,9892	53,0653	0,06	-	26,70	
INVERGORDON	57,6833	4,1667	92	85%	7.053,8043	26,0086	53,8043	27,7957	3,3288	57,1331	0,21	59,59			
JEJU	33,5275	126,5431	92	85%	7.158,6630	95,0883	158,6630	63,5748	74,6415	84,0215	0,13	45,61			
AUCKLANDII	36,8431	174,7695	92	85%	6.581,2174	521,9342	418,7826	103,1516	-	541,0624	122,2798	0,13	-	612,92	
TOKEPOINT,WILLIPABAY,WA	46,7067	123,9667	92	85%	7.163,8696	47,7550	163,8696	116,1146	6,9801	156,8894	0,31	62,31			
BUGRINO	68,8000	49,3333	92	85%	7.032,5000	18,7588	32,5000	51,2588	-	42,0458	74,5458	0,17	-	68,02	
IBIZA	38,9112	1,4498	91	84%	7.095,5165	6,7578	95,5165	102,2743	-	46,3180	141,8345	0,29	-	90,49	
DALHOUSIE	48,0667	66,3833	91	84%	6.962,1099	75,7818	37,8901	37,8917	-	118,1387	80,2486	0,37	-	136,06	

PORTORFORD	42,7383	-	91	84%	6.973,9560	-	26,0440	83,8282	-	112,0609	0,22	-
		124,4983				109,8721			138,1049			178,42
FUNAFUTIB	-	179,1952	91	84%	7.083,5604	51,7299	83,5604	31,8305	30,8276	52,7328	0,14	8,71
	8,5025											
GARIBALDI	45,5533	123,9183	91	84%	7.079,3407	24,2468	79,3407	103,5875	48,7277	128,0684	0,13	70,94
PORTROYAL	17,9333	76,8500	91	84%	6.925,1868	0,1654	74,8132	74,9785	23,6040	98,4172	0,21	89,19
SHOALBAY	-	152,1757	91	84%	7.091,0769	52,1126	91,0769	38,9644	24,6320	66,4449	0,23	0,30
	32,7197											
MONBETUI	44,3500	143,3667	91	84%	7.018,2747	12,5512	18,2747	30,8259	47,3526	65,6273	0,29	60,68
PORTOTORRES	40,8422	8,4039	91	84%	6.974,9670	56,7981	25,0330	31,7651	67,0311	41,9981	0,05	70,76
MALYITAIMYR(MALYITAIMYROSTROV)	78,0833	106,8167	90	83%	6.871,8889	189,9452	128,1111	318,0563	276,2438	404,3549	0,75	543,83
DUBLAT(SAUGORIS.)	21,6333	88,1333	90	83%	7.112,4444	376,0757	112,4444	488,5201	439,4656	551,9100	0,56	858,88
NORTHSOUND	19,3000	81,3167	90	83%	7.127,5222	89,9747	127,5222	37,5475	76,2758	51,2464	0,11	52,02
SAGUNTO	39,6339	0,2062	90	83%	7.141,1444	99,9074	141,1444	41,2371	65,8021	75,3424	0,40	10,77
STLAWRENCE	46,9168	55,3901	90	83%	7.122,4778	46,3199	122,4778	76,1579	14,8755	107,6023	0,31	22,17
ANCHORAGE	61,2383	149,8900	90	83%	7.092,2556	69,5067	92,2556	22,7488	59,0130	33,2426	0,06	45,84
SEWARD	60,1200	149,4267	90	83%	7.144,6556	43,4788	144,6556	101,1768	24,7557	119,8999	0,15	49,57
ZHELANIAI(ZHELANIAMYS)	76,9500	68,5500	90	83%	7.018,6111	60,9192	18,6111	79,5304	80,6660	99,2771	0,16	134,88
MANGALORE(PANAMBURU)	12,9167	74,8000	90	83%	7.143,6000	16,5689	143,6000	127,0311	18,6879	162,2879	0,27	74,19
TWEEDENTRANCESOUTH	-	153,5512	89	82%	7.070,8090	47,9367	70,8090	22,8723	32,5758	38,2332	0,17	17,88
	28,1706											
VILLAGARCIA	42,6007	8,7700	88	81%	7.027,7500	36,0975	27,7500	8,3475	32,3502	4,6002	0,01	39,93
GWANGYANG	34,9036	127,7547	88	81%	7.115,7727	79,4605	115,7727	36,3122	55,1545	60,6183	0,17	39,24
USTKARA	69,2500	64,5167	88	81%	7.113,1818	64,5138	113,1818	177,6956	94,7283	207,9101	0,27	241,13
KLAIPEDA	55,7000	21,1333	88	81%	7.030,4432	75,2904	30,4432	105,7336	93,3912	123,8344	0,15	187,22
PUERTOLIMON	10,0000	83,0333	87	81%	7.087,4253	3,5907	87,4253	91,0160	30,2167	117,6420	0,22	84,64
WAKKANAI	45,4078	141,6853	87	81%	7.003,3448	15,7675	3,3448	19,1124	21,1349	24,4798	0,00	16,60
HILO,HAWAIIISLAND	19,7300	155,0550	87	81%	7.144,9310	27,5667	144,9310	117,3644	5,3206	139,6104	0,13	54,52
NAGOYA	35,0833	136,8833	87	81%	7.143,7126	99,4624	143,7126	243,1751	110,6944	254,4070	0,04	115,87
SANJOSE	12,3333	121,0833	86	80%	7.016,0233	16,8606	16,0233	32,8838	29,4013	45,4246	0,12	55,74
OKHA	22,4667	69,0833	86	80%	7.092,8953	46,3760	92,8953	46,5194	31,0102	61,8851	0,16	8,84
AJACCIO	41,9228	8,7629	85	79%	7.114,0118	54,2263	114,0118	59,7855	27,3927	86,6190	0,23	12,21

MUOSTAH(MUOSTAHOSTROV)	71,5500	130,0333	85	79%	7.002,0471	-	64,7112	2,0471	66,7583	-	83,9381	85,9851	0,19	-	150,56	
WHYALLA	-	33,0167	137,5667	85	79%	7.108,5294	53,5211	108,5294	55,0083	35,9524	72,5771	0,14	5,76	-	-	
BAHIADELOSANGELES	28,9667	-	113,5500	85	79%	7.048,5294	1,3487	48,5294	49,8782	-	35,3697	83,8991	0,27	-	53,88	
CORRAL	-	39,8667	73,4333	85	79%	7.113,1412	34,5648	113,1412	78,5763	7,2252	105,9159	0,20	-	43,51	-	
IRAKLION	35,3485	-	25,1527	85	79%	7.102,0941	26,2310	102,0941	75,8631	7,0210	95,0731	0,13	-	39,02	-	
MILNERBAY(GROOTEYLANDT)	-	13,8601	136,4156	84	78%	7.058,2738	15,9467	58,2738	42,3271	13,9214	44,3524	0,04	-	1,57	-	
TONOURA	34,9000	-	132,0667	84	78%	7.082,0476	23,7485	82,0476	58,2991	14,7644	67,2832	0,05	-	17,46	-	
NAOSISLAND2	8,9183	-	79,5333	84	78%	7.117,3690	79,1479	117,3690	38,2212	63,6925	53,6765	0,16	-	31,73	-	
MONTAUK	41,0483	-	71,9600	84	78%	7.160,0238	46,7148	160,0238	113,3090	26,6362	133,3876	0,17	-	43,33	-	
LAMADDALENA	41,2333	-	9,3667	84	78%	6.944,0238	37,1689	55,9762	18,8073	-	36,5155	19,4607	0,01	-	41,46	
SALVADOR	-	12,9667	38,5167	84	78%	7.071,0238	6,1056	71,0238	64,9183	-	12,7733	83,7972	0,14	-	63,84	
TUKIZI	35,6667	-	139,7667	84	78%	7.134,3214	74,6476	134,3214	59,6738	53,9254	80,3961	0,17	-	3,74	-	
PALERMO	38,1333	-	13,3333	84	78%	7.069,2857	73,5099	69,2857	4,2242	73,8511	4,5654	0,02	-	86,41	-	
CRESCENTCITY	41,7450	-	124,1817	84	78%	7.020,9762	52,8140	20,9762	73,7902	-	87,5552	108,5314	0,30	-	126,15	
SKURU	60,1000	-	23,5500	84	78%	7.075,9762	26,3550	75,9762	49,6212	17,6430	58,3332	0,07	-	23,36	-	
SLIPSHAVN	55,2883	-	10,8278	84	78%	7.123,7024	27,7411	123,7024	95,9613	13,8823	109,8200	0,10	-	52,97	-	
GRONSKAR	59,2833	-	19,0333	84	78%	7.034,0238	69,6294	34,0238	103,6532	-	82,2447	116,2685	0,10	-	151,08	
NEDREGAVLE	60,6833	-	17,1667	84	78%	7.097,7738	26,8427	97,7738	70,9311	14,9884	82,7854	0,09	-	43,55	-	
LUSI	32,1333	-	121,6167	84	78%	7.107,8452	57,5740	107,8452	50,2712	38,1695	69,6758	0,16	-	6,44	-	
TRIESTE	45,6474	-	13,7585	84	78%	7.071,1310	25,1958	71,1310	45,9352	16,9695	54,1615	0,03	-	0,12	-	
BRIDGEPORT	41,1733	-	73,1817	84	78%	7.094,7619	45,0738	94,7619	49,6881	37,4817	57,2802	0,07	-	20,22	-	
MOSULPO	33,2144	-	126,2511	84	78%	6.996,9405	71,1224	3,0595	68,0628	-	110,0147	106,9552	0,26	-	144,58	
PRIGI	-	8,2800	111,7300	83	77%	7.150,1325	70,3381	150,1325	79,7944	43,2755	106,8571	0,26	-	4,70	-	
LIVORNOII	43,5463	-	10,2993	83	77%	7.770,9518	191,8089	770,9518	579,1429	61,1085	709,8433	1,20	-	132,97	-	
IWASAKI	40,5833	-	139,9167	82	76%	7.093,6707	17,8589	93,6707	75,8118	6,1269	87,5438	0,09	-	45,83	-	
PORTCHALMERS	-	45,8147	170,6241	82	76%	7.079,5000	40,6151	79,5000	38,8849	24,1142	55,3858	0,15	-	14,06	-	
HONOLULU	21,3067	-	157,8667	81	75%	7.044,8272	42,6134	44,8272	87,4406	-	54,9832	99,8104	0,10	-	117,97	
LALIBERTAD	-	2,2000	80,9167	81	75%	7.084,2840	-	11,2397	84,2840	95,5236	-	28,8000	113,0839	0,11	-	68,67

MARDELPLATA(NAVALBASE)	-	-	81	75%	7.123,8272	0,5945	123,8272	123,2327	-	21,2971	145,1243	0,16	-	64,29
PORTVILAB	-	-	80	74%	7.151,7125	77,4240	151,7125	74,2885	47,7663	103,9462	0,22	11,25	-	-
SANDPOINT,POPOFIS.,AK	55,3367	160,5017	79	73%	7.008,5316	30,0715	8,5316	38,6032	44,1361	52,6678	0,11	64,63	-	-
ILETLAMERE	4,8938	52,1905	79	73%	7.068,9873	22,2517	68,9873	46,7357	0,8991	69,8864	0,22	32,12	-	-
SELDOVIA	59,4400	151,7200	79	73%	7.111,4937	47,4574	111,4937	64,0362	32,4277	79,0660	0,11	4,30	-	-
BETIO	1,3651	172,9330	78	72%	7.054,1026	3,1093	54,1026	57,2118	32,3315	86,4341	0,22	49,64	-	-
SHEKPIK	22,2203	113,8944	78	72%	7.018,4231	8,4410	18,4231	9,9821	16,8116	1,6114	0,03	16,04	-	-
DANANG	16,1000	108,2167	78	72%	6.951,9359	76,1055	48,0641	28,0414	101,8117	53,7476	0,22	108,75	-	-
BERGENPOINT,STATENIS.	40,6367	74,1417	77	71%	7.191,8571	141,5084	191,8571	50,3487	129,4909	62,3662	0,16	104,58	-	-
BUKOM	1,2256	103,7785	76	70%	7.228,5395	98,4584	228,5395	130,0811	44,8525	183,6870	0,40	14,63	-	-
GENOVAII	44,4101	8,9255	76	70%	7.061,5789	20,6593	61,5789	40,9197	8,9017	52,6772	0,10	5,33	-	-
CAPEMAY	38,9683	74,9600	76	70%	7.074,1184	40,9429	74,1184	33,1755	19,7846	54,3339	0,17	0,11	-	-
CUXHAVEN2	53,8667	8,7167	76	70%	7.077,9737	26,9458	77,9737	104,9195	49,9494	127,9231	0,17	109,76	-	-
ISLAY(PORTELEN)	55,6276	6,1899	75	69%	6.954,6933	80,7914	45,3067	35,4847	91,0769	45,7702	0,04	92,96	-	-
CHARLOTTEAMALIE	18,3350	64,9200	75	69%	7.053,4667	8,9695	53,4667	44,4972	1,3725	54,8392	0,07	16,47	-	-
VARDO	70,3750	31,1040	74	69%	7.082,8108	10,5189	82,8108	93,3297	47,7830	130,5938	0,31	103,11	-	-
SABANG	5,8883	95,3167	74	69%	7.097,8243	67,3903	97,8243	30,4341	60,2305	37,5938	0,07	48,67	-	-
VENEZIA(PUNTADELLASALUTE)	45,4333	12,3333	74	69%	7.906,5676	175,2423	906,5676	731,3252	62,8844	843,6831	0,89	151,93	-	-
FORMENTERA	38,7347	1,4190	73	68%	7.846,1918	301,7500	846,1918	544,4418	173,2875	672,9043	1,22	32,39	-	-
DOVER	51,1144	1,3227	73	68%	7.080,3836	34,5727	80,3836	114,9563	48,7540	129,1375	0,16	153,34	-	-
ASAMUSHI	40,8975	140,8592	73	68%	7.338,8356	134,7417	338,8356	204,0940	84,1779	254,6578	0,42	44,56	-	-
SOLOMON'SISLAND(BIOL.LAB.)	38,3167	76,4517	73	68%	7.044,5890	0,2591	44,5890	44,3300	10,4547	55,0438	0,10	27,92	-	-
CALDERA	-	27,0667	72	67%	7.325,2917	128,7036	325,2917	196,5881	103,0720	222,2197	0,14	62,08	-	-
PORTKEMBLA	-	34,4738	72	67%	7.078,7500	0,2108	78,7500	78,5392	2,4181	81,1681	0,09	35,65	-	-
HEUKSANDO	-	34,6839	72	67%	7.061,3472	5,0958	61,3472	56,2514	16,3055	77,6527	0,20	58,40	-	-
SAIPAN	-	15,2333	72	67%	6.992,2083	74,3648	7,7917	66,5731	82,2656	74,4740	0,19	136,38	-	-
DURBAN	-	29,8742	72	67%	7.162,1389	103,6996	162,1389	58,4393	71,1743	90,9646	0,31	50,11	-	-
PORTOCORSINI	-	44,5000	72	67%	7.059,5417	10,6176	59,5417	70,1593	18,5419	78,0835	0,05	45,75	-	-

SANDAKAN	5,8100	118,0672	71	66%	6.982,3521	2,0057	-	17,6479	-	19,6536	15,6520	-	33,2999	-	0,19	59,48
LERWICK	60,1540	1,1403	70	65%	7.040,5714	1,9954	40,5714	38,5760	4,2428	44,8143	0,09	34,53	-	-	-	-
RABAU	4,2000	152,1833	70	65%	7.072,8714	31,8275	72,8714	41,0440	25,2713	47,6002	0,02	22,59	-	-	-	-
MATSUYAMAI	33,8667	132,7000	70	65%	7.040,5714	1,9954	40,5714	38,5760	4,2428	44,8143	0,09	34,53	-	-	-	-
OCEANCITYINLET	38,3283	75,0917	70	65%	7.289,4857	152,9267	289,4857	136,5590	84,9421	204,5436	0,56	25,08	-	-	-	-
PORTADELAIDE(OUTERHARBOR)	34,7798	138,4807	69	64%	7.081,4058	25,3839	81,4058	56,0219	0,9299	80,4759	0,19	22,30	-	-	-	-
DAESAN	37,0075	126,3528	69	64%	7.018,1449	53,6479	18,1449	71,7929	96,9454	115,0904	0,36	126,59	-	-	-	-
MIYAKESIMA	34,0672	139,4808	68	63%	7.106,0147	60,9622	106,0147	45,0525	47,1169	58,8978	0,12	24,53	-	-	-	-
UNO	34,4886	133,9494	67	62%	6.943,6866	88,2943	56,3134	31,9809	94,4812	38,1677	0,04	104,45	-	-	-	-
MACAU	22,2000	113,5500	67	62%	7.246,2687	64,0167	246,2687	182,2519	45,1797	201,0890	0,12	6,23	-	-	-	-
KOPER	45,5481	13,7246	66	61%	7.029,2424	2,5991	29,2424	26,6433	0,4522	28,7902	0,03	7,34	-	-	-	-
CARTAGENA	10,4000	75,5500	65	60%	7.035,3231	34,3466	35,3231	69,6697	54,1586	89,4816	0,06	52,95	-	-	-	-
MIKUNI	36,2547	136,1489	65	60%	7.033,9077	31,3467	33,9077	65,2544	46,9942	80,9019	0,13	75,22	-	-	-	-
KANTONISLAND-B	2,8167	171,7167	64	59%	7.027,2969	39,1319	27,2969	66,4288	63,6598	90,9567	0,17	100,86	-	-	-	-
BROOME	18,0008	122,2186	63	58%	7.111,6032	30,8576	111,6032	80,7456	11,2757	100,3275	0,14	20,61	-	-	-	-
TVARMINNE	59,8500	23,2500	61	56%	7.124,4098	65,6689	124,4098	58,7410	58,1415	66,2683	0,07	45,23	-	-	-	-
ALESUND	62,4694	6,1519	61	56%	7.059,8197	18,3830	59,8197	41,4367	7,5561	52,2636	0,07	18,93	-	-	-	-
AMHERST	16,0833	97,5667	60	56%	7.169,5667	54,7397	169,5667	114,8269	28,6739	140,8927	0,32	74,34	-	-	-	-
WESTCOAST	1,3000	103,7667	60	56%	7.109,3167	54,4809	109,3167	54,8357	34,5141	74,8026	0,21	4,00	-	-	-	-
BOLVANSKIINOS(FEDOROVA)	70,4500	59,0833	60	56%	7.071,0833	5,8544	71,0833	76,9377	28,9577	100,0411	0,20	94,38	-	-	-	-
FRENCHFRIGATESHOALS	23,8683	166,2883	60	56%	6.949,1000	61,8924	50,9000	10,9924	53,2476	2,3476	0,07	45,32	-	-	-	-
PUNTAARENAS	53,1667	70,9000	60	56%	7.112,4667	47,9043	112,4667	64,5623	36,7932	75,6735	0,09	5,26	-	-	-	-
CHETYREHSTOLBOVOI	70,6333	162,4833	59	55%	7.018,3220	47,3484	18,3220	65,6705	57,8831	76,2052	0,13	107,55	-	-	-	-
BANGOR	54,6648	5,6695	59	55%	7.118,1695	64,1888	118,1695	53,9807	48,7453	69,4241	0,13	27,00	-	-	-	-
GRINDAVIK	63,8333	22,4333	58	54%	7.088,6207	16,4829	88,6207	72,1378	11,3617	77,2590	0,04	0,23	-	-	-	-
PORTELIZABETH	33,9511	25,6297	58	54%	6.974,6552	0,5809	25,3448	24,7640	8,1184	17,2264	0,10	42,56	-	-	-	-
KALININGRAD	54,7000	20,4833	57	53%	7.066,9825	4,3116	66,9825	71,2941	20,4456	87,4281	0,15	50,70	-	-	-	-
BUNDABERG,BURNETTHEADS	24,7667	152,3833	56	52%	7.115,0536	8,5480	115,0536	106,5056	35,0920	150,1456	0,81	94,09	-	-	-	-

GEOJEDO	34,8014	128,6992	56	52%	7.107,5357	51,6193	107,5357	55,9164	40,2126	67,3231	0,08	28,37
URAKAWAI	42,1667	142,7667	55	51%	7.000,3818	49,4060	0,3818	49,7879	55,7329	56,1148	0,05	67,67
KINLOCHBERVIE	58,4566	5,0504	55	51%	7.011,9273	37,1236	11,9273	49,0509	43,2441	55,1714	0,05	52,30
MATI,DAVAOORIENTAL	6,9500	126,2167	54	50%	7.151,9444	80,9442	151,9444	71,0002	70,2736	81,6709	0,13	48,80
DAYTONABEACH	29,2333	81,0000	53	49%	7.034,3208	17,1455	34,3208	51,4663	23,7402	58,0610	0,05	47,49
GANGHWADAEGYO	37,7319	126,5222	51	47%	7.102,5098	34,3433	102,5098	68,1666	4,7162	97,7936	0,19	12,10
VIGOII	42,2431	8,7260	50	46%	7.080,3200	6,2946	80,3200	74,0254	2,4082	82,7282	0,06	10,49
OITAI	33,2661	131,6867	50	46%	7.002,9000	61,3221	2,9000	64,2221	69,8354	72,7354	0,11	100,53
PORTIRENE	18,3833	122,1000	47	44%	7.110,7021	77,9314	110,7021	32,7708	56,2020	54,5001	0,19	18,52
BUCKSPORT,WACCAMAWR.	33,6467	79,0950	47	44%	7.221,8511	105,0001	221,8511	116,8509	88,8999	132,9512	0,16	53,30
SETROIA	38,5000	8,9000	46	43%	7.157,7391	54,1557	157,7391	103,5834	32,1568	125,5824	0,16	0,55
ST.PETERSBURG	27,7600	82,6267	45	42%	7.288,2444	69,7430	288,2444	218,5015	43,7658	244,4787	0,46	159,47
KANTONISLAND	2,8000	171,7167	44	41%	7.072,7273	13,0362	72,7273	59,6911	17,2696	89,9968	0,29	72,37
SHUTEHARBOUR2	20,2833	148,7833	44	41%	7.120,0455	76,6688	120,0455	43,3767	70,3244	49,7210	0,03	68,66
CHRISTIANSTEDHARBOUR	17,7500	64,7050	44	41%	7.063,6136	49,3362	63,6136	14,2774	41,2783	22,3354	0,07	31,21
KAVALLA	40,9346	24,4121	41	38%	7.073,0976	30,8009	73,0976	42,2967	14,7728	58,3248	0,15	22,56
POINTREYES	37,9950	122,9767	41	38%	6.971,9268	5,7426	28,0732	22,3305	2,5490	25,5241	0,03	14,05
CAPETOWN(GRANGERBAY)	33,9053	18,4347	36	33%	7.048,1111	31,0254	48,1111	79,1365	45,1846	93,2957	0,18	91,68
LYMINGTON	50,7403	1,5071	36	33%	7.096,5556	32,2217	96,5556	64,3338	10,2021	86,3534	0,31	33,63
INCHEONSONGDO	37,3381	126,5861	36	33%	7.051,3889	19,7452	51,3889	71,1341	45,2639	96,6528	0,28	81,35
LINAKHAMARI	69,6500	31,3667	36	33%	7.158,5556	86,7475	158,5556	71,8081	65,7129	92,8427	0,25	40,26
HAIKOU	20,0167	110,2833	36	33%	6.938,5556	87,5163	61,4444	148,9607	146,4207	207,8651	0,50	242,36
CENTURI	42,9658	9,3498	36	33%	7.092,3889	40,7361	92,3889	51,6528	37,9053	54,4836	0,03	34,02
PORTISABEL	26,0600	97,2150	36	33%	7.115,6389	61,5922	115,6389	54,0467	50,3554	65,2835	0,10	11,68
VISAKHAPATNAM	17,6833	83,2833	35	32%	7.024,0000	48,9920	24,0000	24,9920	47,1419	23,1419	0,05	31,33
TALCAHUANO	36,6833	73,1000	34	31%	7.011,0000	78,0906	11,0000	89,0906	102,7573	113,7573	0,27	155,08
HORNBAEK	56,0911	12,4583	34	31%	7.081,6471	124,6736	81,6471	206,3206	144,9864	226,6335	0,25	302,86
KASHIWAZAKI	37,3567	138,5083	32	30%	6.937,5000	5,3550	62,5000	67,8550	22,6056	85,1056	0,21	88,74
STENUNGSUND	58,0933	11,8325	32	30%	7.050,3125	61,2909	50,3125	10,9784	69,3116	18,9991	0,07	79,32

BUSANNEWPORT	35,0775	128,7869	32	30%	7.002,4375	-	6,4956	2,4375	8,9331	18,1332	-	15,6957	-	0,46	90,77
GLADSTONE	-	-	32	30%	7.002,5000	0,0624	2,5000	2,4376	-	20,1634	22,6634	0,19	-	-	73,56
DIKSON	73,5000	80,4000	31	29%	6.964,2903	91,6272	35,7097	55,9175	-	99,6545	63,9448	0,10	-	-	137,17
BURNIE	-	-	30	28%	6.986,8333	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOSASHIMIZU	41,0501	145,9150	30	28%	6.986,8333	66,3157	13,1667	53,1490	-	80,1924	67,0258	0,04	-	-	81,23
RIODEJANEIRO	32,7792	132,9589	30	28%	7.036,9333	27,9934	36,9333	8,9400	-	23,3135	13,6198	0,11	-	-	15,61
TOULON	-	-	30	28%	7.132,7000	78,8319	132,7000	53,8681	-	70,8832	61,8168	0,08	-	-	42,70
TALARA	22,9333	43,1333	30	28%	7.020,3333	0,1826	20,3333	20,1508	-	4,3530	15,9803	0,01	-	-	2,47
PLOCE	-	-	29	27%	7.082,7586	13,6996	82,7586	69,0591	-	9,2896	73,4690	0,06	-	-	17,83
OFUNATOI	43,1129	5,9147	24	22%	7.001,6250	22,7955	1,6250	21,1705	-	24,5760	22,9510	0,03	-	-	30,97
KETCHIKAN	39,0667	141,7167	24	22%	7.097,4583	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CASCAIS	55,3317	-	22	20%	7.097,4583	7,5357	97,4583	104,9940	-	28,8046	126,2629	0,22	-	-	81,72
ACAJUTLA	55,3317	131,6250	22	20%	6.943,4545	68,9967	56,5455	12,4512	-	65,4208	8,8753	0,00	-	-	71,91
KNYSNA	38,6833	-	22	20%	7.122,6818	0,8932	122,6818	121,7886	-	4,4969	127,1787	0,05	-	-	42,07
STJEANDELUZ(SOCAA)	13,5667	89,8333	22	20%	7.033,6364	0,7369	33,6364	32,8994	-	1,2138	34,8502	0,04	-	-	14,92
CHESAPEAKEBAYBR.TUN.	-	-	20	19%	7.348,4500	137,7035	348,4500	210,7465	-	110,9846	237,4654	0,40	-	-	26,70
NEWPORT	34,0494	23,0456	16	15%	7.146,3125	13,9960	146,3125	132,3165	-	8,0870	138,2255	0,05	-	-	40,87
BELYNOS	43,3952	1,6816	14	13%	6.851,8571	20,5677	148,1429	127,5751	-	8,5741	139,5687	0,05	-	-	4,02
MOKUOLOEISLAND	36,9667	76,1133	12	11%	7.130,3333	60,6601	130,3333	69,6732	-	48,5916	81,7417	0,06	-	-	44,59
MOKPO	51,5500	2,9874	12	11%	7.246,5000	83,6321	246,5000	162,8679	-	49,6283	196,8717	0,50	-	-	0,63
LAUTOKA	69,6000	60,2167	12	11%	7.043,3333	1,9436	43,3333	41,3897	-	23,5300	66,8634	0,25	-	-	89,19
PETROPAVLOVSK-KAMCHATSKY	46,6833	71,8833	12	11%	7.067,5000	1,8406	67,5000	65,6594	-	11,4343	78,9343	0,19	-	-	72,47
TABLEBAYHARBOUR	21,4317	157,7900	11	10%	7.090,0000	-	3,6986	90,0000	-	93,6986	5,3400	0,08	-	-	34,13
PARADIP	34,7797	126,3756	9	8%	7.052,7778	17,7319	52,7778	35,0459	-	0,5839	52,1939	0,17	-	-	27,90
SHEERNESS	17,6049	177,4383	9	8%	7.250,0000	1,9880	250,0000	248,0120	-	12,0849	262,0849	0,08	-	-	30,83
TAIMIUWAN	52,9833	158,6500	7	6%	7.070,0000	-	0,0883	70,0000	-	70,0883	18,3387	0,20	-	-	73,84
TAEAN	-	-	6	6%	7.065,1667	5,0422	65,1667	70,2089	-	40,0398	105,2065	0,56	-	-	187,06
KHALKISNORTH	20,2667	86,7000	4	4%	7.136,5000	-	72,2755	136,5000	-	208,7755	84,8782	0,11	-	-	193,96
BUSANNEWPORT	51,4456	0,7434	2	2%	7.037,0000	17,2724	37,0000	19,7276	-	0,2598	36,7402	0,22	-	-	36,22
GLADSTONE	22,2697	114,2886	-	0%	7.000,0000	26,2642	-	26,2642	-	26,2642	26,2642	0,04	-	-	30,12
DIKSON	38,4723	23,5926	-	0%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
BURNIE	36,9131	126,2389	-	0%	7.000,0000	63,2616	-	63,2616	-	66,6251	66,6251	0,32	-	-	106,38

SHIMONOSEKIII	33,9667	130,9500	-	0%	7,000,000	90,4834	-	-	90,4834	-	90,4834	0,41	-	18,92
LECONQUET	48,3594	4,7808	-	0%	7,000,000	0,1704	-	0,1704	10,4566	10,4566	10,4566	0,16	-	48,61
ROTHERA	67,5713	68,1298	-	0%	7,000,000	1,0654	-	1,0654	14,7471	14,7471	14,7471	0,07	-	13,51
BUENOSAIRE	34,6000	58,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	22,7801	-	22,7801	22,7801	22,7801	22,7801	0,25	-	42,36
BEDFORDINSTITUTE	44,6833	63,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	51,7918	-	51,7918	51,7918	51,7918	51,7918	2,55	-	83,65
CHIMAWAN,LANTAUISLAND	22,2333	114,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	4,9571	-	4,9571	4,9571	4,9571	4,9571	0,07	-	12,26
NAPOLI	40,8414	14,2692	-	0%	7,000,000	65,8204	-	65,8204	74,7575	74,7575	74,7575	0,14	-	93,14
PORTSMOUTH	50,8023	1,1113	-	0%	7,000,000	117,6770	-	117,6770	117,6770	117,6770	117,6770	0,66	-	181,50
STAVANGER	58,9743	5,7301	-	0%	7,000,000	95,6363	-	95,6363	95,6363	95,6363	95,6363	0,22	-	158,67
ALBANY	35,0337	117,8926	-	0%	7,000,000	28,8864	-	28,8864	28,8864	28,8864	28,8864	0,37	-	55,74
PORT-SAINT-FRANCOIS	46,2667	72,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	7,8673	-	7,8673	7,8673	7,8673	7,8673	0,13	-	21,84
ULLADULLAHARBOUR	35,3577	150,4765	-	0%	7,000,000	2,5650	-	2,5650	14,1984	14,1984	14,1984	0,17	-	31,83
NORTHSHIELDS	55,0074	1,4398	-	0%	7,000,000	84,8574	-	84,8574	84,8574	84,8574	84,8574	0,27	-	157,50
LASPALMAS,PUERTODELALUZ	28,1363	15,4257	-	0%	7,000,000	185,5025	-	185,5025	185,5025	185,5025	185,5025	1,59	-	368,02
SEAVEYISLAND	43,0800	70,7417	-	0%	7,000,000	140,4123	-	140,4123	140,4123	140,4123	140,4123	0,24	-	208,54
OKADA	34,7894	139,3914	-	0%	7,000,000	24,8077	-	24,8077	24,8077	24,8077	24,8077	0,36	-	3,16
URAKAWAI	42,1667	142,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3758	-	0,3758	0,3758	0,3758	0,3758	0,11	-	31,96
BONAVISTA	48,6510	53,1150	-	0%	7,000,000	63,3969	-	63,3969	63,3969	63,3969	63,3969	0,19	-	48,48
MURORAN	42,3500	140,9500	-	0%	7,000,000	18,4026	-	18,4026	19,6436	19,6436	19,6436	0,07	-	31,34
NEZUGASEKI	38,5633	139,5458	-	0%	7,000,000	10,4047	-	10,4047	10,4047	10,4047	10,4047	0,21	-	67,67
RICHARDSBAY	28,8119	32,0786	-	0%	7,000,000	72,2110	-	72,2110	73,8060	73,8060	73,8060	0,20	-	119,63
KARIYA	33,4731	129,8492	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9416	-	2,9416	2,9416	2,9416	2,9416	0,15	-	10,52
CHAMPLAIN	46,4333	72,4000	-	0%	7,000,000	102,5414	-	102,5414	127,2637	127,2637	127,2637	0,74	-	341,23
DONGFANG	19,1000	108,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	31,3329	-	31,3329	31,3329	31,3329	31,3329	0,01	-	32,06
ISLAMARTINGARCIA	34,1833	58,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8967	-	61,8967	61,8967	61,8967	61,8967	0,14	-	76,06
RHODOS	36,4417	28,2364	-	0%	7,000,000	56,1171	-	56,1171	56,1171	56,1171	56,1171	0,35	-	81,89
MUKHO	37,5503	129,1164	-	0%	7,000,000	62,4817	-	62,4817	62,4817	62,4817	62,4817	0,39	-	85,97
ANHEUNG	36,6736	126,1322	-	0%	7,000,000	57,7834	-	57,7834	57,7834	57,7834	57,7834	1,06	-	89,97

BALANACAN,MARINDUQUE	13,5333	121,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	3,5114	-	3,5114	-	3,5114	0,19	28,50
MYSSHMIDTA	68,9000	179,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	118,1043	-	118,1043	118,1043	118,1043	1,14	145,92	
FANNING-B	3,9000	159,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	67,0619	-	67,0619	67,0619	67,0619	1,86	16,89	
FUNAFUTI	-	179,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	125,0384	-	125,0384	125,0384	125,0384	0,67	54,64	
GREYMOUTH	42,4500	171,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	66,0042	-	66,0042	66,0042	66,0042	0,29	36,07	
NAURU-B	0,5294	166,9101	-	0%	7,000,000	8,2007	-	8,2007	5,4187	5,4187	0,02	13,55	
TORSHAVN	62,0167	6,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	2,1626	-	2,1626	2,1626	2,1626	0,23	55,35	
TROMSO	69,6474	18,9613	-	0%	7,000,000	40,6503	-	40,6503	40,6503	40,6503	0,43	50,21	
TERPIAI-TUMSA	73,5500	118,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	57,1673	-	57,1673	57,1673	57,1673	0,28	91,73	
MIYAZU	35,5333	135,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	2,8598	-	2,8598	2,8598	2,8598	0,26	73,29	
MATARANI	17,0000	72,1167	-	0%	7,000,000	26,4999	-	26,4999	26,4999	26,4999	0,37	50,82	
NAGAEVO	59,5500	150,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,9971	-	1,9971	8,1621	8,1621	0,20	70,26	
SE-LAHA	70,1500	72,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	11,5806	-	11,5806	11,5806	11,5806	0,03	4,77	
VISE(VISEOSTROV)	79,5000	76,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	38,2527	-	38,2527	38,2527	38,2527	0,10	66,09	
PORTLAND(MAINE)	43,6567	70,2467	-	0%	7,000,000	31,9248	-	31,9248	31,9248	31,9248	0,07	46,46	
RATAN	63,9861	20,8950	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5605	-	1,5605	1,5605	1,5605	0,05	27,03	
ALICANTE(INNERHARBOUR)	38,3389	0,4812	-	0%	7,000,000	32,1903	-	32,1903	32,1903	32,1903	0,16	9,36	
TARAWA-A,BETIO	1,3667	172,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	1,8082	-	1,8082	1,8082	1,8082	0,44	38,64	
STANLEY	-	57,8649	-	0%	7,000,000	11,7170	-	11,7170	11,7170	11,7170	0,17	11,37	
NAGAPATTINAM	10,7667	79,8500	-	0%	7,000,000	109,1069	-	109,1069	109,1069	109,1069	0,95	172,42	
STERLEGOVA(STERLEGOVAMYS)	75,4167	88,9000	-	0%	7,000,000	26,6536	-	26,6536	26,6536	26,6536	1,02	40,43	
ZEMLIABUNGE	74,8833	142,1167	-	0%	7,000,000	21,9388	-	21,9388	21,9388	21,9388	0,23	12,01	
IMMINGHAM	53,6302	0,1874	-	0%	7,000,000	68,7721	-	68,7721	68,7721	68,7721	0,06	111,36	
TEIGNMOUTHPIER	50,5439	3,4921	-	0%	7,000,000	9,0201	-	9,0201	9,0201	9,0201	1,05	116,47	
EDEN	37,0737	149,9077	-	0%	7,000,000	86,9419	-	86,9419	86,9419	86,9419	0,01	83,65	
PYEONGTAEK	36,9667	126,8228	-	0%	7,000,000	41,8445	-	41,8445	41,8445	41,8445	0,00	41,39	
TOKYOII	35,6500	139,7667	-	0%	7,000,000	9,8786	-	9,8786	9,8786	9,8786	0,59	95,50	
SANJUAN	15,3667	75,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	73,9596	-	73,9596	73,9596	73,9596	0,04	70,29	

KATAKOLON	37,6448	21,3197	-	0%	7,000,000	26,8531	-	26,8531	-	26,8531	0,09	33,93
NANTUCKETISLAND	41,2850	70,0967	-	0%	7,000,000	52,4086	-	52,4086	52,4086	52,4086	0,25	3,07
HARRINGTONHBR	50,5000	59,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	6,9222	-	6,9222	6,9222	6,9222	0,04	26,85
OGI	37,8147	138,2811	-	0%	7,000,000	51,9532	-	51,9532	51,9532	51,9532	0,49	84,97
SALGRUND	62,3333	21,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	8,5217	-	8,5217	8,5217	8,5217	0,03	23,71
AMRUM(WITTDUEN)	54,6167	8,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	9,1859	-	9,1859	9,1859	9,1859	0,75	58,19
BELLABELLA	52,1667	128,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	2,0749	-	2,0749	2,0749	2,0749	0,15	36,94
ALEXANDROUPOLIS	40,8441	25,8783	-	0%	7,000,000	50,2039	-	50,2039	50,2039	50,2039	0,43	15,84
PALERMOII	38,1214	13,3713	-	0%	7,000,000	260,5215	-	260,5215	260,5215	260,5215	0,49	320,26
MAPUTO	25,9667	32,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	4,1144	-	4,1144	4,1144	4,1144	0,05	16,60
DUNBAR	56,0059	2,5169	-	0%	7,000,000	99,6898	-	99,6898	99,6898	99,6898	0,02	106,57
ARRECIFE	28,9719	13,5301	-	0%	7,000,000	6,0963	-	6,0963	6,0963	6,0963	0,74	29,41
PHILADELPHIA(PIER9N)	39,9333	75,1417	-	0%	7,000,000	17,9134	-	17,9134	17,9134	17,9134	0,13	38,17
INCHEON	37,4519	126,5922	-	0%	7,000,000	26,5849	-	26,5849	26,5849	26,5849	0,25	80,52
OSHOROI	43,2094	140,8581	-	0%	7,000,000	1,9610	-	1,9610	1,9610	1,9610	0,18	34,77
URAGAMI	33,5583	135,8964	-	0%	7,000,000	24,2477	-	24,2477	24,2477	24,2477	0,03	28,78
LOKONPAI	22,3667	114,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	88,4967	-	88,4967	88,4967	88,4967	0,37	66,25
REGGIOCALABRIAI	38,1217	15,6489	-	0%	7,000,000	18,5389	-	18,5389	18,5389	18,5389	0,17	6,78
RUSSKAIAGAVANII	76,1833	62,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	30,0834	-	30,0834	30,0834	30,0834	0,43	14,40
QUEENCHARLOTTECTY	53,2500	132,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	9,9767	-	9,9767	25,0547	25,0547	0,17	70,81
KUREI	33,3336	133,2433	-	0%	7,000,000	53,1277	-	53,1277	53,1277	53,1277	0,57	82,45
LESKINA(LESKINAMYS)	72,3167	79,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	15,1494	-	15,1494	15,1494	15,1494	0,50	4,41
WAKAYAMA	34,2217	135,1456	-	0%	7,000,000	6,0801	-	6,0801	12,3442	12,3442	0,29	97,65
IQUIQUE	20,2167	70,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	9,0053	-	9,0053	9,0053	9,0053	0,03	6,34
ULLEUNG	37,4914	130,9136	-	0%	7,000,000	16,2226	-	16,2226	16,2226	16,2226	0,17	51,48
LAPUSH	47,9133	124,6367	-	0%	7,000,000	340,5379	-	340,5379	340,5379	340,5379	3,03	686,24
BATUMI	41,6333	41,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	12,3962	-	12,3962	12,3962	12,3962	0,11	43,76
BELEM	1,4500	48,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	34,0657	-	34,0657	34,0657	34,0657	0,43	59,95
GERALDTON	28,7760	114,6019	-	0%	7,000,000	63,8023	-	63,8023	63,8023	63,8023	0,09	55,44

TANDAG,SURIGAOODELSUR	9,0833	126,2000	-	0%	7,000,0000	31,2562	-	-	31,2562	31,2562	-	0,12	16,28
WAGLANISLAND	22,1831	114,3028	-	0%	7,000,0000	35,5964	-	-	35,5964	35,5964	-	0,81	11,97
NAPLES	26,1317	81,8067	-	0%	7,000,0000	1,3103	-	-	1,3103	1,3103	-	0,29	63,15
ST-JOSEPH-DE-LA-RIVE	47,4500	70,3667	-	0%	7,000,0000	16,1539	-	-	16,1539	16,1539	-	0,30	36,78
NORTHSYDNEY	46,2167	60,2500	-	0%	7,000,0000	83,4440	-	-	83,4440	89,3202	-	0,10	109,95
LYPYRTTI	60,6000	21,2333	-	0%	7,000,0000	129,0534	-	-	129,0534	129,0534	-	0,09	197,48
PRAVDY(PRAVDYOSTROV)	76,2667	94,7667	-	0%	7,000,0000	122,6270	-	-	122,6270	122,6270	-	0,83	150,70
HIERRO	27,7841	17,9016	-	0%	7,000,0000	2,7133	-	-	2,7133	2,7133	-	0,05	6,35
LIANYUNGANG	34,7500	119,4500	-	0%	7,000,0000	88,2545	-	-	88,2545	88,2545	-	0,18	123,90
OMINATO	41,2500	141,1500	-	0%	7,000,0000	44,5664	-	-	44,5664	44,5664	-	1,60	19,71
LANGARAPOINT	54,2500	133,0333	-	0%	7,000,0000	2,0634	-	-	2,0634	2,0634	-	0,23	56,44
GALVESTONI,PLEASUREPIER,TX	29,2850	94,7883	-	0%	7,000,0000	0,4070	-	-	0,4070	6,9804	-	0,13	44,04
ST.NAZAIRE	47,2700	2,2000	-	0%	7,000,0000	49,3948	-	-	49,3948	49,3948	-	0,40	130,31
DAKAR2	14,6833	17,4167	-	0%	7,000,0000	37,1606	-	-	37,1606	37,1606	-	0,40	63,45
CAOPASSERO	36,6667	15,3000	-	0%	7,000,0000	2,9587	-	-	2,9587	2,9587	-	0,02	7,55
STE-ANNE-DES-MONTS	49,1333	66,4833	-	0%	7,000,0000	30,6100	-	-	30,6100	30,6100	-	0,38	0,04
NAURU	0,5333	166,9000	-	0%	7,000,0000	16,5429	-	-	16,5429	16,5429	-	0,44	61,78
KHALKISSOUTH	38,4609	23,5895	-	0%	7,000,0000	15,2607	-	-	15,2607	15,2607	-	0,00	15,95
HIRTSHALS	57,5956	9,9639	-	0%	7,000,0000	65,8679	-	-	65,8679	65,8679	-	0,07	105,98
TREGDE	58,0064	7,5548	-	0%	7,000,0000	110,0033	-	-	110,0033	114,5377	-	0,02	107,06
SVIATOINOS(SVIATOINOSMYS)	72,8333	140,7333	-	0%	7,000,0000	1,7493	-	-	1,7493	1,7493	-	0,08	9,18
DELFIJIL	53,3264	6,9331	-	0%	7,000,0000	39,0066	-	-	39,0066	39,0066	-	0,05	69,70
LIMETREEBAY,STCROIX	17,6933	64,7533	-	0%	7,000,0000	154,5260	-	-	154,5260	154,5260	-	0,18	176,27
HAGI	34,4333	131,4167	-	0%	7,000,0000	35,9759	-	-	35,9759	35,9759	-	0,19	6,29
WESTBAYHARBOUR	50,7089	2,7641	-	0%	7,000,0000	87,8042	-	-	87,8042	93,7480	-	0,73	184,32
BUNBURY	33,3234	115,6600	-	0%	7,000,0000	3,5298	-	-	3,5298	3,5298	-	0,23	57,14
GOTEBORG-RINGON	57,7167	11,9667	-	0%	7,000,0000	11,5459	-	-	11,5459	11,5459	-	0,13	27,31
BARAHONA	18,2000	71,0833	-	0%	7,000,0000	68,4097	-	-	68,4097	68,4097	-	0,08	58,34

SETTLEMENTPOINT	26,7100	-	-	0%	7,000,000	12,6967	-	-	12,6967	-	-	0,22	-	27,72
TADOUSSAC	48,1333	69,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	14,5618	-	14,5618	14,5618	14,5618	-	0,19	-	12,04
NOSY-BE	-	13,4000	48,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	18,9728	-	18,9728	18,9728	18,9728	0,32	-	38,51
GUADALUPEISLANDII	28,8833	-	118,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	3,2559	-	3,2559	-	3,2559	1,51	-	26,96
GEDSER	54,5728	-	11,9256	-	0%	7,000,000	57,3578	-	57,3578	-	57,3578	0,12	-	82,04
ULLAPOOL	57,8953	-	5,1579	-	0%	7,000,000	-	2,4049	-	2,4049	3,4246	0,04	-	12,10
LEVKAS	38,8345	-	20,7121	-	0%	7,000,000	19,2284	-	19,2284	-	19,2284	0,05	-	15,28
SMOGEN	58,3536	-	11,2178	-	0%	7,000,000	12,3912	-	12,3912	-	12,3912	0,87	-	94,49
ITOI	34,8956	-	139,1331	-	0%	7,000,000	26,7185	-	26,7185	-	26,7185	0,25	-	7,74
CADIZIII	36,5401	-	6,2862	-	0%	7,000,000	19,8385	-	19,8385	-	19,8385	0,22	-	74,48
BORKUM(FISCHERBALJE)	53,5575	-	6,7478	-	0%	7,000,000	37,3255	-	37,3255	-	37,3255	0,38	-	12,74
KOBE	34,6833	-	135,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	291,5005	-	291,5005	-	291,5005	2,00	-	620,72
SABINEPASS	29,7050	-	93,8533	-	0%	7,000,000	6,2144	-	6,2144	-	6,2144	0,16	-	10,56
CAGLIARI	39,2102	-	9,1143	-	0%	7,000,000	153,3243	-	153,3243	143,6709	143,6709	0,15	-	125,95
SANFERNANDO,LAUNION	16,6167	-	120,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	54,7567	-	54,7567	-	54,7567	0,10	-	42,04
URANGANII	-	25,3000	152,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	33,0801	-	33,0801	33,0801	33,0801	0,19	-	12,15
MAISAKA	34,6819	-	137,6089	-	0%	7,000,000	28,6020	-	28,6020	-	28,6020	0,15	-	9,19
SEWELLPOINT,HAMPTONROADS	36,9467	-	76,3300	-	0%	7,000,000	7,2169	-	7,2169	-	7,2169	0,99	-	37,43
POINTTUPPER	45,6000	-	61,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	21,5424	-	21,5424	-	21,5424	0,78	-	7,49
SOUTHBEACH	44,6250	-	124,0417	-	0%	7,000,000	15,7004	-	15,7004	-	15,7004	0,11	-	11,53
LAPALOMA	-	34,6500	54,1500	-	0%	7,000,000	10,2039	-	10,2039	-	10,2039	0,08	-	0,15
RUSSKAYAGAVAN	76,2000	-	62,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	38,7201	-	38,7201	-	38,7201	0,83	-	70,32
TEJN	55,2497	-	14,8378	-	0%	7,000,000	70,9422	-	70,9422	-	70,9422	0,18	-	86,28
MOULMEIN	16,4833	-	97,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	0,5821	-	0,5821	-	0,5821	0,08	-	22,92
PALERMO	-	34,5667	58,4000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,3200	-	1,3200	-	1,3200	0,16	-	43,39
WONSAN	39,1667	-	127,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	10,4017	-	10,4017	5,4829	5,4829	0,10	-	18,92
PUERTOPRINCESA,PALAWAN	9,7500	-	118,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	35,4133	-	35,4133	-	35,4133	0,02	-	39,79
GADEOKDO	35,0247	-	128,8108	-	0%	7,000,000	60,9431	-	60,9431	-	60,9431	0,27	-	13,60

RONNSKAR	63,0667	20,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	122,3281	-	-	122,3281	122,3281	-	0,22	217,21
BALLINA	28,8667	153,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	150,7088	-	-	150,7088	150,7088	-	0,61	216,10
FUNCHAL	32,6440	16,9131	-	0%	7,000,000	23,4771	-	-	23,4771	23,4771	-	0,17	49,55
TUMACO	1,8333	78,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	73,7007	-	-	73,7007	73,7007	-	0,09	89,34
GAZENICA	44,0833	15,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	40,4672	-	-	40,4672	40,4672	-	0,11	22,33
IRAKLIONII	35,3485	25,1527	-	0%	7,000,000	11,6774	-	-	11,6774	11,6774	-	0,13	28,53
NEWESTMINSTER	49,2000	122,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	0,3075	-	-	0,3075	0,3075	-	0,06	3,85
LAHADATU	5,0189	118,3461	-	0%	7,000,000	75,5954	-	-	75,5954	75,5954	-	0,02	74,08
PORTTARANAKI	39,0562	174,0344	-	0%	7,000,000	65,3335	-	-	65,3335	65,3335	-	0,02	63,24
FORTPULASKI	32,0333	80,9017	-	0%	7,000,000	17,0960	-	-	17,0960	17,0960	-	0,01	15,48
AUCKLAND-WAITEMATAHARBOUR	36,8431	174,7695	-	0%	7,000,000	44,0447	-	-	44,0447	42,8631	-	0,21	69,65
JUNGFRUSUND	59,9500	22,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	233,2875	-	-	233,2875	233,2875	-	0,45	445,54
MONACO(FONTVIEILLE)	43,7288	7,4215	-	0%	7,000,000	36,9026	-	-	36,9026	36,9026	-	0,09	50,51
BRIGHTON	35,0333	138,5167	-	0%	7,000,000	9,8091	-	-	9,8091	9,8091	-	0,22	21,01
HONDAU	20,6667	106,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7722	-	-	1,7722	1,7722	-	0,06	16,73
GUANTANAMOBAY	19,9067	75,1467	-	0%	7,000,000	66,6276	-	-	66,6276	66,6276	-	0,17	128,42
GINGERVILLECREEK	38,9583	76,5550	-	0%	7,000,000	69,4558	-	-	69,4558	69,4558	-	0,19	109,23
PORTLYTELTON	43,6056	172,7219	-	0%	7,000,000	42,8562	-	-	42,8562	42,8562	-	0,04	51,33
HACHINOHEI	40,5333	141,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	37,0294	-	-	37,0294	37,0294	-	0,14	29,88
ROSALES	38,9333	62,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	11,9508	-	-	11,9508	11,9508	-	0,15	54,79
PORTBURY	51,5000	2,7285	-	0%	7,000,000	32,0313	-	-	32,0313	32,0313	-	0,07	29,73
YAMBA	29,4297	153,3619	-	0%	7,000,000	34,9220	-	-	34,9220	34,9220	-	0,09	77,27
HALDIA	22,0333	88,1000	-	0%	7,000,000	26,6553	-	-	26,6553	26,6553	-	4,49	96,21
SANTOTOMASDECASTILLA	15,7000	88,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	23,3602	-	-	23,3602	23,3602	-	0,02	19,61
CONSTANTZA	44,1667	28,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	24,7025	-	-	24,7025	26,0363	-	0,17	104,94
KUCHINOTSU	32,6053	130,1953	-	0%	7,000,000	50,2414	-	-	50,2414	50,2414	-	0,10	44,42
TWEEDHEADS	28,1695	153,5496	-	0%	7,000,000	126,7484	-	-	126,7484	107,9375	-	0,36	68,60
ATLANTICCITY	39,3550	74,4183	-	0%	7,000,000	92,6975	-	-	92,6975	92,6975	-	0,15	155,56
CHARCHANGA	22,2167	91,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	13,8827	-	-	13,8827	13,8827	-	0,03	9,40

ALGECIRAS2	36,1770	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	21,6281	-	-	21,6281	-	21,6281	0,02	20,97
SOLNECHNAIA(SOLNECHNAIABUKHTA)	78,2000	103,2667	-	0%	7.000,0000	42,8632	-	-	42,8632	-	42,8632	0,08	29,91
SIBAURA	35,6333	139,7500	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,4506	-	-	0,4506	-	0,4506	0,01	2,98
WEWAK	-	3,5500	143,6333	-	7.000,0000	25,7504	-	-	25,7504	-	25,7504	0,06	16,40
SOUTHISLANDPLANTATION,WINYAHBAY	33,2350	-	79,2033	-	7.000,0000	52,3304	-	-	52,3304	-	52,3304	0,72	78,78
CORPUSCHRISTI,GULFMEXICO,TX	27,5833	-	97,2167	-	7.000,0000	33,0711	-	-	33,0711	-	33,0711	0,08	46,53
KARUMBA	-	17,5000	140,8333	-	7.000,0000	1,0715	-	-	1,0715	-	1,0715	0,15	38,86
NASEI	28,3833	-	129,5000	-	7.000,0000	1,9819	-	-	1,9819	-	1,9819	0,23	49,94
BAMFIELD	48,8500	-	125,1333	-	7.000,0000	12,0487	-	-	12,0487	-	12,0487	0,94	85,53
PUERTOCASTILLA	16,0167	-	86,0333	-	7.000,0000	2,7897	-	-	2,7897	-	9,0702	0,14	47,50
CANANEIA	-	25,0167	47,9333	-	7.000,0000	31,4461	-	-	31,4461	-	31,4461	0,10	61,08
SOOKE	48,3667	-	123,7333	-	7.000,0000	71,5390	-	-	71,5390	-	71,5390	0,12	84,16
ST.MALO	48,6411	-	2,0282	-	7.000,0000	3,3573	-	-	3,3573	-	3,3573	0,14	61,53
KORSOR	55,3322	-	11,1422	-	7.000,0000	20,0103	-	-	20,0103	-	20,0103	0,03	35,36
LIVERPOOL(GLADSTONEDOCK)	53,4497	-	3,0180	-	7.000,0000	38,9980	-	-	38,9980	-	31,9332	0,12	10,48
VIESTE	41,8881	-	16,1770	-	7.000,0000	28,8393	-	-	28,8393	-	36,8780	0,14	57,26
STONYPOINT	-	38,3721	145,2247	-	7.000,0000	30,8888	-	-	30,8888	-	30,8888	0,06	36,14
MAYPORT	30,3933	-	81,4317	-	7.000,0000	39,0719	-	-	39,0719	-	39,0719	0,07	65,30
REALQUEZON	14,6667	-	121,6000	-	7.000,0000	17,8391	-	-	17,8391	-	17,8391	0,48	89,71
BARENTSBERGII(SPITSBERGEN)	78,0667	-	14,2500	-	7.000,0000	247,3216	-	-	247,3216	-	247,3216	0,45	356,70
PADREISLAND	26,0683	-	97,1517	-	7.000,0000	64,6946	-	-	64,6946	-	64,6946	0,02	62,92
BAHIAESPERANZA	-	63,3000	56,9167	-	7.000,0000	44,0888	-	-	44,0888	-	44,0888	0,16	22,99
SANDIEGO(QUARANTINESTATION)	32,7133	-	117,1733	-	7.000,0000	269,0285	-	-	269,0285	-	269,0285	0,67	549,10
PASAIHARBOUR,SANSEBASTIAN	43,3218	-	1,9315	-	7.000,0000	37,3756	-	-	37,3756	-	37,3756	4,99	25,05

SHIMIZU-MINATO	35,0117	138,5175	-	0%	7,000,000	-	10,6205	-	10,6205	10,6205	0,34	23,64
BJORN	60,6333	17,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	40,1333	-	40,1333	40,1333	40,1333	0,04	42,28
NEWCASTLEII	-	32,9167	151,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,4534	-	57,4534	57,4534	0,37	30,00
GULEOBDO	37,1944	125,9953	-	0%	7,000,000	25,2556	-	25,2556	25,2556	25,2556	0,29	10,68
BIRKENHEAD(ALFREDDOCK)	53,4000	3,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	48,3741	-	48,3741	48,3741	48,3741	0,27	81,27
FYNHAV	54,9950	9,9869	-	0%	7,000,000	75,6420	-	75,6420	66,0700	66,0700	0,32	27,68
VALENCIA	39,4420	0,3113	-	0%	7,000,000	30,4814	-	30,4814	30,4814	30,4814	0,26	13,23
KUREII	34,2333	132,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	5,1367	-	5,1367	5,1367	5,1367	0,05	5,85
WESTTUAS	1,3444	103,6340	-	0%	7,000,000	49,9773	-	49,9773	44,0116	44,0116	0,22	2,25
GRANDISLE	29,2633	89,9567	-	0%	7,000,000	99,7835	-	99,7835	66,7284	66,7284	0,58	45,79
BAR	42,0833	19,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	62,3208	-	62,3208	62,3208	62,3208	0,18	34,14
PESCHANYI(PESCHANYIMYS)	79,4333	102,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	67,7816	-	67,7816	80,7567	80,7567	0,32	168,10
SODERSKAR	60,1167	25,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	8,2718	-	8,2718	8,2718	8,2718	0,07	37,06
SPRINGMAIDPIER	33,6550	78,9183	-	0%	7,000,000	1,8922	-	1,8922	1,8922	1,8922	0,18	43,94
LEMSTROM	60,1000	20,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	47,4659	-	47,4659	57,2941	57,2941	0,24	223,19
ST.JOHN'S,NFLD.	47,5667	52,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	27,1809	-	27,1809	27,1809	27,1809	0,02	18,30
NEWCASTLEI	32,9167	151,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	72,8619	-	72,8619	72,8619	72,8619	0,41	115,71
WELLINGTONHARBOUR	41,2843	174,7798	-	0%	7,000,000	78,0882	-	78,0882	78,0882	78,0882	0,56	116,19
VIS-CESKAVILA	43,0667	16,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	33,5412	-	33,5412	33,5412	33,5412	0,15	61,16
PORTAUPRINCE	18,5667	72,3500	-	0%	7,000,000	153,4086	-	153,4086	153,4086	153,4086	0,18	96,92
ELFINCOVE,PORTALTHORP	58,1950	136,3467	-	0%	7,000,000	19,3519	-	19,3519	19,3519	19,3519	0,33	16,52
DUNAI(DUNAIOSTROV)	73,9333	124,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	137,8281	-	137,8281	137,8281	137,8281	0,01	136,66
HAYPOINT	21,2833	149,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	57,5209	-	57,5209	57,5209	57,5209	0,70	92,74
NAKANOSIMA	29,8419	129,8478	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7483	-	1,7483	1,7483	1,7483	0,19	47,24
RAFINA	38,0333	24,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	62,7181	-	62,7181	62,7181	62,7181	1,40	134,20
APALACHICOLA	29,7267	84,9817	-	0%	7,000,000	5,6075	-	5,6075	13,0926	13,0926	0,15	50,15
RHODOSII	36,4417	28,2364	-	0%	7,000,000	35,6773	-	35,6773	35,6773	35,6773	0,22	10,60
ISHIGAKI	24,3333	124,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	14,4178	-	14,4178	14,4178	14,4178	1,51	45,43
SANCRISTOBAL	0,9000	89,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	7,9251	-	7,9251	7,9251	7,9251	0,52	35,28

SANTANDERIII	43,4613	- 3,7908	-	0%	7,000,000	- 83,1271	-	83,1271	- 83,1271	83,1271	0,21	- 122,63
BOURNEMOUTH	50,7143	- 1,8749	-	0%	7,000,000	- 13,3206	-	13,3206	- 13,3206	13,3206	0,08	- 7,81
PORTMAURIZIO	43,8667	- 8,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 137,4834	-	137,4834	- 137,4834	137,4834	0,51	- 396,96
CATANIAII	37,4981	- 15,0938	-	0%	7,000,000	- 168,3154	-	168,3154	- 168,3154	168,3154	0,01	- 170,17
CEBU	10,3000	- 123,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 49,2431	-	49,2431	- 49,2431	49,2431	0,14	- 86,55
ULSAN	35,5019	- 129,3872	-	0%	7,000,000	- 40,9394	-	40,9394	- 40,9394	40,9394	0,71	- 93,82
NETTEN	66,9667	- 171,9333	-	0%	7,000,000	- 68,5527	-	68,5527	- 68,5527	68,5527	0,66	- 210,16
VLISSINGEN	51,4422	- 3,5961	-	0%	7,000,000	- 224,0138	-	224,0138	- 224,0138	224,0138	0,42	- 424,04
SINES	37,9500	- 8,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	- 21,0833	-	21,0833	- 21,0833	21,0833	1,65	- 81,47
GOTEBORG-KLIPPAN	57,6833	- 11,9000	-	0%	7,000,000	- 57,3633	-	57,3633	- 57,3633	57,3633	0,10	- 123,43
BELFAST2	54,6000	- 5,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 31,5755	-	31,5755	- 31,5755	31,5755	0,12	- 82,92
SAINTPIERREETMIQUELON	46,7788	- 56,1683	-	0%	7,000,000	- 42,7524	-	42,7524	- 37,9301	37,9301	0,08	- 28,40
NELSON	- 41,2613	- 173,2728	-	0%	7,000,000	- 22,2706	-	22,2706	- 22,2706	22,2706	1,61	- 61,69
ONAGAWA	38,4333	- 141,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	- 46,4458	-	46,4458	- 47,6180	47,6180	0,03	- 57,66
CHAMPERICO	14,2833	- 91,9167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 18,0296	-	18,0296	- 18,0296	18,0296	0,27	- 39,26
PORTMACDONNELLI	- 38,0000	- 140,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	- 45,3894	-	45,3894	- 45,3894	45,3894	0,21	- 106,22
LEVERDON	45,5500	- 1,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	- 131,7989	-	131,7989	- 131,7989	131,7989	0,21	- 117,84
CUTLER	44,6500	- 67,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 93,7202	-	93,7202	- 93,7202	93,7202	0,51	- 136,98
KUNSAN	35,9833	- 126,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	- 26,2207	-	26,2207	- 26,2207	26,2207	0,09	- 8,54
ANTIFER	49,6500	- 0,1500	-	0%	7,000,000	- 24,2640	-	24,2640	- 24,2640	24,2640	0,02	- 22,52
KOMATSUSHIMA	34,0092	- 134,5878	-	0%	7,000,000	- 54,2808	-	54,2808	- 54,2808	54,2808	3,37	- 109,89
ARUNPLATFORM	50,7698	- 0,4921	-	0%	7,000,000	- 12,3415	-	12,3415	- 18,5077	18,5077	0,18	- 43,27
LAE	- 6,7500	- 147,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	- 65,1851	-	65,1851	- 65,1851	65,1851	0,39	- 1,16
CAIRNS	- 16,9167	- 145,7833	-	0%	7,000,000	- 91,7591	-	91,7591	- 91,7591	91,7591	0,05	- 80,87
PORTNOLLOTH	- 29,2567	- 16,8678	-	0%	7,000,000	- 2,8586	-	2,8586	- 2,8586	2,8586	0,06	- 12,14
BALINTANG,QUEZON,PALAWAN	9,3500	- 118,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	- 19,7150	-	19,7150	- 19,7150	19,7150	0,15	- 38,15
RORVIK	64,8595	- 11,2301	-	0%	7,000,000	- 14,5248	-	14,5248	- 14,5248	14,5248	0,45	- 46,62
ALERT	82,4900	- 62,3200	-	0%	7,000,000	- 79,8034	-	79,8034	- 79,8034	79,8034	0,16	- 46,15

LEHAVRE	49,4819	0,1060	-	0%	7,000,000	59,8143	-	-	59,8143	58,4707	-	58,4707	0,20	-	29,45
PORTARANSAS,H.CALDWELLPIER	27,8267	-	-	0%	7,000,000	8,1350	-	-	8,1350	8,1350	-	8,1350	0,11	-	15,47
TAIPOKAU,TOLOHARBOUR	22,4425	114,1839	-	0%	7,000,000	19,3355	-	-	19,3355	19,3355	-	19,3355	0,14	-	32,49
KINGSTON	-	36,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	3,8692	-	3,8692	3,8692	-	3,8692	0,28	-	11,08
ESPERANZA,VIEQUES	18,0933	-	-	0%	7,000,000	57,2075	-	-	57,2075	37,9966	-	37,9966	0,38	-	8,89
ROVINJ	45,0833	13,6283	-	0%	7,000,000	67,5669	-	-	67,5669	67,5669	-	67,5669	0,21	-	40,54
BODRUMII	37,0333	27,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5262	-	-	1,5262	1,5262	-	1,5262	0,51	-	33,94
WYNDHAM	-	15,4533	-	0%	7,000,000	46,8236	-	-	46,8236	46,8236	-	46,8236	0,34	-	80,22
KIGILIAH	73,3333	139,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	23,6992	-	-	23,6992	23,6992	-	23,6992	0,35	-	46,89
HOSOJIMA	32,4286	131,6694	-	0%	7,000,000	42,4342	-	-	42,4342	42,4342	-	42,4342	0,06	-	33,45
SALAMANDER	-	33,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	521,9683	-	-	521,9683	475,2645	-	475,2645	1,95	-	5,27
BELLEDUNE	47,9000	-	-	0%	7,000,000	19,5674	-	-	19,5674	18,7739	-	18,7739	0,06	-	29,90
KUREIII	34,2333	132,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	3,8657	-	-	3,8657	3,8657	-	3,8657	0,57	-	126,86
CHRISTMASISLAND	1,9833	-	-	0%	7,000,000	81,0771	-	-	81,0771	81,0771	-	81,0771	2,00	-	211,98
UGORSKIISHAR(UGORSKIISHARPROLIV)	69,8167	60,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	68,2367	-	-	68,2367	70,8087	-	70,8087	0,06	-	89,95
PORTLAND	-	38,3434	-	0%	7,000,000	21,6107	-	-	21,6107	31,3403	-	31,3403	0,16	-	63,02
TOWERPIER	51,5000	0,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	82,5961	-	-	82,5961	82,5961	-	82,5961	0,65	-	8,53
WALVISBAY	-	22,9493	-	0%	7,000,000	-	9,4848	-	9,4848	9,4848	-	9,4848	0,03	-	5,12
FAMAGUSTA	35,1167	33,9500	-	0%	7,000,000	29,7112	-	-	29,7112	29,7112	-	29,7112	0,14	-	23,25
GOTEBORG-TORSHAMNEN	57,6847	11,7906	-	0%	7,000,000	25,6941	-	-	25,6941	25,6941	-	25,6941	0,25	-	48,61
PORTRUSH	55,2068	-	-	0%	7,000,000	48,2639	-	-	48,2639	48,2639	-	48,2639	0,16	-	19,91
TADIBE-IAHA	70,3667	72,5667	-	0%	7,000,000	79,1024	-	-	79,1024	79,1024	-	79,1024	0,35	-	113,14
HAMADAI	34,8972	132,0661	-	0%	7,000,000	33,3431	-	-	33,3431	33,3431	-	33,3431	0,00	-	33,95
CHATHAMISLAND	-	43,9463	-	0%	7,000,000	38,8166	-	-	38,8166	38,8166	-	38,8166	0,47	-	68,78
CARLOFORTE	39,1480	8,3095	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8668	-	-	61,8668	61,8668	-	61,8668	0,10	-	52,95
PEVEK	69,7000	170,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	23,5339	-	-	23,5339	23,5339	-	23,5339	0,11	-	4,76
ESBJERG	55,4608	8,4411	-	0%	7,000,000	67,6427	-	-	67,6427	67,6427	-	67,6427	0,24	-	139,75
PORTCHICAGO,CALIFORNIA	38,0550	-	-	0%	7,000,000	45,1550	-	-	45,1550	45,1550	-	45,1550	2,50	-	110,15

CHRISTMASISLANDII	1,9833	-	-	0%	7,000,000	22,5516	-	-	22,5516	22,5516	-	0,01	20,72
RIKITEA	23,1223	134,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	89,9012	-	89,9012	89,9012	89,9012	-	1,24	51,99
ITOI	34,9667	139,1167	-	0%	7,000,000	1,7726	-	1,7726	1,7726	1,7726	-	0,11	27,34
DAVAO,DAVAOGULF	7,0833	125,6333	-	0%	7,000,000	40,2743	-	40,2743	40,2743	40,2743	-	0,11	81,56
TAPPI	41,2425	140,3814	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9846	-	19,9846	19,9846	19,9846	-	0,12	5,13
MILLPORT	55,7498	4,9063	-	0%	7,000,000	91,8847	-	91,8847	91,8847	91,8847	-	0,03	84,69
MONAISLAND	18,0900	67,9383	-	0%	7,000,000	5,1743	-	5,1743	3,2974	3,2974	-	0,09	10,69
PORTANGELES,WASHINGTON	48,1250	123,4400	-	0%	7,000,000	16,7873	-	16,7873	16,7873	16,7873	-	0,35	24,85
NANSHA	9,5500	112,8800	-	0%	7,000,000	196,7377	-	196,7377	196,7377	196,7377	-	0,22	237,82
PINEYPOINT,MARYLAND	38,1333	76,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	30,4654	-	30,4654	30,4654	30,4654	-	0,31	8,21
ABURATSUBO	35,1603	139,6153	-	0%	7,000,000	37,4864	-	37,4864	37,4864	37,4864	-	0,08	40,57
YAIZU	34,8706	138,3272	-	0%	7,000,000	60,1396	-	60,1396	60,1396	60,1396	-	0,12	82,74
WLADYSLAWOWO	54,8000	18,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	50,5576	-	50,5576	50,5576	50,5576	-	0,49	26,73
SOUTHPASS	28,9900	89,1400	-	0%	7,000,000	3,5037	-	3,5037	3,5037	3,5037	-	0,12	17,81
TOPOLOBAMPO	25,6000	109,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	68,2460	-	68,2460	68,2460	68,2460	-	0,00	68,30
SIMONSBAY	34,1878	18,4401	-	0%	7,000,000	3,8003	-	3,8003	2,3460	2,3460	-	0,21	69,66
PLUMISLAND	41,1667	72,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	1,5074	-	1,5074	1,5074	1,5074	-	0,25	65,29
PUERTOWILLIAMS	54,9167	67,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9035	-	19,9035	19,9035	19,9035	-	0,59	15,99
RANGIROA	14,9458	147,7060	-	0%	7,000,000	12,7620	-	12,7620	21,7273	21,7273	-	1,11	173,09
LUDERITZ	26,6433	15,1550	-	0%	7,000,000	0,1970	-	0,1970	0,1970	0,1970	-	0,08	11,04
TANGGU	39,0000	117,7167	-	0%	7,000,000	53,9189	-	53,9189	57,5524	57,5524	-	0,03	60,41
TARANTO	40,4333	17,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	92,1012	-	92,1012	92,1012	92,1012	-	0,34	120,78
LEIXOES	41,1833	8,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	76,5118	-	76,5118	76,5118	76,5118	-	0,18	98,44
EVANSHEAD	29,1167	153,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	125,0919	-	125,0919	125,0919	125,0919	-	0,24	155,10
WACHAPREAGUE	37,6067	75,6867	-	0%	7,000,000	46,7118	-	46,7118	81,2002	81,2002	-	0,41	91,21
MACKAY	21,1000	149,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	3,3836	-	3,3836	3,3836	3,3836	-	0,59	21,30
FORTALEZA	3,7167	38,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	98,5179	-	98,5179	98,5179	98,5179	-	0,05	113,30
CONCARNEAU	47,8737	3,9074	-	0%	7,000,000	123,5019	-	123,5019	123,5019	123,5019	-	0,15	94,01
ARINAGA	27,8469	15,4015	-	0%	7,000,000	12,9066	-	12,9066	12,9066	12,9066	-	0,04	9,20

GIRNE	35,3500	33,3333	-	0%	7.000,0000	57,4241	-	57,4241	57,4241	-	57,4241	0,34	83,24
KOBBAKLINTAR	60,0333	19,8833	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,4405	-	0,4405	0,4405	-	0,4405	2,64	79,75
ANGRADOHEROISMO	38,6500	27,2333	-	0%	7.000,0000	38,0534	-	38,0534	38,0534	-	38,0534	0,00	38,07
DIEGORAMIREZ	56,5000	68,7167	-	0%	7.000,0000	19,5866	-	19,5866	19,5866	-	19,5866	0,17	47,88
COCOSISLAND(HOMEIS.)	12,1167	96,8944	-	0%	7.000,0000	3,5762	-	3,5762	3,5762	-	3,5762	0,05	10,18
LARKHARBOUR	49,1000	58,3667	-	0%	7.000,0000	5,4945	-	5,4945	5,4945	-	5,4945	0,26	6,00
PRUDHOEBAY,ALASKA	70,4000	148,5267	-	0%	7.000,0000	19,3032	-	19,3032	26,1093	-	26,1093	1,29	275,35
DRAGHALLAN	62,3667	17,5333	-	0%	7.000,0000	190,5133	-	190,5133	190,5133	-	190,5133	0,50	464,79
SWINOUJSCIE	53,9167	14,2333	-	0%	7.000,0000	133,7383	-	133,7383	133,7383	-	133,7383	0,06	207,07
CHABAHARII	25,2958	60,6033	-	0%	7.000,0000	48,1839	-	48,1839	48,1839	-	48,1839	0,06	51,88
ESPERANCE	33,8709	121,8954	-	0%	7.000,0000	35,6404	-	35,6404	35,6404	-	35,6404	0,04	39,03
CHARLESTONI	32,7817	79,9250	-	0%	7.000,0000	7,7272	-	7,7272	7,7272	-	7,7272	0,18	15,95
ISABELADESAGUA	22,9333	80,0167	-	0%	7.000,0000	42,1282	-	42,1282	42,1282	-	42,1282	0,07	50,13
STOMPNEUSBAY	32,7167	17,9833	-	0%	7.000,0000	3,9375	-	3,9375	3,9375	-	3,9375	0,01	1,46
PAGOBAY,GUAM	13,4283	144,7967	-	0%	7.000,0000	34,7041	-	34,7041	34,7041	-	34,7041	0,15	17,07
MAJURO-B	7,1000	171,3667	-	0%	7.000,0000	8,7452	-	8,7452	8,7452	-	8,7452	0,08	2,46
VIRGINIABEACH	36,8500	75,9667	-	0%	7.000,0000	18,2228	-	18,2228	12,4985	-	12,4985	0,05	1,16
MALYEKARMAKULY	72,3667	52,7000	-	0%	7.000,0000	4.245,1482	-	4.245,1482	4.245,1482	-	4.245,1482	2,58	4.281,21
VADSO	70,0667	29,7500	-	0%	7.000,0000	38,1765	-	38,1765	38,1765	-	38,1765	1,97	89,42
MOMMARK	54,9333	10,0667	-	0%	7.000,0000	149,5602	-	149,5602	149,5602	-	149,5602	0,15	192,32
LYTTELTONII	43,6056	172,7219	-	0%	7.000,0000	19,9147	-	19,9147	19,9147	-	19,9147	0,05	23,38
BRISBANE(WESTINNERBAR)	27,3667	153,1667	-	0%	7.000,0000	1,0586	-	1,0586	1,4166	-	1,4166	0,05	14,08
KWAJALEIN	8,7317	167,7350	-	0%	7.000,0000	69,8579	-	69,8579	69,8579	-	69,8579	0,04	78,93
SANFELIX	26,2922	80,1086	-	0%	7.000,0000	1,1905	-	1,1905	1,1905	-	1,1905	1,16	125,99
ANTALYAI	36,8333	30,6167	-	0%	7.000,0000	34,9738	-	34,9738	34,9738	-	34,9738	0,12	42,17
DUBROVNIK	42,6583	18,0633	-	0%	7.000,0000	64,0084	-	64,0084	64,0084	-	64,0084	0,13	39,55
KUSHIMOTO	33,4758	135,7733	-	0%	7.000,0000	55,6726	-	55,6726	55,6726	-	55,6726	0,06	65,20
KOTELNYI(KOTELNYIOSTROV)	76,0000	137,8667	-	0%	7.000,0000	17,3734	-	17,3734	17,3734	-	17,3734	0,17	48,19
ADEN	12,7883	44,9742	-	0%	7.000,0000	86,4664	-	86,4664	86,4664	-	86,4664	0,09	122,56

HAKATA	33,6189	130,4078	-	0%	7,000,000	16,5064	-	-	16,5064	16,5064	-	16,5064	0,26	-	4,59
ONISAKI	34,9039	136,8236	-	0%	7,000,000	59,6229	-	-	59,6229	59,6229	-	59,6229	0,23	-	18,97
MONTEREY	36,6050	121,8867	-	0%	7,000,000	10,2329	-	-	10,2329	19,1203	-	19,1203	0,13	-	48,46
MASAN	35,2100	128,5889	-	0%	7,000,000	0,6718	-	-	0,6718	0,6718	-	0,6718	0,14	-	17,58
MALINHEAD	55,3667	7,3333	-	0%	7,000,000	19,5413	-	-	19,5413	19,5413	-	19,5413	0,04	-	25,17
SIROS	37,4400	24,9458	-	0%	7,000,000	47,4903	-	-	47,4903	47,4903	-	47,4903	0,03	-	49,91
NISINOOMOTE	30,7350	130,9922	-	0%	7,000,000	61,8141	-	-	61,8141	61,8141	-	61,8141	0,05	-	59,47
DARWIN	12,4718	130,8459	-	0%	7,000,000	6,5117	-	-	6,5117	17,7296	-	17,7296	0,21	-	78,46
HONIARA-B	9,4289	159,9554	-	0%	7,000,000	58,8020	-	-	58,8020	58,8020	-	58,8020	0,24	-	79,98
ROCKPORT	28,0217	97,0467	-	0%	7,000,000	51,2580	-	-	51,2580	51,2580	-	51,2580	0,17	-	30,14
AMASRA	41,4333	32,2333	-	0%	7,000,000	11,5387	-	-	11,5387	11,5387	-	11,5387	0,62	-	29,12
NASEIII	28,5000	129,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	68,9825	-	-	68,9825	68,9825	-	68,9825	0,32	-	92,33
ARGENTIA	47,3000	53,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	20,3379	-	-	20,3379	20,3379	-	20,3379	0,49	-	38,88
FREDERICIA	55,5608	9,7544	-	0%	7,000,000	33,6620	-	-	33,6620	33,6620	-	33,6620	0,05	-	65,50
RAU-CHUA	69,5000	166,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	30,3641	-	-	30,3641	49,5579	-	49,5579	0,12	-	81,93
PORTHARDY	50,7167	127,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	81,5493	-	-	81,5493	81,5493	-	81,5493	0,15	-	65,77
MALAKAL-B	7,3333	134,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	28,6166	-	-	28,6166	28,6166	-	28,6166	0,09	-	25,88
FORT-DE-FRANCEII	14,6015	61,0632	-	0%	7,000,000	13,8934	-	-	13,8934	13,8934	-	13,8934	0,02	-	16,17
CHUJADO	33,9617	126,3003	-	0%	7,000,000	16,7858	-	-	16,7858	16,7858	-	16,7858	0,09	-	9,06
LAPAZ	24,1667	110,3500	-	0%	7,000,000	21,6761	-	-	21,6761	21,6761	-	21,6761	0,48	-	4,28
SANTABARBARA,CALIFORNIA	34,4083	119,6850	-	0%	7,000,000	68,1843	-	-	68,1843	68,1843	-	68,1843	0,08	-	78,78
RIVIERE-AU-RENARD	49,0000	64,3833	-	0%	7,000,000	58,2292	-	-	58,2292	58,2292	-	58,2292	0,25	-	29,95
LOWESTOFT	52,4731	1,7501	-	0%	7,000,000	55,9640	-	-	55,9640	55,9640	-	55,9640	0,10	-	30,10
TAGO	34,8069	138,7642	-	0%	7,000,000	0,2407	-	-	0,2407	0,2407	-	0,2407	0,34	-	63,54
NAPOLI(ARSENALE)	40,8667	14,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	22,8679	-	-	22,8679	22,8679	-	22,8679	0,20	-	37,69
PUERTOANGEL	15,5000	96,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	4,2541	-	-	4,2541	4,2541	-	4,2541	0,08	-	14,44
ENSENADA	31,8500	116,6333	-	0%	7,000,000	0,9833	-	-	0,9833	0,9833	-	0,9833	0,14	-	17,91
USHUAIAI	54,8167	68,2167	-	0%	7,000,000	2,0183	-	-	2,0183	2,0183	-	2,0183	0,23	-	57,92

TUBUAI	-	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	51,5614	-	-	51,5614	-	0,02	49,21
PULAU LANGKAWI	6,4308	99,7642	-	0%	7.000,0000	29,0371	-	29,0371	29,0371	29,0371	0,10	18,61
KALIX	65,6969	23,0961	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,7872	-	0,7872	0,7872	0,7872	0,20	11,15
CATANIA	37,5000	15,1333	-	0%	7.000,0000	208,0487	-	208,0487	208,0487	208,0487	0,37	315,37
SHIJIUSUO	35,3833	119,5500	-	0%	7.000,0000	155,3188	-	155,3188	155,3188	155,3188	0,07	170,97
PORTERIN	54,0854	4,7681	-	0%	7.000,0000	38,6308	-	38,6308	38,6308	38,6308	1,51	102,86
DIGBY	44,6333	65,7500	-	0%	7.000,0000	14,0709	-	14,0709	14,0709	14,0709	0,25	16,02
VALKARKAI	70,0833	170,9333	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,3146	-	0,3146	0,3146	0,3146	0,09	10,36
BLUFF(SOUTHLANDHARBOUR)	-	-	-	0%	7.000,0000	45,5319	-	45,5319	45,5319	45,5319	0,03	42,52
ACAJUTLA2	13,5833	89,8333	-	0%	7.000,0000	30,9781	-	30,9781	30,9781	30,9781	0,24	78,11
PASAJES	43,3266	1,9218	-	0%	7.000,0000	111,0209	-	111,0209	111,0209	111,0209	0,31	207,83
GRANADILLA	28,0853	16,4896	-	0%	7.000,0000	50,5826	-	50,5826	50,5826	50,5826	0,08	56,07
EASTPORT	44,9033	66,9817	-	0%	7.000,0000	40,1776	-	40,1776	40,1776	40,1776	0,16	47,52
VIKER	59,0360	10,9498	-	0%	7.000,0000	75,5357	-	75,5357	75,5357	75,5357	0,40	41,87
OSLO	59,9086	10,7345	-	0%	7.000,0000	139,7704	-	139,7704	139,7704	139,7704	0,37	251,42
PALMEIRA	16,7500	22,9833	-	0%	7.000,0000	7,0056	-	7,0056	7,0056	7,0056	0,43	38,03
TACLOBAN, LEYTE	11,2500	125,0000	-	0%	7.000,0000	13,5429	-	13,5429	13,5429	13,5429	0,63	47,13
BOULOGNE	50,7275	1,5775	-	0%	7.000,0000	59,1310	-	59,1310	59,1310	59,1310	0,31	163,76
TOKYOI	35,6667	139,7667	-	0%	7.000,0000	39,2152	-	39,2152	39,2152	39,2152	0,30	113,87
CABOCRUZ	19,8333	77,7333	-	0%	7.000,0000	32,0981	-	32,0981	32,0981	32,0981	0,11	20,45
PELABUHANKELANG	3,0500	101,3583	-	0%	7.000,0000	1,7836	-	1,7836	1,7836	1,7836	1,08	18,79
BAIE COMEAU	49,2333	68,1333	-	0%	7.000,0000	32,5900	-	32,5900	32,5900	32,5900	0,12	48,95
PROGRESO	21,3000	89,6667	-	0%	7.000,0000	21,6477	-	21,6477	14,2645	14,2645	0,15	35,93
LANDSORTNORRA	58,7689	17,8589	-	0%	7.000,0000	23,9859	-	23,9859	23,9859	23,9859	0,39	3,99
LEITHII	55,9898	3,1817	-	0%	7.000,0000	3,6518	-	3,6518	3,6518	3,6518	1,92	62,29
SAINTJOHN, N.B.	45,2667	66,0667	-	0%	7.000,0000	19,0209	-	19,0209	19,3786	19,3786	0,11	80,63
NORTHSALAMINOSII	37,9796	23,5342	-	0%	7.000,0000	51,4595	-	51,4595	51,4595	51,4595	0,21	32,07
TANGACHIMADAM	9,2833	79,2500	-	0%	7.000,0000	103,0480	-	103,0480	103,0480	103,0480	0,90	76,82

PICTOU	45,6833	-	62,7000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	33,3504	-	33,3504	0,55	-	71,62
LACORUNAI	43,3643	-	8,3989	-	0%	7,000,000	-	44,2341	-	44,2341	0,77	-	141,59
SAGYLLAH-ARY	73,1500	-	128,8833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	2,3963	-	2,3963	0,29	-	68,15
THESSALONIKI	40,6325	-	22,9349	-	0%	7,000,000	-	20,1265	-	20,1265	0,42	-	80,76
PORTALMA	-	-	23,5833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	13,9729	-	13,9729	0,38	-	25,09
AYUKAWA	38,2967	-	141,5053	-	0%	7,000,000	-	36,5729	-	36,5729	0,15	-	70,22
USTKA	54,5833	-	16,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	34,5105	-	34,5105	0,49	-	108,56
POTI	42,1667	-	41,6833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	109,3595	-	109,3595	0,06	-	94,08
RUSTICO	46,4667	-	63,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	4,5125	-	4,5125	0,19	-	34,94
SALALAH	16,9333	-	54,0000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	76,3133	-	76,3133	0,29	-	45,63
MILFORDHAVEN(NEWTONNOYES)	51,7000	-	5,0167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	71,6129	-	71,6129	0,11	-	142,81
RANGOON	16,7667	-	96,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	17,8843	-	17,8843	0,09	-	33,38
ODOMARI	31,0236	-	130,6892	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,2272	-	7,2272	0,12	-	1,24
AION	69,9333	-	167,9833	-	0%	7,000,000	-	27,0621	-	27,0621	0,26	-	10,01
SULTANSHOAL	1,2333	-	103,6500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,5760	-	7,5760	0,85	-	23,39
BONANZA	36,8022	-	6,3381	-	0%	7,000,000	-	24,1836	-	24,1836	0,47	-	38,11
KUDAT	6,8794	-	116,8436	-	0%	7,000,000	-	44,9089	-	44,9089	0,19	-	65,46
DUTCHHARBOR	53,9000	-	166,5333	-	0%	7,000,000	-	31,8113	-	31,8113	0,18	-	100,67
BARENTSBURG	78,0667	-	14,2500	-	0%	7,000,000	-	16,9499	-	16,9499	0,19	-	22,74
TUTICORIN	8,7500	-	78,2000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	19,1316	-	19,1316	0,14	-	11,70
PATRAI	38,4167	-	21,7287	-	0%	7,000,000	-	15,1186	-	15,1186	0,20	-	7,54
NEDRESODERTALJE	59,2000	-	17,6167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	155,3188	-	155,3188	0,23	-	252,66
KOBENHAVN	55,7050	-	12,6000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	20,7575	-	20,7575	0,18	-	43,63
RODRIGUESIS	-	-	19,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	3,7153	-	3,7153	0,51	-	78,11
TANJUNGGELANG	3,9750	-	103,4300	-	0%	7,000,000	-	589,0359	-	589,0359	0,17	-	578,90
CHOSHII	35,7333	-	140,8667	-	0%	7,000,000	-	1,8902	-	1,8902	0,11	-	26,10
DIEPPE	49,9291	-	1,0838	-	0%	7,000,000	-	4,7446	-	4,7446	0,14	-	24,59
RINCONISLAND	34,3483	-	119,4417	-	0%	7,000,000	-	45,8475	-	45,8475	0,01	-	43,83

TRONDHEIM	63,4333	10,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	137,4191	-	-	137,4191	137,4191	-	0,29	312,45
SOUTHPORT	33,9150	78,0183	-	0%	7,000,000	50,5014	-	50,5014	50,5014	50,5014	-	0,37	123,39
SEATTLE	47,6017	122,3383	-	0%	7,000,000	38,9975	-	38,9975	38,9975	38,9975	-	0,56	60,97
HAMMERFEST	70,6646	23,6832	-	0%	7,000,000	12,9481	-	12,9481	12,9481	12,9481	-	0,14	29,60
KUREIV	34,2406	132,5503	-	0%	7,000,000	10,3070	-	10,3070	10,3070	10,3070	-	0,19	47,61
ANTOFAGASTA2	23,6531	70,4044	-	0%	7,000,000	57,7029	-	57,7029	57,1015	57,1015	-	0,19	21,10
CURRIMAOILOCOSNORTE	17,9833	120,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	40,2826	-	40,2826	40,2826	40,2826	-	0,13	29,85
ST-JEAN-PORT-JOLI	47,2167	70,2833	-	0%	7,000,000	18,2488	-	18,2488	18,2488	18,2488	-	0,68	107,58
NAPOLI(MANDRACCHIO)	40,8429	14,2575	-	0%	7,000,000	6,2031	-	6,2031	6,2031	6,2031	-	0,20	24,49
ARGENTINEISLANDS	65,2462	64,2574	-	0%	7,000,000	47,8894	-	47,8894	47,8894	47,8894	-	0,01	49,47
ALAMEDA(NAVALAIRSTATION)	37,7717	122,2983	-	0%	7,000,000	22,2000	-	22,2000	22,2000	22,2000	-	0,34	11,96
TAKAMATSUI	34,3514	134,0569	-	0%	7,000,000	1,4119	-	1,4119	1,4119	1,4119	-	0,17	27,88
EXMOUTH	21,9549	114,1409	-	0%	7,000,000	56,1899	-	56,1899	56,1899	56,1899	-	0,75	96,30
ST-FRANCOIS	47,0000	70,8167	-	0%	7,000,000	21,4182	-	21,4182	21,4182	21,4182	-	0,04	19,31
VICTORIA	48,4167	123,3667	-	0%	7,000,000	65,1943	-	65,1943	65,1943	65,1943	-	0,23	32,40
PORTBLOC	45,5685	1,0616	-	0%	7,000,000	64,1075	-	64,1075	64,1075	64,1075	-	0,78	29,36
XIAMEN	24,4500	118,0667	-	0%	7,000,000	69,1788	-	69,1788	69,1788	69,1788	-	0,03	77,93
PORTFERREOL	43,3591	6,7176	-	0%	7,000,000	7,3360	-	7,3360	7,3360	7,3360	-	1,30	65,13
NEWROCHELLE	40,8933	73,7817	-	0%	7,000,000	50,7768	-	50,7768	50,7768	50,7768	-	0,05	51,61
CALAIS	50,9694	1,8677	-	0%	7,000,000	16,3719	-	16,3719	16,3719	16,3719	-	0,10	25,24
MURMANSKII	68,9667	33,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	10,1869	-	10,1869	12,3651	12,3651	-	0,17	67,28
KAWAIHAE,HAWAIIISLAND	20,0367	155,8300	-	0%	7,000,000	8,9232	-	8,9232	8,9232	8,9232	-	0,19	31,28
PAGETISLAND	32,3667	64,6667	-	0%	7,000,000	4,4368	-	4,4368	4,4368	4,4368	-	0,18	35,50
HOBART	42,8773	147,3410	-	0%	7,000,000	0,4778	-	0,4778	0,4778	0,4778	-	0,24	60,42
LUMUT	4,2400	100,6133	-	0%	7,000,000	45,4249	-	45,4249	45,4249	45,4249	-	2,79	6,11
VICTORHARBOUR	35,5625	138,6354	-	0%	7,000,000	28,9835	-	28,9835	28,9835	28,9835	-	0,04	18,28
TOLCHESTERBEACH,MARYLAND	39,2133	76,2450	-	0%	7,000,000	54,1228	-	54,1228	54,1228	54,1228	-	0,25	62,35
VANKAREM	67,8333	175,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	7,9316	-	7,9316	7,9316	7,9316	-	0,25	36,28

KEPPELHARBOUR	1,2667	103,8167	-	0%	7,000,000	-	7,5833	-	7,5833	-	7,5833	0,90	-	18,84
HIRONPOINT	21,7833	89,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	5,7894	-	5,7894	5,7894	5,7894	5,7894	0,20	-	17,19
OFUNATOII	39,0197	141,7533	-	0%	7,000,000	66,7426	-	66,7426	66,7426	66,7426	66,7426	0,01	-	68,77
GARIBALDI	45,5550	123,9183	-	0%	7,000,000	36,0537	-	36,0537	36,0537	36,0537	36,0537	0,07	-	44,89
RODBYHAVN	54,6558	11,3486	-	0%	7,000,000	30,6832	-	30,6832	30,6832	30,6832	30,6832	0,02	-	28,00
DEVONPORT	41,1847	146,3624	-	0%	7,000,000	55,8984	-	55,8984	55,8984	55,8984	55,8984	0,27	-	29,86
HUELVA	37,1320	6,8337	-	0%	7,000,000	17,3544	-	17,3544	17,3544	17,3544	17,3544	3,74	-	86,62
LOWHEAD	41,0644	146,7947	-	0%	7,000,000	48,0154	-	48,0154	48,0154	48,0154	48,0154	0,22	-	25,80
GARDENREACH	22,5500	88,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	257,0730	-	257,0730	257,0730	257,0730	257,0730	0,10	-	281,32
CIUDADMADERO	22,2500	97,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	29,8444	-	29,8444	29,8444	29,8444	29,8444	0,40	-	124,92
ANCUD	41,8669	73,8319	-	0%	7,000,000	41,0596	-	41,0596	41,0596	41,0596	41,0596	0,41	-	22,88
KOLOBRZEG	54,1833	15,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	83,2483	-	83,2483	83,2483	83,2483	83,2483	0,03	-	87,50
WAJIMA	37,4058	136,9003	-	0%	7,000,000	3,1470	-	3,1470	3,1470	3,1470	3,1470	0,21	-	29,42
JANGHANG	36,0069	126,6878	-	0%	7,000,000	82,0034	-	82,0034	82,0034	82,0034	82,0034	0,29	-	122,26
HINKLEYPPOINT	51,2106	3,1313	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5234	-	44,5234	44,5234	44,5234	44,5234	0,09	-	35,62
SUMOTO	34,3406	134,9067	-	0%	7,000,000	35,8741	-	35,8741	35,8741	35,8741	35,8741	0,28	-	44,87
SOUDHAS	35,4875	24,0825	-	0%	7,000,000	73,4175	-	73,4175	73,4175	73,4175	73,4175	0,42	-	120,98
ANCONA	43,5833	13,4833	-	0%	7,000,000	48,7109	-	48,7109	48,7109	48,7109	48,7109	0,09	-	19,08
TUXPAN	21,0000	97,3333	-	0%	7,000,000	2,9585	-	2,9585	2,9585	2,9585	2,9585	0,09	-	13,60
LAJESDASFLORES	39,3785	31,1686	-	0%	7,000,000	17,1448	-	17,1448	17,1448	17,1448	17,1448	0,57	-	82,33
LACORUNAI	43,3573	8,3893	-	0%	7,000,000	84,1211	-	84,1211	84,1211	84,1211	84,1211	0,42	-	25,36
TALLINN	59,4500	24,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	72,0437	-	72,0437	72,0437	72,0437	72,0437	0,90	-	123,60
TOWNSVILLE	19,2500	146,8333	-	0%	7,000,000	63,6123	-	63,6123	63,6123	63,6123	63,6123	0,10	-	46,46
SANTACRUZDELAPALMA	28,6797	17,7664	-	0%	7,000,000	29,3744	-	29,3744	29,3744	29,3744	29,3744	0,14	-	59,42
MOTRIL2	36,7202	3,5236	-	0%	7,000,000	47,8764	-	47,8764	47,8764	47,8764	47,8764	0,10	-	53,89
MORMUGAO	15,4167	73,8000	-	0%	7,000,000	19,9490	-	19,9490	19,9490	19,9490	19,9490	1,81	-	91,30
ROSYTH	56,0167	3,4500	-	0%	7,000,000	4,4048	-	4,4048	4,4048	4,4048	4,4048	0,24	-	54,25
MOBILESTATEDOCKS,ALABAMA	30,7050	88,0400	-	0%	7,000,000	42,2099	-	42,2099	42,2099	42,2099	42,2099	0,57	-	13,32

CHENNAI	13,1000	80,3000	-	0%	7,000,000	-	2,1766	-	2,1766	-	2,1766	0,13	-	66,70
CUTLERII	44,6417	67,2967	-	0%	7,000,000	65,3635	-	65,3635	65,3635	-	65,3635	0,31	-	54,83
IJMUIDEN	52,4622	4,5547	-	0%	7,000,000	126,1608	-	126,1608	126,1608	-	126,1608	0,15	-	189,76
SHIMONOSEKIII	33,9250	130,9278	-	0%	7,000,000	16,6297	-	16,6297	16,6297	-	16,6297	3,74	-	69,05
NEMKOVA(NEMKOVAOSTROV)	71,4167	150,7500	-	0%	7,000,000	44,5655	-	44,5655	44,5655	-	44,5655	0,90	-	113,56
NARVIK	68,4283	17,4258	-	0%	7,000,000	65,4685	-	65,4685	65,4685	-	65,4685	0,01	-	69,36
KRENKELIA(HEISAOSTROV)	80,6167	58,0500	-	0%	7,000,000	3,7740	-	3,7740	2,1997	-	2,1997	0,09	-	23,77
SANTAMONICA(MUNICIPALPIER)	34,0083	118,5000	-	0%	7,000,000	31,4410	-	31,4410	25,1976	-	25,1976	0,45	-	7,21
TROIS-RIVIERES	46,3333	72,5500	-	0%	7,000,000	25,0358	-	25,0358	25,0358	-	25,0358	0,59	-	39,28
ISLADECEDROS	28,1000	115,1833	-	0%	7,000,000	28,5312	-	28,5312	28,5312	-	28,5312	0,44	-	0,66
OSCARSBORG	59,6781	10,6049	-	0%	7,000,000	286,2251	-	286,2251	286,2251	-	286,2251	0,52	-	504,89
FORSMARK	60,4086	18,2108	-	0%	7,000,000	8,5385	-	8,5385	8,5385	-	8,5385	0,11	-	14,36
ASHDODII	31,8313	34,6405	-	0%	7,000,000	47,2106	-	47,2106	47,2106	-	47,2106	0,28	-	24,45
ANTOFAGASTA	23,6500	70,4167	-	0%	7,000,000	14,1624	-	14,1624	14,1624	-	14,1624	0,19	-	42,43
NANOOSEBAY	49,2667	124,1333	-	0%	7,000,000	0,1519	-	0,1519	0,1519	-	0,1519	1,11	-	18,65
WALTONONTHENAZE	51,8500	1,2667	-	0%	7,000,000	3,6099	-	3,6099	3,6099	-	3,6099	0,01	-	2,33
MAMBAJAOCAMGUIN	9,2500	124,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	16,3598	-	16,3598	16,3598	-	16,3598	0,06	-	12,29
KOBEII	34,6822	135,1903	-	0%	7,000,000	166,5524	-	166,5524	166,5524	-	166,5524	0,68	-	198,64
MOZI	33,9500	130,9667	-	0%	7,000,000	23,8867	-	23,8867	23,8867	-	23,8867	2,56	-	635,11
CAGLIARI	39,2000	9,1667	-	0%	7,000,000	187,0510	-	187,0510	187,0510	-	187,0510	0,55	-	306,82
KLAGSHAMN	55,5222	12,8936	-	0%	7,000,000	73,5050	-	73,5050	73,5050	-	73,5050	0,57	-	130,27
FUERTEVENTURA	28,4925	13,8582	-	0%	7,000,000	80,3391	-	80,3391	80,3391	-	80,3391	0,28	-	56,57
GIBARA	21,1083	76,1250	-	0%	7,000,000	1,0601	-	1,0601	1,0601	-	1,0601	0,12	-	23,83
ABERDEENII	57,1500	2,0833	-	0%	7,000,000	90,3009	-	90,3009	90,3009	-	90,3009	0,25	-	206,57
KEELUNGII	25,1333	121,7333	-	0%	7,000,000	18,7760	-	18,7760	18,7760	-	18,7760	0,38	-	153,80
PORTDOUGLAS2	16,4833	145,4667	-	0%	7,000,000	12,1696	-	12,1696	11,0235	-	11,0235	0,16	-	32,55
BUENAVENTURA	3,9000	77,1000	-	0%	7,000,000	30,5220	-	30,5220	30,5220	-	30,5220	0,67	-	7,29
NOUMEA-CHALEIX	22,3000	166,4333	-	0%	7,000,000	7,4247	-	7,4247	7,4247	-	7,4247	0,41	-	15,79

PORTALLEN,HANAPEPEBAY,KAUAIISLAND	21,9033	-	159,5917	-	0%	7.000,0000	-	100,6504	-	100,6504	100,6504	0,55	-	167,33
FULFORDHARBOUR	48,7667	-	123,4500	-	0%	7.000,0000	9,1520	-	9,1520	9,3638	9,3638	0,13	-	34,96
NEWCASTLEV	-	32,9240	151,7886	-	0%	7.000,0000	99,7645	-	99,7645	99,7645	99,7645	0,10	-	123,36
SANCLEMENTEISLAND	33,0000	-	118,5500	-	0%	7.000,0000	0,6366	-	0,6366	0,6366	0,6366	0,35	-	85,11
PENRHYN	-	9,0167	158,0667	-	0%	7.000,0000	49,2339	-	49,2339	49,2339	49,2339	0,65	-	25,01
VRANGELIA(VRANGELIAOSTROV)	70,9833	-	178,4833	-	0%	7.000,0000	79,5077	-	79,5077	79,5077	79,5077	0,02	-	74,30

Table 4. PSMSL Trends analysis

Number of years	Years	Trend Unc. mm/yr	RMS mm	Time to 1.0mm Y	Time to 0,5mm Y	Time to 0,1mm Y	Latitude	Longitude	Country	Name
128	1889 - 2017	0.65 + 0.09	85,2	24,5	39,3	116,1	56,147222	10,223889	DNK	AARHUS
54	1965 - 2018	1.21 + 0.40	72	27,2	46	155,5	44,019444	144,285833	JPN	ABASHIRI
79	1932 - 2014	0.97 + 0.20	94,6	27,7	44,9	134,6	57,144056	-2,077361	GBR	ABERDEEN I
104	1862 - 1965	0.45 + 0.22	92,4	31,4	55,2	186	57,15	-2,083333	GBR	ABERDEEN II
59	1960 - 2018	2.11 + 0.41	121,3	30,3	50,9	159,6	31,576944	131,409444	JPN	ABURATSU
86	1930 - 2018	3.61 + 0.18	120,2	25,2	42,3	132,5	35,160278	139,615278	JPN	ABURATSUBO
31	1967 - 2000	7.58 + 1.83	129	50,8	81,4	240,9	16,833333	-99,916667	MEX	ACAPULCO
51	1916 - 1969	1.86 + 0.47	97,8	29,1	51,5	175,7	12,788333	44,974167	YEM	ADEN
47	1954 - 2000	0.06 + 1.25	157,6	55,7	92,9	287,4	69,933333	167,983333	RUS	AION
48	1971 - 2018	1.30 + 0.55	135,1	29,8	51,8	168,9	32,0175	130,190833	JPN	AKUNE
79	1940 - 2018	0.79 + 0.26	71,8	31,4	50,2	148,6	37,771667	-122,298333	USA	ALAMEDA (NAVAL AIR STATION)
31	1987 - 2017	4.01 + 1.31	100,1	37,3	59,9	178	-35,033722	117,892556	AUS	ALBANY
30	1949 - 1978	-0,98	104,7	23,2	36,9	109,7	50,583333	-126,95	CAN	ALERT BAY

70	1945 - 2018	0.85 + 0.30	130,5	31,1	49,7	146,4	62,469414	6,151946	NOR	ALESUND
61	1944 - 2006	1.80 + 0.24	89,1	23,8	38	111,8	31,216667	29,916667	EGY	ALEXANDRIA
49	1969 - 2018	1.72 + 0.52	81,6	31,9	51,2	151,9	40,844139	25,878272	GRC	ALEXANDROUPOLIS
53	1944 - 2001	0.40 + 0.23	57,7	20,8	33,7	100,2	36,116667	-5,433333	ESP	ALGECIRAS
36	1960 - 1995	-0,19	67,5	22,5	37,3	115,6	38,33892	-0,481229	ESP	ALICANTE II
24	1955 - 1979	2.01 + 1.39	120,3	31,1	49,9	147,1	18,766667	-95,766667	MEX	ALVARADO
46	1950 - 1995	2.60 + 1.52	180,6	63	104,2	NaN	69,616667	162,3	RUS	AMBARCIK
69	1950 - 2018	4.14 + 0.75	162,3	55,5	94,2	299,2	69,75	61,7	RUS	AMDERMA
56	1963 - 2018	2.19 + 0.55	188,7	37,6	59,5	174,9	54,616667	8,383333	DEU	AMRUM (WITTDUEN)
27	1991 - 2018	3.24 + 3.85	262,8	74,3	120,4	NaN	73,216667	113,5	RUS	ANABAR
38	1974 - 2018	-0,21	130,7	46,2	76,1	231,7	69,326067	16,134848	NOR	ANDENES
44	1951 - 1994	3.63 + 0.88	137,2	40,3	64,5	190,3	76,8	110,75	RUS	ANDREIA (ANDREIA OSTROV)
30	1989 - 2018	1.25 + 0.52	138,3	19,1	30,7	90,7	36,673611	126,132222	KOR	ANHEUNG
88	1929 - 2018	3.67 + 0.19	138,6	28,5	46,2	137,7	38,983333	-76,48	USA	ANNAPOLIS (NAVAL ACADEMY)
24	1965 - 1988	0,38	275,7	67,5	109,5	NaN	69,083333	76,85	RUS	ANTIPAIUTA
73	1946 - 2018	-0,6	60,3	28,5	45,7	135,2	-23,653056	-70,404444	CHL	ANTOFAGASTA 2
51	1968 - 2018	2.48 + 0.50	98,5	31,6	50,8	150,8	29,726667	-84,981667	USA	APALACHICOLA
70	1948 - 2018	1.72 + 0.62	106,4	51,3	82,4	244,2	13,438333	144,653333	GUM	APRA HARBOUR, GUAM
33	1979 - 2018	0.62 + 0.75	85	30,6	47,9	141,6	38,913333	-123,706667	USA	ARENA COVE, CALIFORNIA
47	1972 - 2018	2.65 + 0.43	88,8	25,7	41,8	125,4	47,3	-53,983333	CAN	ARGENTIA
59	1960 - 2018	1.26 + 0.41	69,8	30,7	51,5	160,2	-65,246233	-64,257417	ATA	ARGENTINE ISLANDS
61	1950 - 2018	0.62 + 0.28	58,6	27,1	44,6	142,3	28,97185	-13,53	ESP	ARRECIFE

64	1955 - 2018	0.51 + 0.37	90,5	29,9	50,8	162,1	40,8975	140,859167	JPN	ASAMUSHI
94	1925 - 2018	0,08	121,5	34,4	55,5	163,4	46,206667	-123,768333	USA	ASTORIA (TONGUE POINT)
104	1912 - 2018	4.11 + 0.15	151,6	28,5	45,9	136,5	39,355	-74,418333	USA	ATLANTIC CITY
94	1904 - 1998	1.26 + 0.17	67,4	28,5	45,9	136,5	-36,84307	174,76946	NZL	AUCKLAND II
51	1968 - 2018	3.64 + 0.43	119,7	28,1	45,5	136,5	38,467778	139,255	JPN	AWA SIMA
51	1959 - 2010	5.26 + 0.32	112,6	23	37,9	115,5	38,296667	141,505278	JPN	AYUKAWA
34	1895 - 1928	-0,93	102,1	23,3	37,4	111,2	58,366667	11,25	SWE	BACKEVIK
74	1930 - 2013	1.19 + 0.27	90,2	30,4	50,7	165,9	45,3	14,533333	HRV	BAKAR
111	1908 - 2018	1.44 + 0.16	121,9	31,8	51,1	151,7	8,966667	-79,566667	PAN	BALBOA
116	1903 - 2018	3.20 + 0.13	150,1	28,9	46,5	139,5	39,266667	-76,578333	USA	BALTIMORE
30	1986 - 2016	1.81 + 1.56	84,5	42	67,4	199,4	-0,433333	-90,283333	ECU	BALTRA-B
48	1971 - 2018	0.03 + 0.51	111,8	30,5	48,7	143,2	48,85	-125,133333	CAN	BAMFIELD
25	1965 - 1990	1.23 + 0.87	69,8	23,3	37,4	111,2	42,083333	19,083333	MNE	BAR
68	1948 - 2018	2.21 + 0.18	65,4	21,7	34,8	103,6	44,391667	-68,205	USA	BAR HARBOR, FRENCHMAN BAY, ME
25	1993 - 2017	5.39 + 0.70	84,4	19,5	31,1	91,2	41,34177	2,1657	ESP	BARCELONA
70	1949 - 2018	-2,26	112,4	37,1	59,7	177,3	78,066667	14,25	SJM	BARENTSBURG
63	1949 - 2013	-2,31	111,8	37,9	61,1	181,6	78,066667	14,25	SJM	BARENTSBURG II (SPITSBERGEN)
61	1937 - 2018	0.73 + 0.32	105,3	35,4	58,7	190,1	55,756389	12,903333	SWE	BARSEBACK
58	1961 - 2018	0.48 + 2.73	467,6	124,2	210,2	NaN	46,5	-72,25	CAN	BATISCAN
46	1973 - 2018	3.67 + 0.46	101,6	27,1	43,6	129,7	34,72	-76,67	USA	BEAUFORT, NORTH CAROLINA
26	1993 - 2018	1.56 + 6.84	487,7	94,9	151,5	NaN	46,4	-72,383333	CAN	BECANCOUR
46	1918 - 1963	0,16	93,4	24,7	39,4	115,6	54,6	-5,916667	GBR	BELFAST 2

57	1962 - 2018	0,32	112,6	28,3	44,8	133,1	52,166667	-128,133333	CAN	BELLA BELLA
98	1916 - 2018	0,2	105	33,7	55,8	172,4	60,398046	5,320487	NOR	BERGEN
30	1985 - 2018	4.97 + 0.76	102,5	27,3	43,6	129,1	40,636667	-74,141667	USA	BERGEN POINT, STATEN IS.
24	1995 - 2018	4.90 + 1.86	76,1	36,8	59	175	1,365056	172,933	KIR	BETIO
25	1993 - 2017	2.58 + 0.63	70,2	18,2	29,1	85,8	43,35153	-3,04513	ESP	BILBAO
42	1953 - 1994	1.89 + 1.25	167,2	49,1	79,2	235,8	69,883333	175,766667	RUS	BILLINGA
85	1892 - 1976	-5,85	220,4	35,6	56,5	165,5	60,633333	17,966667	SWE	BJORN
67	1950 - 2018	-0,84	140,6	45,2	73,3	219,7	67,28829	14,390813	NOR	BODO
42	1951 - 1992	0.69 + 1.74	177,5	62,1	100,3	299,6	70,45	59,083333	RUS	BOLVANSKII NOS (FEDOROVA)
24	1993 - 2016	3.86 + 1.01	77	24,4	38,5	113,1	36,80221	-6,33813	ESP	BONANZA
31	1988 - 2018	1.17 + 5.01	236,4	110,4	180,3	NaN	-10,60255	141,910133	AUS	BOOBY ISLAND
54	1963 - 2016	2.32 + 0.41	145,3	29,8	47,4	138,9	53,5575	6,747778	DEU	BORKUM (FISCHERBALJE)
32	1986 - 2017	5.00 + 0.85	153,4	28,5	45,6	134,6	36,406389	126,486111	KOR	BORYEONG
98	1921 - 2018	2.84 + 0.23	97,4	32,7	55,4	175,9	42,353333	-71,053333	USA	BOSTON
42	1969 - 2016	1.50 + 0.55	90,9	30,3	48,5	142,9	43,527302	-1,51483	FRA	BOUCAU
65	1929 - 1995	1.86 + 0.54	111,4	43,1	73,9	217	42,483333	27,483333	BGR	BOURGAS
31	1987 - 2017	2.96 + 0.79	90,2	26,3	42,2	125,2	-20,016667	148,25	AUS	BOWEN II
193	1807 - 2018	0.99 + 0.11	107,9	36,9	64,7	228,7	48,3829	-4,49504	FRA	BREST
54	1965 - 2018	2.98 + 0.39	87,8	28,2	45,4	134,7	41,173333	-73,181667	USA	BRIDGEPORT
50	1966 - 2018	0.92 + 0.83	72,5	46,1	75,7	229,5	-27,366667	153,166667	AUS	BRISBANE (WEST INNER BAR)
27	1992 - 2018	6.54 + 2.13	115,6	46,1	73,8	219,3	-18,000833	122,218639	AUS	BROOME
31	1988 - 2018	0.87 + 1.08	74,3	33	53,2	159,6	-28,536811	153,552111	AUS	BRUNSWICK HEADS

28	1941 - 1969	0.94 + 0.59	78,1	20,2	32,1	94,5	3,9	-77,1	COL	BUENAVENTURA
82	1905 - 1987	1.51 + 0.32	108,6	37,7	60,7	180,6	-34,6	-58,366667	ARG	BUENOS AIRES
28	1963 - 1990	9.52 + 1.73	146,6	40,7	65,4	193,5	68,8	49,3333	RUS	BUGRINO
58	1958 - 2017	1.75 + 0.49	108,5	36,7	59	174,7	-33,323444	115,659972	AUS	BUNBURY
53	1966 - 2018	2.28 + 0.76	82,9	43	72,7	228	-24,766667	152,383333	AUS	BUNDABERG, BURNETT HEADS
26	1993 - 2018	3.15 + 0.64	57,2	19,2	30,8	90,6	-41,050083	145,915	AUS	BURNIE
58	1961 - 2018	2.12 + 0.30	97,3	24	40	123,4	35,096111	129,035556	KOR	BUSAN
25	1993 - 2017	3.27 + 1.09	70,6	26,3	42,8	125,7	19,833333	-77,733333	CUB	CABO CRUZ
41	1973 - 2018	3.97 + 0.68	89,1	33,6	58,8	215,9	21,9	-84,9	CUB	CABO DE SAN ANTONIO
58	1961 - 2018	3.57 + 0.43	96,6	32,4	52,4	153,8	36,5401	-6,2862	ESP	CADIZ III
38	1897 - 1934	1.91 + 0.28	67,4	15,5	25,2	76,8	39,2	9,166667	ITA	CAGLIARI
48	1971 - 2018	4.01 + 0.53	105,4	30,8	49,8	148,6	38,573333	-76,068333	USA	CAMBRIDGE II
48	1967 - 2018	-1,22	97,9	30,8	49,3	145,5	50,016667	-125,233333	CAN	CAMPBELL RIVER
26	1992 - 2017	4.70 + 0.88	92,2	23,7	38	113,7	-19,277333	147,058444	AUS	CAPE FERGUSON
24	1979 - 2002	3.57 + 1.17	84,8	26,7	42,9	126,8	35,223333	-75,635	USA	CAPE HATTERAS, NORTH CAROLINA
33	1984 - 2016	4.03 + 1.61	117,3	45,9	73,7	218,6	-20,587972	117,186028	AUS	CAPE LAMBERT
50	1966 - 2018	4.60 + 0.51	106	32,7	52,9	158,1	38,968333	-74,96	USA	CAPE MAY
48	1967 - 2017	2.46 + 0.81	117	43,8	70,2	208,1	-24,898694	113,651028	AUS	CARNARVON
44	1949 - 1992	5.29 + 0.28	88,8	17,1	28,5	93,4	10,4	-75,55	COL	CARTAGENA
106	1882 - 1993	1.31 + 0.20	74,3	31,4	55,1	181,7	38,683333	-9,416667	PRT	CASCAIS
70	1948 - 2018	1.27 + 0.50	89,9	42,3	70,7	230,5	10,3	123,916667	PHL	CEBU
79	1939 - 2018	2.26 + 0.37	107,1	37	64,3	207,9	29,135	-83,031667	USA	CEDAR KEY II

30	1985 - 2014	3.37 + 0.57	149,2	20,2	32,6	97	5,265	103,186667	MYS	CENDERING
74	1945 - 2018	0.68 + 0.20	59,1	24,5	39,5	117,9	35,8924	-5,31589	ESP	CEUTA
32	1963 - 1994	4.04 + 7.28	487,2	126,4	201,9	NaN	46,433333	-72,4	CAN	CHAMPLAIN
97	1922 - 2018	3.31 + 0.21	137,5	32,3	53,3	160,2	32,781667	-79,925	USA	CHARLESTON I
47	1971 - 2018	1.10 + 0.51	107,9	30,3	48,3	141,9	43,345	-124,321667	USA	CHARLESTON II
35	1976 - 2016	2.53 + 0.47	62,5	22,5	36,2	107,7	18,335	-64,92	VIR	CHARLOTTE AMALIE
80	1938 - 2017	3.17 + 0.18	94,7	24,4	39,6	118,8	46,233333	-63,116667	CAN	CHARLOTTETOWN
58	1953 - 2012	0.48 + 0.29	110,1	25,9	41,2	121,2	13,1	80,3	IND	CHENNAI
44	1975 - 2018	1.58 + 0.36	84,3	21,8	34,6	102,9	49,651299	-1,63563	FRA	CHERBOURG
34	1985 - 2018	0.95 + 0.79	85,7	29	46,3	136,7	48,863333	-122,756667	USA	CHERRY POINT
32	1985 - 2016	6.05 + 0.67	103,8	24,4	38,9	114,6	36,966667	-76,113333	USA	CHESAPEAKE BAY BR. TUN.
43	1951 - 1993	1.24 + 1.16	170,4	47,4	75,8	223,2	70,633333	162,483333	RUS	CHETYREHSTOLBOVOI
43	1976 - 2018	3.30 + 0.57	112,4	29,1	47,3	145,8	27,083333	142,183333	JPN	CHICHIJIMA
37	1982 - 2018	3.52 + 0.52	94,3	22,7	37,8	116,6	35,744444	140,858333	JPN	CHOSHI-GYOKO
41	1974 - 2014	1.00 + 1.25	90,7	47,6	76,4	226,2	1,983333	-157,483333	KIR	CHRISTMAS ISLAND II
35	1984 - 2018	2.42 + 0.34	118,2	16,9	26,8	78,7	33,961667	126,300278	KOR	CHUJADO
78	1940 - 2018	-8,25	244,6	55,7	94,9	NaN	58,766667	-94,183333	CAN	CHURCHILL
41	1953 - 1994	0.12 + 1.05	87	42,8	68	200,7	7,446667	151,846667	FSM	CHUUK, MOEN ISLAND
29	1957 - 1987	3.69 + 0.59	95,6	21,1	34	104,2	18,633333	-91,85	MEX	CIUDAD DEL CARMEN
24	1897 - 1921	0.81 + 0.69	60,4	18,8	30,5	93,7	42,05	11,816667	ITA	CIVITAVECCHIA
71	1939 - 2013	1.63 + 0.30	84,7	29,5	50,4	161,7	9,966667	76,266667	IND	COCHIN (WILLINGDON IS.)
25	1993 - 2017	7.29 + 1.03	119,6	25,4	40,5	119	-12,116694	96,894417	CCK	COCOS ISLAND (HOME IS.)

36	1954 - 1992	1.27 + 1.73	112,9	57,6	93,8	281,8	-34,483333	-57,85	URY	COLONIA
62	1933 - 1996	1.34 + 0.60	107	43,9	71,9	224,2	44,166667	28,666667	ROU	CONSTANTZA
53	1965 - 2018	3.60 + 0.93	134,4	50,6	88	289,7	60,558333	-145,751667	USA	CORDOVA
21	1998 - 2018	6.97 + 1.23	116,6	23,2	38,5	113,3	27,583333	-97,216667	USA	CORPUS CHRISTI, GULF MEXICO, TX
29	1990 - 2018	-0,68	92,6	35,9	57,5	169,2	-39,878333	-73,422778	CHL	CORRAL II
84	1933 - 2018	-0,56	91,6	27,5	44	129,4	41,745	-124,181667	USA	CRESCENT CITY
25	1982 - 2009	2.00 + 0.78	42,1	23,3	37,8	113,3	44,641667	-67,296667	USA	CUTLER II
176	1843 - 2018	2.10 + 0.08	191,9	32,5	52,6	155,9	53,866667	8,716667	DEU	CUXHAVEN 2
54	1954 - 2018	2.23 + 0.48	186,7	35,1	60,9	200,3	38,866667	121,683333	CHN	DALIAN
36	1978 - 2013	3.19 + 0.54	158,7	23,7	38,1	112,6	16,1	108,216667	VNM	DANANG
28	1991 - 2018	6.05 + 2.00	125,5	45,5	73,1	217,2	-12,471778	130,845861	AUS	DARWIN
45	1967 - 2018	3.80 + 0.51	110,7	30,7	52,3	180,8	30,25	-88,075	USA	DAUPHIN ISLAND
60	1949 - 2018	2.13 + 0.85	104,3	61	107,6	NaN	7,083333	125,633333	PHL	DAVAO, DAVAO GULF
154	1865 - 2018	1.75 + 0.11	151,8	34,7	54,7	168,4	53,326389	6,933056	NLD	DELFIJL
154	1865 - 2018	1.48 + 0.08	131,8	27,4	46,1	129,1	52,964444	4,745	NLD	DEN HELDER
59	1960 - 2018	0.56 + 2.08	408,5	101	169,2	NaN	46,566667	-72,1	CAN	DESCHAILLONS
65	1948 - 2014	3.94 + 0.42	238,9	36,2	59	180,8	22,2	88,166667	IND	DIAMOND HARBOUR
37	1954 - 1994	5.22 + 0.69	108,1	29	46,4	137,2	49,929096	1,083812	FRA	DIEPPE
57	1950 - 2016	1.85 + 0.66	168,6	46,5	74,1	217,5	73,5	80,4	RUS	DIKSON
35	1938 - 1977	0,83	97,3	35,1	57,6	174,6	54,15	-4,466667	IMN	DOUGLAS
70	1898 - 1967	-7,64	227,5	36,2	57,6	168,8	62,366667	17,533333	SWE	DRAGHALLAN
72	1938 - 2009	2.14 + 0.87	106,1	64,1	111,5	NaN	53,35	-6,216667	IRL	DUBLIN

62	1956 - 2017	1.47 + 0.42	79,5	32,4	54,4	172,1	42,6583	18,0633	HRV	DUBROVNIK
34	1985 - 2018	5.02 + 0.63	99	24,8	39,6	116,8	36,183333	-75,746667	USA	DUCK PIER OUTSIDE
60	1951 - 2010	2.41 + 0.57	164,9	40,8	65	190,9	73,933333	124,5	RUS	DUNAI (DUNAI OSTROV)
37	1914 - 1950	0.44 + 0.44	73,5	21	33,9	101,6	56,00593	-2,51688	GBR	DUNBAR
30	1957 - 1986	1.96 + 0.86	89,4	26,9	43,3	127,8	51,048091	2,366698	FRA	DUNKERQUE
37	1979 - 2018	0,95	70	41,4	73	271,1	-27,154722	-109,472778	CHL	EASTER ISLAND-E
89	1930 - 2018	2.20 + 0.24	72,5	31,3	52,6	163,3	44,903333	-66,981667	USA	EASTPORT
31	1988 - 2018	1.19 + 0.87	68,4	28,1	45,1	133,3	-37,07366	149,907739	AUS	EDEN
32	1957 - 1988	1.01 + 0.97	68,5	31,3	50,5	151,1	31,85	-116,633333	MEX	ENSENADA
129	1889 - 2017	1.26 + 0.13	183	33,7	53,5	156,8	55,460833	8,441111	DNK	ESBJERG
26	1993 - 2018	4.51 + 1.44	94,1	33,6	53,7	159,7	-33,870889	121,895361	AUS	ESPERANCE
33	1940 - 1974	10.25 + 1.00	132,5	33,9	54,7	163	29,371667	-91,385	USA	EUGENE ISLAND
22	1947 - 1968	-2,34	120,5	30,7	49,3	145	68,583333	16,55	NOR	EVENSKJAER
56	1950 - 2006	2.67 + 0.84	126	50	80,1	236,9	77,716667	104,3	RUS	FEDOROVA (CHELUSKIN MYS)
108	1898 - 2018	2.13 + 0.09	142,4	23,5	37,2	109,4	30,671667	-81,465	USA	FERNANDINA BEACH
93	1924 - 2018	-3,44	199,4	38,5	61,2	180,9	60,031883	20,384817	ALA	FOGLO / DEGERBY
43	1976 - 2018	-3,61	187	39,7	63,1	185	60,408611	18,210833	SWE	FORSMARK
51	1966 - 2018	3.07 + 0.40	101,7	28,1	44,8	134,9	26,646667	-81,87	USA	FORT MYERS
84	1935 - 2018	3.21 + 0.20	135,4	28,5	45,7	135,2	32,033333	-80,901667	USA	FORT PULASKI
128	1890 - 2017	1.10 + 0.07	77,8	22	35,2	104	55,560833	9,754444	DNK	FREDERICIA
123	1894 - 2017	0.07 + 0.11	105,3	27,4	43,7	128,9	57,436389	10,548889	DNK	FREDERIKSHAVN
53	1955 - 2007	8.69 + 1.17	180,8	60,2	104	NaN	28,948333	-95,308333	USA	FREEMPORT

117	1897 - 2018	1.70 + 0.18	119	37,6	60,2	178,3	-32,055833	115,739444	AUS	FREMANTLE
31	1975 - 2005	1.75 + 1.54	87,1	41,8	67,2	198,8	23,866667	-166,283333	USA	FRENCH FRIGATE SHOALS
84	1934 - 2018	1.20 + 0.20	94,3	28,2	45,2	133,1	48,546667	-123,01	USA	FRIDAY HARBOR (OCEAN. LABS.)
54	1965 - 2018	1.48 + 0.37	140,4	25,3	42,8	137,4	32,696111	128,849444	JPN	FUKUE
39	1953 - 1991	0.01 + 0.61	84,6	27,9	44,6	131,6	48,766667	-123,45	CAN	FULFORD HARBOUR
25	1994 - 2018	3.90 + 1.74	87,8	36,5	58,3	172,2	-8,502472	179,195167	TUV	FUNAFUTI B
103	1916 - 2018	-7,69	302,9	41,8	66,7	195,3	64,915833	21,230556	SWE	FURUOGRUND
49	1968 - 2017	2.07 + 0.32	79,5	22,6	36,1	106,8	54,995	9,986944	DNK	FYNHAV
41	1977 - 2018	3.33 + 0.49	109,2	24,5	41,1	128,5	35,024722	128,810833	KOR	GADEOKDO
49	1958 - 2010	6.60 + 0.57	155	34,4	58,2	195,6	29,285	-94,788333	USA	GALVESTON I, PLEASURE PIER, TX
110	1909 - 2018	6.49 + 0.19	234,2	35,7	57,4	170,1	29,31	-94,793333	USA	GALVESTON II, PIER 21, TX
28	1989 - 2016	3.11 + 0.59	50,4	19,1	30,7	91,1	-0,683333	73,15	MDV	GAN II
33	1974 - 2006	1.28 + 0.86	218,1	29,7	47,3	139,3	21,95	88,016667	IND	GANGRA
49	1951 - 1999	2.91 + 0.62	159,2	35,6	56,6	165,8	54,4	18,683333	POL	GDANSK/NOWY PORT
126	1892 - 2017	1.21 + 0.09	106,5	25,1	39,9	117	54,572778	11,925556	DNK	GEDSER
43	1951 - 1993	2.71 + 0.80	115,3	37	59,1	174	77,6	101,516667	RUS	GEIBERGA (GEIBERGA OSTROV)
91	1884 - 1996	1.18 + 0.07	76,2	18,4	29,4	86,2	44,4	8,9	ITA	GENOVA
37	1982 - 2018	4.78 + 0.48	125,6	22	36	109	34,028333	127,309167	KOR	GEOMUNDO
25	1993 - 2017	6.29 + 2.30	118,9	44,5	71,4	211,8	-28,775972	114,601889	AUS	GERALDTON
30	1987 - 2016	3.09 + 0.77	175,2	24,8	40,6	125,2	6,226389	102,106667	MYS	GETING
43	1976 - 2018	2.77 + 0.54	84,3	27,7	45,4	142,1	21,108333	-76,125	CUB	GIBARA
22	1996 - 2017	0.28 + 0.86	72,5	19,7	31,4	91,9	43,55803	-5,69835	ESP	GIJON II

40	1978 - 2017	3.36 + 0.63	89,3	29	46,9	140,6	-23,853833	151,313667	AUS	GLADSTONE
51	1951 - 2002	3.74 + 0.45	103,1	29,5	47,6	141,6	37,246667	-76,5	USA	GLOUCESTER POINT
31	1987 - 2017	3.17 + 2.01	83,9	52,5	86,6	264,5	-27,95	153,416667	AUS	GOLD COAST SEAWAY 2
53	1954 - 2006	0.89 + 0.68	106,2	40,4	65	192,9	79,55	90,616667	RUS	GOLOMIANYI (GOLOMIANYI OSTROV)
28	1990 - 2017	4.20 + 2.18	215,3	47,7	76,2	225	-10,561667	142,151667	AUS	GOODS ISLAND
50	1969 - 2018	0.39 + 0.41	120,3	28,8	43,8	128	57,684722	11,790556	SWE	GOTEBORG - TORSHAMNEN
71	1887 - 1958	-1,34	125,4	34	54,6	161,5	57,716667	11,966667	SWE	GOTEBORG-RINGON
71	1947 - 2018	8.94 + 0.50	213,6	42,7	71,6	222,5	29,263333	-89,956667	USA	GRAND ISLE
30	1964 - 1993	2.16 + 3.95	374,4	75,6	120,2	NaN	46,583333	-72,033333	CAN	GRONDINES
45	1888 - 1932	-2,69	157,6	31,9	50,7	149,8	59,283333	19,033333	SWE	GRONSKAR
33	1938 - 1971	1.63 + 0.63	60,1	23,5	40,5	143,1	19,906667	-75,146667	CUB	GUANTANAMO BAY
35	1952 - 1989	3.97 + 0.92	158,5	35,5	57,2	169,9	27,916667	-110,9	MEX	GUAYMAS
38	1981 - 2018	2.96 + 0.64	142,7	27,9	45,1	134,7	35,975556	126,563333	KOR	GUNSAN (OUTER PORT)
29	1941 - 1969	2.28 + 0.53	91,3	18,9	30,8	88,5	40,533333	141,533333	JPN	HACHINOHE I
40	1971 - 2010	2.69 + 0.68	97,3	30,3	50,1	153,5	40,531667	141,527778	JPN	HACHINOHE II
21	1971 - 1991	0,16	140,1	15,6	24,5	72,1	34,433333	131,416667	JPN	HAGI
53	1966 - 2018	2.25 + 0.46	144,1	28,7	50	166,9	33,618889	130,407778	JPN	HAKATA
58	1961 - 2018	-0,68	75,9	31,3	55,5	189,7	41,781667	140,724722	JPN	HAKODATE I
41	1971 - 2014	2.72 + 0.52	219,4	28	44,9	131,9	22,033333	88,1	IND	HALDIA
96	1896 - 2012	3.07 + 0.16	106	26,6	45,8	147,9	44,666667	-63,583333	CAN	HALIFAX
34	1985 - 2018	5.08 + 0.29	145,7	14,9	23,5	69,3	34,897222	132,066111	JPN	HAMADA II
90	1929 - 2018	-0,52	200,9	44,2	70,3	206,2	60,562767	27,1792	FIN	HAMINA

59	1957 - 2018	0.89 + 0.35	125,1	30,3	48,4	142,3	70,664641	23,683227	NOR	HAMMERFEST
122	1889 - 2018	-2,44	199,3	38,5	61,1	180,9	59,822867	22,976583	FIN	HANKO / HANGO
53	1953 - 2017	1.85 + 0.38	153,1	29,4	46,7	136,8	57,118889	8,595556	DNK	HANSTHOLM
154	1865 - 2018	1.42 + 0.08	147,1	28,9	45,8	134,3	53,175556	5,409444	NLD	HARLINGEN
66	1953 - 2018	-0,37	120,6	32,2	51,7	152,7	68,801261	16,548236	NOR	HARSTAD
32	1985 - 2016	3.80 + 1.11	99,7	34,3	55,3	164,6	-21,283333	149,3	AUS	HAY POINT
91	1928 - 2018	-1,09	133,3	33	53,7	161,1	63,425224	9,101504	NOR	HEIMSJO
35	1984 - 2018	-0,04	106,8	27,8	44,2	129,1	58,995212	9,856379	NOR	HELGEROA
140	1879 - 2018	-2,08	203	40,4	64,2	188,1	60,153633	24,956217	FIN	HELSINKI
40	1979 - 2018	0.98 + 0.44	118,3	21,4	36,1	115,1	34,683889	125,436389	KOR	HEUKSANDO
34	1962 - 1997	1.22 + 0.83	114,6	31,1	50,2	149,8	54,031833	-2,92025	GBR	HEYSHAM
27	1992 - 2018	6.55 + 1.97	117,2	43,4	69,6	206,9	-31,825556	115,738583	AUS	HILLARYS
79	1927 - 2018	3.10 + 0.24	98	31,5	51	152	19,73	-155,055	USA	HILO, HAWAII ISLAND
27	1991 - 2018	4.08 + 0.64	91,4	20,6	33	95,8	51,210611	-3,131333	GBR	HINKLEY POINT
21	1983 - 2003	3.86 + 2.41	258,1	38,2	61	179,5	21,783333	89,466667	BGD	HIRON POINT
54	1964 - 2017	4.55 + 0.44	149,1	28,6	48,8	172,9	34,353056	132,464722	JPN	HIROSIMA
125	1892 - 2017	-0,1	129	29,1	46,5	136,5	57,595556	9,963889	DNK	HIRTSHALS
29	1988 - 2017	1.84 + 0.80	73,6	25,6	41	121,3	-42,877328	147,340953	AUS	HOBART
155	1864 - 2018	2.39 + 0.08	143,7	27,1	43,6	129,1	51,9775	4,12	NLD	HOEK VAN HOLLAND
57	1957 - 2013	2.03 + 0.40	105,4	30,5	49,2	146,3	20,666667	106,8	VNM	HONDAU
24	1995 - 2018	5.21 + 2.85	104,7	49,7	79,5	235,3	-9,428917	159,955361	SLB	HONIARA-B
49	1962 - 2013	-4,38	178,6	63	104,8	NaN	18,8	105,766667	VNM	HONNGU

46	1972 - 2018	1.53 + 0.51	123,8	30	47,8	141,8	70,980318	25,972697	NOR	HONNINGSVAG
114	1905 - 2018	1.48 + 0.12	76	27,7	44,4	131,2	21,306667	-157,866667	USA	HONOLULU
127	1891 - 2017	0.41 + 0.14	117,9	31,5	51,3	159,3	56,091111	12,458333	DNK	HORNBAEK
88	1930 - 2018	0,24	116,2	37,4	64,7	211,9	32,428611	131,669444	JPN	HOSOJIMA
147	1872 - 2018	1.51 + 0.28	133	52,5	94,1	NaN	52,462222	4,554722	NLD	IJMUIDEN
51	1965 - 2016	2.92 + 1.33	104,2	65,3	110,9	NaN	-22,896667	-43,166667	BRA	ILHA FISCAL
54	1960 - 2013	0.50 + 0.55	71,5	35,4	57,6	173,9	53,630222	-0,187417	GBR	IMMINGHAM
57	1960 - 2018	1.17 + 0.68	153,2	43,5	75,1	241,5	37,451944	126,592222	KOR	INCHEON
33	1986 - 2018	0,2	60	28,9	46,3	136,9	-20,204444	-70,147778	CHL	IQUIQUE II
40	1954 - 1993	3.45 + 0.85	124,5	35,7	57	167,6	77,15	89,2	RUS	ISACHENKO (ISACHENKO OSTROV)
32	1987 - 2018	2.18 + 0.56	128,3	21,7	34,4	101,4	24,332222	124,163611	JPN	ISHIGAKI II
23	1961 - 1983	0.90 + 1.05	131,6	23,8	38,7	115,7	34,2	129,3	JPN	IZUHARA
34	1985 - 2018	3.08 + 0.32	132,4	15,6	24,8	74,3	34,197778	129,291667	JPN	IZUHARA II
61	1954 - 2014	0.02 + 0.48	129,7	37,1	59,4	175,4	75,95	82,95	RUS	IZVESTIA TSIK (IZVESTIA TSIK OSTROVA)
55	1964 - 2018	5.06 + 0.32	153,9	23,1	39,2	134,2	33,5275	126,543056	KOR	JEJU
29	1990 - 2018	2.66 + 0.92	68	27,3	44	130,7	-35,122003	150,7076	AUS	JERVIS BAY II
64	1950 - 2016	1.01 + 0.25	86,6	25,2	40,2	118	16,738333	-169,53	UMI	JOHNSTON ISLAND
28	1984 - 2011	3.05 + 0.71	109,9	22,1	35,8	107,6	1,461667	103,791667	MYS	JOHOR BAHRU
45	1948 - 1994	0,13	60,6	37,1	59,6	176,9	6,066667	121	PHL	JOLO, SULU
80	1936 - 2018	-13,07	327,8	31,3	50,5	154,1	58,298333	-134,411667	USA	JUNEAU
77	1858 - 1934	-2,75	175,6	37,5	55,6	162,8	59,95	22,366667	FIN	JUNGFRUSUND
26	1971 - 1996	-0,02	75,3	25,6	41,2	122,6	1,3	103,716667	SGP	JURONG

71	1948 - 2018	-0,53	140,8	39,3	63,2	187,2	68,212639	14,482149	NOR	KABELVAG
67	1951 - 2018	2.07 + 0.28	70,1	28,4	45,7	135,9	20,895	-156,476667	USA	KAHULUI HARBOR, MAUI ISLAND
66	1953 - 2018	-1,19	127,4	31,1	53,5	183,6	34,144167	135,191389	JPN	KAINAN
34	1973 - 2011	4.35 + 0.68	86,7	29,1	47,9	145,6	37,023678	22,115839	GRC	KALAMAI
44	1975 - 2018	-4,84	222,9	45,2	72	211,2	65,696944	23,096111	SWE	KALIX
38	1981 - 2018	1.84 + 2.60	309,4	72,2	114,8	NaN	33,130278	139,804722	JPN	KAMINATO II (HATIZYO SIMA)
60	1959 - 2018	2.37 + 0.36	122,3	28,3	47,1	155,4	28,083333	121,283333	CHN	KANMEN
37	1973 - 2011	0.65 + 1.10	67,5	41,1	66,5	197,6	-2,816667	-171,716667	KIR	KANTON ISLAND-B
41	1937 - 1986	1,16	85,1	66,2	114,9	NaN	24,811667	66,975	PAK	KARACHI
45	1972 - 2017	1.97 + 0.47	143	25,7	43,6	138,7	33,473056	129,849167	JPN	KARIYA
33	1985 - 2017	3.51 + 1.64	311,7	46,1	73,8	218	-17,5	140,833333	AUS	KARUMBA
63	1956 - 2018	1.08 + 0.39	118,5	30,7	52,6	167,4	37,356667	138,508333	JPN	KASHIWAZAKI
92	1927 - 2018	-6,05	249,3	40,9	65,1	190,9	62,34395	21,214833	FIN	KASKINEN / KASKO
49	1969 - 2018	2.46 + 0.62	81,6	35,1	58,3	179,8	37,644822	21,319681	GRC	KATAKOLON
50	1968 - 2018	1.94 + 0.27	78,4	19,2	32,3	106,4	35,129444	140,249444	JPN	KATSUURA
26	1992 - 2018	7.16 + 1.37	85,7	33,9	55,6	168,2	20,036667	-155,83	USA	KAWAIHAE, HAWAII ISLAND
39	1956 - 1994	0.64 + 0.90	125,3	35,7	62,3	200,1	25,133333	121,733333	TWN	KEELUNG II
99	1920 - 2018	-6,52	277,8	41,9	66,6	194,9	65,673367	24,51525	FIN	KEMI
100	1919 - 2018	-0,24	111,5	27,7	44,2	129,9	55,331667	-131,625	USA	KETCHIKAN
106	1913 - 2018	2.40 + 0.12	109	24,8	40,2	119,9	24,555	-81,806667	USA	KEY WEST
49	1969 - 2018	0.74 + 0.83	78,6	43,4	71,1	215,2	38,472289	23,592631	GRC	KHALKIS NORTH
37	1975 - 2012	3.66 + 0.86	84,8	33,7	55,6	200,3	38,371514	26,141189	GRC	KHIOS

50	1956 - 2018	1.35 + 0.21	81,3	21,9	34,9	102,9	54,372222	10,156944	DEU	KIEL-HOLTENAU
68	1951 - 2018	1.09 + 0.60	144,8	47,4	77,3	232,1	73,333333	139,866667	RUS	KIGILIAH
30	1983 - 2014	4.70 + 1.75	106,7	46	73,9	220,3	-20,623611	116,749056	AUS	KING BAY
67	1952 - 2018	3.69 + 0.26	110,2	27,1	43,4	128,7	37,165	-75,988333	USA	KIPTOPEKE BEACH
41	1945 - 1987	-1,1	128	30,2	48,1	142,9	61,916667	5,633333	NOR	KJOLSDAL
88	1930 - 2018	0.36 + 0.19	110,7	28,9	46,1	134,9	55,522222	12,893611	SWE	KLAGSHAMN
112	1898 - 2018	1.49 + 0.18	178,8	38,7	61,7	182	55,7	21,133333	LTU	KLAIPEDA
78	1940 - 2018	1.71 + 0.81	168,8	65,5	117,8	NaN	11,8	99,816667	THA	KO LAK
25	1992 - 2018	4.88 + 1.78	197,6	39,6	63,5	187,4	10,45	99,25	THA	KO MATTAPHON
63	1940 - 2002	1.07 + 0.34	142,2	28,8	47,7	146,6	13,15	100,816667	THA	KO SICHANG
76	1940 - 2018	2.08 + 0.98	148,8	77,2	136,7	NaN	7,833333	98,433333	THA	KO TAPHAO NOI
129	1889 - 2017	0.61 + 0.12	106,4	28,9	46,6	142,2	55,705	12,6	DNK	KOBENHAVN
34	1984 - 2018	2.43 + 0.81	125,8	30,3	48,5	142,9	33,499167	133,569167	JPN	KOCHI III
34	1985 - 2018	-8,19	127,8	28,5	45,5	133,9	57,731667	-152,511667	USA	KODIAK ISLAND, WOMENS BAY
49	1951 - 1999	1.28 + 0.54	138,7	32,5	51,6	151,1	54,183333	15,55	POL	KOLOBRZEG
42	1950 - 1991	2.81 + 1.02	165,3	42,5	68,8	205,5	67,483333	-174,65	RUS	KOLUCHIN
61	1958 - 2018	2.11 + 0.44	134	32,2	55,5	194,6	34,009167	134,587778	JPN	KOMATSUSHIMA
29	1962 - 1991	0,47	76,9	21,4	34,1	100,2	45,54811	13,72455	SVN	KOPER
121	1897 - 2017	0.84 + 0.09	85,2	24,8	40	116	55,332222	11,142222	DNK	KORSOR
36	1980 - 2018	1.35 + 0.62	115,1	27,8	44,2	129,4	54,060278	14,000833	DEU	KOSEROW
35	1954 - 1988	-5,11	152,3	38,1	61,1	181,9	73,65	109,733333	RUS	KOSYSTYI (KOSYSTYI MYS)
29	1988 - 2016	3.97 + 0.95	86,6	27,9	44,8	132,9	5,983333	116,066667	MYS	KOTA KINABALU

68	1951 - 2018	4.39 + 0.54	179,6	44,7	71,2	209,3	76	137,866667	RUS	KOTELNYI (KOTELNYI OSTROV)
34	1954 - 1987	2.05 + 0.63	98,4	25	39,8	116,4	78,6	98,833333	RUS	KRASNOFLOTSKIE (KRASNOFLOTSKIE OSTROVA)
36	1963 - 1999	-0,55	87,5	42,3	69,2	208,6	80,616667	58,05	RUS	KRENKELIA (HEISA OSTROV)
66	1953 - 2018	-0,32	129,3	33,7	54,4	161,7	63,113859	7,734352	NOR	KRISTIANSUND
44	1975 - 2018	3.17 + 0.30	142,1	19,6	31,9	92,5	32,605278	130,195278	JPN	KUCHINOTSU
33	1986 - 2018	4.49 + 0.70	80,7	25,8	41,6	124,4	1,325278	103,442778	MYS	KUKUP
132	1887 - 2018	0.02 + 0.12	133,2	31,9	49,8	146,1	56,105278	15,589444	SWE	KUNGSHOLMSFORT
45	1974 - 2018	-0,96	126,2	29,4	46,7	137	58,996667	11,127222	SWE	KUNGSVIK
46	1973 - 2018	-1,27	126,4	40,9	67,4	205,4	33,333611	133,243333	JPN	KURE I
51	1968 - 2018	3.40 + 0.40	139,4	27,2	44	130,1	34,240556	132,550278	JPN	KURE IV
61	1958 - 2018	3.73 + 0.58	133,5	40,2	68,1	214,1	33,475833	135,773333	JPN	KUSHIMOTO
71	1947 - 2018	8.48 + 0.42	188,7	34,7	62,5	218,7	42,975556	144,371389	JPN	KUSHIRO
72	1947 - 2018	1.88 + 0.35	79,5	35	55,9	165,8	8,731667	167,735	MHL	KWAJALEIN
75	1944 - 2018	2.42 + 0.26	97	30,1	48	142,6	43,3686	-8,39775	ESP	LA CORUNA I
33	1955 - 1997	0.76 + 0.63	78,6	29,5	47,7	142,2	43,364347	-8,398887	ESP	LA CORUNA II
25	1993 - 2017	3.03 + 0.96	78,8	24,4	38,8	114	43,35731	-8,38933	ESP	LA CORUNA III
93	1925 - 2018	2.09 + 0.15	89	26,1	41,8	123,7	32,866667	-117,256667	USA	LA JOLLA (SCRIPPS PIER)
45	1950 - 1994	-0,41	71,9	34,6	55,3	163,3	-2,2	-80,916667	ECU	LA LIBERTAD II
25	1952 - 1976	1.83 + 1.16	100,4	27,7	44,6	132,3	24,166667	-110,35	MEX	LA PAZ
119	1887 - 2005	-2,75	184,9	35,6	56,7	166,1	58,742222	17,865278	SWE	LANDSORT
27	1992 - 2018	3.37 + 0.52	51,7	17,4	27,7	82,2	28,1466	-15,4075	ESP	LAS PALMAS C (PUERTO DE LA LUZ)
25	1993 - 2017	3.89 + 0.91	55,2	23,4	38,1	119	28,14056	-15,41181	ESP	LAS PALMAS D

26	1993 - 2018	5.02 + 1.29	64,4	31	49,9	148	-17,604917	177,43825	FJI	LAUTOKA
47	1971 - 2017	2.84 + 0.32	88,7	21,8	34,7	101,6	48,359402	-4,78083	FRA	LE CONQUET
54	1959 - 2017	2.65 + 0.45	92,3	32,5	52,6	157,7	49,4819	0,106	FRA	LE HAVRE
70	1949 - 2018	5.61 + 0.46	133,8	39,7	65,8	210,7	13,15	123,75	PHL	LEGASPI, ALBAY
28	1989 - 2017	1.99 + 0.77	77,3	24,2	39	115,5	55,989833	-3,181694	GBR	LEITH II
23	1964 - 1995	1.03 + 0.95	79,5	24,4	38,9	114	41,183333	-8,7	PRT	LEIXOES
48	1889 - 1936	-3,94	167	32,6	51,7	152,6	60,1	20,016667	ALA	LEMSTROM
43	1974 - 2018	1.57 + 0.43	65,7	24,5	39,7	116,1	37,129675	26,847994	GRC	LEROS
58	1957 - 2015	0.37 + 0.36	96,7	26,7	45,5	147,9	60,154028	-1,140306	GBR	LERWICK
29	1990 - 2018	3.12 + 0.75	91,5	23,6	37,9	111,8	46,497501	-1,79373	FRA	LES SABLES D OLLONNE
29	1990 - 2018	2.80 + 0.55	74,5	19,5	31	91,2	42,05	3,2	ESP	L'ESTARTIT
48	1970 - 2018	5.70 + 0.58	113,8	33,2	53,3	157,6	38,834544	20,712108	GRC	LEVKAS
80	1919 - 2018	3.49 + 0.21	120,4	30,3	48,9	141,8	38,781667	-75,12	USA	LEWES (BREAKWATER HARBOR)
47	1971 - 2018	5.41 + 0.51	121,6	29,5	47,3	139,9	37,995	-76,465	USA	LEWISSETTA, VIRGINIA
63	1865 - 1936	0.88 + 0.36	165,1	35,8	56,9	166,8	56,533333	20,983333	LVA	LIEPAJA
33	1984 - 2016	3.18 + 0.59	65,8	23	36,9	109,8	17,693333	-64,753333	VIR	LIME TREE BAY, ST CROIX
24	1995 - 2018	1.34 + 1.87	145,8	36,4	57,8	170,1	-31,516667	159,066667	AUS	LORD HOWE ISLAND
26	1993 - 2018	1.15 + 0.73	78,3	21,1	33,7	98,8	-38,547194	143,988833	AUS	LORNE
95	1924 - 2018	1.03 + 0.15	71,3	26,7	42,8	127,2	33,72	-118,271667	USA	LOS ANGELES
46	1973 - 2018	3.04 + 0.46	70,4	26,4	43,2	130,6	47,083333	-64,883333	CAN	LOWER ESCUMINAC
59	1956 - 2015	2.62 + 0.33	86,7	27,3	44,8	135,9	52,473111	1,750111	GBR	LOWESTOFT
32	1986 - 2017	3.71 + 0.72	91,4	25,8	41	122,3	-18,516667	146,383333	AUS	LUCINDA

34	1985 - 2018	2.95 + 0.74	96,1	27,6	44,2	130,7	4,24	100,613333	MYS	LUMUT
79	1858 - 1936	-5,09	204,8	35,2	56	163,8	60,85	21,183333	FIN	LYOKKI
78	1858 - 1936	-4,74	198	34,1	54,1	158,3	60,6	21,233333	FIN	LYPYRTTI
74	1924 - 2000	2.28 + 0.25	78,2	28,8	46,6	139,8	-43,60563	172,72194	NZL	LYTTELTON II
171	1848 - 2018	1.67 + 0.08	132,5	31,7	50,8	150,1	51,9175	4,249722	NLD	MAASSLUIS
57	1925 - 1982	0.38 + 0.80	110,4	48,4	83,2	266	22,2	113,55	MAC	MACAU
48	1966 - 2017	2.36 + 0.45	98,2	29,4	48,1	145,8	-21,1	149,233333	AUS	MACKAY
61	1955 - 2016	1.94 + 0.36	62,9	26,2	47,3	184,6	17,97	-67,045	PRI	MAGUEYES ISLAND
30	1951 - 1980	0.23 + 0.58	133	20,8	33,1	97,7	35,483333	135,4	JPN	MAIZURU I
43	1975 - 2018	4.29 + 0.21	138,3	15,4	24,5	71,8	35,476667	135,386944	JPN	MAIZURU II
26	1982 - 2007	5.09 + 0.44	130,9	15	23,8	69,7	35,45	135,316667	JPN	MAIZURU III
30	1969 - 1999	2.63 + 1.06	76,9	32,1	50,6	149,2	7,1	171,366667	MHL	MAJURO-B
25	1994 - 2018	4.65 + 1.49	81,3	32,8	52,4	154,6	7,106028	171,372806	MHL	MAJURO-C
59	1944 - 2012	0.70 + 0.64	73,1	46,8	84,1	285,3	36,7127	-4,41546	ESP	MALAGA
25	1993 - 2017	2.01 + 0.95	67,3	24,1	39,1	117,2	36,71184	-4,41709	ESP	MALAGA II
46	1971 - 2016	2.35 + 1.38	131,8	57,1	91,4	270,1	7,333333	134,466667	PLW	MALAKAL-B
26	1991 - 2016	4.39 + 0.76	54,6	21,4	35	105,9	4,183333	73,533333	MDV	MALE-B, HULULE
41	1959 - 2001	-0,69	100,5	35,1	58	177,2	55,366667	-7,333333	IRL	MALIN HEAD
73	1944 - 2018	0.77 + 0.26	123,6	28	46	147,7	61,933776	5,11331	NOR	MALOY
48	1950 - 1998	1.15 + 1.31	133,4	60,5	105,8	NaN	72,366667	52,7	RUS	MALYE KARMAKULY
42	1950 - 1991	2.82 + 0.80	98,5	35,9	58,5	175,5	78,083333	106,816667	RUS	MALYI TAIMYR (MALYI TAIMYR OSTROV)
108	1911 - 2018	-5,58	253,3	39,8	62,9	184,8	61,594383	21,463433	FIN	MANTYLUOTO

27	1954 - 1982	3.58 + 1.51	103	38,2	61,4	181,8	19,05	-104,333333	MEX	MANZANILLO
61	1958 - 2018	1.25 + 0.53	88,6	38,5	63,9	195,8	-38,033333	-57,516667	ARG	MAR DEL PLATA (NAVAL BASE)
25	1991 - 2017	1.57 + 1.12	87,5	27,3	43,7	129	35,820063	14,532955	MLT	MARSAXLOKK (FORMALLY VALLETTA)
127	1885 - 2016	1.31 + 0.13	84,1	29,9	49,7	153,6	43,278801	5,35386	FRA	MARSEILLE
54	1965 - 2018	-1,5	161,6	36,4	57,8	169,2	58,553611	16,837222	SWE	MARVIKEN
27	1942 - 1969	-0,15	48,1	21,7	34,7	103,2	-17	-72,116667	PER	MATARANI
55	1964 - 2018	0.10 + 0.34	121,9	26,2	42,2	125,5	33,858889	132,712222	JPN	MATSUYAMA II
72	1929 - 2000	2.47 + 0.29	128,2	30,4	49,2	146	30,393333	-81,431667	USA	MAYPORT
46	1932 - 1980	2.27 + 0.23	94,6	18	28,8	84,1	25,768333	-80,131667	USA	MIAMI BEACH
71	1947 - 2018	1.37 + 0.22	82,5	25,6	40,9	120,3	28,211667	-177,36	UMI	MIDWAY ISLAND
49	1968 - 2017	4.14 + 0.60	140,1	34,6	56,9	172,7	36,254722	136,148889	JPN	MIKUNI
30	1986 - 2015	1.31 + 0.58	110,8	20,8	33,3	96,6	55,749806	-4,906333	GBR	MILLPORT
25	1994 - 2018	5.16 + 2.68	221,5	49,7	79,9	236,5	-13,860056	136,415583	AUS	MILNER BAY (GROOTE EYLANDT)
42	1966 - 2007	1.73 + 0.58	85,7	28,9	46,4	137,9	34,616667	138,883333	JPN	MINAMI IZU
56	1957 - 2012	2.46 + 0.45	147,3	29,6	51,7	175,2	32,623056	130,451389	JPN	MISUMI
25	1941 - 1965	5.72 + 0.78	94,9	21,1	33,8	99,2	39,633333	141,966667	JPN	MIYAKO I
49	1967 - 2018	2.33 + 0.54	94	32,7	54,2	165,6	39,643056	141,975278	JPN	MIYAKO II
59	1960 - 2018	3.60 + 0.49	149,6	33,2	58,2	215	34,779722	126,375556	KOR	MOKPO
53	1958 - 2018	1.48 + 0.31	66,2	27,3	46,1	129,5	21,431667	-157,79	USA	MOKUOLOE ISLAND
28	1980 - 2007	0.80 + 0.46	61,9	16,5	26,3	77	44,35	143,366667	JPN	MONBETU II
70	1948 - 2018	3.36 + 0.35	95,2	33,7	55,1	167,7	41,048333	-71,96	USA	MONTAUK
45	1974 - 2018	1.59 + 0.52	69,9	28,8	46,3	137,1	36,605	-121,886667	USA	MONTEREY

71	1938 - 2018	1.08 + 0.35	118	38,3	61,2	181,7	-34,9	-56,25	URY	MONTEVIDEO (PUNTA LOBOS)
30	1988 - 2017	1.80 + 0.62	65,5	21,7	34,8	103,2	-26,683333	153,133333	AUS	MOOLOOLABA 2
39	1954 - 1992	1.02 + 1.40	161,6	48,8	78,2	230,7	71,416667	67,583333	RUS	MORZHOVAIA (HARASAVEI MYS)
33	1985 - 2017	4.35 + 0.85	95,9	29,5	47,7	142,8	-17,583333	146,083333	AUS	MOURILYAN HARBOUR
49	1959 - 2007	1.95 + 0.39	142,1	23,8	40,3	138,2	33,95	130,966667	JPN	MOZI
53	1965 - 2017	1.01 + 0.49	90,2	29	52,6	183,8	37,550278	129,116389	KOR	MUKHO
123	1878 - 2010	0.81 + 0.11	66,1	25,2	43,1	140,2	18,916667	72,833333	IND	MUMBAI / BOMBAY (APOLLO BANDAR)
44	1951 - 1994	3.12 + 0.92	173,9	41,5	66	194	71,55	130,033333	RUS	MUOSTAH (MUOSTAH OSTROV)
67	1952 - 2018	2.06 + 0.90	133,9	61,8	105,5	NaN	68,966667	33,05	RUS	MURMANSK
60	1952 - 2011	2.52 + 1.07	135,5	63	106,4	NaN	68,966667	33,05	RUS	MURMANSK II
40	1968 - 2007	1.41 + 0.27	58,7	15,5	25,8	80,7	42,35	140,95	JPN	MURORAN
43	1976 - 2018	8.05 + 0.64	153,5	31,5	50,7	150,3	33,266389	134,164444	JPN	MUROTOMISAKI
34	1956 - 1990	0.54 + 0.88	108,8	31,8	50,8	150	69,55	32,4333	RUS	MYS PIKSHUEVA
44	1950 - 1993	1.94 + 0.98	157,4	43,5	71,2	215,5	68,9	-179,366667	RUS	MYS SHMIDTA
34	1985 - 2018	5.67 + 0.87	98,3	30,8	49,4	146	40,766667	-124,216667	USA	N. SPIT, HUMBOLDT BAY
54	1965 - 2018	2.63 + 0.27	148	20,7	34	110,8	32,735	129,866111	JPN	NAGASAKI
39	1980 - 2018	-1,54	122,4	26,2	41,8	123,1	35,091389	136,880833	JPN	NAGOYA II
52	1967 - 2018	2.27 + 0.29	123,5	22,9	36,5	107,2	26,213333	127,665278	JPN	NAHA
35	1984 - 2018	4.12 + 0.36	131,5	17,4	28	83	29,841944	129,847778	JPN	NAKANO SIMA
54	1965 - 2018	3.69 + 0.35	79,2	26	42,4	127,5	41,285	-70,096667	USA	NANTUCKET ISLAND
53	1966 - 2018	2.78 + 0.42	92,1	28,7	46,8	140,8	26,131667	-81,806667	USA	NAPLES
81	1932 - 2018	-2,11	147,6	34,9	55,7	163,8	68,428286	17,425759	NOR	NARVIK

38	1981 - 2018	2.23 + 0.38	134,6	19,8	31,3	92,2	28,5	129,5	JPN	NASE III
64	1955 - 2018	1.78 + 0.38	69,9	30,2	51,7	178,7	21,953333	-159,355	USA	NAWILIWILI BAY, KAUAI ISLAND
84	1935 - 2018	-1,54	128,4	27,9	44,5	131,1	48,366667	-124,611667	USA	NEAH BAY
91	1896 - 1986	-5,78	228,4	35,8	56,9	166,5	60,683333	17,166667	SWE	NEDRE GAVLE
102	1869 - 1970	-3,25	180,4	34,1	54,3	158,9	59,2	17,616667	SWE	NEDRE SODERTALJE
45	1950 - 1994	2.20 + 0.84	176,5	39,5	65	199,1	66,966667	-171,933333	RUS	NETTEN
55	1961 - 2018	0.77 + 1.12	221,9	62,1	104,2	NaN	46,7	-71,566667	CAN	NEUVILLE
30	1935 - 1965	-0,96	103,6	24,3	38,8	114	58,966667	9,883333	NOR	NEVLUNGHAVN
49	1970 - 2018	0,34	272,8	44,3	70,3	206,1	49,2	-122,916667	CAN	NEW WESTMINSTER
80	1939 - 2018	2.69 + 0.27	90	31,6	51,7	156,1	41,36	-72,09	USA	NEW LONDON
24	1958 - 1981	1,18	76,5	31,5	51,5	155,3	40,893333	-73,781667	USA	NEW ROCHELLE
148	1856 - 2018	2.84 + 0.09	155,5	28,8	47,5	150,9	40,7	-74,013333	USA	NEW YORK (THE BATTERY)
52	1966 - 2017	1.67 + 0.55	68,5	33,2	55,9	174,6	-32,924	151,788583	AUS	NEWCASTLE V
27	1992 - 2018	3.14 + 0.86	74,5	24,2	39,3	118	50,781778	0,057028	GBR	NEWHAVEN
103	1916 - 2018	1.86 + 0.11	97,4	28,9	37	109,2	50,103	-5,542833	GBR	NEWLYN
88	1931 - 2018	2.78 + 0.16	92,9	25,3	41	122,7	41,505	-71,326667	USA	NEWPORT
35	1956 - 1990	1.75 + 0.66	68,2	26,4	42,3	125,3	33,603333	-117,881667	USA	NEWPORT BAY
36	1978 - 2016	2.83 + 0.45	76,2	22,6	36	105,9	43,695599	7,2855	FRA	NICE
51	1967 - 2017	2.70 + 0.43	90,3	28,5	46,2	138,7	51,15	2,733333	BEL	NIEUWPOORT
22	1997 - 2018	-11,07	137,3	28,5	45,3	133,1	60,683333	-151,396667	USA	NIKISKI, ALASKA
53	1966 - 2018	2.41 + 0.19	131,3	18,2	27,6	80,7	30,735	130,992222	JPN	NISINOOMOTE
36	1950 - 1985	0,49	118,3	67,7	112,5	NaN	22,3	114,2	HKG	NORTH POINT

116	1896 - 2017	1.90 + 0.12	104	27,7	44,8	133,6	55,007444	-1,439778	GBR	NORTH SHIELDS
49	1970 - 2018	3.78 + 0.42	91	25,6	42,8	133,7	46,216667	-60,25	CAN	NORTH SYDNEY
26	1993 - 2018	6.76 + 1.34	80,6	32,1	51,1	152,1	-21,136806	-175,180694	TON	NUKU'ALOFA B
38	1977 - 2018	-3,94	107	32,4	54,1	168,4	78,928545	11,938015	SJM	NY-ALESUND
53	1966 - 2018	1.88 + 0.50	118,7	31,6	53,1	166,4	31,023611	130,689167	JPN	ODOMARI
37	1974 - 2010	4.72 + 0.36	94,4	17,3	29	95,7	39,019722	141,753333	JPN	OFUNATO II
49	1970 - 2018	-1,27	108	21,1	35	112,1	39,942222	139,705833	JPN	OGA
44	1974 - 2018	0.70 + 0.63	110,5	32,9	53,5	159,7	37,814722	138,281111	JPN	OGI
47	1972 - 2018	1.40 + 0.59	133,6	32,2	53	161,6	33,266111	131,686667	JPN	OITA II
54	1965 - 2018	-0,47	77,5	27,9	45,1	134,7	34,789444	139,391389	JPN	OKADA
29	1976 - 2007	0.74 + 1.17	63	36	60,9	190,7	22,466667	69,083333	IND	OKHA
42	1976 - 2018	1.42 + 0.37	120,2	22,1	35,2	103,3	26,179444	127,824444	JPN	OKINAWA
132	1887 - 2018	-0,95	158,8	34,8	55,2	161,7	57,366111	17,097222	SWE	OLANDS NORRA UDDE
48	1971 - 2018	7.93 + 0.40	144,1	25,7	41,2	121,4	34,608333	138,222222	JPN	OMAEZAKI II
32	1986 - 2017	5.47 + 1.66	124,9	45,4	72,9	216,1	-21,649667	115,131528	AUS	ONSLow
77	1937 - 2017	1.81 + 0.19	89,3	25,1	40,4	120	51,233333	2,916667	BEL	OOSTENDE
23	1995 - 2017	4.86 + 1.31	91,1	27,6	44,2	130,9	35,795	-75,548333	USA	OREGON INLET MARINA, NORTH CAROLINA
64	1954 - 2018	-1,48	143	33,2	53,6	159,7	59,678073	10,604861	NOR	OSCARSBORG
32	1930 - 1962	0.17 + 0.39	79,9	16,9	27,5	85,9	43,216667	140,866667	JPN	OSHORO I
56	1963 - 2018	0.53 + 0.15	81,1	15,8	24,8	72,9	43,209444	140,858056	JPN	OSHORO II
58	1961 - 2018	-0,01	151,9	34,7	55,2	161,5	57,275	16,478056	SWE	OSKARSHAMN
109	1886 - 2018	-2,64	176,7	50,9	85,4	268,7	59,908559	10,73451	NOR	OSLO

130	1889 - 2018	-6,12	306,5	42,7	67,9	199,6	65,040317	25,418233	FIN	OULU / ULEABORG
54	1965 - 2018	2.71 + 0.33	151,6	24,7	40,3	121,9	32,976667	130,220556	JPN	OURA
49	1967 - 2018	-0,7	103,3	23,9	37,9	111,8	34,076389	136,207222	JPN	OWASE
68	1949 - 2018	3.94 + 0.66	105	50,5	86,7	NaN	-14,28	-170,69	ASM	PAGO PAGO
59	1960 - 2018	2.09 + 0.48	117,4	35,5	57	168,2	-34,566667	-58,4	ARG	PALERMO
33	1985 - 2018	3.85 + 0.65	104,1	25,3	40,7	121,5	30,151667	-85,666667	USA	PANAMA CITY, ST.ANDREWS BAY, FL
40	1977 - 2016	2.61 + 0.45	52,9	23,2	37,2	109,9	-17,533081	-149,572724	PYF	PAPEETE-B, FARE UTE POINT, SOC.IS.
42	1977 - 2018	0.93 + 0.72	91,8	33,7	54,1	160,2	48,65	-123,45	CAN	PATRICIA BAY
29	1984 - 2012	2.30 + 1.00	95,5	28,9	46,1	135,7	3,05	101,358333	MYS	PELABUHAN KELANG
39	1978 - 2016	2.22 + 0.93	75,5	37,1	59,5	176,2	-9,016667	-158,066667	COK	PENRHYN
95	1924 - 2018	2.51 + 0.23	115,1	34,3	56,3	169,7	30,403333	-87,21	USA	PENSACOLA
31	1962 - 1992	3.96 + 1.16	113,2	34,2	54,5	159,8	79,433333	102,483333	RUS	PESCHANYI (PESCHANYI MYS)
61	1958 - 2018	3.32 + 0.52	112,8	38,1	63,1	194,2	52,983333	158,65	RUS	PETROPAVLOVSK-KAMCHATSKY
62	1950 - 2011	3.34 + 0.75	169,2	50,3	82,5	250,1	69,7	170,25	RUS	PEVEK
118	1901 - 2018	2.99 + 0.17	147	34,9	56,3	167,1	39,933333	-75,141667	USA	PHILADELPHIA (PIER 9N)
30	1966 - 1995	2.52 + 1.00	78,9	29,8	48,3	144,3	45,683333	-62,7	CAN	PICTOU
104	1915 - 2018	-6,86	284,9	41,9	66,6	195,7	63,708567	22,689583	FIN	PIETARSAARI / JAKOBSTAD
53	1926 - 1986	1.84 + 0.44	165,8	34,8	55,6	161,9	54,95	20,216667	RUS	PIONERSKY
45	1972 - 2016	5.47 + 0.90	117,7	41	72,3	240,1	36,047222	129,383889	KOR	POHANG
29	1976 - 2004	2.13 + 1.93	95	45,6	73,1	216,2	6,983333	158,233333	FSM	POHNPEI-B
85	1915 - 2018	1.04 + 0.17	86,4	28	45,4	134,2	49,333333	-123,25	CAN	POINT ATKINSON
24	1993 - 2016	4.69 + 1.28	88	28,4	45,4	133,8	-4,666667	55,533333	SYC	POINT LA RUE

44	1975 - 2018	2.18 + 0.59	81,9	30,9	49,4	146	37,995	-122,976667	USA	POINT REYES
25	1964 - 1988	1,09	88,7	34	54,6	162,5	47,133333	-2,25	FRA	POINTE ST. GILDAS
69	1900 - 1979	-0,14	76,1	48,4	80,1	245,5	48,516667	-68,466667	CAN	POINTE-AU-PERE
60	1926 - 1990	-1,23	110,5	29,6	47,3	139,5	69,2	33,4833	RUS	POLYARNIY
57	1950 - 2016	1.85 + 0.66	168,6	46,5	74,1	217,5	73,333333	70,05	RUS	POPOVA (BELYI OSTROV)
76	1941 - 2017	2.41 + 0.25	107,7	29,5	47,1	139,1	-34,779761	138,480728	AUS	PORT ADELAIDE (OUTER HARBOR)
22	1974 - 1995	0.58 + 1.73	105,3	31,9	51	150	49,233333	-124,816667	CAN	PORT ALBERNI
32	1986 - 2017	3.20 + 0.67	84,1	24,4	39,1	116	-23,583333	150,866667	AUS	PORT ALMA
43	1976 - 2018	0.47 + 0.63	105,5	31,3	50,1	147,8	48,125	-123,44	USA	PORT ANGELES, WASHINGTON
59	1959 - 2018	2.87 + 0.38	70,9	29,2	49,2	153,3	47,566667	-59,133333	CAN	PORT AUX BASQUES
42	1977 - 2018	2.09 + 0.87	98,6	38,3	61,2	181,6	38,055	-122,04	USA	PORT CHICAGO, CALIFORNIA
25	1988 - 2012	2.81 + 4.29	86,9	92,5	156,7	NaN	-16,483333	145,466667	AUS	PORT DOUGLAS 2
22	1996 - 2017	2.96 + 1.29	97,5	24,8	41,8	123,2	-35,021781	137,768319	AUS	PORT GILES
54	1965 - 2018	-0,14	106	27,3	43,7	128,3	50,716667	-127,483333	CAN	PORT HARDY
52	1966 - 2017	2.52 + 0.87	111,1	47	75,7	225,1	-20,317583	118,574417	AUS	PORT HEDLAND
73	1945 - 2018	4.03 + 0.34	129,9	34,6	56,8	172,4	26,06	-97,215	USA	PORT ISABEL
33	1958 - 1990	1.93 + 0.67	73,3	25,2	40,3	119,4	40,95	-73,076667	USA	PORT JEFFERSON
27	1992 - 2018	3.51 + 0.62	65,2	19,5	31,1	92	-34,47375	150,911861	AUS	PORT KEMBLA
52	1966 - 2017	1.92 + 0.37	94	26,6	42,3	124,7	-34,715903	135,870011	AUS	PORT LINCOLN
32	1987 - 2018	4.69 + 0.87	96,2	29	47,4	148	-20,15	57,5	MUS	PORT LOUIS II
24	1995 - 2018	6.39 + 1.74	65,2	37,6	63,8	200,9	-43,60563	172,72194	NZL	PORT LYTTTELTON
32	1987 - 2018	2.58 + 0.57	72,1	21,7	34,8	102,8	-31,426792	152,910983	AUS	PORT MACQUARIE

32	1964 - 1995	2.37 + 1.22	112,6	46	62,8	215,2	26,553333	-97,421667	USA	PORT MANSFIELD
32	1985 - 2018	1.30 + 0.84	102,9	30,2	48,3	142,3	42,738333	-124,498333	USA	PORT ORFORD
77	1941 - 2017	1.39 + 0.54	87,6	48,2	81,3	254,6	-33,177644	138,01165	AUS	PORT PIRIE
72	1946 - 2018	0.97 + 0.23	69,8	26,6	42,6	126,1	35,176667	-120,76	USA	PORT SAN LUIS
28	1986 - 2013	2.98 + 1.12	69,1	30,3	49,2	147,3	-32,714881	152,182239	AUS	PORT STEPHENS (TOMAREE)
47	1972 - 2018	1.87 + 0.52	99	29,9	47,8	141,2	48,111667	-122,756667	USA	PORT TOWNSEND
43	1976 - 2018	2.23 + 0.40	89,1	23,2	37,1	108,5	47,644274	-3,445852	FRA	PORT TUDY
25	1994 - 2018	0.71 + 1.71	66,6	36,4	74	175,1	-17,755333	168,307694	VUT	PORT VILA B
27	1992 - 2018	3.14 + 0.73	81	21,8	34,7	102,1	-38,343444	141,613167	AUS	PORTLAND
107	1912 - 2018	1.89 + 0.18	79,4	31,6	51,8	156,6	43,656667	-70,246667	USA	PORTLAND (MAINE)
57	1961 - 2018	0.61 + 1.41	258,3	73	116,8	NaN	46,683333	-71,883333	CAN	PORTNEUF
43	1968 - 2010	2.07 + 0.54	105	27,3	45,6	142,1	54,842556	-5,120028	GBR	PORTPATRICK
27	1964 - 1994	7.30 + 9.47	577,8	200,8	NaN	NaN	46,266667	-72,616667	CAN	PORT-SAINT-FRANCOIS
51	1936 - 1986	3.71 + 0.35	100,6	25,1	40,1	118,4	36,821667	-76,293333	USA	PORTSMOUTH (NORFOLK NAVY YARD)
136	1874 - 2015	6.75 + 0.23	297,6	47,3	79,9	269,3	42,166667	41,683333	GEO	POTI
44	1950 - 1993	2.23 + 0.92	151,6	41,5	66,2	194,5	76,266667	94,766667	RUS	PRAVDY (PRAVDY OSTROV)
39	1951 - 1989	0.12 + 0.81	128	33,9	54,3	160,6	74,666667	112,933333	RUS	PREOBRAZHENIA (PREOBRAZHENIA OSTROV)
44	1969 - 2018	0.05 + 0.96	77,6	47,7	81,8	262,5	38,959078	20,756628	GRC	PREVEZA
94	1909 - 2018	1.14 + 0.16	115,1	29,4	47,1	138,7	54,316667	-130,333333	CAN	PRINCE RUPERT
33	1952 - 1984	4.88 + 1.13	100,7	36,1	60,2	186,4	21,3	-89,666667	MEX	PROGRESO
71	1939 - 2017	2.24 + 0.24	82,4	27,9	45,3	136	41,806667	-71,4	USA	PROVIDENCE (STATE PIER)
32	1952 - 1983	3.60 + 0.87	111,4	29,1	46,4	136,3	64,416667	-173,233333	RUS	PROVIDENIA

24	1995 - 2018	4.05 + 1.45	134,1	30,9	49,3	155,5	70,4	-148,526667	USA	PRUDHOE BAY, ALASKA
21	1948 - 1968	7.87 + 1.19	83,2	24	40,3	125,2	15,833333	-87,95	HND	PUERTO CORTES
38	1958 - 1998	2.22 + 0.73	87,2	32,2	53	161,5	-42,766667	-65,033333	ARG	PUERTO MADRYN
33	1986 - 2018	3.87 + 0.84	106,5	29,1	46,5	136,7	6,430833	99,764167	MYS	PULAU LANGKAWI
33	1986 - 2018	4.04 + 0.81	105,4	28,6	45,5	134,1	5,421667	100,346667	MYS	PULAU PINANG
30	1986 - 2015	2.79 + 0.65	130,7	22	36	109,5	2,807222	104,14	MYS	PULAU TIOMAN
25	1942 - 1966	5.91 + 1.99	92,4	40,3	64,6	191,5	9,966667	-84,833333	CRI	PUNTARENAS
45	1950 - 1994	0,46	213,2	28,8	46,5	139	39,9	119,6	CHN	QINHUANGDAO
33	1986 - 2018	2.87 + 0.87	116,1	29,9	48,1	143,3	22,291111	114,213333	HKG	QUARRY BAY
83	1911 - 2011	0.09 + 0.36	147,1	43,5	69,8	206,4	46,833333	-71,166667	CAN	QUEBEC (LAUZON)
53	1966 - 2018	0.35 + 0.42	83,5	29,2	46,9	138,9	53,25	-132,066667	CAN	QUEEN CHARLOTTE CITY
64	1918 - 1982	0.84 + 0.28	86,7	26,8	43,6	131,1	-38,583333	-58,7	ARG	QUEQUEN
37	1977 - 2013	0.33 + 0.85	127,5	32,9	54,7	178,7	13,766667	109,25	VNM	QUINHON
95	1923 - 2018	-6,44	273,3	42,5	66,8	195,6	64,666333	24,40705	FIN	RAAHE / BRAHESTAD
25	1994 - 2018	3.56 + 0.97	64,2	24,4	39,1	115,2	-21,20475	-159,784778	COK	RAROTONGA B
127	1892 - 2018	-7,54	336,6	40,5	64,4	188,6	63,986111	20,895	SWE	RATAN
48	1950 - 2001	0.27 + 1.37	166,1	64,2	104,1	NaN	69,5	166,583333	RUS	RAU-CHUA
86	1933 - 2018	-4,21	211,3	40,7	64,6	189,5	61,133533	21,425817	FIN	RAUMA / RAUMO
33	1985 - 2017	3.96 + 0.63	106,9	24,1	38,6	113,4	39,558333	-75,573333	USA	REEDY POINT
62	1957 - 2018	2.31 + 0.39	102,2	32,2	52,4	157,9	64,150583	-21,939889	ISL	REYKJAVIK
25	1942 - 1966	2,63	202,6	48,6	77,5	227,4	37,566667	-77,45	USA	RICHMOND
47	1970 - 2016	2.05 + 0.30	63	20,8	33,1	97,5	-23,122268	-134,966749	PYF	RIKITEA

34	1985 - 2018	0.76 + 0.68	62,6	26	41,7	123,1	48,483333	-68,516667	CAN	RIMOUSKI
27	1962 - 1989	3.53 + 1.07	75	29,2	47	139,4	34,348333	-119,441667	USA	RINCON ISLAND
51	1968 - 2018	0.15 + 0.44	117,4	28,8	46,1	134,2	57,249722	12,1125	SWE	RINGHALS
50	1969 - 2018	1.02 + 0.65	61,5	35,9	60,8	190,5	49	-64,383333	CAN	RIVIERE-AU-RENARD
60	1948 - 2016	5.95 + 0.63	157,2	47,3	79,6	249,2	28,021667	-97,046667	USA	ROCKPORT
31	1955 - 1985	1.32 + 1.13	99,2	33,7	54,3	161,4	54,655833	11,348611	DNK	RODBYHAVN
30	1989 - 2018	6.41 + 1.22	106,5	34,8	58,3	192	-19,666667	63,416667	MUS	RODRIGUES IS
61	1867 - 1936	-6,67	222,3	35,4	56,2	164,6	63,066667	20,8	FIN	RONNSKAR
32	1987 - 2018	2.39 + 0.54	88,4	21,1	33,7	98,3	51,619722	3,681944	NLD	ROOMPOT BUITEN
49	1970 - 2018	-0,5	130,3	28,1	45,6	141,8	64,859456	11,230107	NOR	RORVIK
44	1975 - 2018	1.84 + 0.38	82,9	22,9	36,3	106,5	48,718399	-3,96586	FRA	ROSCOFF
25	1994 - 2018	4.66 + 0.88	85,7	22,7	36,8	109,8	-23,161028	150,790167	AUS	ROSSLYN BAY
30	1964 - 1993	0.54 + 1.63	84,9	43,8	73,1	226,1	56,016667	-3,45	GBR	ROSYTH
61	1956 - 2016	0.92 + 0.33	83	27,6	45,4	144,9	45,0833	13,6283	HRV	ROVINJ
70	1866 - 1936	-2,54	173,9	35,2	56	163,8	59,766667	22,95	FIN	RUSSARO
38	1953 - 1990	-0,05	121,9	32,2	53,5	170,8	76,183333	62,583333	RUS	RUSSKAIA GAVAN II
37	1953 - 1989	-0,41	122	31,6	52,4	169,6	76,2	62,583333	RUS	RUSSKAYA GAVAN
35	1951 - 1985	1,16	117,6	44,8	72,4	214	77,166667	96,433333	RUS	RUSSKII (RUSSKII OSTROV)
23	1993 - 2018	6.34 + 1.69	124,4	35,8	57,5	170,5	29,728333	-93,87	USA	SABINE PASS NORTH
54	1965 - 2018	2.21 + 0.44	129,4	28,4	48,8	157,8	36,201389	133,331111	JPN	SAIGO
84	1929 - 2017	2.22 + 0.25	86,8	33,5	54,3	163,6	45,266667	-66,066667	CAN	SAINT JOHN, N.B.
60	1958 - 2018	2.55 + 0.48	146,6	33,6	59,5	204,7	35,547778	133,243056	JPN	SAKAI

29	1953 - 1984	2.69 + 1.19	102,6	33,7	53,8	158,7	16,166667	-95,2	MEX	SALINA CRUZ
113	1906 - 2018	2.19 + 0.12	97,7	26,7	43	127,5	32,713333	-117,173333	USA	SAN DIEGO (QUARANTINE STATION)
164	1855 - 2018	1.47 + 0.11	97,9	36,2	58,5	174,6	37,806667	-122,465	USA	SAN FRANCISCO
53	1963 - 2018	2.03 + 0.27	64,8	22,7	36,5	108,7	18,458333	-66,115	PRI	SAN JUAN
34	1985 - 2018	2.17 + 0.83	140,2	30,7	47,7	139,7	55,336667	-160,501667	USA	SAND POINT, POPOF IS., AK
86	1933 - 2018	4.10 + 0.18	129,7	27,1	43,6	128,9	40,466667	-74,008333	USA	SANDY HOOK
69	1950 - 2018	1.56 + 0.45	157,5	40	63,8	187,3	74,666667	138,9	RUS	SANNIKOVA (SANNIKOVA PROLIV)
79	1933 - 2018	1.56 + 0.19	81	27,5	44,1	130,4	34,008333	-118,5	USA	SANTA MONICA (MUNICIPAL PIER)
75	1944 - 2018	2.26 + 0.33	90,9	34,4	55,8	167,8	43,4613	-3,7908	ESP	SANTANDER I
25	1993 - 2017	1.33 + 0.63	71,1	18,3	29,2	85,7	43,4613	-3,79076	ESP	SANTANDER III
52	1967 - 2018	2.21 + 0.31	150,3	22,3	36,7	117,7	33,158056	129,723889	JPN	SASEBO II
74	1936 - 2018	0.86 + 0.23	116,6	29,5	46,9	137,5	54,510833	13,643056	DEU	SASSNITZ
49	1937 - 1987	-0,2	217,3	80,9	133,1	NaN	21,65	88,05	IND	SAUGOR/SAGAR
120	1899 - 2018	2.07 + 0.12	112,2	28	45,4	134,5	47,601667	-122,338333	USA	SEATTLE
53	1927 - 1985	1.75 + 0.32	59,5	24,5	41,3	139,2	43,08	-70,741667	USA	SEAVEY ISLAND
23	1967 - 1989	-1,3	166,7	31	49,2	144,2	70,15	72,566667	RUS	SE-LAHA
53	1966 - 2018	-9,32	198,3	33,8	53,9	158,5	59,44	-151,72	USA	SELDOVIA
55	1954 - 2018	0,46	114,6	63,6	109,8	NaN	1,466667	103,833333	SGP	SEMBAWANG
34	1985 - 2018	3.92 + 0.66	127,7	25,4	41,5	125,2	33,24	126,561667	KOR	SEOGWIPO
38	1981 - 2018	0,74	64,9	33,2	53,4	160,1	50,2	-66,4	CAN	SEPT-ILES
83	1910 - 1994	1.26 + 0.39	107,6	44,9	71,9	212,8	44,616667	33,533333	UKR	SEVASTOPOL
54	1964 - 2018	-2,28	135,8	33,4	54,7	174	60,12	-149,426667	USA	SEWARD

91	1928 - 2018	4.69 + 0.19	151,6	29,9	49,1	142,3	36,946667	-76,33	USA	SEWELLS POINT, HAMPTON ROADS
50	1950 - 1999	0.48 + 0.74	147,3	40,6	65,4	194,7	73,183333	143,233333	RUS	SHALAUROVA (SHALAUROVA MYS)
37	1968 - 2006	1.73 + 1.17	71,1	44,7	80,4	271,5	51,445639	0,743444	GBR	SHEERNESS
61	1958 - 2018	5.91 + 0.38	138,3	31,4	50,5	151,6	35,011667	138,5175	JPN	SHIMIZU-MINATO
34	1958 - 1992	0,19	143	27,6	44,6	133	33,966667	130,95	JPN	SHIMONOSEKI I
52	1967 - 2018	0,54	117,1	33,1	56,4	195,4	33,683611	135,375278	JPN	SHIRAHAMA
33	1983 - 2017	3.56 + 0.63	86,5	24,3	39,2	116,8	-20,283333	148,783333	AUS	SHUTE HARBOUR 2
47	1961 - 2007	1.62 + 0.36	88,1	22,2	37,1	122,4	35,633333	139,75	JPN	SIBAURA
36	1983 - 2018	0.51 + 0.75	124,7	29,8	47,3	138,5	55,5575	14,357778	SWE	SIMRISHAMN
34	1978 - 2018	3.28 + 0.46	71,8	23,1	38	115,2	37,95	-8,883333	PRT	SINES
48	1969 - 2018	-1,38	91,4	52,4	89,8	287,6	37,439969	24,945808	GRC	SIROS
81	1938 - 2018	-2,24	125	27,9	44,6	131,3	57,051667	-135,341667	USA	SITKA
28	1989 - 2017	-5,08	192,4	43	68,4	200,6	63,190556	19,0125	SWE	SKAGSUDDE
62	1945 - 2018	-17,51	431,1	36,9	58,8	192	59,45	-135,326667	USA	SKAGWAY
26	1993 - 2018	3.53 + 1.13	112,3	28,2	44,9	131,4	55,416667	12,829444	SWE	SKANOR
37	1900 - 1936	0,07	165,3	34,1	54,1	158,6	60,1	23,55	FIN	SKURU
120	1896 - 2017	1.08 + 0.10	86	24,6	39,2	119	55,288333	10,827778	DNK	SLIPSHAVN
108	1911 - 2018	-1,59	126,7	31,5	50,6	152	58,353611	11,217778	SWE	SMOGEN
71	1866 - 1936	-1,46	174,2	36,6	58,3	170,6	60,116667	25,416667	FIN	SODERSKAR
45	1974 - 2018	2.52 + 0.20	96,8	14,6	23,2	71,6	38,207222	128,594167	KOR	SOKCHO
40	1951 - 1990	4.32 + 0.86	112,9	36	57,8	171	78,2	103,266667	RUS	SOLNECHNAIA (SOLNECHNAIA BUKHTA)
81	1938 - 2018	3.82 + 0.20	129,3	27,3	44	130,8	38,316667	-76,451667	USA	SOLOMON'S ISLAND (BIOL. LAB.)

37	1974 - 2010	4.71 + 0.31	100,2	16,6	26,7	79	37,830833	140,962222	JPN	SOMA
61	1958 - 2018	2.39 + 0.64	234	45	71,9	211,7	71,866667	82,7	RUS	SOPOCHNAIA KARGA
43	1969 - 2011	0.25 + 1.24	80,8	51,2	87	275,1	35,487453	24,082481	GRC	SODHAS
52	1967 - 2018	1.72 + 0.47	121,2	31	49,6	147,1	44,625	-124,041667	USA	SOUTH BEACH
68	1933 - 2015	1.25 + 0.16	71,2	21,3	35,2	108,8	51,51445	0,72378	GBR	SOUTHEND
50	1969 - 2018	-5,64	204,9	40,2	63,9	187,3	62,363333	17,531111	SWE	SPIKARNA
64	1955 - 2018	1.00 + 0.44	81,5	35,1	58	178,1	43,5067	16,4417	HRV	SPLIT - GRADSKA LUKA
55	1953 - 2007	0.63 + 0.38	76,7	26,9	44,8	147,1	43,508333	16,391667	HRV	SPLIT RT MARJANA
27	1992 - 2018	3.63 + 0.50	64,5	16,9	27	79,1	-42,545861	147,932722	AUS	SPRING BAY
35	1978 - 2018	2.80 + 0.88	106,7	35,8	59	181,1	33,655	-78,918333	USA	SPRINGMAID PIER
24	1993 - 2016	2.59 + 0.78	87,9	20,1	32	93,7	49,183333	-2,116667	JEY	ST HELIER (JERSEY) 2
37	1966 - 2010	0.95 + 0.43	70,5	23,7	37,8	111	43,395239	-1,681623	FRA	ST JEAN DE LUZ (SOCOA)
78	1933 - 2018	2.05 + 0.20	111,6	27	43	126	32,373333	-64,703333	BMU	ST. GEORGES / ESSO PIER (BERMUDA)
62	1957 - 2018	1.95 + 0.31	101,4	28,1	44,9	132,3	47,566667	-52,716667	CAN	ST. JOHN'S, NFLD.
24	1995 - 2018	2.05 + 0.98	82	23,6	37	121,3	48,641102	-2,02818	FRA	ST. MALO
72	1947 - 2018	2.78 + 0.22	100,7	25,2	41,1	124,1	27,76	-82,626667	USA	ST. PETERSBURG
93	1919 - 2018	0.38 + 0.13	99,7	25,1	40,1	118,4	58,974339	5,730121	NOR	STAVANGER
53	1966 - 2018	-0,48	127,4	29,4	46,9	138,6	58,093333	11,8325	SWE	STENUNGSUND
61	1950 - 2017	1.30 + 0.70	171,4	51,8	82,9	244,1	75,416667	88,9	RUS	STERLEGOVA (STERLEGOVA MYS)
26	1970 - 1995	1.80 + 1.43	89,4	33,2	53	156,5	49,116667	-123,183333	CAN	STEVESTON
56	1963 - 2018	0.57 + 0.63	115,7	40,6	65,7	196,7	47	-70,816667	CAN	ST-FRANCOIS
47	1972 - 2018	-0,49	113,3	55,7	92,3	282,4	47,45	-70,366667	CAN	ST-JOSEPH-DE-LA-RIVE

130	1889 - 2018	-3,62	211,6	36,2	57,7	169	59,324167	18,081667	SWE	STOCKHOLM
24	1993 - 2016	2.87 + 0.90	77,7	22,3	35,7	105	-38,372139	145,224694	AUS	STONY POINT
41	1977 - 2018	2.48 + 0.53	109,7	26,5	42,6	126,2	58,207806	-6,388972	GBR	STORNOWAY
62	1900 - 1967	-1,72	124,7	26,3	41,8	122,6	58,95	11,183333	SWE	STROMSTAD
46	1972 - 2018	2.99 + 0.41	79	25,3	41,1	119,9	1,233333	103,65	SGP	SULTAN SHOAL
54	1965 - 2018	2.97 + 0.54	137,7	33,2	57,2	200,8	34,340556	134,906667	JPN	SUMOTO
37	1951 - 1987	1.98 + 1.24	147,8	42,8	68,6	202,9	72,833333	140,733333	RUS	SVIATOI NOS (SVIATOI NOS MYS)
183	1811 - 1999	0.80 + 0.08	124,8	32,4	53	161,1	53,916667	14,233333	POL	SWINOUJSCIE
108	1886 - 1993	0.60 + 0.18	62,1	28,4	49,5	165,2	-33,85	151,233333	AUS	SYDNEY, FORT DENISON
103	1915 - 2018	1.01 + 0.15	67,8	26,9	45	140	-33,854667	151,225778	AUS	SYDNEY, FORT DENISON 2
35	1955 - 1989	-0,97	183	50,6	81,1	239	70,366667	72,566667	RUS	TADIBE-IAHA
37	1981 - 2018	5.37 + 0.46	103,5	22,6	35,9	105,6	34,806944	138,764167	JPN	TAGO
54	1963 - 2018	3.35 + 0.55	131,5	46,1	59,8	179,6	22,4425	114,183889	HKG	TAI PO KAU, TOLO HARBOUR
53	1966 - 2018	3.25 + 0.36	142,1	25	41,5	128,7	35,593611	134,315833	JPN	TAJIRI
33	1958 - 1991	2.55 + 1.11	140,8	36,7	60,6	184,8	34,35	134,05	JPN	TAKAMATSU
27	1992 - 2018	1.87 + 0.76	137,5	22,4	35,6	104,8	34,351389	134,056944	JPN	TAKAMATSU II
36	1930 - 1965	3.48 + 0.65	77,3	25,5	44,1	144,5	4,884556	-1,745028	GHA	TAKORADI
28	1942 - 1969	0.97 + 0.70	57,2	22	35,1	103,5	-4,616667	-81,283333	PER	TALARA
30	1989 - 2018	3.53 + 0.85	109,7	26,7	43,3	128,8	1,266667	103,85	SGP	TANJONG PAGAR
35	1984 - 2018	3.11 + 0.55	144,4	22,8	37,3	113,4	3,975	103,43	MYS	TANJUNG GELANG
34	1985 - 2018	2.57 + 0.70	75,7	26,6	42,5	125,5	2,215	102,153333	MYS	TANJUNG KELING
32	1987 - 2018	2.39 + 0.54	134,9	22,3	33,7	100,7	1,931667	104,115	MYS	TANJUNG SEDILI

61	1958 - 2018	1.93 + 0.34	129,6	29,1	46,5	138,1	34,338889	135,178056	JPN	TAN-NOWA
34	1985 - 2018	0,14	84,7	27,5	46,8	149	41,2425	140,381389	JPN	TAPPI
74	1944 - 2018	1.24 + 0.47	75,4	40,7	71,2	259,4	36,0086	-5,6026	ESP	TARIFA
33	1985 - 2018	3.97 + 0.93	68,8	32,3	52,6	158,9	-37,64099	176,1811	NZL	TAURANGA (SALISBURY WHARF)
31	1988 - 2018	2.85 + 1.55	64,9	42	68,5	205,2	4,233333	117,883333	MYS	TAWAU
25	1993 - 2017	1.92 + 1.30	123,9	29,7	47,2	138,2	55,249722	14,837778	DNK	TEJN
24	1994 - 2017	3.68 + 0.86	66,9	21,6	34,8	103,3	28,477217	-16,241117	ESP	TENERIFE
47	1943 - 1990	0,38	117,8	32,6	52,4	152,8	69,2	35,1167	RUS	TERIBERKA
41	1956 - 1996	2.53 + 0.73	142,8	33	53,4	159,9	73,55	118,666667	RUS	TERPIAI-TUMSA
49	1969 - 2018	3.81 + 0.55	95,9	33,1	53,4	158,4	40,632542	22,934933	GRC	THESSALONIKI
26	1993 - 2018	4.13 + 1.17	94	29,1	46,4	137	-32,148944	133,641333	AUS	THEVENARD
61	1949 - 2009	1.54 + 0.42	158,1	28,8	54,7	160,2	71,583333	128,916667	RUS	TIKSI (TIKSI BUKHTA)
22	1961 - 1983	1.54 + 1.10	61,2	24,8	39,4	117	51,466667	0,366667	GBR	TILBURY
30	1989 - 2018	2.08 + 0.61	106,5	21,3	34	99,3	56,623111	-6,064222	GBR	TOBERMORY
89	1910 - 2018	-1,04	125,1	29,1	46,3	136	49,15	-125,916667	CAN	TOFINO
40	1979 - 2018	0.02 + 0.75	146,6	33,1	52,4	154,5	46,706667	-123,966667	USA	TOKE POINT, WILLIPA BAY, WA
51	1968 - 2018	2.91 + 0.62	140,5	35,8	59,5	183	34,040833	131,802778	JPN	TOKUYAMA II
36	1983 - 2018	1.27 + 0.53	85,6	22,4	37,6	112	35,648611	139,77	JPN	TOKYO III
24	1995 - 2018	4.45 + 1.24	108,7	27,7	44,4	131,2	39,213333	-76,245	USA	TOLCHESTER BEACH, MARYLAND
42	1977 - 2018	2.23 + 0.19	107,2	13,7	21,9	64,2	34,8275	128,434722	KOR	TONGYEONG
88	1894 - 1983	0.33 + 0.27	143,1	32,1	56,2	189,5	34,9	132,066667	JPN	TONOURA
60	1958 - 2018	1.73 + 0.51	118,2	36,1	61,9	199	32,779167	132,958889	JPN	TOSA SHIMIZU

52	1929 - 1982	1.84 + 0.58	71,5	36,1	59,9	184,5	51,5	0,083333	GBR	TOWER PIER
60	1959 - 2018	2.09 + 0.36	93,1	29,5	47,7	142,6	-19,25	146,833333	AUS	TOWNSVILLE I
44	1975 - 2018	3.67 + 0.23	130,9	16,4	26,1	76,7	36,762222	137,224722	JPN	TOYAMA
155	1856 - 2018	1.65 + 0.06	113,4	23,2	36,8	108,2	53,958056	10,872222	DEU	TRAVEMUNDE
91	1928 - 2018	0.26 + 0.12	86,1	22,3	35,6	105,1	58,006377	7,554759	NOR	TREGDE
24	1995 - 2018	5.17 + 0.96	118,8	23,4	37,2	109,3	28,415	-80,591667	USA	TRIDENT PIER, PORT CANAVERAL
126	1875 - 2018	1.31 + 0.10	101	29,2	46,6	137,6	45,647361	13,758472	ITA	TRIESTE
94	1925 - 2018	1,89	601,2	170,3	296,1	NaN	46,333333	-72,55	CAN	TROIS-RIVIERES
66	1953 - 2018	-0,09	121,2	32,9	52,7	155,6	69,647424	18,961323	NOR	TROMSO
40	1949 - 1989	0,04	129,6	45,1	72,5	214,4	63,433333	10,433333	NOR	TRONDHEIM
29	1990 - 2018	-0,89	117,6	23,2	38,6	113,4	63,436484	10,391669	NOR	TRONDHEIM 2
30	1988 - 2018	2.26 + 1.06	104,5	31	49,3	155,5	22,487222	114,014167	HKG	TSIM BEI TSUI
102	1917 - 2018	2.40 + 0.26	123,9	40,6	65	191,4	44,1	39,066667	RUS	TUAPSE
97	1922 - 2018	-3,3	205,6	40,3	64,1	188,1	60,428283	22,100533	FIN	TURKU / ABO
75	1944 - 2018	0.02 + 0.45	94,5	41,5	69,3	215,2	35,017222	138,890278	JPN	UCHIURA
41	1953 - 1993	1.42 + 0.85	118,4	36,5	59,7	187,6	77,5	82,2	RUS	UEDINENIA (UEDINENIA OSTROV)
41	1950 - 1990	0.50 + 0.79	170,3	37,5	55,7	163,1	69,816667	60,75	RUS	UGORSKII SHAR (UGORSKII SHAR PROLIV)
33	1983 - 2015	1.87 + 1.15	118,8	36,5	59,7	180,5	57,89525	-5,157889	GBR	ULLAPOOL
40	1979 - 2018	3.65 + 0.81	124,4	34,5	55,1	162,5	37,491389	130,913611	KOR	ULLEUNG
54	1963 - 2016	1.62 + 0.49	93,6	32,4	53,6	162,2	35,501944	129,387222	KOR	ULSAN
59	1956 - 2018	-3,96	135,9	40,9	67	202,7	53,88	-166,536667	USA	UNALASKA
61	1958 - 2018	4.95 + 0.38	162,6	31,3	50,3	149,3	34,488611	133,949444	JPN	UNO

54	1965 - 2018	2.41 + 0.58	106,9	36,7	59,6	178,3	33,558333	135,896389	JPN	URAGAMI
32	1971 - 2002	-2,52	55,8	16,1	26,5	85	42,166667	142,766667	JPN	URAKAWA II
31	1987 - 2017	2.88 + 0.98	62,1	30,6	49,9	149,8	-25,3	152,916667	AUS	URANGAN II
58	1950 - 2013	1.91 + 0.60	150	44,5	72	214,7	69,25	64,516667	RUS	UST KARA
31	1950 - 1980	-0,04	369,4	43,6	69,6	202,8	73	119,866667	RUS	UST OLENEK
49	1951 - 1999	1.71 + 0.59	149,9	34,3	54,6	159,6	54,583333	16,866667	POL	USTKA
71	1866 - 1936	-2,39	170,5	34,3	54,6	159,9	59,783333	21,366667	FIN	UTO
50	1969 - 2018	0,43	118,3	29	47,4	143,3	33,227222	132,551111	JPN	UWAJIMA II
134	1884 - 2018	-7,07	333,7	39	62	181,6	63,081533	21,571183	FIN	VAASA / VASA
29	1990 - 2018	4.87 + 0.49	91,3	17,9	28,5	83,8	24,711667	-81,105	USA	VACA KEY
44	1975 - 2018	-4,19	139,8	48,3	81,7	258	61,125	-146,361667	USA	VALDEZ
23	1995 - 2017	3.36 + 1.18	82,7	26	44,6	153,8	39,44203	-0,311128	ESP	VALENCIA
36	1956 - 1991	3.00 + 1.43	160,1	46,1	74,6	222,1	70,083333	170,933333	RUS	VALKARKAI
52	1950 - 2001	2.72 + 0.73	163,2	41,2	67,7	203,7	67,833333	-175,833333	RUS	VANKAREM
95	1887 - 1981	-0,7	116,6	27,5	43,6	127,9	57,1	12,216667	SWE	VARBERG
34	1984 - 2018	0.69 + 0.67	119,8	26,6	42,8	129,6	70,374978	31,104015	NOR	VARDO
68	1929 - 1996	1.22 + 0.43	102,8	38,4	61,5	181,1	43,183333	27,916667	BGR	VARNA
24	1889 - 1913	2.41 + 1.03	91,9	24,9	39,8	116,4	45,416667	12,35	ITA	VENEZIA (ARSENALE)
89	1909 - 2000	2.48 + 0.26	108,1	35,3	57,8	175,5	45,433333	12,333333	ITA	VENEZIA (PUNTA DELLA SALUTE)
52	1966 - 2017	1.34 + 0.53	101	33,7	53,9	159,3	-35,562481	138,635403	AUS	VICTOR HARBOUR
109	1910 - 2018	0.76 + 0.14	94,7	28,8	46,1	136	48,416667	-123,366667	CAN	VICTORIA
75	1944 - 2018	2.05 + 0.31	96,9	33,8	54,1	160,4	42,238	-8,731	ESP	VIGO

25	1993 - 2017	1.67 + 0.93	81,7	23,6	37,6	110,2	42,24314	-8,726	ESP	VIGO II
42	1977 - 2018	0.98 + 0.57	113,6	28,7	45,6	133,7	56,142222	12,579167	SWE	VIKEN
28	1991 - 2018	0,04	115,7	27,2	43	126,2	59,036046	10,949769	NOR	VIKER
25	1994 - 2018	4.62 + 0.71	96,4	19,7	31,5	92,8	25,73	-80,161667	USA	VIRGINIA KEY, FL
71	1937 - 2013	1.05 + 0.21	155,9	26,1	41,4	121,7	17,683333	83,283333	IND	VISAKHAPATNAM
103	1916 - 2018	-0,93	154,1	34,8	55,5	162,7	57,639167	18,284444	SWE	VISBY
59	1953 - 2011	0.20 + 0.50	114,7	35,2	58,6	190,4	79,5	76,983333	RUS	WISE (WISE OSTROV)
157	1862 - 2018	1.27 + 0.34	116,5	60,3	113,6	NaN	51,442222	3,596111	NLD	VLISSINGEN
51	1950 - 2000	2.21 + 0.95	135,5	49,1	84,4	267,7	70,983333	-178,483333	RUS	VRANGELIA (VRANGELIA OSTROV)
35	1979 - 2013	3.82 + 1.01	165,5	37,5	56,9	170,2	10,333333	107,066667	VNM	VUNGTAU
50	1889 - 1938	-0,71	189,8	38,2	60,5	177,8	60,7	28,733333	RUS	VYBORG
87	1930 - 2018	0.03 + 0.28	123,4	31,4	55,6	197,8	37,405833	136,900278	JPN	WAJIMA
61	1958 - 2018	-0,07	127	30	49,1	142,9	34,221667	135,145556	JPN	WAKAYAMA
66	1951 - 2018	2.11 + 0.26	90,9	27,4	43,5	127,8	19,29	166,616667	MHL	WAKE ISLAND
44	1975 - 2018	3.38 + 0.24	90,6	16,9	27,1	79,5	45,407778	141,685278	JPN	WAKKANAI
35	1983 - 2017	0.83 + 0.89	90,3	32,2	51,7	152,7	-33,926017	137,615169	AUS	WALLAROO II
36	1983 - 2018	1.80 + 0.28	123,7	15,2	24,3	71,2	34,315278	126,759722	KOR	WANDO
163	1856 - 2018	1.26 + 0.06	110,3	26	41,4	121,4	54,169722	12,103333	DEU	WARNEMUNDE 2
88	1931 - 2018	3.30 + 0.23	136	32,2	51,5	151,9	38,873333	-77,021667	USA	WASHINGTON DC
44	1966 - 2017	3.53 + 0.92	256,8	46,6	74,5	220,1	-12,666667	141,866667	AUS	WEIPA
74	1945 - 2018	2.71 + 0.24	78,2	27,2	44,1	132,2	-41,28434	174,7798	NZL	WELLINGTON HARBOUR
21	1998 - 2018	4.12 + 1.19	80,8	23,7	38,1	113	1,3	103,766667	SGP	WEST COAST

98	1921 - 2018	1.20 + 0.23	129,7	33,8	56	172,5	53,363056	5,22	NLD	WEST-TERSCHELLING
34	1985 - 2018	3.60 + 0.88	78,4	30,9	49,1	146,1	-35,75743	174,35003	NZL	WHANGAREI HARBOUR (MARSDEN POINT)
33	1981 - 2014	7.48 + 0.96	109,4	32,7	53,2	159,8	54,49	-0,614694	GBR	WHITBY
31	1987 - 2017	1.57 + 0.98	78,3	30,4	48,7	143,6	-33,012783	137,590356	AUS	WHYALLA III
53	1965 - 2018	1.37 + 0.24	106,4	20,2	32,2	94,3	58,440972	-3,086306	GBR	WICK
68	1932 - 1999	2.35 + 0.27	89,4	27,9	44,9	133,4	40,793333	-73,781667	USA	WILLETS POINT
83	1936 - 2018	2.44 + 0.35	106,5	37,1	63	216,2	34,226667	-77,953333	USA	WILMINGTON
30	1989 - 2018	0.32 + 0.89	131,7	27,6	44	129,2	50,516667	-128,033333	CAN	WINTER HARBOUR
170	1849 - 2018	1.44 + 0.06	115	25,5	40,7	119,8	53,898889	11,458056	DEU	WISMAR 2
49	1951 - 1999	2.46 + 0.64	161,7	36,2	57,5	168,3	54,8	18,416667	POL	WLADYSLAWOWO
31	1962 - 1992	1.30 + 0.51	123,3	19,7	31,5	92,9	39,166667	127,45	PRK	WONSAN
85	1933 - 2018	2.88 + 0.19	94,3	27,6	44,9	134,8	41,523333	-70,671667	USA	WOODS HOLE (OCEAN. INST.)
27	1992 - 2018	-2,71	118,2	32,8	52,5	156,8	54,650722	-3,567167	GBR	WORKINGTON
33	1985 - 2017	6.08 + 1.60	153,6	45,5	72,9	215,3	-15,453278	128,101028	AUS	WYNDHAM
29	1990 - 2018	4.32 + 0.90	105,1	27	43,1	126,3	16,833333	112,333333	CHN	XI SHA
50	1954 - 2003	1.16 + 0.64	125,5	35,9	59,3	181,2	24,45	118,066667	CHN	XIAMEN
37	1981 - 2018	5.69 + 0.75	111,6	31	49,9	148,2	34,870556	138,327222	JPN	YAIZU
79	1940 - 2018	-7,91	230,4	66	119,6	NaN	59,548333	-139,733333	USA	YAKUTAT
32	1987 - 2018	1.84 + 1.07	81,6	33,4	53,9	160,3	-29,429712	153,361875	AUS	YAMBA
52	1967 - 2018	3.64 + 0.36	78,6	25,6	41,3	123,2	43,833333	-66,133333	CAN	YARMOUTH
52	1966 - 2017	1.48 + 0.33	125,9	23,8	38,6	116,7	34,747222	127,765556	KOR	YEOSU
36	1889 - 1924	-5,71	177,9	35,9	57,1	167,1	63,833333	23,033333	FIN	YKSPIHLAJA

61	1957 - 2018	4.78 + 0.26	116,5	24,2	39,3	117,6	35,288056	139,651389	JPN	YOKOSUKA
95	1887 - 1981	0.61 + 0.16	117,1	27,9	44,4	129,9	55,416667	13,816667	SWE	YSTAD
36	1951 - 1992	2.79 + 0.36	77,5	22,3	33,1	98	44,016667	145,866667	RUS	YUZHNO KURILSK
24	1995 - 2018	2.49 + 0.94	81,2	22,9	36,4	106,6	44,1233	15,235	HRV	ZADAR
32	1985 - 2016	1.56 + 1.01	48,5	32,2	52,5	158	-6,15	39,183333	TZA	ZANZIBAR
53	1962 - 2017	2.83 + 0.34	94,8	26,2	42,3	126,1	51,35	3,2	BEL	ZEEBRUGGE
37	1951 - 1987	2.76 + 0.82	140,7	32,3	51,3	150,7	74,883333	142,116667	RUS	ZEMLIA BUNGE
60	1959 - 2018	2.37 + 0.30	122,3	26,4	42,6	126,2	21,583333	111,816667	CHN	ZHAPO
45	1951 - 1995	1,18	119,2	57,1	99,8	NaN	76,95	68,55	RUS	ZHELANIA II (ZHELANIA MYS)
33	1959 - 1992	2.19 + 1.07	137,5	35,2	57,7	182,2	76,15	152,833333	RUS	ZHOHOVA (ZHOHOVA OSTROV)

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